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Stream A. Decision making and public participation in environmental modelling

This stream through its various sessions seeks to bring together academic experts, action researchers and practitioners to explore recent developments in participatory decision making, modelling, design and research to solve complex problems of today. We will focus on questions related to the latest trends in participatory research, what role AI and Machine Learning can play in advancing participatory methods, how to organise, support and promote stakeholder participation, as well as how diversity among stakeholder groups can help and related areas.

- [Come to the table! Stakeholder engagement in modelling for agricultural transformation](#)
- [Connecting stakeholder engagement to governance processes and decision making for climate adaptation and sustainability](#)
- [Tools and software for participatory modeling and decision support](#)
- [Improving participatory processes through analysis of narratives, knowledge sources, emotions, values, biases and schema](#)

Stream B. Modeling environmental fate of contaminants, human well-being and ecological public health

Environmental modelling of the environmental fate of a variety of contaminants in and across all environmental media is a powerful tool for regulatory and management strategies. Topics in this stream may cover aspects of modelling the chemical and physical transformation of pollutants in air, water and soil, the impact of pollution on human and ecosystem health, biodiversity and the integrated assessment of potential synergies and unintended consequences of technical, behavioural and nature-based solutions.

- [Environmental modelling in the changing assessment landscape: Busier, more contested, more important](#)
- [Modeling of freshwater and marine systems](#)
- [Advances and contemporary issues in water quality modelling](#)

Stream C. Computational methods, workflows, informatics and integrated systems in environmental modelling

This stream will cover a range of approaches including open integrated system, and computational intelligence methods in environmental modeling, e.g., computational workflow development, data analytics, and hybrid models of AI and environmental informatics.

- [Ninth Session on Data Mining as a Tool for Environmental Scientists \(DMTES-2024\)](#)
- [Optimization-based environmental modelling](#)
- [Intelligent modeling methods and easy-to-use systems for environmental problems](#)
- [Facilitating Environmental Modeling— automated, cloud-based workflows](#)
- [Modelling to evaluate outcomes of environmental watering](#)
- [Exploring the Synergy: AI, ML, and Process-Based Modelling Action](#)
- [Computational Intelligence and AI Systems for scientific computing in water resources](#)
- [CIROH 1: Modelling and framework advances in the U.S. National Water Model and similar large scale modeling](#)
- [CIROH 2: Data and hydroinformatics advances in the U.S. National Water Model and large scale modeling systems](#)
- [Development and evaluation of surrogate models using machine learning to emulate results of calibrated process models](#)
- [Open modeling and simulation](#)
- [Advances in Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence for environmental modelling and decision support](#)
- [Artificial Intelligence Tools and Software Libraries for environmental modeling, computing and communication](#)

Stream D. System design, identification and uncertainty in modelling complex environmental & agricultural systems

Modelling complex environmental and agricultural systems inevitably leads to a problem of the design or structure of the system and the identification of the “true values” of numerous parameters that affect model predictions. This stream will include topics related to the methods, tools, and applications in systems design, parameter identification, and evaluation of uncertainty of model predictions. We particularly welcome sessions and submissions that address the impact of a lack of knowledge about the systems design or parameters on likely outcomes in agricultural or environmental problems.

- [New and improved methods in agricultural systems modelling](#)
- [Harmful Algae Blooms \(HAB\) research and development in the Great Lakes Region and beyond](#)
- [Good modelling practice for better social and environmental outcomes](#)
- [Modeling food and agricultural systems for a circular bioeconomy](#)
- [Water infrastructure system modelling and optimization for a sustainable future](#)

Stream E. Socio-environmental systems modelling for planetary health and environmental sustainability

The stream will cover novel approaches to earth system modelling, software frameworks for predictions of complex interrelationships of environmental factors and their consequences for the planetary health. This includes approaches to simulation of human-environment interactions and integration of environmental and social determinants to assess risks to human health, quantitative and qualitative methods for sustainability assessment, and approaches to monitoring progress towards attainment of Sustainable Development Goals at the global, national, regional, and local levels.

- [Addressing the Grand Challenges to accelerate use of socio-environmental systems modelling in actionable science](#)
- [Hybrid and data-driven approaches to assessing and attaining planetary health and environmental sustainability](#)

Stream F. (Big) data solutions for environmental systems planning, management, and operation

Fast advances in remote sensing techniques, in-situ observation systems, and information and communication technologies have contributed to the proliferation of Big Data on environmental systems. Big Data brings about new opportunities for a better understanding of complex systems through new forms of information processing, storage, retrieval, and analytics. Machine learning, which refers to computer algorithms that automatically learn from data, can advance our prediction capability on complex systems with less human intervention. Collectively, Big Data and ML techniques have shown great potential for data-driven decision-making, operation research, and process optimization in planning and managing environmental systems. We encourage the submission of papers that provide insights into novel data solutions, software technologies, and computational and machine-learning methods to guide human activities on environmental systems, including, but not limited to, environmental systems planning, management, and operations.

- [Intelligent water resources science and engineering](#)

Stream A. Decision making and public participation in environmental modelling

Come to the table! Stakeholder engagement in modelling for agricultural transformation

Combining Agent-Based Modelling, Optimization and Stakeholder Integration to Minimize Trade-Offs of an Agricultural Transformation

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Summary

Socially and politically, there is currently a demand for a transformation of agriculture that preserves and promotes the diverse functions of agroecosystems and the ecosystem services they provide. Additionally, agriculture should adapt to the increasingly noticeable effects of climate change. We present an inter- and transdisciplinary approach that aligns agent-based modelling with multi-objective optimization to identify trade-offs of such a transformation and suitable policy measures that address these. To create practice-relevant solutions, we integrate stakeholders at different levels of the framework and with different methods.

Introduction

In Germany and Europe, especially in productive agricultural landscapes, today's agriculture is oriented towards monofunctional management. This means that food, fodder and biomass are produced in large quantities, but little consideration is given to other ecosystem services, e.g. drought protection, climate regulation or habitat for biodiversity. Accordingly, a transformation of agriculture is being called for by societal and political actors. The aim is to make agricultural landscapes increasingly multifunctional, i.e. maintain or promote the diverse functions of agroecosystems and the ecosystem services they provide. In addition, there is the need to adapt to the increasingly noticeable impacts of climate change. However, such a transformation comes along with different trade-offs. We combine the results of multi-objective spatial optimization and an agent-based model with different levels of stakeholder involvement (Fig. 1). The aim is to identify optimal spatial allocations of agricultural management practices that minimize ecological and socio-economic trade-offs under climate change. Further, suitable policy measures that support this transformation will be defined.

Methodology and Results

As a first step, so-called opportunity maps were created that show where ecosystem services can be improved in the study region of North-West Saxony, Germany. The maps were developed together with experts on the respective ecosystem services by using interviews and the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). These maps serve as a first information for the following modelling exercises. Additionally, agricultural management practices that are relevant in the study region currently and in future were collected and prioritized during a workshop with local stakeholders. In the modelling framework, these practices are spatially allocated with the aim of minimizing ecological and socio-economic trade-offs. Ecological trade-offs are determined using multi-criteria optimization that produces Pareto-optimal solutions with different spatial arrangements of the management practices. Within the optimization process, these are evaluated using a process-based model with regard to their suitability for maximizing ecosystem services. The socio-economic trade-offs are identified using an agent-based model (ABM). This model simulates farmers' management decisions based on various policy measures. The ABM is informed by the results of qualitative farmer interviews that identified different types of farmers with respect to their behaviour. The solutions of both modelling approaches are then aligned analogous to the conceptual approach of Bartkowski et al. (2020), to analyze how “close” the socio-economically “optimal” allocation of management practices comes to the biophysically “optimal” allocation. In addition, socially preferred solutions will be selected using preferences for ecosystem services. The latter are based on the

results of a choice experiment with participants from the general public. To take climate change effects into account, the analysis is carried out for different climate scenarios.

Figure 1. General framework of the approach

In addition to the results of the individual work packages, the expected results of the entire approach are (i) identified trade-offs that can arise in the transformation of intensively used agricultural landscapes towards multifunctionality under climate change and (ii) socially accepted transformation paths that minimize these trade-offs and the necessary policy measures.

Conclusions

The results allow the identification and development of policy instruments that aim at supporting a successful agricultural transformation towards multifunctionality. North-West Saxony was selected as a study region because it is an example of intensively used agricultural landscapes in Germany where trade-offs are expected to be most prevalent. Therefore, the recommendations obtained from the modelling results can partly be transferred to regions that are similar to the study area in terms of landscape characteristics and socio-economical structure. In addition, the high level of stakeholder integration in the various modelling steps ensures a high degree of social and practical relevance of the results.

Acknowledgements

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Optimizing Digital Extension Platforms for Farmers: A Critical Analysis and Recommendations

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Summary

This study compares the challenges and advantages of developing intelligent digitized Agricultural Extension systems to enhance the communication of actionable knowledge from Extension resources to farmers. As these resources migrate to digital platforms, farmers face navigation and searching difficulties, which may result in delayed responses. To address these issues, we proposed a conceptual approach integrating mined multimedia patterns and expert knowledge within a standardized framework for AI-assisted decision support systems. Furthermore, we thoroughly examined current decision-making procedures in Agricultural Extension, highlighting relevant research gaps. Finally, we suggested practical recommendations to address each gap.

Introduction

While agricultural research translates well to scientific publications and technical reports, farmers prefer applicable knowledge and specific recommendations. Traditionally, Agricultural Extension services have provided the solution to this gap. However, the decline in funding has proven to be a limiting factor for such activities (Wang, 2014). Consequently, Extension know-how and services have migrated online (e.g., websites and social media) and exist in different formats (audiovisual and textual), thus forming complex digital libraries. However, these libraries can be difficult to navigate, thus hindering users from quickly accessing the information they need. Furthermore, this challenge is exacerbated by the fact that farmers' inquiries are highly dependent on their location and specific crop needs. Given the challenges above, this study proposes a conceptual framework to offer guidelines for standardizing unstructured Agricultural Extension data. In other words, our targeted objectives are as follows: (a) highlight the challenges related to the multimedia facet of Agricultural Extension data; (b) summarize the literature review of current mining techniques being used as solutions to those challenges; (c) emphasize the shortcomings of such techniques; and finally (d) suggest a conceptual AI-empowered decision support system that incorporates expert knowledge and insights from all mined AE data.

In summary, we structured our study in two main parts to meet these objectives. On the first hand, we provided a six-step decision-making blueprint. Then, we identified areas where knowledge within these steps is lacking and proposed practical solutions to fill those gaps.

Methodology and Results

Our methodology focuses on our proposed six-step decision-making blueprint, where we discuss three characteristics surrounding each of the six steps. These characteristics include a descriptive overview, a section listing the challenges surrounding that step, and a theory-applications section. The six steps are described as follows. The first three focus on the life cycle of Agricultural Extension data, respectively covering its primary and secondary sources (Data Source Identification), how it is synthesized from different data formats (Data Collection), and how it is preprocessed and cleaned before its use (Data Transformation). The fourth step, (Multimedia Data Mining) examines multimedia-data mining algorithms currently used in Agricultural Extension. While the fifth step (Decision-Making Framework) outlines potential human- and AI-based procedures for guiding decision-making, step six (Decision Support Systems) proposes the implementation of these procedures through various decision-support systems.

Following the aforementioned comprehensive methodology, our results culminate in recommendations that will address the knowledge gaps we identified for each of the six steps. Table 1 provides an excerpt of the result associated with step 6 (Decision Support Systems).

Table 1. Knowledge Gaps for Agricultural Decision Support Systems (ADSS) and our recommendations

Key Issues	Knowledge Gaps	References	Suggestions
Low Adoption Issues Maintenance and User experience issues	Digital illiteracy and the limited availability of smartphones.	Thar et al. (2021)	Promote affordable, community-tailored ADSSs for farmers and EEs through workshops and outreach.
	Non-intuitive graphical user interface	Rose et al. (2016)	Offer better documentation and training for farmers, enhancing their understanding and troubleshooting.
	Poor software architecture	Jones et al. (2003)	Developed crop-specific computer code and established a community for knowledge-sharing and problem-solving.
	Non-scalability and Non-accessibility.	Zhai et al. (2020)	Leverage cloud platforms to scale ADSSs; Improve accessibility by raising awareness of ADSSs through workshops.

Conclusions

The migration of Extension resources to digital platforms has presented both search and navigational obstacles and necessitated the inclusion of additional data sources beyond Extension publications, namely spatiotemporal data. To address these obstacles, a conceptualized framework is proposed that integrates mined multimedia patterns and Extension Education expertise into decision support systems. Incorporating the latest AI technologies, such as Natural Language Processing techniques, can further enhance this framework. The study outlines six sequential steps for decision-making within the Agricultural Extension field, including identifying data sources, collecting data, transforming data, conducting multimedia data mining, improving decision-making frameworks, and implementing AI with human-in-the-loop decision support systems. The study also identifies knowledge gaps in existing data-driven research about Agricultural Extension and provides suggestions to overcome them, such as improving information delivery, creating central databases, promoting data standardization, and incorporating expert knowledge into AI.

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Co-Creating Decision Support Software: The Case of Precision Livestock Farming

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Summary

Permanent grassland is a key component of agricultural land worldwide. To make pasture management more cost-efficient and sustainable, digitalization and modern sensor technology need to be integrated (MacPherson et al, 2022). Special software tools are necessary to effectively incorporate the data from modern sensors into operational processes. We present a decision support software for grassland farmers “SMILe”, which was developed in an interdisciplinary co-creation process within the “GreenGrass” project with potential users. Living labs integrated into “GreenGrass” accompany the research and software development activities by involving various different stakeholders to discuss concepts and prototypes of the software.

Introduction

The integration of new modern sensor technology into grassland management not only offers new opportunities but also presents new challenges. While advanced software solutions are necessary to process these new data, understanding the existing management practices and farmers’ needs is crucial in the software development process to ensure the creation of a product that meets the demands of practitioners. The development of information systems represents an instance of socio-technical change (Luna-Reyes, Zhang, Gil-García & Cresswell, 2005), in which social practices are transformed by novel technologies, but at the same time shape these innovations. As a consequence, successful socio-technical transitions cannot be based on inventions from the lab, but requires participatory processes that allow for aligning social and technical dimensions. Against this background, we present the co-creation process of a software prototype developed as part of the research project “GreenGrass” (greengrass-project.de) referred to in German as the “Softwarebasierte Mehrebenen Informationssystem für Landwirte” (SMILe), which serves as decision support software for farmers (Sturm, Schöttker, Kadir & Wätzold, 2022). A core element of SMILe is the virtual herding technology developed within GreenGrass, which utilizes virtual fences. Grazing animals are located and enclosed within virtual boundaries defined on the pasture lands using a collar. Information about the animals’ location as well as acoustic signals and electrical impulses to prevent them from leaving predefined grazing areas are transmitted via the collar. SMILe enables the planning, simulation, and optimization of virtual fences, and utilizes drone and satellite data to estimate biomass, drought conditions, and grass cover on the pasture lands, thereby providing better insights into their grazing potential and condition. To develop a practice-oriented software, the process has been accompanied by potential users since the conceptual phase, discussing functionality and potential use in various stages of the software prototype in a co-creation process.

Methodology and Results

We rely on a transdisciplinary research infrastructure established in three German grassland farming regions: Marshlands located at the Weser estuary, the lower mountain range Solling, and lowlands along the river Havel west of Berlin. In each of these regions, we have established living labs based on networks of practitioners meeting on a regular basis and tailored to the specific requirements of the agroecological context (McPhee et al, 2021). Practitioners involved include actors from pasture-based farming, animal welfare, nature and landscape conservation, administration, business development and the downstream value chain. Precision agriculture innovations including virtual fencing, remote sensing and decision support have been presented, discussed, tested and refined in participatory workshop formats following a Reflexive Interactive Design Approach (Elzen

& Bos, 2019). Based on actor and system analyses, design requirements and suggestions from practitioners have been iteratively collected and systematised allowing for a process of reflexive learning (Möck & Feindt, 2023). SMILe has been the subject of the co-creation process in five workshops or group discussions in the living labs between January 2021 and January 2024. The co-creation process was initiated for SMILe at the data and algorithm level. What functionalities do users anticipate from the newly collected data? What interconnections do they perceive in the various data layers? And how do they envision integration into the daily workflow of grassland management? Based on the discussion of potentials within the new data sources and modelling opportunities as well as the feasibility of the goals (expectation management), the first prototype was designed. In an iterative process, functionality and user-friendliness of SMILe were enhanced as with each prototype feedback became more and more specific.

Conclusions

New technologies, along with associated new data and software, present not only new opportunities but also new challenges. Integrating these new approaches requires acceptance from potential users, which is only ensured when new tools can be meaningfully integrated into daily workflows and provide clear added value. An assessment of desired or needed new functionality, purely from a scientific perspective, without considering the knowledge of farmers and other stakeholders in grassland, always carries the risk of overlooking important processes, thereby jeopardizing acceptance. The collaborative development of SMILe with stakeholders in living labs resulted in a prototype supporting the integration and implementation of novel precision agriculture technologies including virtual fencing and remote sensing. As an interface for remote control, but also combining the available sensor data and offering decision support to users, SMILe now meets the economic and ecological decision-making and monitoring requirements of farmers.

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OPTAIN - Optimal Strategies to Retain and Re-Use Water and Nutrients in Small Agricultural Catchments in Europe

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Summary

Natural/Small-scale Water Retention Measures (NSWRMs) can mitigate conflicts between agricultural water use and other human and ecological demands on water. However, there is still a lack of knowledge about their effectiveness under different conditions. We present the Horizon 2020 project OPTAIN, which uses a harmonized approach to identify efficient techniques for the retention and reuse of water and nutrients in 14 European case studies. The project workflow, stakeholder-based NSWRM selection, innovative model developments (SWAT+) and simulation results are presented. The next step is to optimize the spatial allocation and combination of NSWRMs, based on environmental and economic sustainability indicators.

Introduction

The increasing number of droughts and heavy rainfall events is exacerbating existing conflicts among agricultural water use and other human and environmental demands for water. Natural/Small Water Retention Measures (NSWRMs; Magnier et al., 2024) can help to mitigate such conflicts and serve a sound management of head watersheds, contributing to i) an improved water quality and more resilient agriculture and society and ii) to the achievement of various sustainable development goals and environmental objectives. Although there is a comprehensive set of techniques to increase water and nutrient retention at both the catchment and farm level, knowledge is still lacking on the effectiveness of different scale- and region-specific measures across various soil-climatic regions and agricultural systems under changing climate conditions. The EU Horizon 2020 project OPTAIN (OPTimal strategies to reTAIN and re-use water and nutrients in small agricultural catchments across different soil-climatic regions in Europe) proposes a social and scientific journey towards the increasing and better understanding of the multiple benefits of NSWRMs. OPTAIN identifies efficient NSWRM to better adapt to extreme events (floods, droughts) and to increase the natural retention capacity of small agricultural catchments across three biogeographical regions of Europe, in close collaboration with local actors. Project outcomes are elaborated from the current state of knowledge, the experience of stakeholders from 14 case studies and innovative scientific modelling and optimization approaches on the farm and catchment scales.

Methodology and Results

Core elements of the project are the harmonized approach and the extensive stakeholder involvement from the start of the project. Each of the 14 case studies established a so-called “Multi-Actor Reference Group”

(MARG). At regular MARG meetings, local issues in the case studies were discussed and 235 measures from 42 different NSWRM categories were identified and documented. The most relevant NSWRM (66 measures from 29 categories) are currently being catalogued in exchange with the WOCAT (<https://qcat.wocat.net/en/wocat/>) and the NWRM.eu (<http://nwrn.eu/index.php/>) databases. Before modelling the impact and efficiency of the measures with the SWAT+ model at the catchment scale and for cross-validation with the SWAP model at the field scale, several procedures to standardize the model input data across all case studies had to be carried out on different levels. Modelling protocols and several R scripts have been developed that allow a comprehensible, improved setup, calibration, and evaluation of both models (Schürz et al., 2022; Farkas et al., 2022). An important improvement of the routing of water in SWAT+ models has been achieved in the project by the development of the Contiguous Object Connectivity Approach COCOA), which allows a flexible connectivity of all spatial units and thus a better simulation of the impact of linear structures (hedges, buffer strips, etc.) and on-site NSWRM (crop rotations, conservation tillage, etc.) in the landscape. The developed R scripts (Plunge et al., 2024) and model improvements will help SWAT+ and other model users worldwide to facilitate data preparation, model pre-processing, setup, calibration, evaluation and simulating the efficiency of NSWRM and climate change on water and nutrient retention. First results of simulating the impact of NSWRM in the German case study show, for instance, positive impacts of low tillage and grassed waterways, among others, on water (reduction of peak flows and increasing low flows), nutrient (mainly on nitrogen components) and sediment retention. The next step here is to link SWAT+ and an economic model with the multi-criteria optimization platform CoMOLA to identify the most efficient allocations of NSWRM combinations. Local and regional policies have been analyzed to identify similarities and gaps in existing policies supporting NSWRM implementation for future harmonisation of water and agricultural policy on local, regional, national and EU levels. The interim results of this analysis have been published in policy briefs and highlight the need for better harmonization of agro-environmental policies, intersectoral cooperation and awareness-raising among all actors involved. Furthermore, a learning environment is under development to make the gained knowledge available.

Conclusions

Preliminary conclusions indicate notable differences among European countries and case studies, which present a challenge for comparative environmental studies. OPTAIN aims to tackle these challenges by enhancing the harmonisation of data, methods, and policies to improve the valuation and acceptance of environmental measures, such as NSWRM. Huge efforts have been made to improve the modelling of the efficiency of NSWRM with regard to water and nutrient retention in the 14 case studies. The developed R scripts for model input data preparation and harmonization as well as for the entire chain of model setup, calibration, evaluation and post-processing is of great help for all SWAT+ and other model users world-wide.

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Connecting stakeholder engagement to governance processes and decision making for climate adaptation and sustainability

Enhancing the Knowledge Bases for Decision-Making in the Environmental Courts: A Call for Collaborative Innovation

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Summary

This presentation explores the environmental decision-making within the Swedish Land and Environment Courts, particularly in relation to hydropower and the current relicensing processes in Sweden. We highlight the critical need for innovative tools to capture and represent the complexity of environmental impacts in the material submitted to the Courts – i.e. the basis for their decision. By sharing the current challenges, we extend an invitation to tool developers to engage in conversation and collaborate with us, aiming to enhance legal outcomes and promote sustainability in Sweden.

Introduction

The reevaluation of hydropower in Sweden is influenced by the EU's Water Framework Directive, which aims to protect and improve aquatic environments within the EU. The Directive, adopted in 2000, requires member states to maintain "good ecological status" for water bodies (Directive 2000/60/EC). For hydropower in Sweden, this means that hydropower plants must be reevaluated to ensure they meet modern environmental standards. The reevaluations focus on minimizing negative environmental impacts, such as effects on water flows and habitats for aquatic organisms, which may involve requirements for fish passages, altered flow regimes, and other measures to improve water quality and biodiversity (Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management, 2018).

With the introduction of new environmental permits for hydropower plants and an increased need for collaboration between various stakeholders, the Swedish Land and Environment Courts are engaged in a process where legal decisions must consider a wide range of values and aspects. This development signifies a change in how information is compiled and presented to the courts, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive collaboration to ensure that all relevant environmental aspects are taken into account in the reevaluations.

Environmental law plays a central part for the transition towards sustainability. This project aims for more effective decisions in the Swedish Land and Environment Courts related to climate, water and biodiversity by improving the knowledge basis handed in to the courts. The question of knowledge is central, because values that cannot be described monetary or quantitatively are generally valued less in the courts' decisions (Ågren, 2023). The courts need a knowledge basis with a better representation of connections, uncertainty and long-term effects.

It is well known that stakeholders can contribute to a more comprehensive knowledge basis (e.g. Hage et al., 2010). Poorly run collaborative processes will not aid the production of a sustainable knowledge basis for the courts. Our goal here is to select and adapt existing tools that enable the courts to make more informed decisions. The tools should encompass how collaboration between various stakeholders can occur with respect to gathering and present knowledge from different aspects, perspectives, and values. This knowledge then needs to reflect the complexity while providing the Land and Environment Courts with enough to make a decision. It also involves linking different system levels/scales since each decision (permit) is directly connected to other decisions on water regulation in the same drainage basin. This also affects the energy system at large. We think participatory modelling tools can be suitable due to their ability to handle complexity (Hedelin et al., 2021; Voinov et al., 2018). The tools will aim not only to enhance the immediacy and sustainability of court decisions but also to establish a model for integrating environmental considerations into legal frameworks in Sweden going forward.

Approach

A number of efforts have recently been made to improve the process of “selecting the right tool for the job” (e.g. Voinov et al., 2018). There already exist numerous tools that have great potential to aid our problem. This presentation and conference attendance are important steps in the process of identifying and adopting 1-3 tools suitable for the Swedish context. We will present an overview of the current processes and challenges encountered in environmental decision-making in Sweden, particularly focusing on the collaboration required for hydropower plants examinations. The presentation and conference will function as a platform where we explain the particularities of the Swedish case and the audience can share ideas and suggest methods and tools that they find appropriate.

Conclusions

This presentation aims to highlight the urgent need for enhanced tools and methodologies in the realm of environmental law, particularly within the context of the Swedish Land and Environment Courts' decision-making processes. By inviting collaboration with developers of innovative tools, we hope to foster a dialogue focused on practical solutions for the current challenges in environmental rulings in Sweden. Our objective is to explore potential improvements in the courts' knowledge basis to ensure more comprehensive and sustainable decisions are made. This initiative represents a step towards a more informed and effective legal approach to environmental issues in Sweden, with the hope that successful practices can inspire similar efforts in other jurisdictions.

Acknowledgements

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A Participatory Agent-Based Model to Evaluate Climatic Effects on Education and Migration Decisions in Senegal

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Summary

We developed a participatory agent-based modelling approach with migration and rural development professionals in Senegal to analyze policy-driven questions of rural investment and mobility under climate uncertainty. Our stakeholder discussions identified the need to develop a new computational module that accurately represents human capital investment decisions as part of a broader livelihood portfolio. We applied this model to environmental change scenarios identified by our stakeholder group, which demonstrate different migration and education patterns under drought and saltwater intrusion. Our results suggest that different policy approaches will be required to promote rural development under different types of climatic stress.

Introduction

Agriculture is often the most significant source of employment in developing countries; yet, climate-driven threats to agricultural livelihoods pose challenges to economic mobility at the individual scale and to economic development at the societal scale. These are particular challenges for countries in West Africa, which face concurrent pressures of historical economic underinvestment, a demographic youth bulge, and rapidly-changing climatic conditions. Agent-based models (ABMs) can help decision-makers explore feedbacks between these changing societal-level processes and individual livelihood decision-making.

Methodology and Results

We conducted a series of in-person and online workshops with a group of policymaking and academic professionals whose work focused on migration in Senegal to develop a conceptual model for rural investments and mobility under future climate uncertainty. As a result of these workshops, we extended a previously-developed ABM of livelihood and migration decisions, the Migration, Intensification, and Diversification as Adaptive Strategies (MIDAS; Bell, Hernandez, & Oppenheimer, 2019) model, to include representation of livelihood capabilities and aspirations as part of agents' decision portfolio (Carling, 2002; Haas, 2021). This approach helps us better address a question identified by stakeholders during a participatory systems mapping exercise: how will environmental change shape human capital investments, including migration and education?

While previous versions of MIDAS and other ABMs account for the ability of agents to project future income streams from various livelihood options, they generally constrain agents' choices to only those options for which they have enough training and resources at a given time step. In this extension, we allow agents to consider future livelihood aspirations that are not currently accessible to them, but may be enabled by their near-term livelihood activities and investments (Fig. 1). This provides a consistent framework for representing real-world decision-making in which individuals may consciously plan life course paths that involve near-term investments (e.g. educational training) to facilitate a range of future livelihood options.

With our stakeholder group, we identified three focal scenarios to analyze using this approach: (i) a Base Case that projects the current geographic distribution of economic opportunities into the future; (ii) a short-term Senegal River Drought scenario in the country's northeast, and (iii) a long-term Saltwater Intrusion scenario in the country's relatively prosperous coastal regions. Our preliminary results find that individual migration and higher education investments lead to greater individual income benefits in the Senegal River Drought scenario compared to the Saltwater Intrusion scenario (Fig. 2, left). Such investments provide a pathway for individuals to cope with short-term environmental shocks by accessing other livelihood opportunities that are relatively

insulated from drought. By contrast, saltwater intrusion chronically diminishes high-income opportunities, absent new economic development policies. At a societal scale, we find that Senegal River Drought increases migration from regions adjoining the Senegal River (e.g. Matam, Kanel, and Bakel) to a nearby arc of regions in the country’s center (Fig. 2, right), while Saltwater Intrusion catalyzes migration from traditionally prosperous coastal departments (e.g. Louga and Saint-Louis) to the groundnut producing region in Senegal’s southwest.

Figure 1. Agents evaluate livelihood portfolio options as a combination of near-term livelihoods (capabilities) and potential longer-term opportunities (aspirations) if they gain skills and/or educational training.

Figure 2. (Left) Mean individual income in the years prior to and following an agent’s first migration trip (solid lines) and completing post-secondary education (dashed lines) for three scenarios: Base Case (blue), Senegal River Drought (green), and Saltwater Intrusion (purple). (Right) Senegalese departments that lose population (red) and gain population (blue) for the Senegal River Drought scenario, relative to Base Case.

Conclusions

While still preliminary, our results demonstrate that different types of environmental changes lead to fundamentally different migration and educational patterns. This is in part driven by how such changes shape the individual-scale payoffs to human capital investments. Therefore, different approaches will be required to build resilience to different climate impacts: shorter-term shocks require policies that expand access to education and migration, while chronic climate stress requires the development of new climate-resilient industries that incentivize human capital investments. More broadly, our participatory modelling approach demonstrates the importance of co-creating research questions to identify gaps in research across modelling scales.

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Pitfalls of Prediction & Participation in SES Modeling

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Summary

A challenge to modeling social-ecological systems (SES) includes persistent expectations that models should be predictive and/or find “solutions” to particular management concerns. The inherent complexity in SES means that an emphasis on prediction is misplaced and potentially reduces model efficacy in participatory decision-making. Further, an emphasis on public participation in decision-making constricts potential benefits from employing highly sophisticated SES models. There is a need for practitioners to re-think how, why, and when to employ SES-modeling in participatory decision-making.

Introduction

A primary value of SES modeling for decision-making is that computers can do what human brains cannot. While recognizing that SES are too complex for humans to process, there is a simultaneous expectation that SES models be predictive (Allison et al. 2018; Drechsler 2020; Steger et al. 2021; Cockerill 2024). This prevailing emphasis on prediction, which is a proxy for certainty, reflects an historic artifact of a mechanistic, ‘balanced’ view of the world in which linear models can offer definitive predictions (Cockerill et al. 2009; Cockerill et al. 2017; Schlüter et al. 2012). Additionally, model users often presume that if a model predicts something, this will crystallize into a management ‘solution’ and focusing on ‘solutions’ is problematic when addressing wicked problems.

For decades practitioners have suggested that systems models are most beneficial as boundary objects to reveal differences in perspectives and to segregate facts about a physical system from beliefs or values about that system (cf Forrester 1993; Lorie and Cardwell 2006; Lindkvist et al. 2020; Solomon et al. 2020). While there are increasing cautions about expecting prediction (Thompson 2022; Edmonds 2023) using models as boundary objects is not yet a primary focus for SES modeling efforts (Drechsler 2020; Steger et al 2021). This reality is coupled with contemporary expectations that decisions will be made in open, publicly accessible fora. Yet developing models of highly complex systems in a public venue is often a fraught exercise rather than some unalloyed good endeavor.

Approach

This work is based on recent literature reviews of SES modeling as well as reflections from the author’s work in participatory modeling.

Conclusion / Recommendation

One way to shift expectations from prediction and a concomitant expectation of certainty, is to embrace different levels of modeling and participation for different purposes. For example, to gain depth in understanding how any SES functions, experts from diverse disciplines should create complicated models that widely and deeply try to capture system complexity (with concomitant uncertainty) as an endeavor in basic science. Under very specialized circumstances, these sophisticated models could potentially be used in participatory decision-making. Perhaps the greatest value in developing complicated models, however, is to generate better input to populate less complicated models to serve as boundary objects in decision-making (see Sun et al. 2016). To meet expectations for transparency these simpler models should be created collaboratively with decision-makers and/or the general public. While less complicated models necessarily sacrifice how system complexity is represented, they can help engage people in exploring system relationships, in generating better questions about issues, and in learning about system complexity and potential tradeoffs among various decision paths. This approach can also reduce solution-seeking and shift

attention toward identifying ways to cope with uncertainty and to learn how to adapt as new situations arise (Schlüter et al.2019; Elsayah et al., 2020; Rounsevell et al., 2021).

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A Knowledge Base and Interpretive Model for Water Use Management and Governance

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Abstract

The history of humanity, and current practices and decision-making, reflects many disruptions, events, and trends that have affected access to water. Water continues to be a vital issue today, across the planet. Confronted by climate change, land-use change, and often crumbling infrastructure, nations, regions, and communities are faced with major investment and trade-off decisions that require anticipatory adaptive governance and planning. A structured knowledge base describing how major events have historically driven changes in physical water systems and management could be of great help. In principle, this structured knowledge base could be used to develop theories or models to understand and inform decisions affecting water management and governance of social-ecological-technological systems (SETS).

Participatory modelling and engagements can speed up and intensify social learning and improving human capacities for anticipatory adaptive governance and management of complex SETS issues (Glynn et al., 2017). The creation and use of knowledge bases that seek to structure and aggregate different SETS management and governance experiences may also be helpful in transferring knowledge from a diversity of SETS case studies with different social and biophysical settings and dynamics. These knowledge bases can aid meaningful and sustained community and stakeholder engagements through the creation and use of Records of Engagement and Decision-making (RoED, Cockerill et al., 2019).

Here, we present a general knowledge base structure and a high-level interpretive model that we have applied to twenty highly diverse case studies, focused on water use management and governance, mainly from the United States, but also from New Zealand and Chile. Our knowledge base consists of four tables that describe the characteristics of:

- (1) the events, trends, or triggers affecting or driving change in water use (and associated social and biophysical consequences);
- (2) the attendant changes in water use, water supply, and water quality (or other conditions relevant to the built / natural water system);
- (3) the management and governance responses, socio-economic consequences or dependencies, and interactions and impacts on other natural resources; and
- (4) the use, non-use, availability (or lack) of information relevant to governing and managing the water use system and issue, along with the potential transfer value of the case study for understanding other similar water use systems and issues.

Our knowledge base also makes use of causal loop graphics that provide a synthesis, for each case study, of the most important drivers and consequences of change in the built and natural water system. The causal graphics additionally identify social or human actions and decisions, taken with a high degree of explicit intent, from less intentional or conscious drivers of change or consequences. The construction and description of each case is based on a mix of cited journal articles, reports, and news articles. The tables and causal graphics for these case studies has received at least one review with subsequent revisions. Given that available documentation is always

incomplete, and any interpretation and synthesis effort likely to be subjective, we encourage improvements and corrections to be made through active curation and improvement of the knowledge base case study descriptions.

Following the construction of the knowledge base of twenty case studies, we used a grounded theory approach to further synthesize and understand the drivers and consequences of water use changes, and the challenges and mechanisms used by different communities to address those changes. Interestingly, we find that focusing only on the quantitatively most important consumptive uses of water (e.g., irrigation, thermoelectric cooling, public supply), often misses the mark in explaining how different communities perceive, accept (or not) and ultimately drive the management and governance of water systems. We see this focus on resource stock and flow quantifications also as a potential flaw in current water accounting and natural capital accounting efforts (Bagstad et al., 2020; La Notte et al., 2021). Water quality and other types of water condition aspects also matter, including for water reuse and return flows, but are generally not well integrated into water use and availability assessments. Even more importantly, non-consumptive uses of water – such as for recreation, navigation or transport, ecological needs, cultural or spiritual needs – are also rarely well-considered or well-integrated into water system decisions. Social and cultural norms and values come into play as do short-term local-scale considerations of basic needs for water to support existing lifeways and practices (Glynn, Chiavacci, et al., 2022; Glynn, Rhodes, et al., 2022). Governance structures, institutional facilitations or barriers, and historical legacies also play an important role. Included are the past establishment of different laws, policies, and practices at different levels of governance, past and present inter-group conflicts or grievances, and also community experiential learning and collective memories. Planning and investing for the future can be done with some success (e.g., water management and governance in New Mexico), but the possibility and reality of water system failures, for unconsidered or unaddressed reasons, is also ever present.

We hope that our proposed water use knowledge base and high-level interpretive model can contribute to more informed decisions in the governance and management of built and natural water systems.

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The Case of Building “Informed Trust” in Models, and Tools to Put Theory Into Practice

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Summary

Lack of trust in model outputs can inhibit the use of models in decision-making, and ultimately diminish the value of modelling projects. Conversely, if models are treated as irrefutable, outputs can be applied inappropriately, undermining trust in the long term. Thus maximum value from modelling requires stakeholders to have “informed trust”, i.e. an appreciation of what the model can, and can’t, do, and why. Here we describe how informed trust is built through relationships and two-way communication over a project lifecycle, and share tools for building modellers’ skills in developing informed trust in models amongst stakeholders.

Introduction

Models are designed for a specific purpose, e.g. to improve understanding, to answer questions or to inform decisions. Models and model outputs are often used by non-modellers, however, and may even be used in applications for which they were never intended. Furthermore, modelling projects frequently rely on input from non-modellers, either directly (via the provision of funding, data and specialist knowledge of the system being modelled and the questions driving the study) or indirectly (via use of existing data and published information). If people don’t have sufficient trust in the models, the modellers or the project design, they may be reluctant to support the modelling endeavour. The challenge therefore is how to find the balance between trusting models enough, but not too much?

Methodology and Results

In this presentation, present a variety of resources and approaches to support modellers in building “informed trust” in models, through engaging with key stakeholders in a way which encourages understanding of how the model/s work. These resources include a light-hearted video to demonstrate how relationship-building can overcome common conflicts (O’Brien et al., 2022); a framework for characterizing and resolving model-data discrepancies (Vilas et al., 2023 in press); and guidelines on engagement approaches which build, and conversely kill, trust in models.

Conclusions

Informed trust in models finds the balanced between trusting models enough, but not too much, and is built through investing in relationships with relevant parties over the life cycle of modelling projects. Building informed trust through meaningful relationships takes time, money and skill and therefore needs to be factored into project design and budget.

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Justice, Equity and Inclusion Aspects of Participatory Salinity Management in California's San Joaquin Valley

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Summary

The Central Valley Salinity Coalition (CVSALTS) has undertaken a novel participatory approach to address long-term salinity management issues in the Central Valley of California that embraces the planning goals of justice, equity and inclusion. Unlike the majority of environmental planning initiatives in California this activity is anticipated to last decades and is largely financed by a broad coalition of stakeholders who have had representation since the onset of the program. This talk examines some of the environmental justice, equity and inclusion challenges and describes how CVSALTS intends to overcome them after providing a brief background of the unique characteristics of salinity management on the west-side of the San Joaquin Valley – a sub-basin of California's Central Valley.

Introduction

Social justice, stakeholder equity and inclusion principles are now endogenous to most State and bond-funded water resource and water quality grant programs in the State of California. Watershed management best practices and regulation to protect water quality have been recognized as both a social and technical undertaking that includes programs such as: TMDLs – that calculate load allocations based on the assimilative capacity of pollutants discharged to impaired waterbodies; watershed management plans that prescribe a suite of actions to protect environmental resources and other associated pollution control programs. Responsibility for TMDL regulated and nonregulated clean-up is assigned to local stakeholders, watershed management plans are often formulated after a TMDL and are more participatory in design recognizing the characteristics of each watershed and permitting a more flexible compliance strategy to meet water quality standards. All regulatory approaches to water and water quality resource management benefit from a comprehensive understanding of watershed hydrology and contaminant sources as well as the biogeochemistry of the pollutants discharged. Effective communication with stakeholders before and during the imposition of water quality regulation is of critical importance for stakeholders to fully understand this logic, lend their support for the policy, address risk management, mitigation planning, and concerns over equity and for both initial and long-term stakeholder participation. It is well recognized that successful environmental planning and water quality protection at the watershed level can only be successful by engaging with stakeholders early and throughout the implementation process.

Even when stakeholders are engaged in the process this engagement may not be equitable. Although significant progress has been made in the inclusion of social factors in environmental planning and decision making – ultimate success is often sabotaged by a lack of political will or a reluctance to embrace new strategies. The terms social justice, equity, diversity, and inclusion were not in the planning lexicon two decades ago and the lack of a definitive baseline has stymied progress. Another important factor is that the nature of the pollutant being regulated may make it difficult to elaborate secondary impacts and justice, equity and inclusion concerns as is the case with salinity management in the western San Joaquin Valley of California where large agricultural landowners and state, federal and privately managed wetlands are responsible for the bulk of salt load discharge to the San Joaquin River. Controlling salt export can be achieved through strategies such as temporary storage in on-farm and water district managed storage ponds, drainage reuse and recycling, timed release to coincide with periods of high river salt assimilative capacity and, as a last resort, land fallowing. The last option could have an indirect negative impact on agricultural farm worker employment -resulting negative multiplier impacts would affect local commerce and the financial resources of disadvantaged communities. However, direct impacts affect only the major landowning entities and any financial incentives to boost compliance with salinity objectives are enjoyed by these more advantaged entities.

Binary Basin Planning Approach

In 2006, the California Central Valley Water Board, the regulator for water quality developed a novel stakeholder-led approach for addressing critical basin scale water quality issues. The Central Valley Salinity Alternatives for Long-Term Sustainability (CV-SALTS) is a cooperative effort that includes water agencies, regulators, agricultural water district permittees, environmental interests, state, federal and private wetland resource entities and, other stakeholder parties with an interest in Central Valley water quality. The CV-SALTS mission and goal is to successfully implement a Central-Valley wide management plan that tackles both surface water salinity and groundwater nitrate that retains the vitality of California's agricultural economy and sustaining economic growth while ensuring supply of reliable, high-quality drinking water in particular to vulnerable and disadvantaged rural communities in the Central Valley. The westside of the San Joaquin River Basin that is the major source of salts exported from the Central Valley is also the region where nitrate contamination of shallow groundwater is the most acute. By taking this binary Basin planning approach addressing salt and nitrate problems simultaneously CV-SALTS is able to address past deficiencies and prior criticism of a lack of attention to environmental justice, stakeholder equity and inclusion concerns. Unlike prior basin myopic planning approaches that considered either surface water or groundwater this approach takes a more wholistic view with a goal to treat the Basin as a single hydrologic system. This is a realistic and logical change given that it is surface water applications of irrigation water that downward displace nitrates in fertilizer and waste discharges to the shallow groundwater. Nitrate is a tasteless, odorless, and invisible chemical that can cause health effects when found in high levels in drinking water. Hence, assurance of a safe, reliable drinking water supply to all residents of the region is a primary goal.

Progress to date

The presentation provides an overview of progress to date on this CVSALTS Basin planning initiative – the first phase of which is anticipated to take 14 years. The Salt and Nitrate Control Program (SNMP) was approved in 2018 as Amendments to the existing Basin Plan to encourage management of salt and nitrate through the establishment of management zones. In the case of nitrate these management zones are the result of multiple dischargers working collectively to manage nitrates within the defined management area and ensure safe drinking water - ultimately to develop and implement a long-term plan for restoration of groundwater to meet applicable water quality objectives. The use of the management zone concept is most viable regulatory tool for both nitrate and salinity in the first phase of the implementation program salinity however at this initial stage these activities are being conducted independently. At the end of 2023, 513 households were provided with free bottled water under the auspices of the Valley Water Collaborative in the San Joaquin Basin where domestic well nitrate concentrations exceeded drinking water standards. The Salinity Program, on the other hand, elected to use a stakeholder funded Prioritization and Optimization (P&O) Study initiative to offer stakeholders an opportunity to opt out of the Basin-wide cooperative effort and seek compliance as individual entities or otherwise pay into the long-term planning effort. The initial phase of the P&O study has focused on data acquisition activities to establish baseline salinity conditions for future modelling studies and set preliminary planning targets in the process of deciding among potential salinity management strategies. The suite of models for the various phases of the study have been selected, after careful evaluation by CVSALTS technical experts. Data assimilation and compilation and model calibration are ongoing activities.

The talk will highlight the novel and innovative aspects of this stakeholder-led salt and nitrate planning initiative that may provide useful regulatory policy insights for other arid, agriculturally-dominated river basins.

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Eco-efficiency-Based Sustainable Tourism in Small Islands using Participatory Systems Approach: A Case of Riau Islands, Indonesia

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Summary

Tourism in small island ecosystems, such as Riau Islands Province in Indonesia, encounters substantial obstacles despite being a popular destination. Challenges in environmental, social, economic, and institutional aspects impede the progress towards sustainable tourism development. This study highlights the need for integrated governance and stakeholder involvement to address those four aspects as sub-systems in tourism system effectively. Using participatory approaches and system dynamics modeling, this study aims to identify priority interventions as leverage for a sustainable tourism system. This ongoing research seeks to enhance tourism while minimizing environmental impacts.

Introduction

Tourism is a complex system (Baggio, 2008, 2020), particularly in small island ecosystems which are typically highly vulnerable (Weißhuhn et al., 2018), and for which sustainable tourism is therefore challenging. The Riau Islands Province in Indonesia is characterized by a small archipelago, consisting of more than 2400 islands spanning 8,201.72 km² with 96% sea area. It has emerged as a prominent international tourist destination, next to Bali. The high number of tourist arrivals, unfortunately, has not been matched by an increased capacity for tourism management and governance. There is a lack of cross-sectoral institutional coordination and integration to support tourism as an industry. Furthermore, sustainable tourism initiatives encounter environmental challenges, including oil spillage (Purnaweni et al., 2022), solid waste generation (Sari et al., 2023), and marine pollution (Syakti et al., 2018), in addition to limited opportunities for the local economy and employment. This study establishes that sustainable tourism requires harmonious integration of economic, social, environmental, and institutional sub-systems, taking into account both present and future tourism carrying capacity (Global Sustainable Tourism Council (GSTC), 2019; United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) & United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), 2005). To accomplish this, it is imperative to involve stakeholders to evaluate various complex system components and identify leverage points aligned with local assessments and priorities.

Methodology

This research combines participatory approaches, Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) (Warfield, 1976) and system dynamics (Forrester, 1961, 1968) to determine participatory leverage in the sub-system components of institutional governance, i.e. tourism policies that are worthy of being prioritized as priority interventions in a sustainable tourism system with four sub-systems. As this research is currently ongoing, the results cannot be submitted at this time.

Conclusions

This research has the capacity to offer practical recommendations to stakeholders, particularly the tourism industry, local government, and local communities, on how to boost tourist arrivals while at the same time minimizing its adverse effects on the environment, social, and economy. Integration or addition of a spatial modelling approach would be helpful for our research, enabling observation and modelling over time of land-use changes and arrangements of spatial allocation for tourism and waste processing.

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A Six-Step Approach Toward the River Contract in North-East Sardinia (IT)

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Summary

The definition of a clear procedural process in the activation of new river contracts is configured as a central and preparatory activity of DADU in the technical-scientific support of the territories that have shown strong interest to the activation of the River Contracts (CdF). This definition inserts, interprets it, reworks it and contextualizes it to the Padrogiano River (North-East of Sardinia, IT) giving particular attention to the need to reduce the vulnerabilities generated by extreme climatic events and the uncertainty of expected trends.

Introduction

The implementation of public policies aimed at protecting strategic environmental resources, such as rivers, is currently affected - in European experiences, particularly in France and Italy - by CdF, considered as strategic planning tools at a local level. These are forms of concerted and cooperative territorial planning, tools for sharing between public-private partnerships in subjective decisions. They generate an integrated policy in the sector of soil protection, protection of water and environmental resources and valorisation of the territory by relating hydraulic, urban, naturalistic, economic and social aspects. In fact, the main pressures on river territories in Italy are characterized by widespread pollution, by hydro-morphological alterations closely linked to interventions to protect against hydrogeological risk, by specific pollution and by water withdrawals. Furthermore, the artificialisation of waterways and infrastructural transformations, in addition to the growing urbanization of river territories, constitute one of the main factors that expose the population to environmental risks caused by floods.

The function of the CdF is to overcome some critical issues of territorial planning and the complex management of decision-making processes that concern the waterways crossed by the themes illustrated above. The territories of the river basins are in fact affected by a multiplicity of interests: territories need to reduce hydraulic risk, interests for the environmental and urban use of the river, competing uses of the water resource, the need to conserve the biodiversity of the river. These interests express requests that generate conflicts both on a local and large-area scale.

The territorialization and implementation of public policies at the river basin scale gives shape to the CdF which, in over 10 years of diffusion in all Italian regions, have proven to be an effective tool proposed voluntarily by local administrations. It has had wide diffusion in Italy since 2007, when the National Table of River Contracts (TNCdF) established itself as a group of interdisciplinary experts which produced numerous initiatives for the promotion of this instrument. The TNCdF underlines that River Contracts can be considered an effective tool to help improve the adaptive capacity at the level of river basins or individual water covers. The CdF are in fact considered as an action for adaptation that responds to the guidelines of the National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change (SNAC). For this reason, they can contribute to achieving the objectives set by the European Green Deal, as well as to the implementation of the National Strategy for Sustainable Development. "The TNCdF draws its strength and credibility from being a "Community of practice and learning" which aims to produce organized and quality knowledge on integrated river basin management, to which everyone has free access. In this community, which constitutes a rather unique experience in the Italian panorama, the participants aim for continuous learning through awareness of their own knowledge and that of others".

Methodology Phase toward a River and Results

The different experiences in Italy, coordinated by the National Table on River Contracts, and more recently by the coordination of the Ministry of the Environment which established the Observatory on River Contracts, converge on the different phases that are characterizing the decision-making process toward the Contract of Padrogiano River (PRC) in the North-East Sardinia.

The first phase of the decision-making process of PRC is a political phase, that of the so-called "preliminary contract". It is achieved when the territorial leadership of Olbia Municipality signs a "*declaration of intent*". It is the first document that highlights the political vision and the will to implement processes of active protection of the Padrogiano river. It is open to membership by all subjects - from the public and private sectors - in various capacities interested in the territory of the river basin and connected to the use of its waters. DADU supports the territorial leadership in establish this declaration. The declaration defines the principles which inspire the path towards the River Contract, specifies general objectives, highlights the critical issues and specifies the working methodology.

The second phase has a technical approach. It concerns the "*representation of knowledge*", in which a summary report is developed on the environmental values and critical issues of the river basin at different temporal (e.g., climate parameter trend horizon and return times) and spatial (river upstream – estuarine – nearshore area) scales. Possible solution hypotheses are hypothesized from which to start to formulate the action strategies for the next phase.

The third is the "*design phase*" in which strategic scenarios are developed to provide responses to the territory and the vulnerabilities highlighted by the public and private actors involved. In particular, the actors who signed the document of intent for the first phase are present. It is the discussion and sharing phase in which priority strategies are identified; for this reason, various moments of discussion are organized between local institutions and private actors but also civil society subjects: examples include participation tables, focus groups, cultural and training events for territorial animation, etc. The phase ends with the development of a medium-long term "strategic document" through which to evaluate the measures and commitments to be adopted to implement concrete territorial management actions. The document contains a program of priority actions on the basis of which the actors make specific implementation and monitoring commitments.

The fourth phase is that of implementation in which the *Plan of Actions* that must be carried out within three years is explained to make the action to safeguard the river resource effective. The actions will be of different nature (environmental, infrastructural, intangible). The Plan must be organized so that the respective obligations and commitments, implementation times and methods, the necessary human and economic resources, as well as the related financial coverage are clear.

The fifth phase, in fact, is that of the actual *contract sign*, the formal act in which all the actors sign a document which has legal validity as it reports the commitments that each actor assumes to achieve the actions and strategic objectives. It also contains the rules with which the implementation control policies will be implemented and the rules that define the rewards or the sanctioning regime in the event an actor is found to be in default of the signed commitments.

The last phase is that of *action monitoring* which involves the organizational structure of the river contract in a periodic check on the effectiveness of the actions implemented over a three year horizon, on their compliance with the river protection objectives set out in the contract.

Conclusions

The application of the methodology at each phase aims at evaluating the effective level of voluntariness, inclusion, collaboration and assumption of mutual commitments in the Padrogiano CdF. Specifically, from a careful analysis of the in progress technical support, some critical issues of implementation have been highlighted.

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Modelling the Impact Pathways of Collaborative Governance Initiatives in the US

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Summary

The shift from command-and-control to collaborative governance for environmental and water challenges in the US requires a deeper understanding of its impacts. Our research reviews fifty-six cases of collaborative water quality governance initiatives (2010-2022), revealing that improved networking and communication are vital for other outcomes such as conflict resolution. While conflicts and mistrust pose challenges, positive outcomes include actionable knowledge, better decision-making, and water quality improvement. System dynamic modelling highlights trade-offs and dynamics, emphasizing the importance of social outcomes for effective water quality management.

Introduction

Collaborative initiatives represent a fundamental departure from conventional practices, signalling a paradigm shift towards more inclusive and adaptive approaches to water quality management (Scott, 2015). These collaboratives bring together a diverse range of stakeholders, including government agencies, industry representatives, NGOs, and local communities (Gerlak et al., 2012). While these initiatives have reported positive impacts such as improvements in water quality, there remains a significant challenge in establishing clear links between these outcomes and the collaborative themselves (Newig et al., 2019 2023). One of the key challenges lies in understanding the interconnections among impacts and outcomes, which form the basis of impact pathways (Ulibarri et al., 2023). To address these gaps, using qualitative research, first we characterize the features of collaborative initiatives and then articulate the social outcomes and impacts on water quality improvement resulting from collaborative governance initiatives. Furthermore, we explore the relationships and dynamics among these impacts and outcomes to map the intricate pathways through which collaborative efforts contribute to water quality improvement. By elucidating these pathways, we aim to enhance our understanding of the effectiveness of collaborative governance in addressing water quality issues and identify opportunities for optimizing collaborative approaches in the future.

Methodology and Results

This study employs a case survey method to review peer-reviewed articles on collaborative governance in water quality management. Following PRISMA guidelines, 122 relevant articles were identified from 225 initial titles and abstracts, with 56 selected for in-depth analysis. A rigorous coding process yielded 890 codes, facilitating systematic data analysis. Iterative coding was utilized for nuanced insights, complemented by descriptive and exploratory techniques, including system dynamic modeling.

Results: Dynamic of Impacts and outcomes

Among the notable outcomes and impacts, predominant ones are the formulation of more pertinent policies and enhanced compliance with regulations ($n = 53$, 94%), alongside improvements in water quality ($n = 41$, 73%). The results further indicated other outcomes, encompassing fostering networking and communication ($n = 22$, 39%), empowering stakeholders ($n = 20$, 35%), facilitating consensus-building and conflict resolution ($n = 19$, 33%), and generating actionable knowledge ($n = 19$, 33%). Relatively, in certain instances ($n = 21$, 37%), adverse impacts were also identified, such as conflicts, mistrust, and instances where collaboration was used to justify violations of regulations. It is notable that these outcomes and impacts are not achieved in a vacuum and resulted from

process and dynamic pathways (Kirchhoff and Dilling, 2016). Relatively, our results revealed that CGs create a space (third space) where a broad range of actors communicate together and make and even expand their network (Diver, 2022). CGs enable actors to communicate their perspective and experience and at the same time, learn about other people's experiences and perspectives through training, discussion, forums, and workshops, which make them more aware of considerations, complexities, feedback, and interactions of water quality efforts (Figure 1). The results of these communications and interactions produce integrative and actionable knowledge which comes from experiences and fields that are more acceptable and practicable by stakeholders of WQ (Hunt, 2021). These new knowledge and perspectives have built more conscience, trust, and even resolved tensions and disputes at the local level. Upon their responsibility, whether practitioners, agency representatives, scientists, farmers, private sectors, or policy makers, CG initiatives enable them to enact these new attitudes and lessons in current and future endeavors, which in a considerable number of cases produce better policy and more compliance with regulations of WQ. In more cases, CGs have created social and executive capacities for enacting new projects, stewarding, and monitoring the waterscapes, and even tracking the results of WQ regulations (Scott, 2015; Diver, 2022). Epistemic communities, knowledge networks, specific initiatives for specific waterscapes, and taskforces are examples of new social capitals and capacities that are produced new technologies, solutions, and regulations to foster the sharing, practicing, and understanding of water quality issues and respective efforts (Andrew, 2016).

Conclusions

In summary, our nationwide synthesis of fifty-six peer-reviewed articles (published between 2010 and 2022) explored collaborative efforts' outcomes and impacts on water quality in the United States. We discovered that water quality improvement follows complex, non-linear pathways. These pathways facilitate engagement, communication, capacity building, and integrated knowledge, leading to improvements in water quality. However, trade-offs exist among outcomes, especially when addressing conflict resolution or capacity building before focusing on water quality improvement. As a result, it is critical to consider the non-linearity and complexities to achieve intended outcomes and impacts as there is no one size fits all for collaborative governance.

Figure 1. Dynamics of outcomes and impacts in Water Quality Collaboratives

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Tools and software for participatory modeling and decision support

Integrating Optimal Water Management Into an Open-Source Flexible Hydrological Modelling Framework

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Summary

Water management software is used for optimally managing water demand, reservoir operations, and identifying the impacts of different operational strategies in complex watershed systems. Such tools generally tend to simulate only the in-network mass balance, importing surface runoff and reservoir ET from external sources. There is benefit, however, in a fully coupled approach, where optimal management is simulated simultaneously with the hydrologic cycle. Such an approach supports a more rigorous treatment of return flows, and runoff impacts due to changes in agricultural/forestry management or natural phenomena such as wildfire. It is also significantly faster than a loosely coupled approach, due to avoid the need for file-based data transfer between models. This speed is critical for participatory modelling, where models are run in real time to help inform decision makers and enable stakeholders to examine the outcomes of different operational strategies.

Here, we discuss the integration of a linear programming-based water management optimizer integrated within the open-source Raven hydrologic modelling framework (Craig, 2020). Building upon the land use change and reservoir simulation capabilities already present within Raven, the tool supports simultaneous simulation of the non-linear water balance while optimally satisfying a user-specified set of management goals and constraints. These goals, which can be applied conditionally depending upon time of year and system states, are expressed using flexible expression statements. The software is demonstrated using a case study in Western Canada, where it is intended to be used for real-time participatory modelling with stakeholders.

Because Raven is also configurable as a Basic Model Interface (BMI) (Hutton et al., 2020), the tool may be readily integrated with other models in the future. In addition, Raven, which also supports simulation of synthetic tracers and stream temperature, may later be extended to consider these variables in the optimization problem.

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Synthetic Data for Reef Restoration Decision Support

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Summary

A synthetic data pipeline is developed to generate synthetic data for a reef decision support tool, the Adaptive Dynamic Reef Intervention Algorithm (ADRIA). This data is intended to allow publication of model demonstrations without prematurely revealing restoration decisions which are sensitive to rightsholders, and for model testing, validation, and exploration. The data pipeline is developed using the python package Synthetic Data Vault and a test synthetic data set is demonstrated for the purpose of exploring ADRIA's location selection capability, which uses environmental data layers to select reef sites at which to implement restoration activities.

Introduction

ADRIA (Adaptive Dynamic Reef Intervention Algorithms) is a decision-support tool designed to assist in the planning and implementation of restoration projects on the Great Barrier Reef (Iwanaga et al 2023). ADRIA is informed by a parsimonious mathematical model of coral survival, fecundity, growth, and recruitment, forced by environmental drivers, ecological processes, and restorative interventions. The decision-support algorithms in ADRIA use environmental and ecological data layers as criteria to dynamically select locations best suited to implement restoration activities under different ecological and environmental conditions.

Synthetic data mimics the statistical properties of real-world datasets while removing reference to sensitive or confidential information in the original dataset (Quintana, 2020). Synthetic data is also useful for general model testing and development, with many methods available for generating data models (Raghunathan, 2021). Although not widely used in ecological and environmental modelling, synthetic data can support model testing and analyses where rightsholders are sensitive to data disclosure for study areas, or data collection is expensive.

In the context of reef modelling, synthetic data can be used to support model analyses without referring to specific sites, reefs, or study areas. Data generation can also be time consuming and expensive, so the creation of smaller, purpose-built synthetic data sets can allow timely model testing and exploration. Datasets created for this purpose can be designed to test specific aspects of a reef model or explore conditions of interest not represented in available observational datasets.

This presentation will showcase a synthetic data pipeline developed for the reef decision-support tool ADRIA using methods from the Python package Synthetic Data Vault (Patki, Wedge, & Veeramachaneni, 2016) and others. Use of synthetic data for model testing and exploration is demonstrated using a simple 10 site test set with properties modified to test the site selection algorithm in ADRIA. This is used to address 4 key questions about site selection for reef restoration using ADRIA:

- Do heat refugia show better coral survival into the future than other sites?
- When intervening without choosing sites based on heat stress, do outcomes for refugia improve?
- If we guide site selection for intervention based on heat stress, do outcomes for refugia improve relative to the previous case?
- What other factors influence coral survival for heat refugia?

Methodology and Results

ADRIA input data includes several data layers; site data (spatial, describing benthic and geographic information for each reef site), initial coral cover data (spatial), degree heating week data (temporal and spatial, describing the average change in temperature), wave height data (temporal and spatial, describing the maximum wave height) and connectivity (network data, describing the probability of larval flow between sites). Each of these layers were modelled using a different synthetic data model from the python package SDV, chosen to suit the data type being modelled. First the synthetic site data is sampled using the synthetic site data model and then the synthetic spatial coordinates are used to conditionally sample the other data layers using their respective synthetic data models.

The utility of the data (how well it emulates the statistics of the original data) is measured using several methods in the SDMetrics python library, (DataCebo, 2023) chosen to represent how well the synthetic data replicates the distributions of individual variables in each dataset and correlations between pairs of variables. These tests include Chi-squared tests for categorical variables, Kalmagorov-Smirnov tests for continuous variables and correlation matrices. The sample data set used to demonstrate the pipeline is shown to perform well on these metrics, while suggesting some improvements, such as better representation of spatial clustering of sites.

Using the data pipeline developed, a test set of 10 reef sites is designed to have 3 sites which are heat refugia (are always colder on average across time). Using the test set it is shown that these refugia show higher median coral survival than other sites. This survival is improved if implementing restoration activities at random sites and further improved when site selection is guided to prioritise sites which are refugia or providing larvae to refugia. This improvement is found to be more likely if refugia are also protected via solar radiation management (Figure 1).

Conclusions

A synthetic data pipeline is demonstrated for generating data packages for the reef decision support tool ADRIA using an accessible and flexible python package, Synthetic Data Vault. The models created for ADRIA's input datasets generally replicate the statistics of the original datasets well, and a synthetic test set is used to explore ADRIA's location selection algorithms. The test set is very simple but demonstrates exploration of questions around spatial prioritisation during reef restoration using ADRIA.

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Figure 1. Shows the difference in median absolute coral cover between heat refugia sites and non-refugia sites for counterfactual, unguided restorative and guided restorative scenarios at SSP 2. Guided restoration produces a small but significant difference in future cover for heat refugia.

Advancing Nitrogen Management and Water Quality Analysis through Cyberinfrastructure and AI Integration

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Summary

Watershed health is integral to fostering a robust and sustainable Blue Economy, but nitrogen pollution presents a widespread and underestimated threat to both watershed health and the communities reliant on them. The Blue-Green Action Platform Information System (BlueGAP IS) represents a cyber infrastructure designed to support large-scale analysis of water quality and nitrogen analytes data, while also offering customized demographic statistics. Leveraging the capabilities of various AI agents, it enhances user interaction and engagement on nitrogen management topics. Developed in collaboration with academic, non-governmental, and quasi-governmental partners, BlueGAP IS is tailored to address the specific needs of Iowa, Tampa, and the U.S. Virgin Islands. Serving as a cornerstone for understanding nitrogen-related water quality challenges, it fosters global partnerships and promotes sustainable water management practices.

Introduction

The challenge of nitrogen pollution in water bodies necessitates innovative solutions for monitoring and management (Cham et al., 2020). The BlueGAP IS project introduces an advanced cyberinfrastructure that combines large-scale water quality data analysis with tailored demographic statistics. Leveraging AI technologies, this system aims to provide a comprehensive tool for regions critically affected by nitrogen pollution, including Iowa, Tampa, and the U.S. Virgin Islands. This initiative represents a significant collaboration among academic institutions, non-governmental organizations, and quasi-governmental entities, highlighting the importance of interdisciplinary partnerships in addressing environmental challenges.

In addressing the pervasive issue of nitrogen pollution, it is crucial to consider its multifaceted impact on environmental sustainability and public health. Excessive nitrogen, primarily from agricultural runoff and urban waste, contributes to eutrophication in water bodies, leading to oxygen-depleted zones which harm aquatic life and biodiversity (United Nations, 2023; Heil & Muni-Morgan, 2021). Moreover, nitrate pollution poses significant risks to human health, particularly in rural communities reliant on groundwater sources (Craswell, 2021; Follett, 2012). The economic repercussions are equally profound, affecting fisheries, tourism, and water utilities, which are integral components of the Blue Economy (Smith-Godfrey, 2016; Colgan, 2018). To combat these challenges, the BlueGAP Information System utilizes a sophisticated array of AI technologies and cyberinfrastructure tools. By integrating high-resolution spatial and temporal data analysis capabilities, the system not only enhances the accuracy of water quality assessments but also facilitates proactive management strategies. This approach is supported by a robust framework that includes data acquisition from diverse sources (Bernatska et al., 2023) advanced data processing algorithms, and user-friendly interactive platforms that democratize access to critical water quality information (Mount et al., 2010).

Methodology and Results

The BlueGAP IS was developed as a web-based cyber infrastructure system focused on efficiently handling high-dimensional spatiotemporal water quality-related data and optimizing resource utilization. The system architecture employs PostgreSQL with PostGIS spatial extensions for database management, Nginx for web serving, and a combination of React, MUI, JavaScript, HTML, CSS for the frontend, supported by Python, Unicorn, and FastAPI for backend processes.

The system offers unrestricted access to water quality data, integrating data from various repositories such as USGS NWIS and USEPA STORET, among others. It provides a unified platform for discovering information about various champions in selected regions and engaging with their AI agent counterparts, access to extensive datasets, visual representation of time series data, and access to demographic data. The design emphasizes sustainability, modularity, error handling, and efficient data retrieval, adhering to coding principles for a robust and future-proof solution. Data acquisition is managed through cronjobs for systematic updates, with data ingestion using API queries and flat file processing. The system standardizes heterogeneous data from multiple sources, creating a structured and accessible database for user interaction.

The BlueGAP IS showcases diverse features like champions story browsing, action planner, data exploration, and visualization. Users can interact with AI agents for in-depth discussions on nitrogen impacts, navigate through comprehensive data reports, and engage with real-time sensor data across selected regions. The system's user-friendly interface and dynamic data presentation have demonstrated significant potential in enhancing understanding and management of water quality issues.

Conclusions

The initial unveiling of the BlueGAP IS prototype garnered positive feedback, particularly for its innovative approach to water quality management. Key features such as data visualization, AI agent interaction, and champion stories were highlighted for their effectiveness. However, a current limitation involves sensor overlap in locations with multiple sensors, suggesting a potential enhancement through the introduction of a clustering mechanism. Additionally, future development efforts will prioritize incorporating user-requested functionalities, harnessing emerging technologies, and remaining responsive to user needs. These initiatives aim to position BlueGAP IS as a dynamic platform for environmental data analysis and sustainable water management.

Acknowledgements

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HydroSuite: Open Source Collaborative Web-based Software Suite for Hydrological Research and Education

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Summary

HydroSuite is a state-of-the-art collection of web-based software suite for hydrologic workflows with open-source scalable architectures, accessible directly through web browsers. These libraries enable hydrologic data democratization and analysis by encompassing several key aspects of the hydrologic domain, including data management, scientific computing, communication, and community portals. The main purpose of the collection is to simplify data integration, whether acquisition or dissemination, by pushing a significant stack. They facilitate collaboration, knowledge sharing, and innovation, with the potential to reshape hydrologic research, education, and operational activities.

Introduction

In response to the growing demand for accessible online resources serving researchers and interested parties within the environmental and hydrological fields, it becomes imperative to harness and leverage web browser technologies effectively. These play a crucial role in the creation of large-scale complex applications that illustrate the interplay between hydrological sciences and emerging digital developments. A comprehensive approach incorporates efficient data management techniques across both server and client web environments. This extends to the smart handling of externally sourced and publicly accessible data originating from around the globe. By distributing server resource demands, a seamless integration of resources and tools is achieved, resulting in an enhanced dissemination of hydrologic outputs.

With this purpose in mind, we introduce HydroSuite, a collection of open-source software thoroughly developed to cater to the hydrological and environmental community, providing easily accessible tools via browser technology. HydroSuite encompasses a suite of software components, namely: HydroLang (Erazo Ramirez et al., 2022), HydroLang-ML (Erazo Ramirez et al., 2023), HydroLang-BMI (Ewing et al., 2024), HydroCompute (Erazo Ramirez et al., 2024a), and HydroRTC (Erazo Ramirez et al., 2024b). These libraries are designed to tackle an extensive array of applications within the hydrological domain, focusing on user-friendly capabilities and scalable software architecture suitable for broader implementations.

Methodology and Results

The development of these software libraries was done utilizing an open-source, highly scalable ontology that allows for researchers and developers to create workflows through integration of each library's end scope. HydroLang is as a robust library with a variety of functionalities for statistical analysis, modeling, and hydrological tools tailored towards spatiotemporal analysis. Furthermore, it contains functionalities for visualizations, enabling mapping and comprehensive data analytics through charts and tables. It connects with data sources worldwide, accommodating different formats. Within this library, HydroLang-ML and HydroLang-BMI stand out, featuring an HTML-based interface and a simulation-based standard, respectively, catering to a broader user base.

HydroCompute is a high-performance computing library powered by cutting-edge technological advancements of modern browsers to support multithreading on the client side, optimally utilizing the computational resources within a users' devices. The library incorporates different methodologies to enable porting of code from faster programming languages to the browser environment through the Web Assembly standard. The result is an expanded analytical capacity, harnessing client-side hardware for heavy computations. Through the

employment of novel technologies such as Web Workers and WebGPU, HydroCompute enables resourceful data transfers via message passing, which represents an avenue for performance improvement of web applications. HydroRTC is a library that accelerates large-scale data transfer and sharing between peers and servers through decentralized WebRTC and Web Sockets. It's a peer-to-peer and server-to-peer framework enabling efficient data transmission, comprehensive dataset streaming, and task allocation. Facilitating diverse data transfers from satellite imagery to scientific formats like NetCDF, GRIBB, and HDF5, it handles complex and diverse data formats. Leveraging peer-to-peer connectivity, it innovatively disseminates data, whether from server-based repositories or decentralized architectures.

HydroSuite's research scope combines web technologies inherent in the common web browser with server-side technologies, merging them with domain-specific knowledge crucial for comprehensive hydrological analysis. This encompasses data-driven modeling, GIS, statistical analysis, and physical modeling. The libraries democratize information, supplying to diverse users in educational institutions, governmental entities, urban planners, and research avenues. They enable faster and more robust analysis on the web, offering solutions for both server and client-side applications, ensuring these can be deployed across various environments and compatibility with other web-based libraries to enhance application capabilities.

Conclusions

The current technological landscape for web technologies has allowed a significant push towards improvement of data acquisition, sharing, and analysis. These advancements are supported by private and public interested parties that ensure cross-platform compatibility and resource sharing. The collection of software within the HydroSuite aims to empower researchers, educators, and interested users within the hydrological and environmental domain to create end-to-end workflows that enable better and more efficient web applications, with the final goal of creating better analytical tools for disseminating information.

Developed with an object-oriented, highly expandable architecture, the libraries encourage community-driven growth. Users and developers can contribute new use cases, functionalities, and workflow combinations, enriching the toolkit for others. Furthermore, the collection facilitates future expansion by integrating with other web-based libraries, serving as a comprehensive resource hub.

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Development and Application of a DRAINMOD-based Decision-Support Tool for Optimizing the Performance of Saturated Buffers

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Abstract

Saturated buffers (NRCS standard 604) are designed to reduce nitrate loss from subsurface-drained farms. NRCS engineers use the NRCS Design spreadsheet to design saturated buffers. That design criterion is based on choosing a distribution pipe length that diverts at least 5% of the drainage capacity into the saturated buffer. However, designing a saturated buffer may not fit into a one-size-fits-all criterion of 5% of capacity. The objective of this study is to develop and test a new saturated buffer decision-support tool for designing and evaluating saturated buffers. The CIG Classic-funded tool has two model components: DRAINMOD and the saturated buffer module. After the user zooms in to the area of interest, they draw a boundary around the field of interest. The tool automatically retrieves site-specific data including the local SSURGO soil, DAYMET weather, and digital elevation model as input to the tool. The user needs to enter drainage system properties, cropping system, buffer location, and cost of the system. Then, the tool identifies the optimum width of the buffer that maximizes nitrate load removal. The tool also provides financial indices to evaluate the profitability of the saturated buffer. These financial indices include payback period and cost per pound of nitrate removed. During the presentation, we will demonstrate the tool's application for a random farm in Iowa. We also evaluated the tool's prediction compared to observed flow and nitrate load from two saturated buffer sites in Iowa. We expect satisfactory tool prediction of flow and nitrate load based on model evaluation statistics.

Location, Location, Location: Spatial considerations for managing reef resilience under uncertainty

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Summary

Reef ecosystems globally face a future in which loss of coral cover is expected to occur annually due to warmer ocean temperatures. A range of intervention efforts are planned to manage the transition to this future state across the Great Barrier Reef (GBR). Spatial considerations, socio-technical context, and ecological compatibility will be key to guiding deployment decisions but must also consider the spatiotemporal context.

Introduction

Global reef ecosystems are regarded to be under threat of climate change. Recent projections indicate a 90 percent reduction in coral cover globally under a 1.5°C warming scenario, and 99% loss under the 2.0°C scenario (van Hooidonk et al., 2016). It is likely that in the future, coral mortality due to stress induced by warmer ocean temperatures can be expected every year. As coral provide much of the ecosystem services which act as a foundation for healthily functioning reefs, loss of coral can be expected to drive biodiversity loss.

The Great Barrier Reef (GBR) is the world's largest coral ecosystem. Various intervention technologies and methods are under development as part of the Reef Restoration and Adaptation Program (RRAP) to aid in the conservation, restoration, and assisted adaptation of the GBR. These include aquacultural programs (lab-cultivated corals) and assisted migration of coral larvae. The spatial considerations under future uncertainties for the deployment of these interventions are investigated through network analysis in conjunction with modelled data and outcomes. Preliminary assessments to identify key principles to guide reef restoration and management across spatial scales will be presented alongside a discussion of further ongoing work.

Methodology and Results

Identifying suitable reefs, and locations within reefs, for intervention deployment requires careful consideration. Overarching factors which guide deployment decisions include, but are not limited to, the socio-technical context (e.g., societal, logistical, economic), projected environmental conditions, as well as the ecological and biological compatibility of coral deployments with the location of interest. Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis is coupled with exploratory scenario modelling with the ADRIA decision support platform (Iwanaga et al., 2023) to assess a wide range of intervention deployment approaches. Model results and data are assessed to identify locations of interest to support intervention planning (and not necessarily specific locations for deployment) and their spatial attributes.

The analyses vary the number of locations intervened on, the level of intervention effort applied, and the weightings of key criteria used to assess and select locations for interventions. Preliminary assessments reveal there are likely general principles for intervention deployment that are agnostic to the spatial scales being assessed (e.g., GBR-wide down to a specific reef). In addition, spatial analyses indicate clusters of comparatively well-connected reefs in the north and south of the GBR. A utilitarian approach may focus on interventions which maximising benefits for a specific well-connected region. A deontological approach which focuses on a wide spread of intervention activity may instead increase the likelihood of maintaining reef-states across the GBR. Regardless, intervention outcomes are highly dependent on the spatiotemporal context in which interventions occur and require consideration of the intended spatial objectives as well as their implications and consequences.

Conclusions

Identification of suitable deployment locations involves evaluation of a wide range of socio-environmental factors and assessment criteria. The combination of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis and exploratory scenario modelling aids in assessing various intervention approaches and reveals the influence of the spatiotemporal context and its influence on intended objectives and outcomes.

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The RRAP partners acknowledge Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Peoples as the first marine scientists and carers of Country. We acknowledge the Traditional Owners of the places where RRAP works, both on land and in sea Country. We pay our respects to elders; past, present, and future; and their continuing culture, knowledge, beliefs, and spiritual connections to land and sea Country.

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Opportunity Maps for Ecosystem Services – A handy Approach for Environmental Decision Support

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Summary

Agricultural management significantly influences the provisioning of ecosystem services and can cause trade-offs e.g. between water quality, drought or biodiversity protection. It is often not clear where measures for changes or adjustments in management should ideally be applied spatially. We present a method to create opportunity maps that show the potential of improving ecosystem services by agricultural management. The approach combines spatial data analysis with expert interviews and the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). Results are shown for an intensively used agricultural region in Central Germany.

Introduction

Agricultural landscapes are mainly associated with crop and livestock production. However, they provide many other ecosystem services (ES) – such as habitat for biodiversity or carbon sequestration. ES are often impacted negatively by agricultural management. Measures like agri-environmental schemes that aim at improving management and thus the provisioning of ES are often implemented in areas where their effect is negligible. Additionally, there is a lack of easily adaptable and applicable decision-support tools that help identifying areas where ES can be improved through management changes. To study the interrelations and spatial patterns of ES and agricultural management, usually, time- and data-intense process-based models or rather simple ES maps based on land-use type proxies are used. Opportunity maps (De Knecht et al., 2019; GMCA, 2023) offer a compromise between these approaches. However, they have not been applied to the context of agriculture. To fill this research gap, we developed an opportunity-map approach for agricultural landscapes with an improved and adapted scoring method. The result is a reproducible approach that delivers a field-specific spatial overview on where ES can be improved by agricultural management changes.

Methodology and Results

We defined individual evaluation criteria for the ES water quality, habitat for biodiversity, carbon sequestration, and drought protection. The criteria are based on site conditions, management, and other relevant environmental parameters and were scored for their impact on the respective ES with high scores indicating high opportunities to improve the ES (Figure 1). Scores and criteria were developed together with various experts on the respective ES during interviews. Further, each expert assigned weights to the respective evaluation criteria depending on their relative effect on the ES using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Saaty, 1987). Each field's opportunity was calculated from the weighted sum of the criteria scores based on the AHP results. This was done for each ES to create one opportunity map per ES. The overall opportunity map was created by summing up each field's normalized score of each ES weighting all ES equally.

We applied this approach to the intensively used agricultural region of Northwest Saxony, Germany. The results of the field-specific opportunity maps show that water quality and habitat for biodiversity have the highest opportunity to be improved. According to the experts and the AHP results, these ES are mainly influenced by agricultural management (e.g. fertilization, field sizes). Carbon sequestration and drought protection on the other hand, are mainly influenced by site conditions. These are generally favourable in the study region, which leads to lower opportunities although the current agricultural management does not support these ES in large parts of the area. Further, regional differences in ES opportunities could be identified for all four ES.

Figure 1. Overall framework of the opportunity-maps approach. Different layers of spatial data are used to calculate opportunity scores that were developed together with experts. Based on these scores, an overall opportunity map and individual maps for each ecosystem service are created.

Conclusions

The presented approach is novel in the context of agricultural landscapes, fast and reproducible for other German regions. Beyond that, some adjustments can make the approach transferable to other countries. Also, other ecosystem services can be added. Future improvements could include public preferences for single ES to create a weighted overall opportunity map. The approach can help decision-makers to spatially target management suggestions, information campaigns or subsidy schemes for management practices with positive impacts on ES. It can further support the spatial coordination of agri-environmental schemes and facilitate the collaboration with stakeholders through handy and understandable maps.

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Unveiling the Origins of PM_{2.5} Pollution in European Urban Environments: A Comprehensive Analysis

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Summary

This scientific work presents a comprehensive analysis of the sources and origins of PM_{2.5} pollution in European urban environments. The work is based on the results of the 'PM_{2.5} Atlas', a report that has now been published in three versions (in 2017, 2021 and 2023) and that analysis sectoral and geographical source of pollution for 150 European cities. Thanks to the analysis performed for different reference years, we can unveil how PM_{2.5} sources are evolving in time, and better understand how to ultimately improve air quality in EU cities. The results are produced using the SHERPA integrated assessment model, freely available at <https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/eu/dashboard/voila/render/SHERPA/Sherpa.ipynb>, that can be used for participatory modelling and decision support.

Introduction

A key aspect prior to developing air quality plans is to understand geographical and sectoral sources of pollution. This study helps in this direction, providing an analysis of key sources of pollution in urban environments. As full Air Quality Models cannot be used for this purpose (are too time consuming and complex to be run for hundreds of scenarios), surrogate models (or meta-models) are developed for this purpose. The advantage is to have, in this way, an interactive tool that can be used for participatory modelling and stakeholder involvement.

Methodology and Results

The study utilizes a surrogate modelling approach (based on the SHERPA integrated assessment model, Thunis et al., 2018) to uncover the complex sources of PM_{2.5} emissions, including transportation, industrial activities, residential combustion and others. The SHERPA model is trained and validated as a meta-model of a fully-fledged Chemical Transport Model (Pisoni et al., 2019).

Thanks to the creation of SHERPA, source allocation studies can be performed (Khomenko et al., 2023). This research delves into the sectoral and spatial variability of PM_{2.5} pollution, considering the impact of geographical characteristics on pollutant dispersion and accumulation. In particular, this study focusses on three versions of the "PM_{2.5} Atlas" publications (a report we produce every two years), to see how the geographical and sectoral contributions to PM_{2.5} have evolved in the last decade for different EU cities.

The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, urban planners, and environmental practitioners seeking effective strategies to mitigate PM_{2.5} pollution and improve air quality in European urban environments. At the same time, using the SHERPA tool, stakeholders can test different policy scenarios, to see in an interactive way how alternative emission reductions would impact air quality in cities.

Conclusions

By shedding light on the origins of PM_{2.5} pollution, this paper contributes to the understanding of air quality issues and supports the development of targeted interventions to address this pressing environmental and public health concern.

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Exploring Future Scenarios with Time Series Clustering and SIRUS

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Summary

Scenario Discovery aids in identifying decision-relevant conditions by summarising (modelled) future states. Time Series Clustering and SIRUS are two algorithms that can work together to allow the identification of distinct behaviour-based scenario clusters and extract interpretable rules that characterize a target cluster. These rules are useful to inform policy and management decisions and to assist in investigating model behaviour. While SIRUS is effectively able to extract rules containing clauses of the type $a < x$ or $x < b$, a limitation is that SIRUS is unable to determine rules with clauses of the type $a < x < b$.

Introduction

When applying models to support decision making in complex environmental problems, it is common to explore many scenarios representing plausible future states of the world. This process is often called Scenario Discovery. Each scenario can depend on factors that represent from management and interventions decisions to environmental and ecological characteristics of the system being modelled. The challenge is to discover decisions that perform well under a wide range of scenarios while having limited sensitivity to the environmental and ecological uncertainties.

Typically, after running many scenarios, there are two further steps in scenario discovery. The first is to apply some criteria to the model outputs to distinguish a target from a non-target cluster. We achieve that with the help of a Time Series Clustering algorithm, which is convenient when the model's output is in the form of a time series. The second step is to apply some data-mining algorithm to identify combinations of constraints (called rules) on a small number of factors that work as predictors for classifying scenarios as part of the target cluster. This is particularly relevant when we focus our analysis in the decision related factors, as it allows us to inform discussions and decisions. We use an algorithm called SIRUS (**S**table and **I**nterpretable **R**ule **S**et) to extract these interpretable rules.

Methodology and Results

We adopt a scenario discovery approach. After running many scenarios, a Time Series Clustering algorithm is used to cluster these scenarios based on their temporal behaviour. This approach captures each series' temporal behaviour using a metric called Complexity (a measure of its variance over time) which can be used for pairwise comparisons. We then target a cluster for further assessment. We apply the SIRUS classification algorithm, which is a random forest-based approach, to extract sets of governing rules that are human-interpretable for the assessed scenarios. The set representing the factor values used for the n model runs and classifications is given by $D_n = \{(\mathbf{X}_i, Y_i), i = 1, \dots, n\}$, where $\mathbf{X}_i = (X_i^{(1)}, \dots, X_i^{(p)}) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is a vector of p factors values and $Y \in \{0,1\}$ is the binary classification of that scenario as belonging or not to the target cluster. The r -th q -quantile of the set of values for the factor j $\{X_1^{(j)}, \dots, X_n^{(j)}\}$ is denoted by $\hat{q}_{n,r}^{(j)}$. When building a decision tree, SIRUS can only use as split points for each factor j one of the $\hat{q}_{n,r}^{(j)}$. Fixing the allowed split points is what guarantees the stability of this algorithm results.

The rules generated by SIRUS follow the structure "if conditions on x^j then target probability A , else target probability B " where target probability is the probability of being in the target group. These conditions are composed of assertions of the type $x^j < \hat{q}_{n,r}^{(j)}$ or $x^j \geq \hat{q}_{n,r}^{(j)}$. An example of a rule would be "if $x^j \geq 5$ and

$x^{j'} < 10$ then $p_s=25\%$, else $p_s= 80\%$ ". The time series clustering algorithm works is effective to group scenarios based on their behaviour, although we found an inconsistency with the Correction Factor (the quotient of two series complexities) as it is not well defined for constant series.

The SIRUS extracted rules proved to be useful to interpret the modelled interventions and, therefore, inform discussions and management decisions. Besides that, there is a limitation to this algorithm since it is not possible to have rules composed of assertions of the type $\hat{q}_{n,r}^{(j)} \leq x^j < \hat{q}_{n,r+1}^{(j)}$.

Conclusions

Scenario Discovery is a powerful tool to explore many scenarios for decision making in complex environmental problems. In that context, Time Series Clustering and SIRUS proved to be useful to identify and characterize scenario clusters. In particular, the human-interpretability of SIRUS induced rules is a key feature that allows us inform discussions and management decisions. Moreover, there seems to be space for improvement in the type of rule that SIRUS can extract.

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Enhancing Floodplain Decision-Making: A Novel AI Virtual Assistant Integrating GPT and Semantic Technologies

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Summary

This research presents the development of a Floodplain Management Assistant (FPMA), which incorporates advanced GPT models and semantic search technologies. This system provides targeted, location-specific flood risk management information, facilitating improved decision-making for floodplain managers and the public. By integrating datasets from authoritative sources such as FEMA, the virtual assistant ensures the accuracy and relevance of the information it delivers. Future developments aim to incorporate real-time data, enhancing the tool's responsiveness and utility during flood events. This innovative solution plays a dual role, serving both as a decision-support tool and an educational resource to promote community resilience and preparedness.

Introduction

Flooding stands as a formidable natural hazard globally, imposing severe socio-economic impacts and disproportionately affecting vulnerable populations (Lechowska, 2018). Despite advances in flood risk management, persistent gaps in communication, data access, and decision support systems complicate effective management, especially under urgent conditions (Alabbad and Demir, 2022). Traditional methods often fail to deliver timely, location-specific information essential for informed decision-making during flood events. This knowledge gap underscores the need for innovative solutions capable of integrating complex flood risk data with user-friendly, accessible platforms (Sajja et al., 2024).

In addressing these challenges, our research introduces a novel AI-based Virtual Assistant designed to significantly enhance floodplain management. This tool aims to bridge the existing communication and information gaps by providing real-time, tailored information to floodplain managers and the public. Utilizing advanced Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) models and semantic search technologies (Pursnani et al., 2023), the Virtual Assistant interprets vast datasets from authoritative sources such as FEMA and state-based floodplain management bodies. This approach not only ensures the accuracy and relevance of the information provided but also makes it accessible to a diverse user base, thereby democratizing flood risk management.

The Virtual Assistant is engineered to enhance user interaction with complex flood risk data, translating technical FEMA flood maps and management guidelines into easily understandable formats. This functionality is crucial for effective decision-making, allowing users to quickly comprehend their specific risks and the associated management strategies. By integrating cutting-edge AI with an intuitive user interface, the tool facilitates a more informed, equitable, and proactive approach to floodplain management. This strategic application of technology exemplifies a significant leap forward in managing flood risks, particularly in underserved regions where traditional resources are often limited. As such, the AI-based Virtual Assistant not only addresses immediate operational challenges but also contributes to building long-term resilience against flood-related disasters.

Methodology and Results

The development represents a significant advancement in floodplain management, incorporating a methodological framework centered around advanced AI technologies. The process began with comprehensive data collection from credible sources such as FEMA and state floodplain management authorities, ensuring a solid foundation of relevant and authoritative content for training the AI models. Subsequently, GPT models

were fine-tuned with this data to enhance their capability in handling complex floodplain management queries. The integration of semantic search further refined the system's ability to understand and respond to user intents more effectively, enhancing the relevance and precision of the information provided.

An intuitive user interface was developed to facilitate straightforward interaction with the Virtual Assistant, allowing users to input natural language queries and receive easily comprehensible responses. This interface supports diverse forms of input, making the tool accessible to a broad range of users, including those with limited technical expertise. Rigorous testing phases followed, focusing on evaluating the accuracy of the AI in generating responses and the overall user experience. Feedback from these tests was critical in iteratively refining both the AI models and the user interface.

The deployment of the Virtual Assistant demonstrated notable successes in operational settings. The system showed high accuracy in response generation, effectively interpreting and providing actionable information for diverse floodplain management queries. Users reported improved interaction with flood risk data, highlighting the ease of use and the clarity of the information provided by the Virtual Assistant. These aspects were crucial in enabling users to make informed decisions quickly, especially during critical flood events.

Conclusions

The FPMA marks a transformative advance in the field of flood risk management, leveraging state-of-the-art AI technologies to enhance decision-making and accessibility. The tool provides precise, context-specific information that significantly improves the operational efficiency of floodplain managers and educates the public on flood risks. It facilitates straightforward interactions, allowing users to effortlessly navigate complex flood-related information and make informed decisions rapidly. Rigorous testing has shown that the Virtual Assistant not only meets but exceeds the requirements for practical application, demonstrating high accuracy in response generation and significantly enhancing user engagement with critical flood risk data. Moreover, the tool's impact extends beyond immediate flood response scenarios, acting as a crucial educational resource that promotes long-term community resilience and preparedness. This dual function of operational support and educational outreach underscores the significant potential of the Virtual Assistant to revolutionize floodplain management practices, making them more effective and inclusive.

There are several avenues for further enhancements. One key area is the integration of real-time data sources such as weather forecasts, river gauges, and satellite imagery. This enhancement would enable the Virtual Assistant to provide up-to-the-minute assessments that are crucial during active flood events, thereby improving the timeliness and accuracy of the information provided. Additionally, expanding the tool's decision-making features to include connections with essential resources like the National Levee Database and FEMA Flood Map Service Center could offer a more comprehensive range of data, further enriching the user's ability to make well-informed decisions. Another promising direction involves enhancing the system's support for Letter of Map Changes (LOMC) applications. By automating and streamlining this complex process, the Virtual Assistant could assist users in preparing and submitting LOMC applications more efficiently, predicting outcomes based on historical data, and thus reducing the administrative burden on floodplain managers.

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Evaluating the Feasibility of Greenhouse Farming in Vermont, United States

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Summary

This paper explores the use of fuzzy cognitive mapping (FCM) in encouraging stakeholders in the Carpathian Convention to adopt a more calibrated, systems approach to decision-making for improving biodiversity outcomes. Supplementary to this research question, it asks whether expected biodiversity outcomes differ based on how FCM is conducted, either via (1) individual interviews, or (2) data generated from group consensus. Such analysis aims to better understand the synergies and trade-offs of integrating biodiversity considerations for the livelihoods of people and nature.

Introduction

Mountains are essential to Earth's life-support system, harboring rich biological and cultural diversity and providing essential ecosystem services (Schmeller et al., 2022; Thorn et al., 2021; Kato, Rambali & Blanco-Gonzalez, 2021; Brunner & Grêt-Regamey, 2016). They play a crucial role in biodiversity conservation and global regulating processes, including water, food, energy, hazard mitigation and more (Schmeller et al., 2022; Brunner & Grêt-Regamey, 2016; Romeo, Grita, Parisi & Russo, 2020; Bogdan, Pătru-Stupariu & Zaharia, 2016). At the same time, mountain ecosystems are particularly sensitive to climate change impacts and global changes, causing concerns over their capacity to cope with trends and disturbances (Brunner & Grêt-Regamey, 2016; Schmeller et al., 2022; Thorn et al., 2020; Bezáková & Bezák, 2022). Human actions are driving the triple planetary crisis of climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss, threatening the planet's functioning and ability to support life and the future of humanity (UNFCCC, 2022; Grima, Ringhofer, Singh, Smetschka, & Lauk, 2017). Thus, prioritizing mountain biodiversity and supporting mountain communities on the global agenda is crucial for securing healthy ecological systems and meeting the needs of all people within the means of the planet.

However, due to the inherent complexity and vulnerability of mountain landscapes, enhancing their sustainability or resilience is difficult. Resilience is needed for managing complex SESs to ensure the sustainable provision and consumption of ecosystem services (Brunner & Grêt-Regamey, 2016). Understanding the drivers of change in socioecological systems (SES) can help determine the system's dynamics in affecting human well-being and conservation goals, ultimately influencing resiliency. Thus, participatory models for analyzing SES behaviors and developing simulations for resiliency planning emerged (Olazabal & Pascual, 2016; Özesmi & Özesmi, 2004; Gray et al., 2015) and are increasingly utilized in mountain contexts.

One such participatory model is Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping (FCM), which is a semiquantitative method for visually illustrating the relationships between key concepts of a system, including feedback relationships (Gray et al., 2015; Özesmi & Özesmi, 2004). Applying FCM as a participatory model is suitable for incorporating complexity and diverse stakeholder knowledge, especially in data-scarce contexts (Gray et al., 2015). In this context, FCM can be used for understanding resiliency and transition in mountain biodiversity as a SES by defining its current state, analyzing the structure, running scenarios to analyze its functions, and evaluating how changes in drivers create desirable or undesirable outcomes (Gray et al., 2015).

Methodology and Results

Through both individual and focus group participation, we elicited fuzzy cognitive maps of various stakeholders to assess the impact of their suggested interventions on biodiversity outcomes in the Carpathian region. Our initial results show that these proposed interventions have limited long-run effects on biodiversity health, suggesting that a multi-pronged approach will be needed to have any significant effect.

Conclusions

This paper fits well in many sessions in stream A. We will be happy to present in any session that the organizers deem appropriate for this paper.

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A Combined Hydro-Geomorphologic Approach for Riverbed Adaptation Plan

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Summary

The paper summarizes the development of a methodology for the analysis of the morphodynamic evolution of the riverbed on a reduced scenario of infrastructural and management interventions. The methodology consists of a combined geomorphological (IDRAIM) and hydraulic approach (MIKE 21c + HEC-RAS) which on different spatial and temporal scales has demonstrated effectiveness and accuracy in application to the pilot river basin of the Rio Geremeas in South-Eastern Sardinia (IT).

Introduction

The dynamics of river transport of sediments have economic, environmental and human safety relevance in a vast area. The process conditions all human interventions along the watercourse, from the construction of hydraulic structures to the maintenance of ecosystems and restoration of the coasts. Knowing in depth the physical characteristics and river processes is essential in the sustainable management of rivers (Newson & Large, 2006; Vaughan et al., 2009) while the operation of a hydraulic infrastructure such as a dam is, for example, linked to the deposition of sediments in its reservoir. The temporal and spatial scale of the phenomena involved in the process requires a significant use of modeling resources from different disciplines. The first step that it was necessary to analyze is on the slope - watercourse interface and verify which modeling approaches, analytical or numerical, could be implemented to define a coupled methodology of sediment production and transport at the slope scale and the morphological evolution in the riverbed.

In the framework of an institutional collaboration with the Sardinian Water Authority (ADIS), this article summarizes the ongoing activity for the development of an analysis methodology at the river basin scale for river solid transport aimed at the drafting of a sediment management plan. The joint working group was defined in line with the state of the art in the technical-scientific field, which requires the development and application of a multidisciplinary approach not only for watercourse management projects but also for management practices. management of the same, in line with their nature as complex ecosystems. In the last two decades, there has been a clear overcoming of the rigidly mono-disciplinary, "hydraulic" approach, which has led to an excessive simplification of structural applications for flood defense in the face of a broad debate involving land management. over a large area and intervention strategies, structural or management, on watercourses. These intervention strategies aim to maintain or recover, wherever possible, the naturalness of the watercourses which are reassigned the important role they play in containing the risk of flooding. The "hydraulic" component of flood defense is therefore considered strongly interconnected to the morphological dynamics of the riverbed.

Methodology and Results

The proposed model integrates the contribution of geomorphological analysis and hydrodynamic analysis at the river basin scale according to a multidisciplinary approach. It has the characteristics of a combined model that develops over three main phases:

- Phase 1: Characterization of the river system

This phase provides a watershed-scale delineation, characterization and analysis of the river system in its current condition, with particular attention to reach morphology and sediment transfer processes. This part was integrated by analyzing the geomorphological processes at the slope scale with particular reference to the sediment source areas.

- Phase 2: Past evolution and current conditions of the river

The reconstruction of evolutionary trajectories is fundamental to interpret and evaluate the current conditions of the river, both in terms of morphological quality and channel dynamics through the evaluation of the Index of Morphological Quality (IQM) and the Index of Morphological Dynamics (IDM). Multi-temporal analyses are performed using aerial photos, satellite images, existing historical thematic maps and comparisons with newly acquired data (drone). This phase defines an alternative intervention framework along structural and management lines. Describe the methodology applied and present the key findings and results of the research. Highlight the relevance of the work described for advancing the state-of-the-art of environmental modelling and software development.

- Phase 3: Analysis of the hydrodynamic impact of the interventions

With reference to the framework of intervention alternatives, the one-dimensional and two-dimensional numerical modeling defines the hydraulic component and the morphological component of the active riverbed and floodable areas, with reference to the current conditions and the related evolutionary trends;

The geomorphological approach characterizes the river basin by analyzing the source areas of the sediments through the slope processes and the degree of connection with the river processes. The methodology recalls the IDRAIM hydromorphological characterization method, integrated with the analysis of sediment sources, the analysis of the connectivity of the basin and the geomorphological analysis of the watercourses. The system provides the physical basis and a series of procedures through which to allow an understanding of the morphological dynamics processes at a basin scale. While IDRAIM analyzes the river system within the hydrographic network only, in the present project the geomorphological model has implemented in IDRAIM a module for the analysis of gravitational and erosive processes on the slopes, from the valley floor up to the crest of the slope.

The water currents, in relation to the speed values and the characteristics of the turbulence in the flow, are capable of transporting solid materials of different grain sizes. This physical phenomenon, called solid transport, constitutes the point of union between the erosion phenomena which mainly affect the mountainous part of the basin and the deposition phenomena which occur in the valley area and with a lower slope of the watercourse.

Conclusions

The development of the combined approach allows a river basin-scale analysis of complex phenomena that traditionally determine computational limits. Specifically, the study of basin slope-scale production and solid transport are developed on the areas most susceptible to IDRAIM analyses, focusing the computationally expensive hydraulic analysis on a limited number of management and infrastructural adaptation scenarios.

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Advancing Watershed Management: A Multiobjective Optimization and Multicriteria Decision-Making Platform

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Summary

This abstract presents a user interface to facilitate the application of a large-scale multiobjective optimization framework for watershed planning and assessment. Integrating GIS capabilities and multicriteria decision-making modules, including VIKOR and TOPSIS, the interface enables users to set up scenarios, run optimizations, and analyze results for informed decision-making. This work represents a significant advancement in environmental modeling software, making complex optimization analyses accessible and actionable for users with varying expertise levels.

Introduction

Given the increasing water quality challenges posed by widespread agricultural and urban activities, the urgency for sustainable watershed management strategies has never been more critical. Conventional methodologies for selecting Best Management Practices (BMPs) often need to improve in offering a view that allows for comprehensively exploring various scenarios and their potential impacts. In response to this gap, we have enhanced our previously developed multiobjective optimization framework (Toscano-Pulido et al., 2024) with an innovative web interface. This interface facilitates user interaction with complex optimization models and incorporates Geographic Information System (GIS) data visualization and multicriteria decision analysis tools, including VIKOR and TOPSIS (Opricovic, 1998; Hwang and Yoon, 1981, respectively), to support informed and participatory watershed management decisions.

Flexibility in accessing and utilizing this system is paramount, as researchers and practitioners have diverse needs and preferences. To accommodate this, the developed Application Programming Interface (API) is designed to be programming language-agnostic, enabling users to interact with the optimization framework through their preferred programming environments. This approach significantly lowers the barrier to entry for engaging with the system, promoting a broader adoption across various disciplines involved in watershed management.

This initiative aligns with the growing need for flexible, scalable solutions in environmental modeling and software, pushing the boundaries of how we approach and solve complex watershed management challenges.

Methodology and Results

Our methodology integrates a Web Interface and RESTful APIs developed with Django, facilitating interaction between users and the optimization framework. The GIS integration allows users to visually identify BMP locations, while the decision-making module simplifies complex trade-offs using VIKOR and TOPSIS methods. User case studies demonstrate the interface's effectiveness in enabling non-experts to configure scenarios, visualize optimization outcomes, and derive actionable insights. The results underscore the potential of our approach to reduce computational barriers and significantly enhance decision-making in watershed management. The subsequent figures display various screenshots captured from the Multiobjective Optimization and Multicriteria Decision-Making Platform.

1
2
3
 Loads BMP Selection County Selection for Manure Extraction

Pollution Load and Implementation Cost Specification

Pollution Reduction Target:

Pollutant	Initial Load (lbs/year)	Removal Percentage (%)	Expected Load (lbs/year)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nitrogen	30,448,456	<input type="text" value="50"/>	<input type="text" value="15224228"/>
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Phosphorus	1,537,509	<input type="text" value="30"/>	<input type="text" value="153289647"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Sediments	1,166,578.352	<input type="text" value="30"/>	<input type="text" value="116307861694"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Oxygen Units (ug/l)	1	<input type="text" value="30"/>	<input type="text" value="100"/>

Do you have a limit on the allocated budget for BMP implementation?: Yes No Next

Figure 1. Input interface for the Multiobjective Optimization and Multicriteria Decision-Making Platform

Figure 2. Visualization of optimization results post-BMP implementation

Conclusions

The developed web interface significantly advances environmental modeling and software by making sophisticated multiobjective optimization analyses accessible to a broader audience. It encourages participatory decision-making and facilitates the exploration of cost-effective and environmentally sustainable watershed management strategies. This research aligns with the objectives of iEMSs, promising new avenues for collaboration and innovation in environmental modeling and software development.

Acknowledgements

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Immersive Realtime Interactive Modelling for Orchard Design and Planning

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Summary

We introduce 3D real-time software development tools aimed at creating immersive, interactive environments to facilitate intuitive decision-making in Agriculture, focusing on apple orchard design. Leveraging the growing ubiquity of augmented reality in today's smartphone ecosystem (Boland, 2023), we utilize game engines and open frameworks to develop an AR-capable "orchard-builder." Our study demonstrates the potential for making orchard establishment practices accessible through augmented reality, offering promising avenues for streamlined and accessible orchard layout designs.

Introduction

In addressing the critical role of orchard layout decisions in shaping the success of fruit production efforts, we emphasize their impact on management strategies and overall outcomes. However, growers often lack effective means to visualize the consequences of layout choices before executing orchard establishment. We propose leveraging Augmented Reality (AR) as a visual and interactive tool, aligning with the advancements of Industry 4.0. AR enables growers to overlay virtual orchard elements onto their physical farm space, facilitating the exploration of various layout designs and management efficiencies without compromising farm integrity. Our focus is on apple orchards, and we are presenting a case study to illustrate the potential of AR in addressing these challenges.

Methodology and Results

Utilizing Unity Engine as our primary platform, we developed a real-time 3D interactive application aimed at facilitating orchard layout design (Figure 1). AR Foundation, chosen for its openness to development and cross-platform capabilities, served as the framework within Unity. We prioritized enabling users to incorporate their own topography, seamlessly integrating it into the AR scene presented by the device's camera. Leveraging marker-less tracking capabilities through AR Foundation's subsystem implementations enabled precise depth and farm-land surface tracking. Anchors acted as trackable within the scene, guiding the placement of tree seedlings and additional orchard management components.

Figure 1. Block diagram showing the orchard-builder process flow

Despite localization inconsistencies, our AR application provides an intuitive means of working with complex layout patterns (Javaid et al., 2017), offering a test bed for orchard establishment that benefits both farmers and learners. These findings showcase the relevance of our methodology to environmental modeling and software development, demonstrating its potential impact on orchard management practices.

Conclusions

The outcomes of our work demonstrate a significant advancement in orchard establishment processes, offering ease and intuitiveness for users, thereby democratizing orchard establishment practices. By leveraging immersive and interactive technologies through mobile devices, we pave the way for embracing Industry 4.0 in agriculture, moving towards precision farming. The potential impacts of our research extend beyond the current scope, with future endeavors likely to incorporate orchard elements as full-fledged digital twins interacting with the augmented physical environment. These conclusions highlight the transformative potential of our approach to transforming orchard management and environmental modeling practices.

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Developing a Societal Dynamics Model Component for Earth System Models

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Summary

We are developing a Societal Dynamics Model (SDM) that can be integrated with Earth System Models (ESMs), which currently do not include detailed coupled human-environment feedbacks. The prototype, developed using the Python Mesa framework, models geopolitical actors (e.g., nation-states) that may choose to invest in various climate intervention or mitigation strategies based on the environmental conditions they experience—as simulated in the ESM. We hope to gather community input on our prototype and gain insight into how to effectively incorporate stakeholder input through participatory modeling to improve our model's relevance and usefulness in understanding climate risks, uncertainties and possible interventions.

Introduction

Earth System Models (ESMs) are sophisticated tools that simulate Earth system processes and their interactions. These modeling tools have helped improve our understanding of the potential future impacts and consequences of human activities on the Earth. However, ESMs do not typically simulate societal responses to said impacts and cannot represent human-environment feedbacks. To fill this important gap, the SDM4CI project is developing a Societal Dynamics Model (SDM) component that could be coupled with existing ESMs. Stakeholder engagement was included as a central step in the model's development roadmap to inform the way we encode how different social actors interpret and react to shifting climate realities. We propose to present our current prototype for a flexible, general-purpose Societal Dynamics Model that can be coupled with an ESM and solicit feedback on how to best incorporate participatory modeling practices so that the SDM might be of maximal benefit to the broader community.

Methodology and Results

Using the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) Community ESM (CESM) as the base ESM, a prototype version of the SDM component has been developed in Python using the Mesa framework. The SDM component is designed as a multi-agent model, where each agent represents a geopolitical actor (a nation-state in the current implementation). Actors sense the conditions in their discrete geographical extent (represented by a set of ESM grid cells) and use these biophysical cues and societal contexts to decide whether to invest in climate intervention or mitigation strategies. These decisions generate forcing files that can alter CESM simulations for subsequent years which, in turn, alter the conditions each actor can sense in the future. This design supports true coupling between human and natural systems where dynamic feedbacks can be appropriately represented and systematically explored. We will present the current model design and architecture to highlight areas that can be customized related to interpreting CESM outputs and supporting different assumptions on climate trajectories and perceived hazards as well as flexibly parameterizable actors that could represent nation-states, eccentric billionaires, multinationals, or coalitions.

A preliminary version of this prototype has been developed targeting metabolic heat stress using a physiology based metabolic equivalent of task metric developed by Vanos et al. (2023; Figure 1). We solicited community input for the model design and parameterization at an April workshop jointly hosted by NCAR and Arizona State University and have identified new directions and priorities for development including ways to categorize and parameterize climate interventions, establishing an internally consistent typology of climate risks, and potential use cases for SDM model outputs. We hope to gather feedback from this session on additional ways to engage

communities and develop the SDM into a flexible and evolving tool that can help people better understand the risks and uncertainties around climate change and geoengineering.

Figure 1. SDM Prototype Visualization

Conclusions

The aphorism “All models are wrong, but some are useful” attributed to George Box (1979) serves as a guiding design principle for our SDM development. Issues of model credibility were repeatedly raised during our April workshop with common critiques of ESMs including regional biases and inaccuracies in representing local earth systems dynamics. While the specifics of ESM output credibility are out of scope for our SDM since we treat them as exogenous inputs representing “the world as experienced by our simulated actors”, the broader issue of how to trust results from any model still overshadows our work. We hope to address this through a combination of participatory modeling, model transparency, clearly outlined and tunable assumptions, and robust sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification included alongside our model results (Lee et al., 2015). Future work will address model evaluation and validation (“evaludation”; Augusiak et al., 2014), explore additional climate risk and hazard metrics at local and global scales, and focus on the development of credible or at the very least transparent “scenarios” that might be used for ESM ensemble runs with participatory stakeholder input that could loosely map to “politically likely”, “politically feasible”, and “maximum feasible” levels of investment.

We look forward to gaining insights from our colleagues on good participatory modeling practices that can inform future community engagement and support the continued evolution and refinement of an SDM we hope will serve as an open and useful testbed for researchers and practitioners.

Acknowledgements

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**Improving participatory processes
through analysis of narratives,
knowledge sources, emotions, values,
biases and schema**

Computers, Cognition, and Environmental Decision-Making

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Summary

Computer models are powerful tools for learning about environmental issues because they can show relationships over time that humans are unlikely to recognize. However, biocultural evolution has produced human cognitive processes that do not function like computer models, and this presents a challenge when developing and/or using models in environmental decision-making processes. Biocultural evolution encompasses a rich body of evidence dating back decades revealing a dynamic evolutionary relationship between human biology and human culture (cf Simpson 1949; Dunbar 1996; Carroll et al. 2017).

How *Homo sapiens* come to “know” something is a complex process and cognitive tendencies are often at odds with effective participation efforts and/or decision-making about wicked problems, which includes all environmental issues. In going about daily activities, much of human cognition is sub- or unconscious. This has significant evolutionary benefits as it frees the brain for engaging in non-routine or more challenging tasks (Evans and Stanovich 2013). A downside is that as humans, we often don’t actually know what is happening in our brains and this contributes to phenomena like cognitive dissonance. Further, biocultural evolution has rewarded pattern seeking and identifying cause and effect relationships. This highly honed skill has been key to the species’ evolutionary success. Our brains are so tuned to this, that we find patterns and assign cause and effect even when they do not exist (Sloman and Fenbach 2017). Piling on here, because *Homo sapiens* is a strongly social species, biocultural evolution has also encouraged integrating individual and group cognitive functions. This results in individual preferences for agreeing with a perceived majority view and in judging who is ‘in’ or ‘outside’ a particular group (Olsson et al. 2020). It also allows acquired knowledge to transcend space and time (Laland and Rendell 2013). All of these aspects of human cognition get embodied in narratives —conscious and unconscious, individual and social— about any particular environmental issue / concern.

Computer models can help identify instances where what humans think we know is inaccurate or incomplete. But, because humans typically don’t appreciate how much of our thinking or knowledge is subconscious or is dependent on what others think, we resist accepting information that does not align with what we already consider or believe to be true (Campbell 1989). If computer results challenge an existing narrative or schema, with their concomitant norms, values and practices, those results are often dismissed. This, subsequently, makes participatory processes and decision-making within complex systems challenging.

A way forward is to intentionally design processes that reflect the biocultural evolutionary reality of human cognition. We propose that a foundation for any participatory process should include eliciting and documenting narratives from participants to identify perceived patterns of thought and action, perceived cause and effect relationships, and perceived social expectations. One idea is for elicitation practices to be framed around evolutionary-based “resonances,” which reflect what people care about and are willing to express, without any attached value judgments (see Santamaria Cerrutti et al., in review). Leaders in computer-based participatory processes should subsequently engage with participant narratives early in a model-development process and subsequently think about how and why models may show what seems counter intuitive or may disagree with expected relationships. Again, applying “resonances” here allows model-developers and users to employ what we know about biocultural evolution and human cognition to question themselves and engender greater acceptance of modeling processes and results.

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Narratives, Mental Models, Values, and Biocultural Drivers: Frameworks for Participatory Processes and Sustainability Pathways

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Abstract

People construct, develop, internalize, enact, and express narratives constantly, sometimes consciously, but most often unconsciously or subconsciously. In so doing, individuals create simplifications and mental models in and of their inner world that are also reflective of their perceptions of the world around them (e.g., their histories, wants or needs, and plans, the nature of other individuals). Narratives (and associated mental models) are used to make sense of the past and present, to find meaning in oneself and in one's world, and to envision the future (Helgeson et al., 2022). They are used to communicate with others. Narratives - including the symbols they contain - express group norms and behaviours; assign causality; strengthen and express beliefs; convey group or individual identity, and relative status or differentiation.

Narratives are created, maintained, propagated, and adapted to interpret, structure and model signal information from other people, from biota, and from the physical world. The mental models and patterns of thought and action they incorporate, evolve, disperse, and re-aggregate in the minds of individuals and of their collectivities. They are embedded in the beliefs, world views and practices of social groups to which they belong. Narratives shape biocultural evolution (aka gene-culture co-evolution) of humans and other biota and are the result of past evolutionary processes. Narratives can be expressed through a wide diversity of communication types, not only through language and verbal/written expressions, but also through visual images, dance, sensory communications and/or through enacted behaviours.

Narratives shape but mostly reflect lifeways and conditions of human communities, and attendant priorities and values. Understanding and characterizing narratives, their biocultural and social drivers, and the different dimensions of values that they may reveal is essential to facilitating and improving (1) participatory processes, and (2) the decisions needed for management and governance of dynamic social-ecological systems (SES). We have constructed several frameworks that can be used to characterize narratives, values, and biocultural drivers – and consequently to facilitate, analyse, and improve stakeholder and community engagements. This is important for at least two reasons. First, the characterizations and attendant knowledge provided by the frameworks can be used to engage, facilitate participatory processes, and improve critical reflective thinking and decision-making. Second, with consent of the participants, they can also potentially be used to provide transparency on the basis for decisions, not only the scientific information used but also the values, beliefs, emotional resonances, and simple mental models or narratives that came into play. In both cases, recognizing, characterizing, labelling, and understanding the narratives, values, and biocultural drivers that guide human behaviours and decisions allows a measure of control and critical reflective thinking to be exerted and made explicit. Many of the challenges of modernity require improved planning, perspectives, and participatory discussions, that extend beyond the more immediate, less-conscious, bioculturally-inherited, reactions of individuals and their communities.

Our analysis frameworks can be used to create and maintain improved 'Records of Engagement and Decision-making' (RoED), and more generally to track community actions, and management and policymaking (Cockerill et al., 2019). RoED are essential for enabling anticipatory adaptive governance and management of SES, or of SES issues and stressors such as those driven by climate change and land-use change (Glynn et al., 2022). Our frameworks can help understand, recognize and document the emotions, norms, biases, beliefs, heuristics and values (BBHV) that are an essential part of negotiations, inter- and intra-group dynamics, and of decision-making

for navigating SES issues and sustainability pathways (Glynn et al., 2017). We expect that our analysis frameworks will also find use in improving explanatory, and possibly predictive, numerical simulations of SES dynamics, including through integrated environmental modelling (Glynn, 2017; Laniak et al., 2013).

We have applied our frameworks to two water and environmental case studies in New Zealand. Important policy, management, and governance aspects are at stake that involve a diversity of constituencies and socio-economic needs. The case studies also bring together and bridge different forms and sources of knowledge: ‘modern international science and technology’ as well as traditional Māori knowledge and culture. We continue to research and refine our tools, frameworks, and approaches, including for several new projects in New Zealand. We are conducting narrative analyses on various types of documents and applying some of our ideas to survey community attitudes (and their dynamics). We are also testing how to best use our concepts and tools to interpret, facilitate, and improve stakeholder discussions and community engagements.

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Creating Scenarios for Culturally Informed Decision Making to Support Adaptive, Resilient Communities

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Introduction

New developments that inspire, guide, and facilitate more inclusive, informed decision making on complex social-ecological system issues provide new opportunities to address pressing issues of sustainability and resilience. The Knowledge Learning and Societal Change Alliance (KLASICA) focuses on culturally, contextually, and scientifically informed deliberative decision making for actions toward sustainable futures. This approach draws from narratives of vision and social identity to consider societal values alongside scientific and technical options in seeking to foster adaptive and resilient cultures of sustainability. Inspiring, guiding, and facilitating actions on these urgent and critical challenges depends not only on acquiring and interpreting data in research projects, but more crucially on interpreting - making meaning of - that data for use in culturally and contextually informed deliberative decision making. We outline methods to help communities of practice and purpose develop scenarios that are meaningful, credible, and salient in their cultural frames, while simultaneously addressing their economic needs and ecological well-being. This approach aims to facilitate collective behavior change towards sustainable futures, help advance effective and realistic modeling, and record the decision-making processes, contexts, and outcomes.

Background

Climate change is increasing the likelihood of compound events — simultaneous or cascading systemic impacts (Renn et al., 2020) — across the world. Compound events impose greater harm on society and natural systems than singular events and can reduce the ability of overburdened communities to effectively respond and recover. Building climate resilience, (the ability to prepare for anticipated hazards, adapt to changing conditions, and withstand and recover rapidly from disruptions) requires preparing for increasing compound event risks through infrastructure design, planning, disaster preparedness, while also improving resilience and addressing the deep equity and justice issues around climate change. Infrastructure resilience is key to timely and efficient prevention, absorption, recovery, adaptation, and transformation of local to national infrastructure's essential structures and functions, which are exposed to current and potential future hazards.

Recognizing the need to integrate efforts of the disaster and community resilience practitioners with long standing approaches to address sustainable development concerns, Helgeson & O'Fallon (2021) defined resilience windfalls as a co-benefit of an unexpected or sudden gain from resilience planning, including and extending beyond multi-hazard standards. Coupling resilience windfall with resilience dividend gives the net co-benefit and co-cost of investing in enhanced resilience in the absence of a disruptive event. The intent is for resilience dividends and resilience windfalls to be understood and applied together in our understanding of sustainability-related resilience benefits achievable through community-level decision-making and investments.

Finding solutions

We focus here on research regarding the resilience windfalls of climate resilience codes and standards from a social sustainability standpoint, particularly in underserved communities, through (1) regular and ongoing investments that lead to a distinct performance improvement when the system is confronted by a disruptive event and/or (2)

investments that boost the system's ability to address the acute shocks or chronic stressors beyond improving day-to-day operations. What is the net resilience gain, where the prefix 'Net' signifies that it is acceptable for an action to have a negative impact on the resilience of the system into which it is introduced provided it either (a) also generates a resilience gain (has a positive impact) of sufficient scale to offset any negative impacts caused or (b) it is undertaken simultaneously as part of a wider portfolio of actions, which collectively generate a net resilience gain.

Actors and affected populations must believe that the decisions themselves and the potential actions co-created are salient, credible, and legitimate in their context for them to be willing to engage effectively with researchers and their communities. This informed decision-making process can open innovative pathways to locally salient and globally coherent cultures of sustainability and facilitate moving from decision to intention to implementation of societal change in communities anywhere in the world using a very informal low-tech dialogic process or with sophisticated scenario visualization tools (Burns & Roszkowska, 2008; Wolf et al., 2023), all of which fall under the rubric of "decision theater." Decision theater can be substantially enhanced by inclusion of artistic expressions of cultural and social identities in the scenarios of concern being developed by KLASICA. These scenarios are models of alternative choices in context and formed with scientific, technical, and engineering options and constraints combined with salient affective social and cultural factors. The latter factors can be inferred from narrative expressions of social identities and visions of the future. Scenarios are also critically important because of the need to pair highly local vision of sustainable futures with global RCPs and SSPs (Fujimori et al., 2017; Lehtonen et al., 2021). Empirical data on the technical and cultural conditions is used to populate simulations and modelling, which then form a dynamic, adaptive media environment to inform participatory, deliberative decision making on complex socio-economic-ecological issues. A wide, evolving spectrum of technologies, modeling, and practices for informed and inclusive decision-making will contribute to understanding decision-making practices and outcomes. The records of decision-making processes (Glynn et al., 2018) can lead to further insights and refinement of transdisciplinary research and actions that advance the state-of-the-art of environmental modelling and scenario development.

Conclusions

We wish to engage participants in exploring and discussing ways to create effective scenarios that stimulate meaningful dialogues on critical issues for future disaster resilience and cultures of sustainability in the communities in which they work and live. Creating scenarios and facilitating such dialogues are especially important in these times of increasing polarization with many divergent narratives and echo chambers. We explore how images, sounds, and artefacts can be created or adapted from arts, science, and nature as evocative focal points ("boundary objects") for engaging people in meaningful dialogues towards alternatives to address community resilience challenges.

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An Evolutionary, System-of-Systems, Convergence Paradigm Provides Context for Sociocultural Systems

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Summary

An evolutionary system-of-systems convergence paradigm based on a partially quantifiable, scientifically falsifiable, formal theoretical framework can be used to systematically identify, decompose, characterize, and then converge, a nested, evolutionary ensemble of geophysical, biophysical, sociocultural and sociotechnical systems, providing much needed context for understanding human behavior in Anthropocene systems.

Introduction

Evolutionary mechanisms enabled billions of humans to profoundly transform Earth systems. Focusing on geological evolution, genetic evolution, the evolution of the brain, cultural evolution, and technological evolution, a nested evolutionary ensemble of geophysical, biophysical, sociocultural and sociotechnical systems can be identified (Little et al., 2023). The more recent sociocultural and sociotechnical systems have vastly accelerated the temporal rates of interaction among the systems, and vastly increased the spatial extent of interactions across the systems, creating a much more dynamic, globally connected meta-ecosystem. The resulting family of societal challenges (e.g., climate change and impacts, renewable energy, adaptive infrastructure, disasters, pandemics, food insecurity, biodiversity, resilience, sustainable development, and equity) are highly interdependent, and need to be framed and addressed from this evolutionary perspective.

Methodology

To coordinate the required strategic interventions across multiple systems and scales, an evolutionary, system-of-systems (evoSoS) convergence paradigm is required. The nested evolutionary ensemble of Anthropocene systems can be characterized (Little et al., 2023) as follows: (1) Geophysical systems include, for example, geological, ocean, atmospheric, climate, and hydrological systems; (2) Biophysical systems integrate biological and geophysical systems and include, for example, ecological and soil systems; (3) Sociocultural systems are a specialized form of biophysical system, which emphasize social knowledge and culture and include, for example, cognitive, communication, education, economic, legal and governance systems; and (4) Sociotechnical systems are a specialized form of sociocultural system, which emphasize technical knowledge and technology and include, for example, land-use, energy, agricultural, mining, transportation, industrial and other infrastructure systems. It is useful to distinguish between sociocultural and sociotechnical systems because technology and socially mediated technical knowledge greatly enhance human influence and accelerate the coevolutionary mechanisms in the ensemble of Anthropocene systems.

The evolutionary SoS paradigm aims to coherently integrate geophysical sciences, biological sciences, social sciences, engineering, and the humanities, providing a partially quantifiable, causally coherent, scientifically falsifiable, formal theoretical framework. Crucially, this framework can represent human behavior in sociocultural systems (Muthukrishna & Henrich, 2019). Unfortunately, the interdependent relationship between human behavior and context has largely been ignored, although progress has been made by environmental and ecological psychology, and more recently by historical psychology (Muthukrishna et al., 2021). The evolutionary SoS paradigm enables the integration of behavioral science – including the physical, social, and historical contexts that shape perception, reasoning, and decision-making – with the geophysical, biophysical, sociocultural and sociotechnical context in which the behavior occurs.

Human psychology and behavior are shaped by millions of years of genetic and cultural evolution, and a short lifetime of accumulated knowledge and experience (Muthukrishna et al., 2021), offering levers for behavioral

change (Schimmelpfennig & Muthukrishna, 2023). Several major evolutionary mechanisms (i.e., kinship, reciprocity, reputation, signalling, punishment and institutions) (Henrich & Muthukrishna, 2021) can be used to explain human cooperation and competition in sociocultural systems. There are other mechanism of sociocultural systems that can be considered, but as an illustrative starting point, a generic model of a sociocultural system might be represented (Little et al., 2023) as follows. Individuals in sociocultural systems process information (which, from the point of view of the human body, is received and transmitted both internally and externally) using their own cognitive systems, cooperate and compete with other individuals using communication systems, acquire and lose status and leadership positions, acquire and forget knowledge, norms, and institutions, and form alliances with other individuals. Similarly, groups of individuals cooperate and compete with other groups using communication systems, acquire and lose status, acquire and forget knowledge, norms and institutions, and form alliances with other groups. Governance, economic, educational and legal systems guide and constrain the evolutionary dynamics. The resulting social dynamics involve individuals, groups, and groups of groups, with overlapping versions of these agent-based structures propagating through all sociocultural systems.

Human intelligence emerges not from our innate individual brainpower, but from the sharing of information and knowledge in sociocultural systems over generations (Henrich & Muthukrishna, 2023). Larger, more diverse, and more optimally interconnected sociocultural systems give rise to faster innovation, improving our collective ability to address societal challenges. As a result, cultural evolution can turn mindless mobs into wise crowds by facilitating and constraining cognition in a range of sociocultural systems. Unfortunately, the opposite may also be true when conflict emerges among competing sociocultural groups. We can also use the concept of cultural evolvability to tackle the paradox of diversity, which means that cultural trait diversity offers the largest potential for empowering innovation, but also poses systemic challenges at both organizational and societal scales. Although diversity empowers innovation with our collective brain, diversity also reduces cooperation. Fortunately, cultural evolvability enables an understanding of the importance and impact of diversity, revealing how to reap its benefits and reduce its costs. By resolving the paradox of diversity, we can recombine the best innovations from different sociocultural groups and different disciplines, creating conditions conducive to larger scales of cooperation and greater levels of innovation.

Conclusions

The evolutionary SoS convergence paradigm enables the integration of behavioral science with the geophysical, biophysical, sociocultural and sociotechnical context in which the behavior occurs, while providing a more systematic and scientifically rigorous approach that can be used to resolve the paradox of diversity.

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Starting the Conversation: A Lesson in Cross-Cultural Communication for Water Modellers

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Summary

The importance of engaging First Nations peoples in natural resource management is increasingly recognized around the world. In Australia, legislation and funding rules are driving greater engagement between scientists/engineers and First Nations communities. In this context, we developed a project to create simple animation resources to enhance engagement between water modellers and Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people. However our first project exposed some of the common mistakes made when scientists/engineers engage First Nations communities. Here we present the animated story of our journey, which shows how (and how not to) put into practice principles of good engagement.

Introduction

In 2022, the funding guidelines for the Australian-based Queensland Water Modelling Network were updated to include a requirement for First Nations engagement, which led the first author to form a relationship with Aboriginal-owned company Jibija Ung-gwee and animation company Thoughts Drawn Out to produce accessible animation resources to improve dialogue and engagement between water modellers and First Nations people.

Methodology and Results

The original project proposal involved bringing together water modellers and First Nations people at a workshop in the city. However once the project got underway, a number of issues arose, including inadequate budgeting for First Nations' partners' time, and suitable recognition of Intellectual Property. Through a process of co-design, we radically reshaped the project. We also decided to document the story of our collaboration, to bring to life common issues which occur when scientists and engineers engage with First Nations communities, and how these might be resolved.

Conclusions

While there is a plethora of documents providing guidelines on good practice in First Nations engagement (e.g. ((NESP), 2021; AIATSIS, 2020a, 2020b), these are not always put practice. By animating our story, including the challenges we faced along the way and how these were overcome, we hope to encourage more fair, equitable and respectful dialogue between modellers and First Nations people.

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AI-enabled Modeling with Stakeholders: Computational Infrastructure, Knowledge Capture and Reasoning

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Summary

AI-enabled Modeling with stakeholders (AIMS) offers an expansive set of opportunities to advance research. This presentation shares an overview of AI subfields with possible applications to participatory modeling (PM) capable of accelerating the development of AIMS style research and implementation. This presentation highlights results of multiple applied research projects to share results exemplified through and suite of Artificial Intelligence supported computational systems, applications, and sociotechnical research processes. While not comprehensive, the results provide useful insights that active PM researchers will be able to leverage to advance their own approaches with co-design and integrated modeling applications.

Introduction

Adapting AI approaches with science-based data and models is the core for next-generation intelligent, participatory modeling approaches that leverage human-AI interactions and can accelerate participatory modeling research and practice. Surprisingly, the more commonly recognized AI subfields of machine learning and natural language processing may not represent the subfields that best align. Reviews of AI subfields and an AI research roadmap prepared by the broad community of AI researchers document numerous areas of interest to the AI research community (see, for example, U.S. Department of Education, 2021; Gil, Y. and Selman, 2019; Gil et al., 2018). The forefront of AIMS research sits at the nexus between the AI community research interests and the PM community research and application needs.

Methodology and Results

Drawn from alternative subfields of AI research, this presentation highlights key areas and capabilities that our team has studied and are needed to deploy AI-support for research that would be well suited to PM applications:

- Knowledge capture from the subfield of Advanced Sensing and Intelligent Robotics: The Sites and Stories application uses knowledge capture techniques for both structured (sensor) and unstructured (stories) data and information collection. By combining low-cost sensor deployment (Cleveland et al., 2019) and multi-modal capture, such as audio and video, researchers can collect and combine place-based information to represent the conditions of an event, region or place of interest to stakeholders. The Sites and Stories application uses natural language processing to categorize information from these sources and automate data fusion.
- Knowledge Representation and Reasoning: The Model Integration Platform (MINT) streamlines how people can set up and run complex combinations of models to analyze multiple steps quickly and across many iterations. MINT provides front-end problem-framing interfaces to semantically link with data and models within a modeling orchestration platform that enables loose coupling and scenario design (Gil et al., 2021).

- Automated planning and scheduling: The computational infrastructure needs to include reusable environments and digital infrastructure to support the composition and orchestration of integrated data- and model- collections capable of supporting model execution at scale so that AIMS researchers can quickly reuse analyses and generate interactive presentations with stakeholders. Systems that are designed to address the ten dimensions commonly considered part of integrated problems, such as those confronted in water management, will be well placed to support AIMS at scale (Hamilton et al., 2015).

Conclusions

While AI, more commonly reported in science and engineering-based applications, tends to focus on machine learning approaches and, more recently, natural language processing techniques, like Large Language Models, have gained public attention. Subfields of AI in the current landscape may better align with the needs of participatory modeling research and implementation. PM researchers may find valuable contributions via approaches in knowledge representation and reasoning, automated planning and scheduling, optimization techniques for combinatorial problems, and advanced sensing capabilities from intelligent robotics. Both AI and Participatory Modeling are dynamic fields (Voinov et al., 2016) for that reason, a shared goal of PM researchers and the iEMSS community may be to support the need for rapid learning about the AI landscape among the participatory modeling community and encourage the community to evaluate a wide range of possible AI approaches to serve the challenges and opportunities presented at the nexus between these two dynamic fields of study and application.

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Enhancing Hydroinformatics Education through Virtual Reality and AI Integration

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Summary

This paper introduces an innovative Education Room for studying and honing skills in Hydroinformatics. Utilizing a Virtual Environment, Natural Language Processing, and digitized human avatars, the system integrates Unreal Engine, Twinmotion, MethahumanSDK, and Chat-GPT4 technologies. The Education Room features an interactive artificial instructor capable of responding to user queries via voice, enhancing engagement and facilitating experiential learning. Equipped with educational resources, the platform aims to cater to diverse learning styles. The study examines the architecture, services, and challenges of virtual learning systems, emphasizing their potential in educational settings. It underscores the importance of personalized, accessible, and cost-effective platforms for preparing students and researchers for future endeavors.

Introduction

In the realm of Hydroinformatics education, the challenge of effectively conveying complex water-related data and processes presents a significant educational barrier (Demir et al., 2022). Traditional educational methods often fall short in providing the dynamic and interactive experiences required for thorough comprehension of such intricate subjects (Demiray et al., 2023). This gap in pedagogical efficacy highlights the need for innovative solutions that can enhance the learning experience and engagement for students (Alkhwaldi, 2024). Thus, the development of virtual reality (VR) technologies introduces a promising avenue to bridge this gap by creating immersive and interactive learning environments that can transform the traditional educational landscape (Marougkas et al., 2024; Georgakakos and Knighton, 2024).

This project introduces an Education Room utilizing VR, Natural Language Processing, and digitized avatars to create interactive learning environments. Leveraging platforms like Unreal Engine and MethahumanSDK, our initiative aims to revolutionize conventional classrooms, enhancing engagement and enriching learning outcomes. Despite challenges, including technical limitations and accessibility issues, our project represents a significant advancement in educational methodologies through VR integration.

Methodology and Results

The scope of this project is broad and multifaceted, aiming to benefit various stakeholders within the educational sector. Students are the primary beneficiaries, gaining enriched learning experiences tailored to their needs. Educators can enhance teaching methodologies, while researchers explore further applications of virtual reality in education. Educational institutions seek innovation in their curriculum, and policy makers aim to improve learning outcomes and accessibility through cutting-edge technologies.

The system architecture aims to enhance Hydroinformatics education through immersive experiences, comprising three interconnected components. Firstly, the Virtual Classroom Environment, crafted with Unreal Engine, replicates traditional classroom settings, providing a familiar yet enriched learning space. Secondly, the Metahuman Instructor Avatar, developed using MetahumanSDK, serves as a realistic virtual instructor capable of engaging with students through natural language, facilitated by ChatGPT-4 integration. Lastly, ChatGPT-4 enables real-time communication, ensuring accurate and contextually relevant responses, thus fostering interactive learning dialogues within the virtual environment (Sajja et al., 2023).

The system initiates with user query submission through an intuitive interface, accommodating various input methods for seamless interaction. Upon receipt, the backend processes the query and engages ChatGPT for context-based response generation, promoting real-time educational dialogue. Subsequently, the response is integrated into the Methahuman avatar, employing advanced animation techniques to ensure lifelike interaction. Finally, the avatar delivers the educational content to the user, facilitating comprehension and engagement, thus enabling effective knowledge transfer within the virtual environment. The development of the virtual instructor for Hydroinformatics is a meticulous process, integrating advanced technologies to provide an engaging and informative learning experience. Leveraging GPT-4 Turbo with an extended context limit, the instructor can engage in complex dialogues, offering detailed explanations and follow-up discussions to enhance learning. The instructor's role, persona, and communication style are carefully crafted to be knowledgeable, approachable, and encouraging, cultivating a positive learning environment.

The project is exported from Unreal Engine using a specialized VR template optimized for the Oculus SDK, integral to the Meta Quest ecosystem. Configurations are adjusted to match Meta Quest's hardware capabilities, including resolution, frame rate, and level of detail settings. Input mapping is fine-tuned for intuitive interaction with Meta Quest controllers. This export process ensures that the educational VR experience is immersive, accessible, and provides a seamless learning experience on Meta Quest devices. Enhanced by collaborative tools and prioritizing accessibility, the virtual classroom ensures inclusivity and adaptability to diverse learning styles. Moreover, the integration of real-world simulations offers students immersive experiences in Hydroinformatics, deepening their understanding of complex concepts. Augmented by an advanced avatar, the learning environment provides dynamic and personalized interactions, enriching the overall educational experience.

Conclusions

This environment enhances engagement, accommodates diverse learning styles, and nurtures collaboration globally, promoting a more inclusive and interactive educational experience for students of Hydroinformatics. Moving forward, future research will focus on addressing technical and accessibility limitations, expanding content areas, and assessing pedagogical effectiveness, ensuring VR and AI technologies effectively enhance learning outcomes and student engagement. The forward trajectory of this research will delve into the integration of augmented reality with VR systems to provide even more immersive and comprehensive educational experiences. As the field evolves, there will also be a significant emphasis on developing adaptive learning systems that can customize educational content to meet individual student needs in real-time. These advancements will likely set new benchmarks in educational technology, pushing the boundaries of how interactive and immersive learning environments can benefit Hydroinformatics education and beyond.

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Enhancing Hydrological Data Visualization Through Extended Reality: A Framework for Environmental Decision-Making

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Summary

This study introduces a novel approach to hydrological data visualization utilizing Extended Reality (XR) technologies to improve environmental planning and decision-making. It transitions from conventional visualizations to Virtual Reality, using the Unity Engine and Mapbox to interact dynamically with real-time data. Users can explore a 3D representation of the continental U.S., accessing comprehensive data from USGS and NOAA. The system is accessible via web browsers and VR devices. It discusses system architecture, overcomes traditional visualization limitations, and suggests future applications in environmental management and disaster response, highlighting XR's transformative potential in hydroinformatics.

Introduction

The field of hydrology has historically relied on traditional two-dimensional visualization techniques to represent complex datasets (Cosio et al., 2023). These methods, often confined to static graphs and maps, have served as fundamental tools for analysis and decision-making in water resource management (Xu et al., 2022). However, with the rapid evolution of technology, particularly in the realm of computational techniques and data processing, there is a growing need to enhance the visualization capabilities to better handle the increasing complexity and volume of hydrological data (Sermet and Demir, 2022).

Recent advancements in Extended Reality (XR) technologies, encompassing both virtual and augmented reality, present a transformative opportunity for the hydroinformatics sector (Demir et al., 2022). XR offers a more immersive and interactive platform, allowing users to visualize and interact with data in three-dimensional spaces (Teegavarapu and Chandramouli, 2021). This shift not only promises to improve the accuracy of data interpretation but also aims to foster a deeper understanding and engagement by displaying hydrological phenomena in a more intuitive and lifelike manner (Demiray et al., 2023).

This framework integrates XR technologies into hydrology, emphasizing the potential for these tools to revolutionize environmental planning and management. Through the use of Unity engine and Mapbox Maps SDK, along with APIs like the USGS API, the proposed framework allows users to dynamically interact with real-time data and navigate a 3D representation of large geographical areas such as the continental United States. This approach not only addresses the limitations of traditional visualization methods but also paves the way for enhanced collaborative decision-making and efficient environmental management in response to both current and emerging challenges in the field of hydrology.

Methodology and Results

This study leverages the Unity game engine, combined with the Mapbox Maps SDK, to construct an immersive hydroinformatics framework. The system is designed to integrate extended reality (XR) for dynamic interaction with real-time hydrological and meteorological data. We utilized APIs from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) to fetch real-time data, ensuring the system provides current environmental conditions and hydrological phenomena. This data integration allows users to interact with live data feeds that reflect actual environmental scenarios, enhancing the system's utility for real-time decision-making and educational purposes.

To facilitate immersive and intuitive control within the virtual environment, the Virtual Reality Toolkit (VRTK) was employed. This toolkit was crucial for developing ergonomic and user-friendly controls, which are pivotal for maintaining user engagement and ensuring ease of navigation through the virtual landscape.

Additionally, the WebXR exporter was used to adapt our Unity-based application for the web. This allows the system to run seamlessly across various platforms without the need for platform-specific modifications. The exported application is hosted on a static web server, enabling easy accessibility through standard web browsers and VR headsets. This approach not only broadens the user base by eliminating the need for specialized hardware but also facilitates effortless updates and maintenance of the system.

The integration of these technologies—Unity, Mapbox Maps SDK, USGS and NOAA APIs, VRTK, and WebXR—forms a robust framework for immersive hydroinformatics. This system enables stakeholders to explore, analyze, and understand complex hydrological data within an interactive 3D environment, promoting a deeper comprehension of hydrological dynamics and facilitating proactive environmental management and planning. Through rigorous testing and iterative development, we ensured that the system is both scalable and adaptable to various hydrological and meteorological scenarios, making it a versatile tool in the arsenal of hydrological research and education.

The implementation of our immersive hydroinformatics system yielded significant insights into the capabilities of extended reality (XR) in enhancing hydrological data visualization and interaction. Our results demonstrated a marked improvement in user engagement and understanding of complex hydrological phenomena through immersive visualization compared to traditional methods.

Conclusions

The development of this XR-based hydroinformatics framework marks a pivotal advancement in the visualization and management of hydrological data. It enhances user engagement and understanding of complex data sets, supporting more informed decision-making in environmental planning. The research opens avenues for further integration of XR technologies in environmental sciences, promising significant impacts on disaster preparedness, educational applications, and collaborative planning efforts. Future work will focus on expanding the system's capabilities to include more diverse environmental scenarios and improving its accessibility across different platforms.

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Integrating AI-Enhanced Adaptive Learning Systems in Environmental Sciences Education

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Summary

This study introduces a framework for artificial intelligence-enabled educational assistant tailored for environmental sciences education in higher education. Utilizing state-of-the-art artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) technologies, the framework provides personalized learning experiences by facilitating access to complex environmental data and integrating seamlessly with existing Learning Management Systems (LMS). The results showcase the potential for enhanced engagement and improved understanding of environmental concepts and software tools, suggesting significant potential for AI in educational settings, especially in disciplines involving complex data interactions.

Introduction

The field of environmental sciences is inherently complex and multidisciplinary, requiring students to engage with a broad spectrum of knowledge that spans geology, biology, chemistry, and physics, often integrated through sophisticated software tools (Lee, 2023). Traditional educational methods in this domain have relied heavily on theoretical instruction and static resources, which can fail to capture the dynamic and interactive nature of environmental issues and processes (Winkler & Söllner, 2018). This educational approach often leaves a gap in student engagement and understanding, particularly in applying theoretical knowledge to solve practical, real-world problems (Holmes et al., 2019). Moreover, the rapid evolution of environmental technologies and methodologies necessitates a learning approach that can adapt quickly and provide students with the latest information and tools, a need not fully met by conventional educational models (Sajja et al., 2023c).

To address these challenges, the introduction of AI in educational settings, particularly through the educational assistant AI framework, offers a promising solution. The framework can transform the learning experience by providing interactive, adaptive, and personalized educational support (Sajja et al., 2023a). Specifically, in environmental sciences education, there is a critical need for tools that can not only deliver information but also interpret complex data sets, simulate environmental processes, and provide hands-on experience with industry-standard software. Educational AI systems must be capable of handling the diverse and often complex queries typical of environmental sciences, necessitating advanced capabilities in NLP and contextual understanding.

Methodology and Results

The development involved a sophisticated system architecture that utilized NodeJS for backend operations to handle server-side logic and data management, and React for the frontend to manage the user interface and enhance user experience. The integration of large language models such as GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 was pivotal (Sajja et al., 2024). These models were selected for their exceptional language understanding capabilities, allowing it to process and interpret complex queries related to environmental sciences. This robust setup enabled seamless integration with widely used LMS such as Canvas and Moodle, ensuring that the assistant could interact effectively with educational content and respond accurately to student inquiries. The system's backend was designed to efficiently fetch and push data to the LMS, facilitating a smooth flow of information

and maintaining the integrity of the educational ecosystem. The framework was experimented with an environmental sciences course. This phase was crucial to test for real-world application and to potentially allow students to ask questions and seek explanations relevant to their studies. The AI was programmed to handle a spectrum of queries, from simple queries requiring direct access to course materials to more complex analytical tasks that involved environmental data interpretation and application of various software tools.

The platform is equipped with a suite of dynamic features designed to enhance the educational experience across various dimensions. For instance, the system includes an automated flashcard feature where students can generate flashcards on specific topics for self-study, enhancing retention and recall. Additionally, the framework offers a quiz module that allows students to take customized quizzes generated based on their learning progress, with the system providing immediate feedback and grading to facilitate self-assessment. The Study Partner feature is another significant addition, acting as a virtual companion that helps students plan their study schedule, reminding them of syllabus timelines and due dates. To assist instructors, it includes a Learning Analytics Dashboard that provides detailed insights into student engagement and performance, enabling educators to tailor their teaching strategies effectively. Furthermore, the system incorporates a homework detection mechanism which identifies when a student's query relates to designated homework or assessment tasks, thus preventing direct answers to promote independent learning. This feature is part of a broader cheating prevention strategy that ensures academic integrity by monitoring patterns that may suggest unethical behavior, such as repeated requests for answers to assessment-related questions. These integrated features make the assistant a comprehensive educational tool that supports both students and educators in creating a more effective and interactive learning environment.

Conclusions

The implementation of the proposed AI framework in environmental sciences education has demonstrated significant potential to enhance student engagement and understanding of the subject matter. The system provides a personalized learning environment that adapts to individual student needs, facilitating a deeper understanding of complex topics and software tools essential in environmental studies. Future research will focus on expanding the capabilities to include more interactive elements such as virtual labs and real-time data analysis, further enhancing its utility in environmental sciences education (Sajja et al., 2023c). Broader integration with various LMS platforms and the inclusion of more diverse educational content can improve the robustness of the tool in the educational technology landscape. The findings encourage continued exploration, particularly in fields that benefit from interactive and adaptive learning tools.

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Analysis of Narratives and Resonances to Support Participatory Modeling and Decisions

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Abstract

Evaluation of current challenges in environmental and natural resource management can come from an understanding of socio-ecological systems (SES). However, SES are very complex and exploring their behaviour, such as with the use of numerical models, often highlights this complexity (Cockerill 2024). Invariably, human decision-making in response to these challenges is influenced by biases, beliefs, heuristics, values and norms (BBHV), as well as by emotions (Cockerill et. al 2019). Narratives are “*a purposeful, affective form of human communication*” (Helgeson et. al., 2022) that provide a window to SES and to these BBHV, emotions and resonances. Resonances reflect what individuals and communities most strongly care about and are willing to express, are emotionally-driven and life-way driven. In this paper, we focus on how the analysis of resonances may help develop shared understanding of different stakeholders’ positions and perspectives, and the needs held by different constituencies.

An understanding of resonances is important because mental and conceptual models are at the root of participatory modelling and numerical models. Decisions and judgments are invariably influenced by the BBHV and experiences of the different participants, constituencies, or actors involved. What people care about can influence decisions on questions to raise, hypotheses to test and scenarios to explore. Establishing thoughtful, well-considered, mental and conceptual models relevant to a complex issue is, in our view, a requirement for building useful numerical models that can be used to improve decision-making and regulatory processes. Also, greater clarity on what people care about and on their prioritizations, may enhance the translation of science and different sources of knowledge into policy (Cockerill et al., in review) – thereby supporting better-considered and more societally-acceptable actions. In doing so, resonances may help better address the complex resource and environmental issues currently faced by society.

We present a database of 81 resonances that can be used to analyse different types of narratives (i.e., written, oral, symbols) across many different socio-cultural contexts, without any attached value judgements. The aim of our resonances database is to facilitate the creation of records of engagement and decision-making (RoED), to inform participatory modeling and to improve environmental decisions.

Initially, resonances, were grouped into ten categories based on our knowledge of social science theories, biocultural evolution and, our personal experiences. We cross-connected our resonances with established theories such as a modern version of Maslow’s human motivations, Haidt’s moral foundations theory and Schwartz’s basic human needs (Kenrick et al., 2010; Haidt and Joseph 2011 ; Haidt 2012; Schwartz 2012). Then, resonances were further informed through our testing on different texts. We tested and refined the resonances (and their definitions) by analyzing different narratives found in policy, planning and research on two examples of current difficult challenges in environmental and natural resource management (i.e., “Protecting Lake Taupo Project (PLT)” and “Chesapeake Bay 2014 Agreement”). We also established connections between the resonances and ten biocultural propensities (Glynn et al., in review).

The resonance database reveals core prioritizations, concerns, mental models, emotions, and BBHV. These resonances were grouped into 10 primary categories, by expressions of: group and identity (i.e., collaboration, betrayal); credibility and responsibility (i.e., blame, responsibility taking); mark and ownership (i.e., status, territory); power and control (i.e., fragility); valuing the past (i.e., conditions, beliefs); valuing the present (i.e.,

stability, protection); rebelling the past or present (i.e., new beliefs and norms); seeking better futures (i.e., people); immediacies of the future (i.e., care for next generations); and focal idealizations (i.e., lifeways). For example, the text from PLT document “*This relationship is real, deep and it is entwined with our history, our stories, our songs. These waters have nourished many generations of Ngati Tuwharetoa*”, reveals several primary categories (and resonances), i.e. : valuing the past (*veneration of ancestors or of history resonance*) and focal idealizations (*place idealization or association resonance*).

We expect that our database will serve as a living document that can be improved with time, experience, and with the contributions of other scientists and practitioners. This rich compendium of resonances can help advance narratives research. It can also inform future typologies to address complex environmental problems (i.e., climate change adaptation) and advance participatory modelling and decision-making.

We will further explore the possibility of using our resonance database in connection with artificial intelligence and large language models to help facilitate community and stakeholder engagements. We welcome feedback and are open to opportunities to test and refine our database and theories.

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Stream B. Modeling environmental fate of contaminants, human well-being and ecological public health

**Environmental modelling in the
changing assessment landscape:
Busier, more contested, more
important**

Assessing Riparian Functioning Condition for Improved Ecosystem Services: A Case Study in the Southeastern USA

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Summary

Using the riparian proper functioning condition (PFC) protocol developed by the U.S. Department of the Interior (DOI) and the U.S. Department of Agriculture and retrieving remote sensing data (e.g., National Hydrography Dataset Plus version 2) through a web-based graphical user interface of US EPA’s Hydrologic Micro Services, we assessed functioning condition of lotic riparian areas of mainstem Back Creek located in the Blue Ridge mountains of Virginia (USA). The assessments concluded that 52% of the assessed length was in PFC, attributed to diverse vegetation, maintained channel characteristics, and floodplain development (where appropriate).

Introduction

Riparian areas or buffer zones are often considered prime locations for best management practices (BMPs) that provide multiple watershed ecosystem services by controlling input and sequestration of non-point source pollutants in streams, lakes, and wetlands (Ghimire et al., 2021; Ghimire et al., 2022). The DOI defined riparian areas as “functioning properly” when adequate vegetation, landform, or woody material is present to dissipate stream-energy associated with high water flows, capture sediment and aid floodplain development, improve floodwater retention and ground-water recharge, develop root masses that stabilize streambanks against erosion, maintain channel characteristics, and support greater biodiversity. The Functional–At Risk (FAR) state refers to limited functioning condition with risk of impairment due to one or more impaired attribute or process. Non-Functional (NF) state refers to an area clearly not providing adequate vegetation, landform, or woody material to dissipate stream-energy and to improve water quality parameters (USDOI, 2015).

Our objective was to assess the lotic riparian condition of the Back Creek to describe possible functionality relationships with stream water quality.

Methodology and Results

We assessed functioning condition of Back Creek recently studied by Ghimire et al. (Ghimire et al., 2021; Ghimire et al., 2022). The PFC protocol (Figure 1) included 17 items in the form of the statements or criteria questionnaires encompassing the hydrologic, vegetation, and geomorphic attributes and processes occurring in or near a stream (E. S. Hall et al., 2019; R. K. Hall et al., 2018; Swanson et al., 2017; USDOI, 2015).

Figure 1. PFC protocol workflow (USDOI, 2015).

We formed an interdisciplinary team of scientists with expertise in biology, botany, soil science, engineering, and hydrology to conduct the PFC assessments. Relevant remote sensing existing data were retrieved using the US EPA’s Hydrologic Micro Services web interface. We delineated the [National Hydrography Dataset](#) Flowlines (NHDFlowlines) as NHD [reaches](#) each with corresponding catchments based on the [NHDPlus](#) (National Hydrography Dataset Plus) geospatial framework, Version 2 (NHDPlusV2) in ArcGIS® Pro. We characterized the hydrology, geomorphology, and vegetation of all 26 NHD reaches totaling 41.1 km. We completed 10 confirmatory field PFC assessments in July 31 through August 4, 2023. A preliminary field reconnaissance was also conducted on September 21, 2022. Results showed (Figure 2).

Conclusions

Each of the 17 PFC assessment items played an important role in impacting the Back Creek water quality. The PFC assessments indicated that over 50% of the assessed Back Creek was in PFC that included the reaches with altered potential. The study is expected to guide future PFC assessment efforts that may include assessing additional reaches within the Back Creek watershed and other watersheds in the region, engaging diverse stakeholders, states, tribes, local landowners, and students through Government - private partnerships.

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Although this work was reviewed by EPA and approved for publication, it may not necessarily reflect official Agency policy. We thank David J. Williams (EPA) for reviewing the abstract. All opinions expressed are the authors’ and do not necessarily reflect the policies and views of US EPA. Mention of trade names or commercial products does not constitute endorsement or recommendation for use.

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Figure 2. The Back Creek, the 26 reaches, and 10 onsite PFC assessment reaches, modified from Ghimire et al. (2022).

An Evolutionary, System-of-Systems, Convergence Paradigm for Societal Challenges of the Anthropocene

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Summary

Humans have been addressing societal challenges since our species evolved roughly 200,000 years ago. An important difference now is that we are using scientific research to help us address societal challenges that are far more complex than previously attempted. The prevailing scientific and academic cultures are arguably the biggest barriers that prevent us from using our rapidly accumulating collective knowledge more effectively.

Introduction

Evolutionary mechanisms enabled billions of humans to profoundly transform Earth systems. Focusing on geological evolution, genetic evolution, the evolution of the brain, cultural evolution, and technological evolution, a nested evolutionary ensemble of geophysical, biophysical, sociocultural and sociotechnical systems can be identified (Little et al., 2023). The more recent sociocultural and sociotechnical systems have vastly accelerated the temporal rates of interaction among the systems, and vastly increased the spatial extent of interactions across the systems, creating a much more dynamic, globally connected meta-ecosystem. The resulting family of societal challenges (e.g., climate change and impacts, renewable energy, adaptive infrastructure, disasters, pandemics, food insecurity, biodiversity, resilience, sustainable development, and equity) are highly interdependent, and need to be integratively framed and addressed.

Methodology

To coordinate the required strategic interventions across multiple systems and scales, an evolutionary, system-of-systems (evoSoS) convergence paradigm is required. Founded on an understanding of how Anthropocene systems coevolved and became increasingly interconnected, an evolutionary perspective is crucially important when representing human cognition, communication, and the resulting human behavior, because it was the evolution of the human brain, combined with the evolution of culture and technology, that drove the evolution of the Anthropocene (Little et al., 2023). The way we think, the way we communicate, and the way we make decisions and transform decisions into behavior, all influence, and are influenced by, the coevolving geophysical, biophysical, sociocultural and sociotechnical systems in which our lives are entwined (Henrich & Muthukrishna, 2021; Muthukrishna et al., 2021). An evoSoS computational framework must be designed to coherently converge the nested evolutionary ensemble of geophysical, biophysical, sociocultural and sociotechnical systems in a multi-level modelling architecture that explicitly represents the various levels of abstraction underlying the structure and behavior of the system of Anthropocene systems. The architecture must enable the development and use of a causally coherent ontology with interoperable computational tools and must enable multiple societal challenges to be addressed at a specific geographic location of interest.

Substantial progress is being made in modeling coupled systems in several closely related, interdisciplinary fields of research. There are many cases where integrated models are sufficient for the purpose, but if the goal is to address the societal challenges, then these interdisciplinary fields all exhibit at least one of three primary limitations: (1) they are not based on the evolutionary mechanisms which gave rise to the Anthropocene and the ensuing societal challenges; (2) they include elements of social systems, but the elements are not based on a causally-coherent theoretical framework of evolved human behavior; and (3) they do not start with a framing that is holistic enough for addressing several interconnected societal challenges with multiple systems that are nested, highly interdependent, and dynamically evolving. Because of these limitations, it is not possible to make coordinated interventions across multiple systems and scales.

Model-based systems engineering (MBSE) and hetero-functional graph theory (HFGT) (Farid et al., 2022) provide a powerful methodology to address these issues. Real-world Anthropocene systems are first translated into the graphical systems modeling language (SysML) to integrate and reconcile ontologies, and then HFGT is used to algorithmically traverse the gap from the graphical SysML model to the associated mathematical model, and ultimately to the computational model. Reference architectures are created in SysML and then instantiated in HFGT. The reference architectures are extensible and agile, without the technical limitations associated with the co-simulation of integrated models, and an HFGT toolbox is available to perform the computations. HFGT is a fusion of MBSE and network science and has been successfully applied to several sociotechnical systems, including the American Multi-Modal Energy system (Thompson & Farid, 2023), which is a system-of-systems comprised of four separate but interdependent infrastructure enterprises: the electric grid, the natural gas enterprise, the oil enterprise, and the coal enterprise. Given their highly generalized descriptions, SysML and HFGT can incorporate and integrate well-known system dynamics, agent-based and network science models. Furthermore, SysML and HFGT are based on the structure of human natural language, relying on a simple ontology with subjects and verb + object predicates that are arranged in a meta-architecture which is independent of discipline. Thus, SysML and HFGT together create a common scientific language and computational framework, providing the means to produce an ontologically coherent computational model of all Anthropocene systems. An important advantage of this common ontology is that it enhances clarity and understanding, thereby reducing complexity. The large number of Anthropocene systems limits the scale at which the models can be integrated with current computing capacities. Fortunately, when addressing societal challenges, we usually only need to make interventions or policy decisions at urban or regional scales. A tiered structure with different levels of abstraction is therefore required (Little et al., 2019). HFGT is especially helpful as it can be used to coherently span spatial and temporal scales. Finally, human decision-making usually takes place at several organizational levels, and we can take advantage of this as we include sociocultural models that involve decision-making at urban and regional scales.

Conclusions

The evolutionary SoS convergence paradigm requires a major transformation in our approach to science and engineering, and a new generation of Anthropocene systems integrators is needed to create a meta-discipline that spans all the disciplines associated with societal challenges of the Anthropocene.

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WISE: A Watershed-Scale Carbon Budget Calculator

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Summary

Current watershed models have limitations in representing carbon cycling processes, hindering their applicability to new scenarios such as watershed-scale carbon budget calculation. To address this, our team developed WISE (Watershed-based Integrated Simulator for Earth-surface), a model that significantly enhances the representation of carbon cycling processes in soil and inland waters, as well as freeze-thaw, glacier, and snow melting processes in cold regions. With WISE, we can go beyond traditional applications in water resource planning and water quality control, and calculate watershed-scale carbon budget accounting for lateral carbon transfer under the impacts of climate change and human activities.

Introduction

Watersheds are an ideal unit for hydrological studies, water resources planning, water quality control, and carbon budget calculation. On one hand, strong connections exist among geographic units within a watershed due to the flow of water from upstream to downstream, which makes watershed a cohesive system for study and management (Winter, 2001). On the other hand, watersheds are demarcated by drainage divides, rendering them relatively independent of one another, which makes the responsibilities and efficacy of managers in different watersheds clear (Heathcote, 2009).

To provide scientific support for watershed management, models are essential tools. Existing watershed models usually emphasize on the hydrologic and nutrient cycling processes, but have limitations in representing the carbon cycling processes which have gained increasing attentions in the context of carbon neutrality goals. The soil carbon modules used in watershed models are mostly outdated (Du et al., 2023), and the processes in inland waters have not been well represented. Moreover, energy balance modules are incomplete compared to mainstream land surface models (Niu et al., 2011). To address these shortcomings, our team developed a model called WISE (Watershed-based Integrated Simulator for Earth-surface), a comprehensive model that simulates multiple processes including hydrology, energy balance, soil erosion, plant growth, nutrient cycling, and carbon cycling. The WISE model can not only be applied to traditional fields like water resource planning and water quality control, but also can be used for carbon budget calculation under the impact of climate change and human activities.

Methodology and Results

WISE is currently undergoing active development based on the SEIMS (Spatially Explicit Integrated Modeling System) watershed modeling framework developed by our team (Liu et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2019). A hierarchy of “subbasin-hillslope-subarea” was adopted for the spatial discretization of simulation units, which can represent spatial heterogeneity while reducing unit count. To date, there are already over 60 modules related to hydrology, energy balance, soil erosion, plant growth, nutrient cycling, and carbon cycling processes. The processes in cold regions, like the freeze-thaw, glacier and snow melting, have also been incorporated into the model. The model has been applied to diverse case studies, including riverine DOC simulation in the Krycklan watershed located in northern Sweden, simulation of soil temperature and moisture in a permafrost watershed in the Qilian Mountain, China. To facilitate model construction for users, we have developed a system capable of delineating watershed boundaries and extracting model parameters for any selected watershed worldwide, complemented by a user-friendly web-based interface.

Conclusions

In this study, we developed a model call WISE, a comprehensive model that simulates multiple processes at the watershed scale, including hydrology, energy balance, soil erosion, plant growth, nutrient cycling, and carbon cycling. Compared to traditional watershed model, WISE notably enhances the simulation of carbon cycling and energy balance processes; in comparison to land surface models, WISE employs a spatial discretization method, which can represent spatial heterogeneity and the lateral transport of carbon more accurately.

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Modeling of freshwater and marine systems

Predictive Modelling of Faecal Indicator Bacteria in the River Catchment of Drinking Water Systems

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Summary

In drinking water treatment plants, both anthropogenic actions and heavy rainfall events can result in an increase in the concentration of faecal contaminants in the input water. The incubation of the samples can take up to 3 days, so an early warning system has been developed to predict the concentration of these microorganisms in water. To do so, a gradient boosted decision tree algorithm, *XGBoost* was used. The model confidence was enhanced computing a 90% confidence interval using conformal predictions. Additionally, SHAP values have been calculated to augment the cutting-edge *XGBoost* model, providing enhanced explainability.

Introduction

One crucial aspect of drinking water treatment plants (DWTP) is microbial contamination, monitored by faecal indicator bacteria. Human-induced events, such as faecal compounds run-off or heavy rainfalls, can lead to peak concentrations events of faecal bacteria in DWTP catchment. Sampling this variable is not immediate; it may take up to 3 days from the occurrence of a peak contamination event to the availability of its concentration in water data. Due to this delay, DWTP managers needs an early warning system to estimate bacteria concentration in order to take necessary steps in the treatment systems to ensure a safe water production.

Using online process sensors, chemical sensors and meteorological data, a predictive model can estimate faecal indicator bacteria concentration. In this work, a regression algorithm was built to predict the magnitude order of the concentration of the most used faecal indicator bacteria (*Escherichia coli*) in DWTP.

Methodology and Results

XGBoost regression algorithm (Chen, T., & Guestrin, C., 2016), a state-of-the-art gradient boosted decision tree model, was used to predict *Escherichia coli* concentration in water. To do so, online quality sensors data was used along meteorological data collected from the river basin. A Bayesian optimization algorithm was used to tune and optimize the *XGBoost* hyperparameters. To enhance the control of risks of a potential misprediction, 90% confidence intervals were computed. This was achieved through the application of Conformal Prediction, a statistically robust uncertainty interval predictor model, which allows a more comprehensive assessment of the uncertainty associated with the predictions (Figure 1). Finally, Shapley Additive Explanations values (Figure 2), which are used to explain the output of black-box models, were used to evaluate the relation of predictors with faecal contamination, and specifically, to detect the places where rainfall leads to higher contamination concentrations.

Figure 1. Prediction results and 90% confidence interval of *Escherichia coli*.

Figure 2. Explainability of the variables using SHAP values

Conclusions

The developed algorithm allows to predict the magnitude order of the concentration of faecal indicator bacteria in a surface drinking water catchment. The confidence of this predictive model was enhanced by using a state-of-the-art gradient boosting model and including a confidence interval with conformal predictions, which is a statistically robust methodology. Also, the potential of Shapley values allows to identify the variables that may contribute to a high faecal contamination concentration in the river.

Acknowledgements

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Within-Reef Coral Larval Connectivity Modelling Identifies Sources and Sinks of Coral Recruitment in the Great Barrier Reef

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Summary

A biophysical model was used to estimate coral larval connectivity within the Moore Reef Cluster, northern Great Barrier Reef. To achieve stability in the connectivity estimates, about 400 particles need to be released at each reef site within the cluster during a spawning night. The model was shown to be highly sensitive to the dimension of velocities and assumptions about larval mortality rates and settling chances. The model results identify sources and sinks of larval recruitment and highlight the influence of different environmental conditions on larval connectivity.

Introduction

The Great Barrier Reef (GBR) is under pressure from climate change impacts and anthropogenic stressors (Brodie et al., 2012; Hughes et al., 2017). To improve the resilience of the GBR under future environmental changes, models are needed to support decisions and interventions. Ocean currents in the GBR transport marine organisms from one site to another, allowing exchange between populations. Connectivity among sites aids the recovery of populations following disturbances, such as coral bleaching and tropical cyclones (Elmhirst et al., 2009).

Coral larval connectivity is a function of physical connectivity and larval behaviour, and can vary dramatically among years according to the times of larval production and the corresponding variation in environmental conditions, such as local tides, winds and currents. Identification of sites that are consistently important as sources or sinks (i.e., larval receiving sites) within a cluster of reefs across multiple spawning periods is required to guide interventions. Because larval dispersal in the GBR can occur on length scales ranging from metres to hundreds of kilometres and the small size of larvae makes it difficult to physically track their dispersal, biophysical models are used to simulate larval dispersal over years to decades (Figueiredo et al., 2022; Gurdek-Bas et al., 2022). In this study, we assess a biophysical model's sensitivity to the dimension of velocities and biological assumptions, and identify consistent source and sink locations for coral larvae within the Moore Reef cluster over four spawning periods. Furthermore, we highlight the need to consider different environmental conditions when assessing coral larval connectivity in the GBR.

Methodology and Results

We used Ocean-Parcels (Delandmeter and Van Sebille, 2019), a particle tracking simulator, with 2D and 3D velocity outputs from a 200–250 m resolution RECOM (Relocatable Coastal Model <https://research.csiro.au/ereefs/models/models-about/recom/>) (Steven et al., 2019) — nested within a 1 km grid resolution hydrodynamic model of the Great Barrier Reef Marine Park (Steven et al., 2019) (<https://research.csiro.au/ereefs/models/models-about/models-hydrodynamics/>) — to simulate the dispersal and settlement of larvae from broadcast spawning *Acropora* coral in the Moore Reef cluster of reefs following the annual mass-spawning in 2015, 2016 and split-spawning in 2017. Particles were randomly released within 334 spatial polygons representing reef sites within the cluster domain from 8:00pm to 11:00pm during three spawning nights across the spawning years considered. To assess the sensitivity of the model to larval mortality rate, we compare results from model simulations with no mortality, 0.12 d⁻¹ and 0.40 d⁻¹ mortality rates.

Results show that stability in the connectivity estimates is achieved when approximately 400 particles are released at each reef site during a spawning night. 3D velocity simulations showed 19.40 – 68.80% more links and sinks than those of 2D simulations. The connectivity networks for the no-mortality scenario had the highest number of links and strongest connections, whereas the 0.40-daily-mortality-rate scenario had the least number of links and weakest connections.

Model results identify important source and sink locations for coral larvae within the Moore Reef cluster. Some locations were consistently important across different spawning years and environmental conditions, while other locations were only important in some years. Our findings could help identify reef locations with high potential for interventions within reef clusters. For example, source locations could be important for maintaining coral populations and for the dispersal of offspring (e.g., heat adapted) generated by restoration efforts whereas sinks maybe more resilient to local and global stressors

Conclusions

The modelling approach used in this study resolved coral larval connectivity down to the scales at which management actions such as reef restoration are to be applied. Identifying the maximum number of released particles for stable connectivity estimates improved within-reef coral larval connectivity estimates. For more reliable connectivity estimates, there is need for more *in situ* data on larval biology and behaviour in the GBR for improved parameterisation of future biophysical models, which is critical for supporting decisions and intervention plans regarding improving the GBR resilience.

Our findings can inform management of coral reefs through climate change, such as the design of marine protected areas and the deployment of proposed interventions within reef clusters. For example, the wider benefits of interventions (e.g., deployment of heat adapted corals) may be optimised when deployed at locations that are a source of larvae to others within comparable habitats across the reef cluster.

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Improved Understanding of Hypoxia and Macroalgae Growth Using a 3D Water Quality Model

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Summary

Eutrophication has increased in distribution and intensity due to human disturbances on coastal ecosystems. In this study, we expanded upon a previously developed 1D water quality model to include 3D hydrodynamics and an additional phytoplankton species. This increased spatial and ecological complexity allows for the assessment of governing pathways which contribute to issues of hypoxia, water clarity, and seagrass loss. Our model structure includes separate components of nutrient loads via the watershed and wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), freshwater inflow, hydrodynamics, and water quality. This work provides insight for other modelling initiatives which seek to balance model complexity and performance.

Introduction

Estuaries are important aquatic ecosystems due to the ecoservices they provide such as primary production, flood protection, water filtration, and habitat for biodiversity ([Boerema and Merie, 2017](#); [NOAA, 2017](#)). Yet, estuaries have faced an exponential increase in the frequency and intensity of eutrophic events, which have aggravated ecosystem degradation ([Diaz and Rosenberg, 2008](#)). Eutrophication, or the excessive input of nutrients and organic matter which results in increased algae and phytoplankton growth, can further cause harmful algal blooms, loss of seagrass beds, coastal acidification, and hypoxia ([Bricker et al., 1999](#)).

Due to the growing problem of eutrophication, many studies have targeted its governing processes and impacts on water quality. One of the most effective strategies to study this phenomenon is through mechanistic models. Mechanistic models are useful tools to study system wide water quality dynamics due to their ability to link stressor and response variables, track changes over time, and fill spatial and temporal gaps in observed data ([Wool et al., 2020](#)). These models can also assist in the development of management strategies such as the Total Maximum Daily Loads (TMDLs) to reduce anthropogenic loadings and improve water quality ([Borusk et al., 2002](#)). Additionally, many modelling initiatives have identified the importance of governing processes of eutrophication such as macroalgae growth ([Brush and Nixon, 2010](#)), sediment diagenesis ([Zhang et al., 2015](#)), and daily fluctuations in phytoplankton biomass ([Knightes, 2023](#)).

The Pawcatuck River Estuary (PRE; Connecticut/Rhode Island, USA) is a small, shallow estuary that has been heavily impacted by eutrophication and identified as one of the most intensively nitrogen loaded estuaries on the North Atlantic Coast ([Fulweiler and Nixon, 2005](#)). Previously, a 1D water quality model was developed to investigate eutrophication in this system ([Cashel et al., 2024](#)). Our current research has expanded upon that model to include 3D hydrodynamics and increased ecological complexity. The goal of this research is to 1) improve our ability to simulate complex hydrodynamics in the PRE, 2) capture the spatiotemporal dynamics of processes resulting in phytoplankton growth and hypoxia, and 3) improve our understanding of light attenuation and nutrient depletion via macroalgae and its distribution on the PRE. Insights from this work have the potential to improve our representation of small, shallow estuaries via water quality models and support local management efforts to encourage seagrass recovery in the system.

Methodology and Results

The 3D, PRE model was constructed using multiple modeling components and calibrated with a variety of observed data. The model framework integrates a watershed model (Hydrological Simulation Program –

FORTRAN, HSPF), a hydrodynamic model (Environmental Fluid Dynamics Code, EFDC), and a water quality model (Water Quality and Analysis Simulation Program, WASP). The watershed model provides total freshwater inflow, watershed loads per segment, groundwater infiltration per segment, and the flows and loads from WWTP's. The hydrodynamic model was developed using EFDC Explorer (v11.8) and the curvilinear grid was generated using the CVLGrid grid-generating software. EFDC provides WASP with a 3D spatial framework as well as inputs of freshwater inflow, depth, salinity, and water temperature. WASP (v8.32) was then used to predict water quality by simulating 18 state variables with several internal submodules. The Light module in WASP simulated light intensity/attenuation, the Advanced Eutrophication module simulated phytoplankton, nutrients, and dissolved oxygen (DO) dynamics, the Macroalgae module simulated the processes governing macroalgae, and the Sediment Diagenesis module was used for benthic nutrient fluxes and sediment oxygen demand (SOD). The observed data collected from 2018-2020 were used to calibrate and validate the models. Continuous sonde data were collected on 15-minute intervals for salinity (ppt), water temperature (°C), depth (m), dissolved oxygen concentration (mg/L), and chlorophyll *a* (µg/L). Grab samples were collected on two week intervals for the same parameters as the sondes as well as carbonaceous biological oxygen demand (CBOD, µg/L), ammonium (µg/L), nitrate (µg/L), total nitrogen (µg/L), orthophosphate (µg/L), and total phosphorus (µg/L). Observed data were collected in various locations along the river to assess longitudinal (upstream-downstream), lateral (side-side), and vertical variations.

Results from this study suggest that model design was an effective strategy for simulating zones of hypoxia, light attenuation, and phytoplankton and macroalgae growth. When compared to observed data, the 3D model structure captured longitudinal salinity gradient as well as the freshwater-induced stratification. Simulations also predicted the large range and variability of salinity observed in the upstream waters. The 3D hydrodynamics emphasized the spatiotemporal variation of processes impacting water quality. Simulating stratification enabled us to capture the vertical profile and the observed benthic zone of hypoxia created by SOD. Additionally, the model suggests hypoxia is driven by CBOD decay in the surface waters, with macroalgae respiration driving variability downstream and phytoplankton respiration impacting the mid- and upstream waters. Observed mean phytoplankton trends were also well-simulated with highest concentrations in the mid- and upstream areas and significantly lower concentrations downstream. The increased ecological complexity through adding a second phytoplankton size class predicted seasonal growth dynamics like seasonal blooms and cyanobacteria growth in nitrogen-deprived conditions, but could not recreate the variability of observed continuous data. The simulation of macroalgae within a 3D framework provided insight to the spatial distribution of macroalgae blooms and thus where seagrass may be hindered via nutrient depletion and excessive shading.

Conclusions

In this study, we expanded upon a previously developed 1D, numerical fate and transport model to include 3D hydrodynamics and increased ecological complexity. The goal of this research was to improve our understanding of hypoxia and seagrass loss in the PRE and to assess the benefits and drawbacks of increased model complexity. We found that the simulation of hydrodynamics in this system was significantly improved by the application of a 3D hydrodynamic model. The increased spatial resolution also captured the spatiotemporal dynamics of processes impacting DO such as SOD, CBOD decay, and respiration. The 3D framework also provided greater insight towards the spatial distribution of macroalgae blooms and their limitation of seagrass. This research has practical implications to aid in the development of TMDLs and local management strategies to improve water quality. This work also can improve our understanding and representation of eutrophication in small, shallow estuaries, which are frequently less studied. Future work will assess the impact of nutrient reduction, land use, and climate change scenarios within the PRE.

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Cyanobacterial Harmful Algal Bloom Forecasting With Bayesian Modelling of Large U.S. Lakes and Reservoirs

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Summary

We present a one-week-out forecasting approach predicting the probability of high-risk cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms (cyanoHABs) occurrence. Freshwater cyanoHABs can pose human, animal, and environmental health risks in lakes and reservoirs. No methodology exists to forecast cyanoHABs nationally at weekly (or finer) timeframes.

Introduction

The interagency CyAN effort provides publicly available satellite monitoring for detecting cyanobacteria biomass in the United States, using the Ocean and Land Colour Instrument (OLCI) onboard the Sentinel-3 satellite. The R package INLA (Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation), a hierarchical, Bayesian, spatiotemporal model was used to forecast World Health Organization (WHO) recreation Alert Level 1 exceedance $>12 \mu\text{g/L}$ chlorophyll-a with cyanobacteria dominance for 2192 satellite resolved lakes in the United States.

Methodology and Results

The INLA model was compared against support vector classifier and random forest machine learning models; and Dense Neural Network, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), and Gneural Network (GNU) neural network models. Environmental co-variates (independent variables) were limited to publicly-available, weekly data at the national scale for operational forecasting. Robust predictors included water surface temperature, precipitation, and lake geomorphology. The INLA model outperformed the machine learning and neural network models with prediction accuracy of 90% (with 88% sensitivity, 91% specificity) and 49% precision as demonstrated by training the model with data from 2017 through 2020 and independently assessing predictions with data from the 2021 calendar year.

Conclusions

The forecasting methodology was robust to missing data and unbalanced sampling between waterbodies. We recommend this methodology as operational for forecasting cyanoHAB occurrence in large lakes and reservoirs across the US.

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Disclaimer: this work was reviewed and approved for publication by the USEPA.

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Web Application of an Integrated Simulation System for Standardized Aquatic Environment Assessment

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Summary

Standard procedures for simulating hydrodynamics and aquatic environments in coastal and estuarine areas are currently lacking. Here, the integrated ecological hydrodynamics simulation system of the Port and Airport Research Institute (EcoPARI), including a standard model with guaranteed accuracy and boundary condition datasets, was developed and installed on a user-friendly web server. EcoPARI can be easily operated by beginners based on its graphical user interface and is expected to be utilized as a “standardized system.” The use of this standardized system is expected to contribute to evidence-based policymaking.

Introduction

In coastal engineering, numerical modeling simulations are commonly used to assess the water environment before the development of ports and power plants in coastal and estuarine areas. In particular, the environment of Ise Bay, Japan, has been widely studied and analyzed. Notably, the Port and Airport Research Institute (PARI) developed a simulation model intended for the Ise Bay Restoration Action Plan established by related Japanese ministries, agencies, and local governments (www.cbr.mlit.go.jp/kikaku/sai_ise/koudou.html). The Port and Harbor Bureau of the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport, and Tourism (MLIT) requested the development of a simulator that can be operated by MLIT employees who lack experience in conducting numerical simulations. Studies on the simulation and parameter calibration of water quality have been conducted and valuable results obtained (Hipsey et al., 2020; Nielsen et al., 2021). However, the developed simulators necessitate installation to conduct simulations. Such systems can only be used by researchers and engineers with advanced knowledge and thus cannot be operated by beginners. Therefore, the EcoPARI was developed to serve as a standardized system. This system was designed for installation on a user-friendly web server and can be operated using a Graphical User Interface (GUI) rather than a command user interface.

Methodology and Results

EcoPARI was developed using the following concepts as a benchmark for the standard system: (1) Models that can accurately simulate the (a) hydrodynamics and ecosystems of coastal and estuarine areas and (b) all ecosystem components, from nutrients and lower-order to higher-order organisms, such as fish and bivalves; (2) A system that can create boundary condition datasets, conduct numerical simulations, and visualize results in a web application and allow the user to run the results in a web browser; (3) A system that can create boundary conditions using standard methods; (4) A system that can perform parameter calibration using a fixed algorithm by referring to observed values; (5) Tools and systems that make it convenient for users to perform simulations or develop highly accurate numerical simulations.

In this abstract, we introduce an web application: EcoPARI-WebGUI as explained in (2). The EcoPARI-Web GUI is an end-to-end system that operates from preprocessing to postprocessing and performs all tasks, from preparing the calculation conditions to visualizing the calculation results, using a GUI via a web browser. Preprocessing

involves the use of tools for the selection of bathymetry data and calculation of grid data prepared in advance and for extraction of the period required for simulation execution from pre-prepared boundary condition datasets. The created file follows the model input format of the EcoPARI-Simulator. The EcoPARI-Web GUI allows for operations such as changing the vertical grid settings or selecting certain parameters, as required by the user.

As a postprocessing tool, the EcoPARI-Web GUI can visualize numerical simulation results via a web browser (Fig. 1). Depending on the selection of the user, two-dimensional horizontal x-z and y-z contours of the simulated compartment and current velocity vectors can be drawn. Moreover, numerical values can be extracted and downloaded from any location as text and three-dimensional distributions of dissolved oxygen can be visualized and displayed in an easy-to-understand manner. The EcoPARI-Web GUI can also visualize the reaction speed of ecosystem models and quantify the scalar amount (stock) of the calculated results as well as the reaction rate (flow) in an ecosystem model.

Figure 1. Screenshot of an EcoPARI-Web GUI visualization

Conclusions

In this Abstract, we introduced the EcoPARI system, which can perform numerical simulations from preprocessing to postprocessing. EcoPARI can create boundary condition files, conduct numerical simulations, and visualize the results in a web server environment using a web browser. EcoPARI allows planners and managers to perform simulations, thereby facilitating desk studies and the incorporation of construction-related ideas into planning and management according to Evidence-Based Policy Making.

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Advances and contemporary issues in water quality modelling

Understanding Uncertainties in Water Quality Monitoring to Inform Future Modeling and Monitoring Design

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Summary

This research aims to evaluate and recommend effective strategies for future water quality monitoring to reduce uncertainty in water quality modeling. We present a novel, integrated approach to assess uncertainty propagation in water quality modeling and to improve understanding of the impact of various sources of measurement uncertainty and different sampling scenarios. This is an ongoing study with three key tasks:

- 1) estimating measurement uncertainty in concentration and flow contributed by different sources;
- 2) designing multiple concentration sampling scenarios with different time intervals and durations;
- 3) testing the effects of measurement uncertainties and sampling scenarios on load estimation and water quality modeling.

The project findings will assist management to improve stakeholders' understanding of uncertainties associated with monitored load estimation and the implications for modeled loads.

Introduction

Pollutant loads are crucial indicators of waterway health, particularly for receiving water, and therefore, they offer vital insights for catchment management. However, monitoring pollutant loads can be prone to uncertainties arising from several stages during the monitoring of flow and pollutant concentration. Additionally, these uncertainties can be influenced by different time intervals and durations of concentration monitoring. Understanding the individual magnitudes of these uncertainties, as well as their relative importance, can offer valuable insights into the confidence of load monitoring and water quality modeling that relies on load estimates for model calibration and assessment. This research aims to assess these uncertainties along with different monitoring scenarios, to recommend effective approaches for future water quality monitoring to reduce uncertainty in predicting annual loads from inland catchments flowing into the Great Barrier Reef (GBR) lagoon in Queensland, north-eastern Australia.

Methodology and Results

This research is a collaboration between Australian National University (ANU) and the Queensland Department of Environment, Science and Innovation (DESI). The study presents an integrated approach to assess uncertainty propagation in water quality modeling. We focus on the key pollutants that are impacting the GBR, and which are the focus for DESI monitoring and modelling programs, namely: fine sediments, dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), particulate phosphorus (PP) and particulate nitrogen (PN). The study consists of three key tasks:

1. **Refine the representation of monitoring uncertainty from existing work.** ANU and DESI have previously collaborated on a project which provided initial conservative estimates of measurement uncertainty in estimating annual pollutant loads (Fu et al., 2021), including uncertainties arising from streamflow sampling, concentration sampling at various flow conditions, as well as sample processing and lab analyses. These

estimates are being refined in the current study, based on review of relevant literature and datasets and expert elicitation. A specific focus of this refinement is considering uncertainty in average concentration across the river channel cross-section.

2. **Develop representative future sampling scenarios and generate synthetic monitoring data.** In consultation with DESI, we will design multiple representative and realistic future scenarios for modifying the current monitoring program, to be evaluated in the subsequent tasks. These sampling scenarios will focus on different temporal resolution of monitoring (e.g., continuous sampling, event-based sampling, grab sampling, sampling over varying periods). We have identified two representative study sites within the GBR catchment area which have accumulated multi-year continuous (i.e., high-frequency) sampling of flow and water quality concentrations. These continuous records will be sub-sampled to produce synthetic datasets to represent the different sampling scenarios to be designed.
3. **Understanding uncertainties in load estimation and water quality modeling from different sampling strategies.** The existing continuous concentration data will be used together with the refined sampling uncertainties (from Task 1) and the synthetic datasets representing different sampling scenarios (from Task 2), to develop multiple time-series of pollutant loads which will inform the total uncertainty in load estimation due to measurement uncertainties, and the impact of individual uncertainty sources and different sampling frequencies. The existing GBR eWater Source model (McCloskey et al., 2021a, b) will be recalibrated to the range of pollutant loads time-series constructed above. The uncertainties in the model parameters and annual load predictions will be interpreted to recommend potential sampling strategy to reduce predictive uncertainty.

To date, we have obtained some initial estimates of the ranges of uncertainty from various sources within Task 1. Results suggest substantial uncertainty in cross-sectional concentration which would require collaborative design of further data collection and further analysis of its role in load estimates and decision support. In parallel, the water quality model required for Task 3 is being set up and tested. We are running the GBR Source model via an open-source Python library, OpenWater. Initial investigations suggests that OpenWater is likely offering an improvement in the runtime compared to Source simulation, which will greatly benefit the final task of model calibration to multiple load time-series representing the ranges of sampling uncertainty.

Conclusions

The research is expected to generate new knowledge on the uncertainty in pollutant load estimation for the GBR catchments studied. The integrated approach we employ accounts for multiple sources of uncertainty and assesses their propagation in water quality modeling, to improve understanding of the impact of various sources of measurement uncertainty and different sampling scenarios. As such, this research will provide valuable insights to management on the design of future monitoring programs and the calibration of water quality models.

Acknowledgements

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Stormwater Flooding With Nature-Based Solution Analysis Within an Underrepresented Coastal Mississippi Community

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Summary

This study performs analysis using nature-based solutions (NBS) to reduce flood risks in Moss Point, Mississippi. Rain gardens and permeable pavement were evaluated. Permeable pavement was most effective, reducing total runoff by 12.9% compared to 1.2% for rain gardens. Combining NBS offered the greatest reduction. This research can inform future implementation of NBS to improve flood mitigation and promote a green economy in Moss Point.

Introduction

Flooding is the most common natural disaster experienced by Americans, as well as the most expensive. Though flooding events have a myriad source, the city of Moss Point, Mississippi most commonly experiences flash flooding, storm surge, and fluvial inundation. From community outreach and conversing with citizens, we found that most residents of the city placed a strong emphasis on flash flooding problems above all else. There are several reasons why this is the case, the most harrowing of which are (1) overgrown and unmaintained culverts and ditches, (2) prolonged and heavy rainfall, and (3) easily saturated soils with low porosity. The city has problems in other sectors as well, with an aging population and lack of career opportunities for children and students. Additionally, hurricane Katrina in 2005 completely destroyed decades worth of paper data before much of it was digitized.

NBS, nature-based solutions, seek to connect natural water mitigation techniques with existing grey infrastructure. The EPA's Stormwater Management Model, SWMM, is on the forefront of stormwater flooding technology when considered in tandem with NBS simulations. We utilize both SWMM and CHI's PCSWMM, Personal Computer Stormwater Management Model, in modelling which NBS strategy is most appropriate for Moss Point while also considering community input and impact.

Methodology and Results

Through literature review, we discovered that Moss Point could be a model city for SWMM analysis and NBS implementation, as most studies that take place in rainy cities, such as Seattle, WA, do not have the same constrictions as Moss Point, such as the soil type and degrading grey infrastructure. While Moss Point has problems that cannot be fixed with NBS alone, the installation of these strategies would not only be a unique opportunity to "start again" with rainwater mitigation, but also a boon regarding its economy and the potential continuation of growth.

Before modelling in SWMM, we approached the socioeconomic problems of Moss Point spatially using ESRI's ArcPro. In GIS analysis, we looked at elevation, tree canopy and impervious area coverage, water body distance, key infrastructure distance, park distance, historic rainfall from 2001-2019, and social vulnerability. These maps were assessed separately and in summary using equal-weight raster calculations. We used these maps to communicate with and educate residents during competency meetings and outreach events; many residents shared with us the discrepancy between our results and their lived experience, namely with our "environmental factors" summary map showing low flooding potential for areas that experience very high flooding.

In SWMM, we discovered that permeable pavement is a more robust NBS for this area when analysing peak runoff because it directly treats impervious surfaces while rain gardens collect runoff from nearby impervious surfaces. In simulation, permeable pavement reduced total runoff by 12.9% versus a 1.2% reduction from the rain gardens. Runoff is reduced further when NBS are combined, especially in cases where a water retention NBS is combined with a water redirection NBS. Vegetative swales are being currently investigated as a city-implemented strategy since residents and city officials alike have highlighted the importance of clearing the city's culverts and ditches.

Conclusions

With these results, we are going to move forward with more testing of the Moss Point area and highlight specific neighbourhoods that are good candidates for NBS installation, namely vegetated swales. Thanks to the competency meetings, we had the opportunity to gain insight on the city that cannot be achieved via data alone. This highlights the importance of community engagement and citizen science, even during the modelling, planning, and simulation stages of research. It is also important to note that this is a community that has lost trust in their government leadership and scientific interloping due to repeated negative experiences and a lack of results.

We believe that the impacts of our continued involvement with the city will be greater than just the scope of NBS compatibility. There are several projects on-going in the city, including living shorelines and other NBS construction. Additionally, we are going to be launching several HOBO water logging devices in key locations to further calibrate our model with flooding frequency and severity in the exact areas that we will be modelling.

Future directions for this research will hopefully see the successful implementation of NBS and reduction of floodwaters in Moss Point neighbourhoods, as well as encouraging city leadership in the direction of green economy and proactive engagement with residents. We also hope that this work and involvement will help city leadership make decisions on their underground piping infrastructure, including the remapping and restoration of large portions of it.

Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the city of Moss Point and its residents for participating in community outreach and engagement while we set out to understand the nuance of its flooding issues and how to mitigate them. We would also like to acknowledge CHI for granting our lab several educational subscriptions to their PCSWMM tech.

Managing and Reducing Uncertainty for Tackling Grand Challenge Issues With Focus on Water Quality Modeling

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Summary

We propose the foundations of a framework and methods that can be used to guide decision choices and further investment in the modeling cycle for tackling grand challenge problems, with illustration for water quality issues. We focus on those choices that are fundamentally technical, albeit still benefiting from a social process. Our framework and methods are instrumental for considering what further information and data need to be collected, what processes and errors need to be modeled better, what range of modeling performance measures to adopt, and in particular what methods of uncertainty assessment to invoke.

Introduction

Modeling is a fundamental underpinning tool to help understand and deal with earth's grand challenge (GC) problems, the example considered here being protection of the quality of the globe's freshwater surface resources. But there are huge uncertainties to be managed in the modeling (design, computational implementation and evaluation) cycle for such socio-environmental problems (Elsawah et al., 2020), including water quality (Fu et al., 2020). Choices made in the modeling decision cycle matter. These relate to the plethora of value-laden assumptions that must be made about future forcing conditions and representation of the underlying system, constrained by the amount and quality of data available to build and evaluate the modeling. Managing uncertainty means recognising the assumptions in our models and the imperfections in our data, documenting them for transparency, assessing their effects as far as practicable on outcomes relative to alternatives, and identifying uncertainties most relevant to decision making, then working towards reducing such uncertainties. Some uncertainties will be irreducible and must be embraced to grasp their effects on outcomes of interest. For the reducible uncertainties, a vital gap of immense global importance in dealing timely with these GC problems is the need for strategies and methods to help decide where and how to invest computational and financial resources to reduce, or at least elucidate, the critical uncertainties that will aid understanding, planning and decision making.

Methodology and Results

We begin with an examination of the modeling cycle (e.g. Badham et al., 2019) and a catalogue of its sources of uncertainty. We argue the foundations of a modeling framework for managing uncertainty in GC problems based on a set of five stages (or principles), each of which may be revisited. We then proceed to articulate the concept of Optimal Experimental Design for reducing uncertainty against cost.

The stages in our framework for managing uncertainty can be summarized as follows.

- Stage 1: Recognise decision points in the modeling cycle and potential sources of uncertainty.
- Stage 2: Exploit a fitness-for-purpose paradigm that considers the concepts of reliability, usefulness and feasibility (Hamilton et al., 2022) as a way of clarifying objectives including quantities of decision interest, constraints, system boundaries, resources available, team composition, and other possible factors in the planning and design stages.

- Stage 3: Characterize remaining choices, which are largely technical in nature, being around data representation, model features, model assumptions and simplifications, scale, the modeling and computational approach, and methods for testing and evaluating the model(s).
- Stage 4: Analyse effects of choices on quantities of interest to prioritize crucial ones and appreciate model uncertainties and limitations.
- Stage 5. Identify investment choices around new information and data on reducing decision-relevant uncertainties and quantify effects on uncertainty and budget required.

Details around the stages are elucidated for water quality modeling. In regard to uncertainty quantification, both existing and new methods are considered, so as to: (a) facilitate more effective and computationally efficient sampling of inputs and parameter space; and (b) design monitoring networks, and other options like the use of qualitative data, for reducing uncertainty. Choices with respect to the communication of modeling results and the types of visualization are crucial considerations addressed to maximize the usefulness and value of the modeling process. Modeling projects are usually best achieved by collaborating with relevant stakeholders throughout the process and stages above. Here careful management may be needed to ensure appropriate equity across stakeholder groups. Above all, a successful environmental modeling project will embrace iteration in the modeling cycle where choices or decision forks can be revisited throughout the process.

Conclusions

Development of an effective strategic approach and methods for modeling GC problems should accelerate progress for assessing and dealing with them. It will require and lead to more cooperation and subsequent progress across scientific communities. We have aimed to lay out some foundations for such an approach. The case of water quality modeling is used to illustrate the approach. Recommendations include use of small-scale simulation modeling (physical domain size, lower mesh resolution, etc.) for global GC issues so as to reduce computational cost and enable more extensive exploration of issues, model decision space and uncertainties, especially in Stage 3 of the framework.

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New Conceptual Semi-Distributed Rainfall-Runoff Model With Improved Water Quality Transport at the Catchment Scale

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Summary

In this study, we propose a new conceptual catchment scale rainfall-runoff and water quality model. The developed model is successfully applied and validated based on real rainfall and observation data from a large watershed—Nakdong River in South Korea. In addition, we show that our model can represent closely the conservative tracer—Chloride-- transport in the widely known experimental watershed, Plynlimon, Wales.

Introduction

Predicting and modelling the nutrients and pollutants load from watersheds is essential to facilitate the effective water quality management of reservoirs and rivers. Even though widely used semi-distributed watershed runoff and water quality models such as HSPF, SWAT, and SWMM have been developing for several decades, their basic assumptions have not changed, including the i) well-mixed storages as computational elements, ii) lack of spatial transport model in a catchment, and iii) kinematic wave routing of overland flow and river channels. As a result, these models show inevitable limitations in representing complicated pollutant transport phenomena such as i) time lag between the input pollutant loading and runoff, ii) water storage age difference in runoff layers, iii) and reactions at the soil-water interface through subsurface and groundwater. In this study, we propose a new conceptual approach to enhance these limitations and develop a semi-distributed rainfall-runoff and water quality model.

Methodology and Results

A novel conceptual approach is proposed and implemented based on the Saint-Venant and advection-diffusion equation for the different runoff paths in a catchment. In our model, the land surface is divided into pervious and impervious. The maximum depth of interception and approximated Penman method for evaporation are applied. Each catchment's runoff paths are separated by the surface (overland flow), subsurface (interflow), and groundwater (base flow), and the flow separation into these layers is accomplished by the Green-Ampt equation. Then, we apply those inflows into three artificial runoff layers--horizontally wide and long-- for flow routing. As a result, each runoff layer has user-defined internal elements to simulate the hydraulics and pollutant transport. They also have water storages represented by an artificial weir at the catchment outlet. This unique conceptual structure of our model enables us to not only reproduce complex runoff processes but also represent realistic pollutant transport phenomena through the runoff layers in a catchment scale. The outflows from catchments are used as inputs for river network model—PipeDream-WQ. We validate the rainfall runoff model using the observation data from a large watershed in Korea. In addition, we provide the Chloride transport simulation results reproducing the observation data at the Plynlimon research catchment, Wales.

Figure 1. Conceptual diagram of the new semi-distributed rainfall-runoff and water quality model

To validate the rainfall-runoff model, new model is implemented to the Nakdong basin in South Korea. This basin consists of 138 subcatchments (average area of 114.8 km²) and a river network model for flow routing and pollutant transport between the subcatchments. We apply the Thiessen averaged rainfall for each subcatchment based on 30 rainfall stations. The flow rate observation data is collected at the downstream points of eight representative tributaries. After the calibration using the 2020-2022 year dataset, our model shows satisfactory (> 0.5) to good (> 0.7) performance in metrics of the NSE (0.605-0.844) and KGE (0.634-0.849) at all considered tributaries. According to the validation results using the 2023 dataset, our model shows similar performances of NSE 0.344-0.845 and KGE 0.464-0.831.

Figure 2. Rainfall runoff model calibration and validation results for eight representative tributaries

To validate the water quality transport model, we apply the model in an experimental watershed at Lower Hafren in the Plynlimon research catchment, Wales. The result shows that our model can represent the Chloride concentration time series closely based on the daily measurement dataset.

Figure 3. Model implementation for Chloride modeling at the Lower Hafren, Plynlimon catchment, Wales

Conclusions

We expect the proposed model will be an effective tool for water managers to enhance the pollutant transport prediction and watershed management plan for large watersheds. For future research, we will incorporate more complicated pollutant transport and reaction dynamics for nitrogen, phosphorus, and organic carbon through runoff paths to go forward to a comprehensive semi-distributed watershed water quality modeling tool.

Acknowledgements

The Plynlimon dataset is opened to public at [Plynlimon research catchment hydrochemistry - data.gov.uk](https://data.gov.uk)

Roof Rainwater Quality Monitoring System Using Low-Cost Sensor Technologies and Arduino Software: A proof-of-concept

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Summary

Deploying rainwater harvesting (RWH) hardware, existing low-cost sensor technologies, and open-source Internet of Thing (IoT) software, we present a methodology for creating an innovative proof-of-concept of RWH water quality monitoring system for sensing and recording the three basic parameters: electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), and water depth (mm) of roof RWH.

Introduction

Globally, rainwater harvesting (RWH) has been creatively used to address water supply needs for various non-potable and domestic potable purposes in the face of climate change and water supply reliability. Previously, we investigated comprehensive human health and environmental implications of RWH using life cycle assessment, life cycle cost assessment, eco-efficiency and sustainability assessment tools (e.g., Ghimire et al., 2019; Ghimire et al., 2014; Ghimire et al., 2017). However, tracing of physical, chemical, or biological contaminants present in RWH was beyond the scope of these studies. An online monitoring system of sensors is critical for monitoring such RWH quality parameters and supporting improved risk-based treatment guidance development.

This study aims to develop a methodology for creating a roof RWH water quality monitoring system called Sensing-Recording-Grading (SRG) system comprising of rainwater collection infrastructures, low-cost sensors hardware and publicly available [Arduino](#) (an open-source electronics platform of hardware and software) that can be implemented for additional field demonstrations.

Methodology and Results

The proof-of-concept of the SRG system is accomplished in three steps: (1) site selection, (2) prioritization of the contaminant of concern, and (3) identification of available sensors and instrumentation of the SRG system. The prototype is built near a federal building of the US EPA ORD located in Athens, Georgia. We prioritized three core contaminants of concern (electrical conductivity, temperature, and water depth) reviewing the globally issued guidelines, which included the World Health Organization (WHO) guideline report and the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) reports (USEPA, 2009, 2016, 2018; WHO, 2022). We used low-cost, commercially-available sensors for sensing and collecting electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), and water depth (mm) data with temporal frequency of 15 minutes (Figure 1). The SRG system is comprised of hardware and the Internet of Thing (IoT) software components: rain barrel, piping, the [Hydros 21 Gen 2](#) (Hydros 21)- electrical Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth (CTD) sensors, a Mayfly Data Logger for controlling/communicating the CTD sensors, publicly available [Arduino](#) (an open-source electronics platform of hardware and software) to program the data logger, and smart mobile and web application for sensor data retrieval (Meter, 2023; SWRC, 2024). Mayfly Data Logger is programmed to record data every 15 - minutes to the microSD card and the data are reported to a website (i.e., [MonitorMyWatershed.org](#)) through cellular service. These data are downloaded for review and analysis. Preliminary results show the potential of RWH quality monitoring using low cost sensors (Figure 2). However, additional field demonstration efforts and data validation are necessary to verify the long-term deployment of the low-cost sensors.

Conclusions

Utilizing the open-source software and hardware of Arduino, we successfully demonstrated the roof RWH SRG system prototype using an EPA office building. The study is expected to guide future data validation and field demonstration efforts that may include monitoring additional RWH quality parameters including dissolved oxygen, turbidity, and surrogate parameters of microbial pathogens (e.g., *E. coli*) associated with feces of birds, mammals, and reptile and metals (e.g., arsenic, lead) associated with the roof materials and piping of the RWH systems.

Figure 1. An overall view of the Roof-RWH SRG system. Photograph was taken January 2024.

Figure 2. An overall view of CTD data in [MonitorMyWatershed.org](https://www.monitormywatershed.org). Screenshot was taken April 2024. (R-RWH = Roof-RWH).

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**Stream C. Computational methods,
workflows, informatics and integrated
systems in environmental modelling**

Ninth Session on Data Mining as a Tool for Environmental Scientists (DMTES- 2024)

A Formal Model of Metadata Design as a Source for Digital Surveys

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Summary

This work provides a tool that allows a stakeholder to define the contents of a questionnaire through a simple form and this is automatically generating both a digital questionnaire (in this case in Google forms) and its corresponding metadata file, according to the formal metadata model described in (Angerri et al 2023) and specially designed to be suitable to guide automatic intelligent data analysis of survey data. This opens the door to make the survey construction easier to stakeholders and concentrate the interactions between stakeholders and analysts in the analytical process.

Introduction

Metadata is the description of a dataset, data about data as said in (Michener, 2005) and (Bargmeyer & Gillman, 2000). In the process of Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD) (Fayyad, Piatetsky-Shapiro, & Smyth, 1996) the role of Metadata is crucial during the entire process, from the very early steps (understanding the problem) where the relevant data is researched and its corresponding metadata built and further used to determine which kind of analysis will be suitable, until the last step (knowledge production) where Metadata helps to the interpretation of the results and to provide added semantical value to the data mining results.

Some projects need to obtain data from citizens, especially when there is no systemic data available, or the available data is not updated or in disrupting situations like a war or pandemics where nobody has historical relevant data yet (Gibert & Angerri, 2021). In this situations building a digital questionnaire to obtain this data helps.

The authors have formalized a metadata model in previous papers (Angerri & Gibert, 2023) (Angerri, Vázquez, & Gibert, 2024) to guide an automatic intelligent data analysis in KDD processes, containing several information used in preprocessing and reporting steps. This model has already been used in several projects described in (Angerri, Vázquez, & Gibert, 2024)

Once evidenced the usefulness of this formal metadata model, the work (Angerri, Vázquez, & Gibert, 2024) introduces a software that automatizes the metadata file generation with two forms that are fulfilled by the stakeholder and contain all the required information about the variables, like the type of variable, the possible values etc, which becomes crucial because the following steps of an intelligent data analysis depend on these characteristics, among others. For example, the Metadata file includes the name of the variables or the entire text of the questions in the questionnaire as well as the modalities of qualitative variables together with their shortnames for getting readability in the graphical representations and other outcomes of the data mining process. In the previous work, once this information is introduced in the forms, the metadata file is automatically generated and it can be further used guide the intelligent data analysis.

In this paper we propose one step forward that is to create the digital questionnaire itself automatically based on the Metadata file.

Methodology and Results

In (Angerri, Vázquez, & Gibert, 2024) the automatic construction of the metadata file is presented and consolidated as a new tool. This invites to think that the metadata file can become the main source to create a survey.

So, the main contribution of this work is the development of a new methodology and the corresponding implementation to generate an online digital questionnaire based on the metadata file information, which takes into account all the variable types, even those new complex types of variables presented in (Gibert & Angerri, 2021) that are more expressive, like the Temporal Basic Variables or the Temporal Qualitative Qualified.

The implementation has been done in Python by using an API connection with Google Forms application. With this tool, the stakeholder is able to fulfil the metadata file information in a form and with a click he simultaneously obtains a metadata file in cvs and the corresponding online survey in Google Forms. The metadata file will be further available to be used in the analytics steps, once the survey has been closed and all answers from the target population collected. This has the great advantage that the stakeholders have only to concentrate their energies in designing the contents of the questionnaire and answering few questions to transfer to the system the questions and possible answers and without technical skills the entire questionnaire and metadatafile can be obtained and suddenly launched.

Conclusions

This contribution generates the opportunity to create faster an online google form surveys and their associated metadata, both automatically generated with the contents of the questionnaire given by the stakeholder in an very easy form. On the other hand, this new methodology saves a lot of time to the data scientist who does not need to manually create the metadata file and also saves the digitalization of the survey in a Google Forms questionnaire, and at the same time empowers the stakeholder (who is not necessarily an expert on data) to create a form and decide at the same time the short labels of the main information. Also, some meetings between the stakeholder and the data scientist will be saved in the creation of the metadata and this gives much space to concentrate the meetings along the analytical part of the process where the expert provides interpretation of intermediate results and helps in some analytical decisions along the KDD process. This novelty also avoids possible discrepancies between the metadata file and the survey, as they are built both from the main source.

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Spatial-Temporal Proposal to Extract Knowledge of Disruptive Events That Occurred in Water Distribution Systems

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Summary

This work proposes a spatial-temporal methodology to extract information from disruptive events that occur in water distribution systems and evaluate the contributions of assumable/estimable parameters in the events. To do this, a database from a small water distribution network in Spain is used. The data is processed and a certain degree of uncertainty is incorporated into the analysis. The results of this proposal showed the feasibility of estimating the contributions of the evaluated parameters to the recorded events. The results are promising in terms of obtaining a prediction system that increase the system resilience by avoiding avoidable disruptive events.

Introduction

Water distribution networks (WDNs) provide an essential service for the development of communities. These systems must face different challenges that affect their proper functioning and must be prepared to face these (Karamouz et al., 2022). Preventable disruptive events (e.g., water leaks) can cause situations that can negatively impact the system (Koop & van Leeuwen, 2017). The lessons learned from the events that occurred in the system can provide useful information to prevent not only events of the same characteristics but also to face new challenges (Savić, 2022). In this sense, this work proposes a methodology to extract knowledge from the lessons learned with the inclusion of a certain level of uncertainty in the information. This aims to increase both the learning capacity (Lawson et al., 2022) and increase the resilience of the system while reducing the occurrence of preventable events.

Methodology and Results

1) Incident Hub. The information analysed in this paper corresponds to data from a WDN incident Hub recorded during a period between July 2021 to Jan 2024 (30 months). The information was analysed by quarter. During the evaluated period, a total of 110 incidents associated with water leaks were obtained out of a total of 135 records. The remaining 25 incidents correspond to maintenance activities, additional scheduled consumption and others. According to the expert opinion (categorical information), 49 of the 110 incidents are associated with pressure inference as the main cause of the leak. The remaining 61 incidents are associated with settlement, fissure/crack, tree roots, age/corrosion, pipe defects, exposed components, and wheter conditions.

2) Measurable/estimable parameters. An EPANET hydraulic model was used to both obtain the spatial location (information provided by the operator) and the pressures in all nodes for an arbitrary day (estimable data every 30 minutes). Comparing the simulated pressures obtained with the hydraulic model with respect to the expected pressure at the recorded leak points (expert opinion), similar trends are observed that allows pressure clustering. A total of 10 arbitrary clusters covered the range of observed pressures are proposed. For each node, the most frequent pressure cluster during the day ($P1$: pressure-based cluster) and the percentage of time spent in that cluster ($P2$: percentage of time spent) were determined. **3) Previous lessons.** The number of times that the same component was affected by a leak event in the evaluation period will be called frequency of occurrence (FO). Homogeneous matrices of size $m \times n$ were obtained for $P1$, $P2$ and FO using MATLAB's griddata function.

4) Migration. In order to introduce a certain level of uncertainty into the data, this work uses (Ayala-Cabrera et al., 2022): $M_{i,j} = ((\sum_{k=1}^{k=4} D_{cell_k}) + D_{i,j})$. with M as the matrix resulting from the migration process, D as the matrices $P1$, $P2$ or FO (with or without variants), it should be mentioned that D is updated with each iteration

with the value of D from the previous iteration. $cell = \{(i + 1, j), (i, j - 1), (i, j + 1), (i - 1, j)\}$, $k = \{1, \dots, 4\}$, $i = \{1, \dots, n\}$ and $j = \{1, \dots, m\}$. Three approaches for M were explored (1) *to-max* (specific contribution of the evaluated parameter), (2) *to-min* (specific contribution of the environment of the evaluated parameter) and (3) *to-both* (combination of both *to-max* and *to-min* approaches).

In this paper only the results of the *to-max* approach are presented for both learned lessons (in this case FO) and assumed/estimable parameters (in this case $P1$). Figure 1a-e presents the matrices of the previous lessons for FO in some specific quarters (50 iterations; iter). Figure 1f, presents the correlations among FO and $P1$ under different levels of uncertainty (i.e. increase in the number of iters). Figure 1g presents the accumulated percentage per quarter evaluated for a total of 49 events associated with pressure as a cause (expert opinion).

Figure 1. (a-e) FO for quarters Q1, Q3, Q5, Q7, Q10 (*to-max* 50 iter). (f) *to-max* analysis, correlation coefficients for FO and $P1$. (g) Leak events associated with pressure; expert opinion.

Figure 1a-e shows the tendency for leaks to accumulate in specific areas. The relationship between the FO and $P1$ matrices, for the *to-max* approach shows the contribution per quarter of $P1$ in FO (Figure 1f). In turn, this contribution of the evaluated parameter shows great similarity with the events recorded as associated with pressure as the main cause of the leak (expert opinion, Figure 1g). These results indicate that it is viable to obtain a prediction system for leak events, based on the relationships between FO and $P1$ (as one of the potential inputs) for the current condition with a view to obtaining a future FO with a certain level of uncertainty.

Conclusions

This work proposes a spatial-temporal methodology to determine the contribution of potential parameters (or parameter relationships) to leak events recorded in the system (lessons learned). It is proposed to introduce a certain degree of uncertainty through the propagation of information among the cells. The analysis of $P1$ with FO under the *to-max* approach showed that it is feasible to capture the contribution of the evaluated parameters to the recorded events.

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Machine Learning Based Wind Energy Prediction Over Hyderabad, Telangana, India

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Summary

Wind energy emerges as a prominent and sustainable alternative to conventional non-renewable sources, boasting minimal environmental impact. Despite the increasing popularity of wind farms, each encounters a distinct set of challenges, necessitating innovative solutions. To accurately forecast wind power generation and optimize turbine maintenance schedules, cutting-edge methodologies are continuously developed and deployed. This paper focuses on wind power forecasting across a region, leveraging Multi Regression Model (MRM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) algorithms to address industry-specific issues. Through comprehensive case studies integrating meteorological variables such as pressure, soil moisture, temperature, solar radiation, eastward wind (u10), northward wind (v10), and wind speed, the effectiveness of different models is thoroughly evaluated. Ultimately, the study identifies the most accurate model, offering invaluable insights for informed decision-making. Specifically targeting the prediction of hourly wind speeds in Hyderabad, this research facilitates the estimation of Wind Power Density (WPD), crucial for assessing wind energy potential. Demonstrating remarkable accuracy in short-range forecasting, with minimal Mean Absolute Error, low Root Mean Square (RMS) Error, and high Index of Agreement, predictions generated by MR, ANN, and RNN models at a 24-hour lead time are validated. The study's findings provide actionable wind speed and wind electricity generation forecasts, serving as indispensable resources for enterprises, government agencies, and industries invested in harnessing wind energy.

Introduction

Energy serves as a foundational element for both practical and physical activities globally, underscoring the importance of identifying its sources. Categorized into renewable and non-renewable types based on their capacity for replenishment, energy resources are pivotal drivers of societal progress. However, the predominant reliance on non-renewable sources poses imminent challenges, necessitating a transition towards sustainable alternatives. Studies, such as those by Arvesen and Hertwich (2011) and Awan and Khan (2014), highlight the environmental repercussions of fossil fuel-based energy production, emphasizing the urgency of adopting cleaner alternatives like wind energy.

The Global Wind Report 2011 indicates a significant rise in installed wind energy capacity worldwide, signaling a growing interest in clean energy solutions. Despite this, India's clean energy share falls short of its ambitious targets, underlining the need for accelerated efforts to meet future energy demands sustainably. The promotion of renewable energy sources, as evidenced by various studies, including those by Baúaran et al. (2015), Jung et al. (2014), Wang et al. (2011), and Chang (2014), is imperative for addressing environmental concerns and achieving a more sustainable future.

Among renewable sources, wind energy emerges as a leading contender, alongside solar and hydro energies, due to its abundance and environmental friendliness. Wind energy stands out as a pollution-free solution to combat global warming, offering immense potential in reducing greenhouse gas emissions. However, the operation of wind farms presents challenges, notably in accurately predicting electricity generation and scheduling turbine maintenance. Researchers have employed diverse methodologies, including statistical and machine learning approaches, to develop predictive models for wind power generation. The forecasting of wind power generation hinges largely on predicting wind speed, which dictates turbine performance. Various techniques, including artificial neural networks (ANN) and linear regression, have been explored for wind speed

prediction. Despite advancements, forecasting precision remains a challenge, prompting the incorporation of numerous geospatial variables to enhance accuracy.

Methodology and Results

This study aims to predict wind potential using continuous hourly data, including temperature, soil temperature, solar radiation, pressure, u10, v10, and previous hour wind speed. Leveraging machine learning techniques such as ANN, MRM and RNN, the study endeavors to identify the most accurate model for wind speed anticipation. The adaptability of these sophisticated models to changing input data ensures the delivery of precise forecasts, essential for effective wind energy planning and management.

Building upon previous research identifying high wind energy zones in Telangana, this study focuses on Hyderabad, Telangana leveraging ANN, MRM and RNN models. The analysis of ten years of historical data reveals promising results, with the RNN model incorporating previous hour wind speed demonstrating superior performance. Statistical metrics such as RMSE and MAE validate the accuracy of the predictive models, providing valuable insights for wind energy planners and administrators.

Conclusions

In this study underscores the significance of forecasting wind energy potential using advanced machine learning techniques. By harnessing historical data and leveraging ANN, MRM and RNN models, accurate wind speed predictions can be obtained, aiding in effective wind energy planning and management. The findings highlight the potential of machine learning in optimizing renewable energy utilization and reducing reliance on non-renewable sources, thereby contributing to a more sustainable future.

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Tracking Leakage in Water Distribution Networks Using Multi-Agent Systems, Machine Learning, and GPR

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Summary

The work seeks to help enhance the sustainability of water distribution networks (WDNs) through improved asset assessment, using ground-penetrating radar (GPR) as a non-destructive method for inspection and advanced data analysis techniques. It focuses on interpreting GPR images to (early) identify leak evolution and assess asset condition, analysing pipe in laboratory settings. Techniques such as the agent race algorithm and artificial neural networks facilitate feature extraction and object categorisation, aiming to automate leak detection and improve data visualization. Findings indicate enhanced interpretability of GPR images, potentially decreasing reliance on human expertise for leak detection, thus aiding in WDN sustainability.

Introduction

WDNs are critical infrastructures that need to be continuously operated, maintained, and adjusted to address challenges (e.g. water leaks issues) that may compromise their proper functioning and, consequently, their sustainability. For effective management of WDNs (that allows to advance in the sustainability of these infrastructures), affordable information –on the pipe layouts, materials, state of health, water leaks, among others– is needed to establish an effective prioritisation strategy of its assets (Angelis et al, 2023). For inspection purposes with non-destructive methods, GPR has been shown to have advantages over other techniques due it is easy to deploy and can record a wide range of pipe materials, water leaks, and asset deterioration in high resolution (Song et al., 2020). However, due to the complexity of the GPR images, the data interpretation can be a difficult task (Kim et al, 2020). Previous studies conducted by Ayala-Cabrera et al. (2016, 2021) have used pre-processing based on multi-agents combined with artificial neural networks to clean the GPR images, thereby favouring the object recognition in GPR data and advancing beyond the classic hyperbola detection. This work focused on exploring the improvement in interpretability (by using the above mentioned approach) in GPR images for a new dataset obtained for a water leaking from a small diameter plastic pipe with a small flow in a laboratory conditions. For this, manual labelling, multi-agent systems and perceptron neural networks were used to capture the evolution (increasing the volume of water leaked) of water leaking from the pipe with a view to identifying the feasibility of (early) detecting leaks.

Methodology and Results

The study used, to reproduce the leak phenomenon, a 24mm diameter polyethylene pipe buried in a 1m³ wooden tank with pavement sand to obtain GPR images using a 1.5 GHz GPR antenna (with 10 ns range/total samples). Data was recorded in three stages: 1) system without water (no water stage), 2) with a small volume of water leaked (1.47L, initial stage leakage), and 3) after one hour and 39minutes of continuous water flow (ave. volume 34.47L, final stage leakage). For each stage, a total of 14 profiles were taken in X,Y direction (Figure 1s).

The evolution of water was followed through 3 steps. 1) **Raw GPR images**. These images are obtained by emitting electromagnetic waves from a directional antenna, which are then reflected back when they encounter different materials. The reflections, indicated by varying wave amplitudes, form a detailed matrix that captures the interfaces between materials (Ayala-Cabrera & Izquierdo, 2021). 2) **Pre-processing**. The GPR data undergoes normalization by rows and is manually labelled. The method includes a pre-processing step, adopting a game theory-based algorithm called "agent race" from Ayala-Cabrera et al. (2016). This algorithm simplifies the complex image data into distinct groups, improving the detection of features by separating noise, identifying horizontal lines, and distinguishing objects. This process makes it easier to identify the boundaries between different materials (Ayala-Cabrera & Izquierdo, 2021). 3) **Images cleaning**. Consecutively, a perceptron neural

network (pNN) is used for further cleaning of the GPR data. This step is critical for reducing noise and achieving appropriate labeling, thereby producing clearer images for detailed analysis (Ayala-Cabrera et al, 2016). Figure 1, presents the GPR images across three stages each manually labelled (a-i) and cleaning using a pNN (j-r) for the 3 profiles (inset s).

Figure 1. Raw GPR image manually labelled and processed with pNN.

In Figure 1, the contrast between manually labelled and cleaned images illustrates the effectiveness of pNN in pattern recognition for pre-processed GPR images and (early) leakage detection. In Figure 1(b,e) shows the difference in the pattern when water is introduced in the system, which is also successfully identified in Figure 1(k,n); orange boxes. In Figure 1(a,d) it can be observed that there is no difference in the pattern as there is no water in the system, but in the final stage (Figure 1g) there is a change which shows the increase in leakage over time (green boxes on these figures), which is also observed in Figure 1p. Figure 1(f,i) shows the change in increasing level of water leaked in the system. However, in Figure 1(o,r) the increase in leakage is not identified due to the homogeneous density of the surveyed area; purple boxes. Based in the results obtained by using pNN, it can be observed that the prediction was considerably successful.

Conclusions

This study introduces a method combining manual labelling, multi-agent systems, and perceptron neural networks for identifying and extracting groups from GPR images, focusing on detecting water leaks evolution from small pipes and small outflows in a laboratory conditions. This method used effectively cleans the images, retaining essential features in the data. The results show successful detection revealing the water leak progression and reducing noise for further analysis. The research indicates that classifying areas in GPR images to identify WDNs components can lead to semi-autonomous data interpretation, reduce reliance on experts for analysis.

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Development of a Data-Mining Algorithm for Energy Cost Optimization in Water Distribution Systems

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Summary

Water treatment and distribution is one of the most energy consumption processes all over the world. Because of this, it is of great interest to develop a methodology to reduce energy costs in existing water distribution systems. In this work, an algorithm to reduce energy costs associated with the pumping of drinking water is developed, including both quality and supply autonomy criteria. The management proposal generated by this tool resulted in significant economic savings.

Introduction

One of the most energy demanding worldwide is the water distribution of water. According to Griffiths-Sattenspiel (2009), the US uses up to 4% of its total energy consumption in these processes, while Spain uses up to 7% of it (Hardy et al., 2010). In drinking water and wastewater systems, this energy can suppose for 30% to 40% of the municipality's energy costs (Copeland & Carter, 2014). In addition, some nations all over the world have adopted time-variable energy tariffs, which cause daily fluctuations in energy prices. This circumstance has increased the need for implementing management criteria aiming to reduce energy costs (Chang et al., 2018). The aim of this study is to develop a data-mining tool with machine learning algorithms to reduce the energy expenses associated with the pumping of drinking water distribution.

Methodology and Results

Tanks from a drinking water distribution network located in Barcelona (NE Spain) were used as a case study. Pumps, tanks, and pipes are used to distribute water along delivery points. Water supplying of this network has a variable energy price agreement which considers three different energy prices throughout the day, which define three different time slots, with relatively low, medium and high energy prices. The on/off status of the pumps is controlled by the tank's PLCs, which can control the valve opening and closure based on three different setpoints, each one associated with one of the three different energy prices. Also, there are two restrictions defined by the drinking water distribution managers: (1) a minimum volume of water must be stored in the tanks to supply the population for 24 hours in cases of emergency, and (2) a maximum water storage level must not be surpassed in the tanks in order to avoid the formation of high concentrations of disinfection by-products (DBPs).

To reduce energy costs, the developed methodology aimed to increase water pumping in cheap energy time slots and decrease it in the expensive energy time slots. To find the optimal tank maximum and minimum levels, a data-mining algorithm and a machine learning predictive algorithm (Good-Pla et al., 2021) were developed to predict water consumption and DBPs potential formation respectively. These algorithms allowed to find maximum and minimum tank volumes, which are the setpoints associated with low and high energy price times slots.

To find the most optimum setpoint of the medium energy price time slot, a water distribution simulation algorithm using data-mining tools was developed. This simulation used historical demand data along historical tank levels. This allowed to simulate the management proposals and compare them with the current management of the tank and with a case where there is no management, which uses the same setpoint along the different energy prices slots. This simulation allowed to quantify the distribution of pumped water between the different energy price time slots (Figure 1) in every management configuration, and the water tank levels of each proposal (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Comparison of the real tank level with a case of no management and with the optimized management

Conclusions

The developed data-mining tool allowed to generate new management setpoints that reduce energy costs associated with water pumping. This management proposal ensures the supplying of water in energy cases by storing a minimum volume to supply the population for 24 hours. Also, the inclusion of a DBPs predictive algorithm allowed to avoid hydraulic retention times that could generate a potentially dangerous formation DBPs concentration in tanks. Finally, a simulation algorithm allowed to compare and evaluate different management proposals.

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Automatic Recommendation of Process Technologies Enabling Circular Economy

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Summary

Improving industrial supply chains' circularity has major positive effects on the economy and environment. However, manufacturers frequently encounter difficulties in identifying how their by-products can be utilized as inputs in unfamiliar processes. Although existing platforms promote the exchange of surplus resources, automatic recommendations are not applied. By implementing a Recommender System (RecSys) that evaluates the economic, environmental, and social impacts of waste transformations, industrial decision-makers can effectively promote the conversion of wastes into valuable products. Our model, which uses Life Cycle Inventory datasets including process data from various industries, demonstrates its ability to rank alternatives based on attributes through graph-based search queries.

Introduction

Recently, companies have experienced unanticipated fluctuations and increased risk exposure in their supply chains. A traditional linear supply chain model is no longer sustainable because of the finite nature of natural resources and the costly and detrimental impacts of raw material extraction and transformation on the environment. In comparison, a circular model encourages greater collaboration across industries to optimize material utilization. One effective method for recovering value from waste is the remanufacturing of used products (Sivarajah and Ragonga, 2020). However, it is often challenging for manufacturers to identify opportunities for waste utilization outside their industrial sectors. To address this, companies often seek the expertise of consultants, who can facilitate the formation of new industrial symbiosis partnerships. Hence, the use of recommender systems can help users make decisions by providing personalized search results in situations where it is difficult to identify the best option on its own.

The objective of this research is to develop a platform for industrial decision-makers to explore and evaluate potential waste transformations into valuable products. The framework should be adaptable to various industrial sectors and geographical contexts, benefiting decision-makers worldwide. It should consider economic, environmental, and social implications when suggesting appropriate actions.

Methodology and Results

We propose a framework that uses Neo4j as the graph database and search engine for a RecSys system. Our designed graph model is populated with information from industrial process and ecoinvent LCI datasets to augment or simulate company-specific process data. A Cypher import query extract and ingests relevant information from these industrial process datasets to the graph database. The nodes (Activity and Products) and relationships (REQUIRED_BY and PRODUCES) with their attributes are created during the import process in alignment with the graph data model design. After the import process is finished, data cleaning and refactoring queries are executed to prepare the data for graph search algorithms. Finally, search algorithms based on user prompts are implemented, and return the ordered recommendations. The questions our RecSys answers to the user can be framed as graph-based search and optimization problems with varying degrees of complexity.

To demonstrate its capabilities, we introduce several decision-making scenarios translated into Cypher queries with a sample case chosen from relevant literature. One of the most likely exchanges in the North Carolina Exo-Industrial Park, according to Chertow (2000), is acetone.

The visualization query results displayed in Figure 1 are produced using liquid acetone as the source material and straightforward pattern-matching queries, such as “Identify all of the additional input products needed by the activities”.

Figure 1. Activities that use acetone as a source material and their associated output

This graphic shows 294 distinct substances – among them liquid acetone – *required by or produced by* the different activities considered. Specifically, the figure includes 219 PRODUCES relationships and 2101 REQUIRED_BY relationships (many activities produce similar outputs or require similar inputs), demonstrating how communicating and interpreting complex and interconnected data in visualization tools is challenging, and justifying the need for a utility-based RecSys to sort and limit the number of results.

Choosing the most important attribute – which may change depending on the situation – is the simplest method of ranking the results. We propose a few attributes that the decision-maker could consider significant: Material Demand; Profitability Transformation and Waste Production; and Complexity of Transformation. Hence, our RecSys can respond to users queries such as “*What are the activities that use my waste as a resource and produce the least amount of waste in the process?*”.

Table 1. Query: Top 10 least waste-producing activities using acetone as source material

Amount	Unit	Activity ID	Outputs	Inputs	Profit	ISIC Code	Location
1.423	kg	14387	1	7	-0.08	2011	RoW
1.423	kg	8665	1	8	-0.02	2011	RER
0.067	kg	3813	1	15	0.51	2011	GLO
0.1	kg	7033	1	15	-0.55	2021	RER
0.1	kg	10810	1	15	-0.55	2021	RoW
0.05	kg	14525	1	20	0.79	2010	GLO
0.86	kg	3492	2	8	2.15	2011	GLO
0.261	kg	14670	2	8	0.16	2011	RER
0.261	kg	8115	2	8	0.16	2011	RoW
0.033	kg	10538	2	8	-0.09	2013	RoW

As an example, Table 1 displays the RecSys’ response to the users’ query to identify the Top 10 activities using acetone as an input that produce the least number of by-products and use the least number of inputs. Results are ordered by the number of outputs descending, number of inputs descending, then profitability ascending. This demonstrates that the model can provide sorted results based on the most important attributes the user deems for decision-making.

Conclusions

The graph data model implemented in Neo4j allows industrial decision-makers to explore and evaluate potential activities that can turn their by-product into a more valuable product. With well-designed utility functions and queries, the system can provide recommendations considering economic, environmental and social impacts of their decisions. The field of industrial symbiosis is complex, and there are numerous ways to enhance the model presented in this research. The data model proposed is flexible enough to be expanded and connected with OntoCAPE Ontology in the future. Using the ontology could be helpful for recommending material substitutions in a process or as an alternative starting point for graph search algorithms. Migrating from Neo4J to Python would also be a huge improvement due to Neo4j’s limitations being a commercial product. Python, a free and open-source software characterized for its flexibility, versatility and extensive libraries, will also allow the model’s ongoing improvement through data science and artificial intelligence.

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Design and Implementation of an Intelligent Sustainability Decision Support System (ISDSS) to Achieve Zero Deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon Rainforest

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Summary

Despite being home to a rich biodiversity and vital freshwater sources, the Amazon has lost a staggering equivalent to 20% of its original forest cover. The study develops an intelligent sustainability decision support system (ISDSS) using a causal loop diagram (CLD) model to analyse deforestation factors (2004–2022) and propose government actions. It aids in understanding deforestation dynamics and suggests priority actions to meet Brazil's Paris Agreement commitment.

Introduction

Evolved over the past 50 million years, the Amazon rainforest harbours nearly one-third of the planet's biodiversity and produces 20% of the world's freshwater. Historically, Brazil has neglected this natural treasure, leading to significant deforestation driven largely by livestock expansion (Abramovay, 2022). In recent years, the Brazilian Amazon has become emblematic of the complex struggle against deforestation. Despite a significant 84% reduction in deforestation rates between 2004 and 2012, they rebounded dramatically, increasing by 153% in the subsequent decade (INPE, 2023). This fluctuation underscores the influence of various factors, with public policies playing a pivotal role in both exacerbating and mitigating deforestation trends. Recognizing the complexity of the issue, the study aims to develop an ISDSS to help achieve zero deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon by 2030. It seeks to understand the factors influencing deforestation rates from 2004 to 2022 and identify effective actions for the future. The approach involves analysing existing knowledge and modelling deforestation dynamics using the CLD using *Vensim* software.

Methodology and Results

Intelligent decision support systems (IDSS) integrate artificial intelligence techniques with various models to aid decision-making processes. These systems, which were first conceptualised by Clyde W. Holsapple in 1977, have evolved significantly over time. They can be categorised into model-driven IDSS and data-driven IDSS, with model-driven systems relying on qualitative reasoning and other AI models to support decisions (Sánchez-Marrè, 2022).

Many problems, especially those related to dynamic systems, involve variables and relationships that change over time, often influenced by feedback loops. CLDs, introduced by Jay Forrester in the 1960s, provide a visual representation of these feedback mechanisms, helping to understand system behaviour and develop effective strategies (Haraldsson, 2004). CLDs consist of nodes and edges, with nodes representing relevant variables and edges indicating the relationships between them. By analysing CLDs, decision-makers can gain insights into system dynamics and devise strategies to address complex issues.

In this study, the ISDSS was developed to address two key questions: identifying the factors driving deforestation and proposing strategies for achieving zero deforestation. Two CLDs were constructed based on data gathered from a research trip to the Amazon and an extensive literature review.

Figure 1. CLD 1 key factors of deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon 2004–2022

By analysing the models created, the government is proposed to act in two distinct areas. The first focuses on land control and governance, aiming to strengthen policies for territorial management and law enforcement to eliminate impunity and bolster public institutions. The second area targets infrastructure and sustainable economy, emphasising the development of the region's income sources through sustainable practices such as valuing standing forests, ultimately improving the quality of life for local communities.

Conclusions

Addressing sustainability challenges requires a multidisciplinary and holistic approach. Systems thinking and causal loop diagrams are effective tools for mapping sustainability issues such as deforestation and identifying strategic variables needed to shift current trends towards more sustainable land use. Overall, the findings underscore the complexity of deforestation dynamics in the Brazilian Amazon and the need for comprehensive, multi-disciplinary approaches to address sustainability challenges effectively.

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Optimization-based environmental modelling

Equity-Informed Multi-Objective Optimization: Examining the Regional Distribution of Emission Control

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Summary

This study explores the global distribution of emission control using an Equity-Informed Multi-objective Optimization approach. We employ a reformulated Social Welfare Function (SWF) within the JUSTICE Integrated Assessment Model (IAM), incorporating four distributive justice principles and search for adaptive Pareto-optimal policies that balance conflicting ethical perspectives and preferences. We highlight the importance of designing the optimization setup for IAMs used to identify optimal emission control policies. This is because uncovering the design choices that perpetuate inequalities is crucial. We argue that normatively robust adaptive policies are essential for fair and equitable policy design and fostering stakeholder consensus.

Introduction

Climate change is a wicked problem that requires consideration of diverse stakeholder values and interests (Verweij, 2022). However, current climate-economy models, such as Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs), often fail to incorporate these ethical perspectives and have been criticized for perpetuating existing biases and inequalities (Rivadeneira & Carton, 2022). These models typically rely on a single utilitarian objective, neglecting the distribution of wealth and climate impacts across regions and contributing to disagreements in climate negotiations (Budolfson et al., 2021).

To address this issue, we have developed a novel JUSTICE IAM (Biswas et al., 2023), which allows exploration of different modelling assumptions carrying distributional consequences. Our model incorporates four rival framings of distributive justice principles - *Utilitarian, Sufficientarian, Egalitarian, and Prioritarian* - that capture the diverse ethical values of stakeholders in climate negotiations. In addition, we move away from optimizing policies under a single objective and instead disaggregate incommensurate objectives such as years above 2°C, damage costs, and abatement costs.

Methodology and Results

Our methodology combines two decision-making frameworks, Multiobjective Robust Decision-Making (MORDM) and Evolutionary Multiobjective Direct Policy Search (EMODPS), to search for adaptive Pareto-optimal policies. MORDM tests policies against deep uncertainties and aims to find robust, Pareto-optimal emission control policies for each rival framing. This approach also balances the tradeoffs between welfare, temperature rise, damage and abatement costs for the different rival framings.

EMODPS enhances the adaptive capabilities of the chosen Pareto-optimal policies by incorporating feedback from temperature rise and rate of change of temperature. The temperature feedback is mapped to the emission control policy lever using a nonlinear approximating network. EMODPS utilizes the ϵ -NSGA-II Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm (MOEA) to search for adaptive-robust Pareto-optimal policies that reconcile conflicting stakeholder perspectives. The MOEA optimizes the hyperparameters of the nonlinear approximating network in order to generate heterogeneous optimal emission control rate for the different regions in JUSTICE IAM.

Figure 1: (a) Emission control rate distribution under utilitarian SWF and (b) Emission control rate distribution under prioritarian SWF

Figure 1 illustrates the global distribution of emission control rates based on two ethical framings: *Utilitarian* and *Prioritarian*. Only the Pareto-optimal policies that maximize welfare are shown in the figure, which is a common technique in IAMs. In the Utilitarian framing, the mitigation burden is disproportionately placed on economically vulnerable and emerging economies like sub-Saharan Africa and India, while regions like the Gulf countries, North America, and Australia mitigate the least. However, the distribution shifts dramatically when the Prioritarian framing is considered. In this case, the burden shifts to North America, the Gulf countries, and Australia, while sub-Saharan Africa and India carry out lower levels of mitigation.

Conclusions

Our study underscores the significance of normative clarity in enabling stakeholder engagement and formulating scientifically rigorous and socially equitable climate policies. By incorporating ethical pluralism into JUSTICE IAM, we provide a framework that allows the exploration of distributional consequences of different optimization setups. Our findings demonstrate that explicitly considering normative values in the SWFs profoundly impact the distribution of mitigation burdens, particularly between developed and emerging economies. Utilitarian approaches shift the burden to developing nations, while Prioritarian perspectives account for disparities in income and climate damages, assigning the mitigation burdens accordingly. By addressing ethical diversity and disaggregating objectives, our approach facilitates the design of more equitable and effective mitigation policies, as indicated by our examination of the regional distribution of emission control.

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Mixed-Precision for Extreme-Scale Geostatistical Modeling on Heterogeneous Platforms

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Summary

Geostatistics involves predicting quantities from geographically distributed data, using statistical models for emulation rather than simulation, to inform economic and policy decisions. It includes techniques like the evaluation of the Gaussian log likelihood function via maximum log-likelihood estimation (MLE), which handles high-dimensional data through the Cholesky decomposition but faces limitations due to computational intensity. This research addresses these challenges by utilizing mixed precisions on Nvidia GPUs and optimizing precision dynamically with PaRSEC to efficiently handle large geospatial datasets. This approach enhances modeling and prediction capabilities, particularly for environmental data exhibiting varying correlation distances.

Introduction

Geostatistics predicts quantities of interest directly from spatially distributed data, which relies on statistical models and the optimization of these models' parameters and is often termed emulation, as opposed to simulation. Geostatistical methods may utilize data derived from simulations and/or observational data. In contrast, other statistical methods, such as Monte Carlo sampling that involves simulations with a varied range of input parameters, can be significantly more computationally intensive than sampling from a parameterized distribution that is based on a considerably fewer number of simulations. Geostatistics plays a crucial role in making economic and policy decisions, including the determination of safety margins for engineering projects, air quality management, the siting of renewable energy infrastructure, and the forecasting of agricultural outputs or tourism earnings. Additionally, climate and weather forecasting constitute a significant portion of supercomputing tasks, where even minor enhancements can yield substantial benefits. A variety of such codes are migrating to environments that use mixed precision, and this research details one such migration.

A fundamental algorithm in stationary spatial statistics is the Gaussian log likelihood function, which fundamentally relies on a dense covariance matrix. This matrix's dimensions correspond to the number of correlated observations, typically a product of the observation sites and the variables recorded at each site. In the method of maximum log-likelihood estimation (MLE), key operations include the inverse application and determinant computation of this matrix. These operations can be efficiently performed using Cholesky decomposition and triangular solutions, although they require quadratic storage and cubic arithmetic operations with respect to the problem's dimension. Such computational expenses occur within the optimization cycle that adjusts model parameters based on the input data, limiting the use of MLE for high-dimensional challenges. The covariance matrix is characterized as dense, symmetric, and positive definite, with a structure influenced by its physical derivation, which justifies certain approximations. The core software of this initiative, ExaGeoStat (Abdulah et al, 2021), offers controlled approximations for tackling extreme-scale MLE challenges by integrating innovative features in mixed-precision algorithms and programming models, all while leveraging the capabilities of hybrid distributed-shared memory computing with the dynamic runtime system PaRSEC (Bosilca et al, 2013).

Our main focus is to demonstrate the ability to perform modeling and prediction on geospatial datasets using MLE with a novel mixed-precision implementation. With the utilization of low-precision Nvidia GPU Tensor Core support, we advance the adaptive three-precision approach (double-precision (FP64), single-precision (FP32), and half-precision (FP16)) for the Cholesky factorization (Cao et al, 2022) on the covariance matrix. In particular, we embed it directly within a single factorization process, where different blocks of the same covariance matrix

(not different copies of the full matrix) are represented in different precisions. Indeed, environmental characteristics typically exhibit a loss of correlation with distance, i.e., data at two nearby locations are on average more similar than data that is widely spaced. By leveraging these physical insights, PaRSEC can decide at runtime to reduce the precision of the tile elements that represent less correlated data while extracting performance from the underlying hardware accelerators. This enables us to achieve extreme-scale geospatial applications and provides new statistical insights at scales otherwise intractable.

Methodology and Results

Computational Platforms. The study was carried out on two computational platforms equipped with different GPUs. (1) Summit Supercomputer at Oak Ridge National Laboratory: This system utilizes Nvidia V100 GPUs and consists of 4,356 compute nodes. Each node is equipped with two 22-core Power9 CPUs, operating at 3.07 GHz, 256 GB of main memory, and is paired with three NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPUs. (2) Leonardo Supercomputer at CINECA datacenter in Bologna, Italy: This system is based on Nvidia A100 GPUs and includes 3,456 compute nodes. Each node houses one Intel Xeon 8358 CPU with 32 cores running at 2.6 GHz and four Nvidia A100 GPUs.

Performance Results. Our mixed-precision approach has been thoroughly tested on Summit and Leonardo supercomputers, evaluating three main aspects: weak scalability, strong scalability, and the impact of mixed-precision relative to FP32 calculations. In terms of weak scalability, the problem size was incrementally increased with the number of GPUs involved. Our results indicate near-linear scalability on Summit, expanding from 768 to 6144 GPUs, and on Leonardo, from 512 to 2048 GPUs. This demonstrates that our methodology can effectively scale with an increase in computational resources. For strong scalability, we kept the matrix size constant while augmenting the number of GPUs. The findings reveal significant scalability on both Summit, with 6144 GPUs, and Leonardo, with 2048 GPUs, indicating that our approach is capable of efficiently distributing a fixed-size problem across more computing resources to accelerate the processing time. Lastly, we investigated the impact of using mixed-precision on computational performance at 1024 nodes on Summit (i.e., 6144 GPUs) and 512 nodes on Leonardo (i.e., 2048 GPUs). The benchmarks shows that the baseline performance of FP32 reached 65% and 82% of the theoretical peak on Summit and Leonardo, respectively. Moreover, the mixed-precision computations yielded performance enhancements over FP32, achieving speedups of up to 2.5X on Summit and 3.5X on Leonardo when the matrix size increased.

Conclusions

In this study, we advance the mixed-precision methodology that capitalizes on the ability of contemporary GPUs to execute rapid computations at reduced precision. This approach facilitates the development of efficient linear algebra solvers, such as Cholesky factorization, enhancing the performance of a variety of applications. By utilizing dynamic runtime system PaRSEC, our method achieves load balancing across different segments of large-scale matrices and effectively conceals communication delays through compute-intensive algorithms. Although this solution is evaluated within the framework of Geostatistical modeling, it holds promise for a broad spectrum of applications that demand swift processing with dense linear solvers.

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Multi-Group Particle Swarm Optimization

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Summary

This contribution introduces Multi-Group Particle Swarm Optimization (MG-PSO), that integrates the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) method as a “global-best” algorithm with a multiple-objective, multi-group approach to find optimal parameter values to fit targeted simulation outputs with field measurements and observations. PSO is a population-based stochastic approach for solving continuous and discrete optimization problems. The introduced multi-group approach aggregates calibration parameters by processes into separate steps repeated over multiple iterations to improve performance and identification of a global best parameter set. The paper will demonstrate the calibration effectiveness to use parameter and objective function groups targeting specific process outcomes, as shown by improved calibration cost function convergence and less computational time. This MG-PSO implementation is available as a Python library based on the ‘pyswarms’ package and uses CSIP model services in the cloud to perform the full parallel evaluation of PSO particles (parameter sets).

In this paper we will introduce the underlying design approach of MG-PSO, its implementation as a Python library package, and demonstrate the application for two examples. The first application is watershed modeling using a component-based, spatially distributed model which implements water, nutrient, and plant processes as simulation components. We will introduce different spatial calibration scenarios and parameter sets for different Hydrological Response Unit (HRU) aggregation approaches with corresponding calibration configurations. Further details will be provided in a companion paper (Green et al., this issue). Second, we discuss the MG-PSO calibration approaches for simulating soil carbon sequestration targeting various historical cropping system regimes and their respective model parameters, reflecting cultivar advancements for improved nutrient uptake. Finally, we address the computational setup of MG-PSO to effectively carry out such studies and provide calibration performance measures but also reflect on computational aspects, such as calibration objective and cloud deployment scaling dependency. Such insight will enable modelers to apply the most appropriate cloud setup for a given calibration problem and cloud resource costs to expect.

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Exploring the Impact of Robustness Metrics and Optimization Approaches for Decision Support Under Deep Uncertainty

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Summary

Robustness is key in decision-making for environmental systems under future uncertainty. Selecting the appropriate robustness metric is complex due to different risk preferences of stakeholders and the impact of different metrics on robust solutions identified. This study explores how various robustness metrics affect robust solutions obtained through post-optimization analysis and robust optimization (i.e. directly optimize the robustness metrics). A reservoir system in Australia has been used as a case study. The results show that while robust optimization often yields more robust solutions, their practicality depends on the robustness metrics used, highlighting the importance of understanding the impact of these metrics for effective decision support.

Introduction

Decision-making under deep uncertainty requires the identification of robust solutions that perform satisfactorily across a range of plausible future conditions. This can be done by using either post-optimization robustness analysis (PORA) or robust optimization (RO), where robustness metrics are used to evaluate different robust solutions under a range of scenarios. As demonstrated in Figure 1, in PORA, robustness is evaluated after the optimization process. In contrast, in RO, robustness metrics are directly considered during the optimization process.

Figure 1. Flow chart of post-optimization robustness analysis (PORA) and robust optimization (RO)

It has been found in past studies that the use of different robustness metrics can lead to different robust solutions (Giuliani & Castelletti, 2016; McPhail et al., 2018). However, these studies are often based on PORA, while RO has never been considered. Therefore, this study aims to provide a thorough investigation into the impact of different robustness metrics and optimization approaches, and their combined interactions on the robustness of the solutions obtained. This will provide guidelines for the selection of robustness and optimization approaches to assist decision-making under uncertainty.

Methodology and Results

We selected a variety of robustness metrics to represent different risk attitudes from stakeholders, including (1) Best-case (Maximax), which indicates the best system performance across all scenarios; (2) Worst-case (Maximin), which indicates the worst system performance across all scenarios; (3) Hurwicz optimism-pessimism rule, where the weighting of the best and worst system performance is considered; (4) Laplace's principle of insufficient reason, which indicates an average performance across all scenarios; (5) Mean-variance, which shows both average performance and how performance varies across scenarios; (6) Undesirable deviations, which shows the relative performance from the median performance values for scenarios where system performance is worse than the median. We also developed different groups of scenarios to represent deeply uncertain future conditions.

A reservoir system in Australia was selected as the case study. Results show that the interactions of optimization approaches and robustness metrics significantly impact the robustness values of solutions as shown in Figure 2. Interestingly, while robust optimization usually yields more robust solutions, the robustness metric used in the optimization process is more impactful. For example, using Undesirable deviations as robustness metrics can lead to operation policies that release no water, which limits the practicability of robust optimization.

Figure 2. Robustness values of two objectives considered in the case study

Conclusions

This study provides an in-depth analysis of how different robustness metrics impact the robust solutions obtained via two optimization approaches: PORA and RO. This highlights the importance of incorporating a comprehensive understanding of robustness metrics and optimization approaches into decision-making process to adequately prepare for uncertain futures for long-term sustainability.

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Interactively Integrating Decision Making Into Evolutionary Multi-Objective Agricultural Optimization

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Summary

Climate-aware evolutionary multi-objective optimization (EMO) runs too slowly to be of practical use to real-world decision makers. However, using progressively-interactive EMO (PI-EMO) seamlessly incorporates human decision making into the evolutionary process, which increases the rate of convergence of the evolutionary algorithm.

Introduction

Humanity must increase its agricultural output to meet the needs of humanity, which is growing in size and often in affluence. In many parts of the world, industrial agriculture has been able to achieve these goals by boosting agricultural yields. However, these gains are typically at the cost of environmental degradation, particularly in the over extraction of water and over use of synthetic fertilizers. Thankfully, research has demonstrated that using evolutionary multi-objective optimization (EMO) can generate agricultural practices that balance production and environmental objectives. However, the state-of-the-art climate-aware multi-objective agricultural algorithms run too slowly to be used in an online application, which is critical to extending this research to real-world farmers. One solution is to interactively use the decision-making expertise of farmers during optimization to minimize the decision space of agricultural optimization. This study, for the first time, incorporates the method of (PI-EMO) in an agricultural application, and measures its improvements to speed and convergence of results.

In classic EMO algorithms, randomly generated solutions are slowly evolved towards increasingly near- or true-optimal solutions. The results of EMO algorithms, Pareto fronts, are then handed to decision makers who choose among the Pareto optimal solutions for each conflicting objective. This classic approach to EMO may find good results, but it wastes a great deal of computation resources by finding an entire Pareto front. Researchers have thus developed algorithms (e.g., PI-EMO) that incorporate user preference into the algorithm interactively, such that the decision maker provides their preferences interactively throughout the evolutionary process. This way, the EMO can more quickly converge on the solutions which are relevant to the decision maker. In this study, we combine this research on PI-EMO and existing state-of-the-art agricultural optimization. PI-EMO is a perfect fit for agricultural optimization, as the trade-offs between production and environmental objectives are nuanced and idiosyncratic to each individual farmer.

Methodology and Results

In this study, we optimize three objectives: maximizing yield, minimizing irrigation usage, and minimizing nutrient leaching. To optimize these variables, we modify the timing/amount of irrigation applied on a single field of Maize over the course of a season. We also optimize the timing of nitrogen applications in order to minimize leaching and maximize nutrient uptake. The performance of each management practice is simulated by the crop model DSSAT, which is calibrated for the given study site in Cass County Michigan. Optimization is performed by a custom version of NSGA-III with the PI-EMO modified dominance principle, which we'll refer to as PI-NSGA-III. In brief, the decision maker ranks the solutions of the optimization periodically throughout the optimization process. These preferences are then used to modify the principle of domination in NSGA-III, which guides the evolution in the direction of the decision maker's preferences.

To measure the performance of PI-EMO, we also ran the same NSGA-III without the PI-EMO domination principle as a benchmark. Results have showed that PI-NSGA-III is able to find Pareto fronts that either consistently match or exceed the Pareto front of the benchmark run with fewer objective function evaluations.

Conclusions

This body of work humanity one step closer to sustainably intensifying our agricultural input, and to thus feed our growing global population. And most importantly, it places agricultural stakeholders at the heart of optimization by interactively weaving their preferences into algorithm. Without the buy-in and collaboration of farmers, any solution to solving our food crisis will fail to be adopted. And better yet, using these methods leads to better and often quicker solutions to agricultural management problems.

Comparing Robust Optimization Approaches for Addressing Hydrologic Model Uncertainty in Infrastructure Planning: A Green Infrastructure Example

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Summary

Water resources infrastructure planning depends upon hydrologic models to estimate flows and storage for candidate designs. However, such models are calibrated with spatially limited flow data relative to the many model parameters. This may result in several equifinal parameters sets that imply different optimal designs. We present and compare three methods for multi-objective optimization of green infrastructure to account for such parametric uncertainty. We find robust optimization methods provide objective values and decisions that are closer to the true optimum than non-robust methods, demonstrating value to considering hydrologic model uncertainty in water resources system designs.

Introduction

Stormwater infrastructure is an effective tool for combating the negative impacts of urbanization on flooding and pollution. However, the optimal location and size of such infrastructure needed to achieve these benefits depends on the spatial distribution of runoff and pollutant loads throughout the watershed. Unfortunately, limited sensing data prevents full spatiotemporal knowledge of these variables, requiring their estimation through hydrologic models whose parameters are highly uncertain. Yet design approaches that account for this uncertainty are rare. This is concerning, as designing to a single assumed parameter set could lead to significant over or under-investment. At the same time, quantifying parametric uncertainty via Bayesian inference can be computationally expensive, limiting its use in design. This talk explores the question of how best to account for parametric model uncertainty in designing infrastructure investments to balance socio-ecological tradeoffs of urbanization and reforestation.

Methodology and Results

We present and compare two methods for multi-objective optimization of green infrastructure to be robust to hydrological model parametric uncertainty. To evaluate our methods, we set synthetic true values for model parameters, simulate “observed” streamflow under this synthetic truth, and use Bayesian calibration to estimate parametric uncertainty. We then compare results from green infrastructure (GI) optimization experiments that use the: 1) synthetic parameterization, 2) maximum likelihood parameterization, 3) several likely parameterizations and likelihood-weighted objectives, and 4) minimization of the worst-case objective values from likely parameterizations. GI optimizations aim to minimize flooding, low flow intensification, and cost.

Conclusions

In comparing the three optimization approaches, we find the robust methods provide objective values and decisions that are closer to those optimized to the synthetic truth, demonstrating value of considering hydrologic model uncertainty in water resources system designs.

Innovative Ranking Methods for Parameter Size Reduction in Large-Scale Multi-Objective Optimization Problem

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Summary

Technological advancements have more significantly degraded water quality in the 21st century than in any previous era within living memory. Best management practices (BMPs) are highly effective at mitigating pollution in watersheds, but their implementation often encounters obstacles like financial constraints, variable effectiveness, and particular site requirements. This study employs optimization algorithms alongside watershed models to address a substantial optimization issue that includes thousands of variables across four counties in West Virginia. It implements three techniques based on land use patterns. Applying these reduction techniques reduced the number of variables by 97% while preserving the optimization outcomes' accuracy.

Introduction

BMPs effectively enhance water quality, yet scaling them up is challenging due to cost constraints (Dong et al., 2018). Watershed models simulate pollutant loads to evaluate multiple BMP scenarios, and integrating optimization techniques into these models can help identify the most cost-effective and efficient scenario (Yuan et al., 2020). The high computational demand due to the system's complexity is a major obstacle in this integration (Boddiford et al., 2023). This study introduces a novel approach called innovization, initially defined by Deb and Srinivasan in 2006, which leverages insights from optimization results to minimize the search space in subsequent optimizations and reduce the computational time (Chiang et al., 2014). This study aims to determine if dominated or combined land use patterns are practical guides for selecting BMPs during optimization. The objectives of this study are to analyze optimization outcomes to 1) explore various strategies for identifying the highest-performing BMPs, 2) compare the top-ranked BMPs in agricultural versus urban settings, and 3) propose a method for grouping BMPs that could lead to effective solutions.

Methodology and Results

This research combines a watershed model (Chesapeake Assessment Scenario Tool - CAST) with a multi-objective optimization algorithm NSGA III (The Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm III) to lower the cost of implementing BMP and total nitrogen load. Optimization iteratively produces a Pareto front, establishing a foundation for innovization, and facilitating the rapid development of more effective strategies for similar watersheds. To implement innovization, the study identifies the BMPs most frequently selected using a land use ranking method, particularly those most commonly used in urban and agricultural areas of West Virginia. From the optimization results, we suggest three different strategies for ranking BMPs: 1) ranking top BMPs by the area they cover, 2) ranking them according to the highest percentage of their allowable coverage, and 3) ranking them by the cost-effectiveness of nitrogen reduction. Additionally, we analyze the BMPs most frequently implemented across these three ranking strategies in agricultural and urban contexts. Finally, we propose a novel innovization technique that combines individual scores from all three strategies to identify the most effective overall ranking method. This method reduces the number of BMPs by selecting only 7 out of over 200 BMPs during optimization. As a result, the total number of variables (e.g., BMP implementation acreage, load sources, agency type) decreases from 65,260 to 1,960, facilitating faster achievement of optimal Pareto front solutions within a more limited search space. The results show that *Strategy 1*, which ranks BMPs by implementation area, assumes these are the most cost-effective BMPs regarding nitrogen reduction per dollar. This assumption is valid since six out of seven top-ranked BMPs are the same for both *Strategy 1* and

Strategy 3, which ranks based on the cost-effectiveness of nitrogen reduction. *Strategy 2* focuses on BMPs that maximize implementation acreage, hypothesizing that these BMPs are best suited for the area. This is inaccurate. Overall, while the strategies led to different BMP selections, there was a notable similarity between *Strategy 1* and *Strategy 3* rankings (Table 1). The results indicate that using a combined approach with all three strategies effectively ranks BMPs and enhances the overall optimization solutions. Table 1 displays the top seven BMPs ranked using three strategies. Each BMP type is assigned a specific color code. BMPs sharing the same color indicate they are of similar types. If a BMP is unique to one ranking and does not appear in others, it is left uncolored.

Table 1. The top selected BMPs are based on three ranking strategies for the two predominant types of land use

Urban Top-Ranked Counties			Agricultural Top-Ranked Counties		
Strategy 1	Strategy 2	Strategy 3	Strategy 1	Strategy 2	Strategy 3
145 (5,074,566 ac)	67 (99%)	145 (7.66 \$/lb N)	145 (5,994,967 ac)	67 (93%)	145 (9.95\$/lb N)
29 (3,084,111 ac)	10 (97%)	29 (28.94 \$/lb N)	29 (4,248,177 ac)	145 (91%)	29 (35.6 \$/lb N)
142 (1,025,548 ac)	145 (90%)	137 (62.41 \$/lb N)	142 (1,382,050 ac)	137 (88%)	137 (63.73 \$/lb N)
30 (569,065 ac)	3 (76%)	46 (98.14 \$/lb N)	137 (1,087,027 ac)	142 (76%)	142 (95.46 \$/lb N)
48 (519,534 ac)	29 (74%)	142 (121.5 \$/lb N)	48 (526,744 ac)	10 (72%)	48 (172.92 \$/lb N)
137 (338,353 ac)	139 (70%)	48 (127.08 \$/lb N)	139 (225,152 ac)	139 (61%)	139 (190.62 \$/lb N)
139 (151,097 ac)	137 (68%)	139 (147.92 \$/lb N)	67 (25,422 ac)	29 (58%)	49 (205.77 \$/lb N)

3: Soil Conservation and Water Quality Plans; 10: Agricultural Stormwater Management; 29: Off Stream Watering Without Fencing; 30: Precision Intensive Rotational/Prescribed Grazing; 46: Forest Harvesting Practices; 48: Cover Crop Traditional Rye Early Drilled; 49: Cover Crop Traditional Rye Early Other; 67: Barnyard Runoff Control; 137: Nutrient Management N Rate; 139: Nutrient Management N Placement; 142: Nutrient Management N Timing; 145: Nutrient Management Plan High-Risk Lawn.

Conclusions

In summary, the combined strategies suggested under the “Innovization” method reduce the complexity of the optimization search space. This simplification has facilitated the faster attainment of optimal Pareto front solutions. The evaluation of three distinct ranking strategies for BMP selection revealed that *Strategy 1* and *Strategy 3* displayed a high degree of correlation, suggesting a solid validity in their assumptions regarding the efficiency of BMPs. The overall findings indicate that a hybrid approach, integrating all three strategies, could enhance identifying the most effective BMPs.

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Optimizing RNN Architectures for Improved Turbidity Predictions: Exploring the Impact of Fine-Tuning in Hydrological Forecasting

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Summary

This study developed three types of recurrent deep learning models – a recurrent neural network (RNN), gated recurrent unit (GRU), and long short-term memory (LSTM) to improve turbidity predictions. We emphasized the importance of fine-tuning these recurrent architectures leveraging their algorithmic strengths. Our study site, located in the Stony Clove watershed within New York's Catskill River system, used hourly time-series data from multi-radar/multi-sensor (MRMS) and the US Geological Survey (USGS) datasets, spanning from 2015 to 2023. We hypothesized that model-specific tuning would yield better predictive performance over generic parameter settings, spotlighting the distinct advantages of each RNN variant in environmental modeling.

Introduction

Turbidity, a key indicator of water quality, reflects the clarity of water and its suitability for consumption and ecological health. High turbidity levels can hide the presence of harmful pathogens, affect aquatic ecosystems, and degrade the taste and odor of drinking water (Mukundan et al., 2013). For communities that rely on unfiltered drinking water sources, managing turbidity is important for ensuring the safety and reliability of a water supply (McHale and Siemion, 2014), and accurate forecasts of turbidity are needed for efficient management of water supply reservoirs. Previous studies (Chen et al., 2024; Huang et al., 2021; Wu, 2023) have employed RNN-based models for water quality prediction (including turbidity) with promising results. Some studies conducted comparisons using standardized hyperparameter settings or lacked hyperparameter optimizations specific to each model architecture (Pirani et al., 2021). Thus, this research explores the model-specific custom-tuning of hyperparameters for RNN, GRU, and LSTM to optimize their performance based on their inherent characteristics and strengths. We illustrate this approach for a turbidity forecasting application helpful in managing operations at the Ashokan Reservoir, a primary source of drinking water for New York City.

Methodology and Results

Since turbidity is highly correlated to discharge, we chose hydrological and meteorological variables as inputs to our models. We processed and combined hourly MRMS and USGS time-series data, interpolating missing values to address data gaps. Our methodology involved custom-tuning hyperparameters (including learning rates, batch sizes, sequence lengths, model layers, layer units, dropout rates, regularization methods, activation functions, and epochs) of the RNN, GRU, and LSTM model parameters to predict turbidity, from input features, including meteorological variables such as hourly precipitation and radar precipitation accumulation, alongside hydrochemical variables like turbidity and stream discharge from the USGS.

We informed our hyperparameter tuning by analyzing the temporal patterns within the data, using Auto-Correlation Function (ACF) and Cross-Correlation Function (CCF) plots, aiding us in setting the right sequence lengths for each model. Furthermore, algorithm-specific optimizations were applied: the RNN was tuned for immediate hydrological responses, while the LSTM and GRU were fine-tuned to predict complex, longer-term environmental patterns in turbidity data, influenced by stream processes.

Previous works have fortified the importance of optimizing hyperparameters (Raji et al., 2022) and our preliminary findings show that custom-tuned models outperform those configured with generic parameters. The

potential for building software or finely-tuned recurrent models capable of forecasting turbidity with lead times ranging from 12 to 72 hours would be beneficial, especially to reservoir management organizations like NYCDEP.

Conclusions

In this study, we explored customized fine-tuning of RNN, GRU, and LSTM models to improve turbidity prediction accuracy. Our efforts have shown that tailoring each model to its unique strengths enhances predictions, offering valuable insights for environmental modeling and water quality management. This approach aligns with the spirit of iEMSs, contributing thoughtfully to the ongoing conversation about refining environmental modeling practices. While our findings underscore the benefits of fine-tuning models, we recognize this as a step in highlighting the potential within existing methodologies rather than pioneering a novel method.

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Streamflow and turbidity (USGS) data were downloaded from <https://waterdata.usgs.gov/nwis>

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The Role of Spatial Units in Spatial Optimization of Watershed Management Practice Scenarios

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Summary

Spatial units, used for configuring best management practices (BMPs) in the watershed, play a vital role in the spatial optimization of BMP scenarios based on the “watershed system simulation–scenario optimization” framework. Spatial units with different spatial characteristics have distinct abilities to represent the application context of watershed management, which is reflected in defining and resolving the spatial optimization problem. The proper selection or preparation of spatial units should be emphasized based on understanding the application context of watershed management to effectively represent knowledge of watershed management.

Introduction

Precision watershed management requires scientific decision-making support that primarily answers the question of when and where to implement which types of best management practices (BMPs) in the watershed so that near-optimal multi-objectives tradeoffs can be achieved (Qin et al., 2018; Shen et al., 2023). The watershed system simulation-based multi-objective optimization framework (simulation-optimization framework for short), developed over the past two decades, has become the scientific method. The core part of applying this method is defining the appropriate optimization problem based on understanding the application context of watershed management, including optimization objectives, geographic decision variables, and constraint conditions (spatial and nonspatial). The spatial units, used for configuring BMPs in the watershed, play a vital role in defining and resolving the optimization problem, which makes it spatial.

The determination of spatial units depends on various features of the application context, such as the watershed management requirement, watershed geographical characteristics, BMP knowledge, available data and models (Zhu et al., 2019). The spatial characteristics of the spatial unit determine its ability to represent watershed management knowledge and optimization requirements, which is reflected in the definition of geographic decision variables and spatial constraints and affects the problem resolution. For example, the slope position units support the formal representation of BMP spatial relationships that perform as spatial constraints in the optimization problem, which can improve rationality and efficiency (Qin et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2021).

Though the importance of spatial units in spatial optimization of BMP scenarios has been widely recognized, the systematic summary and outlook are still lacking. Here, we systematically summarize the pros and cons of existing spatial units in representing the application context of watershed management. Then, we propose potential issues to be addressed to appropriately select and utilize spatial units in applying the simulation-optimization framework.

Methodology and Results

Firstly, we summarize spatial units used in existing spatial optimization of BMP scenarios, such as subbasin, slope position units, fields, and hydrological response units (HRUs) and their spatial characteristics. Then, we analyze the representations of spatial units in defining and resolving the optimization problem, such as utilizing spatial relationships between spatial units to represent BMP interactions and to determine spatial constraints

used in generating BMP scenarios. Next, we summarize the pros and cons of existing spatial units by matching their abilities and the application context of watershed management. Finally, we propose potential research directions, such as proposing application-context-adaptive spatial units for precision watershed management.

Conclusions

Through a systematic summary and outlook of spatial units in spatial optimization of BMP scenarios, a more flexible method of preparing spatial units for configuring BMPs should be proposed to represent the precise application context of watershed management. This work contributes to scientifically applying the simulation-optimization framework to model actual watershed management problems and provide decision-making support.

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Intelligent modeling methods and easy-to-use systems for environmental problems

Stormwater Digital Twin Enhances Real-Time Water Level Predictions Under Uncertainty

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Summary

This study introduces and evaluates a new stormwater digital twin system that integrates streaming sensor data with an online model to track water depths and discharges in a real-world urban drainage network. This new system addresses model and sensor uncertainties using an extended Kalman filter (EKF) for data assimilation. In our proposed scheme, EKF is used both to reject sensor faults and to fuse trusted sensor measurements into the model, thereby producing accurate stormwater depth and discharge predictions.

Introduction

Cities face increasing stormwater management challenges due to urbanization and climate change. To contend with these issues, water managers are increasingly seeking digital twin models that aid decision-making by predicting water depths and discharges in stormwater systems in real-time. Empowered by wireless sensor data, these models show promise in detecting stormwater hazards like floods and combined sewer overflows, and facilitate real-time control of stormwater infrastructure. Despite their potential, however, significant implementation gaps remain, particularly in data quality assurance and control (QAQC). Integrating raw sensor data into models introduces uncertainties, highlighting the need for robust anomaly detection processes. This study introduces a digital twin system equipped with sensor data anomaly detection using EKF to enhance model accuracy and reduce the impacts of uncertainties on decision-making.

Methodology and Results

1. Stormwater digital twin model

The stormwater digital twin system designed in this study consists of a wireless sensor network, an online hydrologic-hydraulic model, and a data assimilation framework that when paired together track the hydraulic states (depths and flows) within an urban drainage network. We evaluate this system through a real-world testbed consisting of a wireless sensor network (Figure 1, left) and an online model (Figure 1, right) that tracks depths and discharges in the Waller Creek watershed near the University of Texas at Austin campus.

Figure 1. Digital twin sensor deployment (left) and software architecture (right)

1.1 Wireless sensor network

In the Waller Creek watershed, 4 wireless sensor nodes (N1-N4) collect real-time depth data using ultrasonic sensors (Maxbotix MB7384) every 15 minutes. Each node features a Particle Boron microcontroller for data acquisition and cellular telemetry. Our cloud architecture, hosted on an Amazon EC2 server, employs InfluxDB for data storage and retrieval, and produces continuous streamflow predictions via an online stormwater model.

1.2 Online stormwater model

The online stormwater model consists of (i) a hydrologic model, which calculates runoff into the channel network using precipitation data, and (ii) a hydraulic model based on the Saint-Venant equations, which routes surface runoff through the channel and pipe network to estimate water depths. To enable continuous simulation, we modify the SCS-CN infiltration algorithm to allow moisture to leave the soil over time through evaporation or baseflow. The online model is executed continuously every hour using forecasted rainfall data.

1.3 Real-time data assimilation

We develop a data assimilation methodology based on EKF that fuses sensor data into the stormwater model in real-time. Crucially, EKF is used to detect sensor outliers before fusing them into the physical model. This innovation prevents spurious sensor faults from being assimilated, thereby preventing false flood alarms.

2 Model Performance Results

2.1 Improving the Accuracy of Real-time Simulation

The digital twin model enhances the accuracy of water depth predictions in our test watershed, especially at ungauged locations. In Figure 2 (left), model performance is evaluated using the Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE) for both the basic stormwater model (no data assimilation) and digital twin model (with data assimilation) at sensor location 4. The basic model without data assimilation yields KGE values of (a) 0.6830 and (b) 0.6324 when utilizing gauged and forecasted rainfall inputs, respectively. In contrast, the digital twin model outperforms in prediction, achieving a KGE of (c) 0.7920 and (d) 0.7857 for gauged rainfall and forecast data, respectively, through the mitigation of input and parameter uncertainties.

2.2 Anomaly rejection performance

The stormwater digital twin model’s anomaly rejection performance is evaluated by comparing its true and false positive rates with other unsupervised classifiers using AUC values from ROC curves. The digital twin with EKF shows nearly perfect detection of sensor faults compared to other methods. For Sensor 2, which features numerous outliers, AUC values are: EKF (1.00), Zscore (0.60), SRD (0.41), OneclassSVM (0.55), KNN (0.35), and RRCF (0.39). For Sensor 4, focusing on moderate outliers, EKF (0.99) also outperforms other methods. These findings underscore EKF’s superior performance in rejecting sensor anomalies in near real-time.

Figure 2. Model performance evaluation (left) and anomaly rejection performance (right)

Conclusions

This study bridges the gap between concept and implementation for stormwater digital twins by building and evaluating a real-world online model powered by streaming sensor data. This system demonstrates excellent performance in detecting sensor outliers and predicting water levels in our test catchment. Ongoing work seeks to extend this digital twin model by integrating water quality sensor data to help water managers better understand impacts of sediment and nutrient pollution.

Watershed Management Decision Support Methods Based on the Simulation-Optimization Framework

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Summary

Here we present some recently-developed new methods of supporting precise watershed management decision-making based on the “watershed system simulation-scenario optimization” framework, which settle down a series of problems in previous methods of different aspects within the framework. And then we discuss some remaining research issues towards an intelligent watershed management decision support.

Introduction

Scientific decision-making is key to precise watershed management. Currently a “watershed system simulation-scenario optimization” methodological framework (or, the simulation-optimization framework, for short) has been proposed to optimize the spatial distribution of watershed best management practices (the so-called BMP scenario) and recommend the corresponding implementation plans (or roadmaps) under the practical considerations, based on comprehensive watershed system simulation. The simulation-optimization framework has been proved to be valuable for supporting scientific decision-making towards precise watershed management.

However, a series of problems exist in previous methods of different aspects within the framework, such as 1) how to achieve watershed system simulation under a balance between modeling flexibility and simulation efficiency, 2) the BMP configuration unit issue on which (new) unit can effectively incorporate those knowledge on practical watershed management, 3) how to extend the spatial optimization dimension during scenario optimization for more effective optimization results, 4) how to extend the temporal optimization dimension to recommend the effective implementation plans for a BMP scenario under the practical considerations, and 5) how to provide user-friendly participatory watershed planning decision-making functionalities to diverse stakeholders.

Methodology and Results

Here we introduce some recently developed new methods based on the simulation-optimization framework, which settle down above-mentioned problems.

1) A novel watershed process modeling framework was proposed to simulate watershed system efficiently in a manner of balance between modeling flexibility and high-performance computing (Zhu et al., 2019).

2) The slope position was proposed as a new type of BMP configuration units to effectively consider those local, practical knowledge of watershed management, so to achieve more reasonable and practical optimization results (Qin et al., 2018).

3) Meanwhile, a novel method of dynamically adjusting the boundaries of BMP configuration units during scenario optimization was proposed to extend the spatial optimization dimension for more effective optimization results (Zhu et al., 2021).

4) A new spatiotemporal optimization method was proposed to optimize the implementation orders of a BMP scenario under the consideration on both the stepwise investment constraints and the temporal effectiveness of BMPs, so to recommend the practical roadmaps for the interest BMP scenario (Shen et al., 2023a).

5) A user-friendly participatory watershed planning system was designed and prototyped to facilitate collaborative decision-making among diverse stakeholders (Shen et al., 2023b).

Application case in a representative small watershed of the southeastern China was conducted to show the effectiveness and practical value of the new-proposed methods and prototype.

Conclusions

Through addressing method challenges within current simulation-optimization framework, the above-presented researches contribute to scientific decision-making for precision watershed management.

We also summarize several remaining research issues as well as our ideas towards intelligent watershed management decision-making support based on the simulation-optimization framework (Jiang et al., 2019; Qin and Zhu, 2022).

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Utilizing ChatGPT for Enhanced Water Quality Management Through Conversational AI Technology

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Summary

The swift progression of language models has significantly advanced the capabilities of artificial intelligence (AI). This paper presents the AI Hub, which utilizes the advanced capabilities of ChatGPT to manage Water Quality (WQ) issues effectively. It introduces several conversational agents that utilize in conjunction with relevant data to provide essential insights into WQ challenges, thereby equipping communities with the necessary tools for effective WQ management. The performance evaluation of these agents shows an accuracy rate of over 89%, emphasizing the utility of AI in enhancing community engagement in environmental preservation and demonstrating the effectiveness of AI in managing sustainable resources.

Introduction

The imperative to maintain and enhance water quality represents a critical concern within environmental science, directly affecting ecological balance, public health, and the economic vitality of communities. Essential nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus, while vital for the growth of aquatic life, can become detrimental pollutants when their levels exceed natural balances due to human activities such as agriculture and urban development (Rolton et al., 2022). The proliferation of these nutrients can lead to nutrient pollution, a pervasive problem that manifests globally as eutrophication and harmful algal blooms, adversely affecting water bodies ranging from small streams and rivers to vast oceans and lakes. These environmental disturbances not only disrupt aquatic ecosystems but also pose severe health risks to populations and present substantial economic challenges to communities that depend on these water resources (Krajewski et al., 2021; US Geological Survey, 2010). Responding to these challenges, the advent of Large Language Models (LLMs) like ChatGPT offers a transformative approach to water quality management (Sermet and Demir, 2021). These models harness extensive datasets and advanced natural language processing capabilities, enhancing decision-making, public engagement, and educational initiatives in environmental science (Pursnani et al., 2023).

This study leverages the potential of ChatGPT to develop a suite of conversational agents designed to provide current, precise, and accessible information on various aspects of water quality, with a specific focus on combating nitrogen pollution. By integrating scientific evidence with engaging narratives, and creating inclusive educational materials, this initiative aims to establish a platform for sustainable management and proactive community involvement, addressing the pressing challenges posed by nutrient pollution. Through a detailed exploration of the design, functionality, and impact of these conversational agents, the study contributes to the broader discourse on employing AI-driven technologies for environmental conservation and sustainable water management (Gozalo-Brizuela et al., 2023).

Methodology and Results

The project is committed to addressing nitrogen pollution through the combined efforts of community engagement, scientific inquiry, and technological innovation. The AI Hub aims to make complex nitrogen pollution data comprehensible and actionable for all stakeholders. By intertwining human-centered narratives with robust scientific data, the approach not only inspires action but also grounds these actions in sustainable

practices. We have developed multiple conversational agents powered by ChatGPT, each focusing on different aspects of WQ management:

- *Virtual Champion*: Tailors advice using local expertise to provide region-specific information.
- *Nitrogen Expert*: Delivers detailed information on nitrogen pollution to facilitate understanding and action.
- *Local WQ Expert*: Provides localized data and solutions for community-specific WQ challenges.
- *Action Planner*: Aids users in developing actionable strategies for WQ improvement.
- *Data Expert*: Offers statistical insights into WQ, using API endpoints for comprehensive data analysis.

The integration of the ChatGPT model into the system is facilitated through an API service, allowing developers to incorporate its functionalities into various applications. For this project, the ChatGPT API was fine-tuned with specific WQ data and prompts to tailor the agents to the needs of the project. These agents interact with the API to provide real-time, context-aware responses to user inquiries, enhancing the conversational experience. The initial outcomes from the deployment of these agents have been promising. The agents have effectively engaged users, providing them with actionable insights and accurate information tailored to their contexts.

Conclusions

The AI Hub has proven to be an innovative and effective tool for WQ management, providing a novel method for accessing and interpreting WQ data. By employing an LLM, the platform supports interactive and instructive communication, with a user-friendly interface that enhances user experience. The deployment of a Quality Likert Scale for evaluation by domain experts confirms the agents' ability to deliver timely, accurate, and relevant information, demonstrating both rapid response times and high success rates in addressing diverse user inquiries. The study's findings not only validate the effectiveness of conversational agents in environmental applications but also suggest avenues for future enhancements.

Future work includes expanding the scope of these conversational agents to include additional environmental parameters and broader geographic regions. This expansion would enable the platform to serve a more diverse global audience, addressing a wider range of environmental issues. Furthermore, continuous improvements in the model's accuracy and responsiveness through ongoing training and updates are planned to keep pace with the evolving nature of environmental data and technology. These future efforts will focus on enhancing the adaptability and scalability of the AI Hub to meet the growing demands of environmental conservation and education.

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Enable Kilometre-scale E3SM Land Simulation With User-Defined Datasets and kiloCraft

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Summary

There is an urgent need for the development of a kilometre-scale E3SM land model (uELM) for high-fidelity land simulations. This study presents a method for conducting km-scale uELM experiments using user-defined forcing datasets within the E3SM modeling framework. It also introduces a tool, kiloCraft, for generating input data for uELM simulations. The method is tested on various computational platforms and across different areas in North America and the Regional Peatland Simulation in the US and Canada.

Introduction

Earth system models (ESMs) simulate the Earth's physical, chemical, and biological processes, providing crucial data on water availability, temperature extremes, and enhancing our comprehension of the interactions between natural and human systems and the Earth's climate. The Energy Exascale Earth System Model (E3SM) is a fully integrated ESM that employs code optimized for high-performance computers to address Earth system science questions (Golaz et al., 2019). Within the E3SM framework, the E3SM Land Model (ELM) models the exchanges between terrestrial land surfaces and other Earth system components, facilitating our understanding of hydrologic cycles, biogeophysics, and terrestrial ecosystem dynamics.

The advent of cutting-edge datasets and exascale computers has made km-scale, ultra-high-resolution ELM (uELM) simulations feasible (Wang et al., 2022). The ELM code is a data-centric software system comprising half a million lines of code, highly customized datatypes, approximately 2000 global arrays, and over 1000 subroutines. In recent years, significant strides have been made in developing a uELM simulation using Exascale computers for high-precision land simulation at continental and global scales. For instance, a unique computational model and framework for uELM simulation on hybrid architectures in exascale computers have been developed (Wang et al., 2022, Yuan et al., 2023) with several uELM porting strategies within a functional unit test framework (Schwartz et al., 2022).

Nowadays, the generation of kilometer-scale datasets and their integration with the existing E3SM modeling framework remain significant challenges in realizing kilometer-scale ELM simulations. The study outlines a method for conducting km-scale uELM experiments using user-defined forcing datasets within the E3SM modeling framework. It uses a data tool, kiloCraft (Wang et al., 2023), to generate input data for uELM simulations. The method also involves a user-defined namelist and data preparation within the Common Infrastructure Modeling Earth (CIME) for the configuration, creation, executions of uELM simulations across various computational platforms.

Methodology and Results

The study present our method to conduct km-scale uELM with user-defined grid resolution, forcing and surface properties, and area of interests. In our study, the km-scale uELM adopts the same grid used by the atomsheric forcing to elimiate time-consuming spatial interproratlon during the simulaiton. uELM also uses obvervation-data constrained daily and subdaily atomperfic forcing with limited temporal interpolation. The method integrates with CIME and ELM initialization using user-defined namelist, grids, resolution, and name conventions. The study also a data generation tool, called kiloCraft, to generate km-scale ELM simuation input data, which includes domain, forcing, surface properities data. Kilocraft also have several fucntions to support data projection

and transformation among different geographic coordinates (such as GWS84 and Lambert Conformal Conic). It also contains a series of function for data sanity check (such as the heterogeneity of landscape surface and distributions of plant functional types). Our method uses on-the-fly interpolation to generate other low-frequency changed datasets using the default datasets from E3SM input data directory. The uELM simulation case configuration and creation involves a user-defined namelist and user data configuration with the case creation workflow using CIME and soft links.

Computational platforms: The study is conducted on various computational platforms including the Summit supercomputer (No.7 in Top500 list), a baseline linux cluster (2560 cores), a CADES-CCSI HPC cluster(1024 cores), a Nvidia DGX station(64 cores and 4 GPUs), and several PCs.

Case studies: We are conducting uELM simulations across at various of areas inside two domains: North America and the Regional Peatland Simulation in the US and Canada. The North American domain is defined using Lambert Conformal Conic coordinates, adopting a grid solution of 1km by 1km, and encompasses 21.5 million land grid cells. The 35 years of forcing data (3 hourly) occupies approximately 40 TB, while the surface properties dataset requires 3.7 GB of disk space (utilizing netcdf4 with level 5 compression). The regional peatland domain comprises 0.6 million land grid cells, using GWS84 coordinates at a resolution of 1/8 of a degree. The total forcing data consumes 1.1 TB, and the surface properties dataset requires roughly 0.3 GB (utilizing netcdf4 with level 5 compression).

Conclusions

The work presented a method for conducting km-scale ultra-high-resolution ELM (uELM) experiments using user-defined forcing datasets within the E3SM modeling framework. This method, which includes a tool called kiloCraft, allows for the generation of input data for uELM simulations. The study has also demonstrated the feasibility of conducting uELM simulations across various computational platforms and geographical areas. The potential impact of this research is significant, as it enhances our understanding of hydrologic cycles, biogeophysics, and terrestrial ecosystem dynamics at the unprecedented km-scale. Future directions for this research could include evaluating the uELM simulation model and expanding its application to other areas of Earth system science. This aligns with the overall objectives of iEMSs and the conference, which aim to advance the development and application of environmental modelling and software.

Acknowledgements

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Facilitating Environmental Modeling— automated, cloud-based workflows

OCAPI-Flow: A FBP-Inspired, Object- Capability-Based Data-Flow Library and Toolset

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Summary

We present OCAPI-Flow, a library and toolset to build arbitrary loose coupled data-flow applications based on Flow-Based-Programming (FBP) semantics and the object capability protocol Cap'n Proto at the foundation. Our goal is to enable scientists to update or create complex data-flows, e.g. representing distributed large scale simulations, themselves.

Introduction

In today's field of environmental and agricultural science the need for large scale simulations and the use of complex models is constantly increasing. Especially the former needs increasing amounts of computational power resulting in the use of High Performance Computers (HPC) or the widely available cloud services. Combining large scale simulations and complex models for scenario analysis, parameter optimization or multi-ensemble simulations means that scientists quickly run into difficulties and limitations. Using HPCs to allow for large simulations often needs dedicated computer scientists or technicians, which ideally work together closely with scientists to create optimized solutions. Unfortunately, there is a constant shortage of technical personal dedicated to support domain scientists. The natural drive to solve this problem is to create simulation platforms and frameworks utilizing HPC and cloud environments. Due to changing needs of scientists, rapidly evolving hardware and software and a difficult to bridge gradient between one button press solutions and highly specific requirements, it is very hard to develop systems which cover many or all use cases.

Our group, tasked to develop and maintain the simulation infrastructure CASSIS at ZALF, is confronted to deal with limited resources, while enabling scientists to fulfil their scientific endeavours. Our strategy is twofold, giving scientists direct access to our HPC to enable capable individuals to work on their own, while offering others automation software which allows them to run configurable, but ready-made simulation setups. This means that in most cases a computer scientist or technician deploys a setup to our HPC environment, trying to be sufficiently generic, thus enabling future reuse and adaptation. Due to the complexity involved, it is often the case that a similar capable person is needed for larger changes later on.

The work we present here, describes our most recent approach to address that problem and make scientists more independent. We combine ideas described in our 2018 iEMSs presentation about ZeroMQ-based data-flows (Berg-Mohnicke, 2018) with the ones about capability secure simulation infrastructures presented at iEMSs 2020 and 2022 (Berg-Mohnicke, 2020, 2022). Together with appropriate tooling, a data-flow-based approach allows for easier creation, execution and supervision of complex simulation setups. Our goal is to find a fine point of balance, where a small group of computer scientists and technicians is able to support a larger group of domain scientists. This will only be possible if OCAPI-Flow's model of operation is able to match a scientists mental model with as little training as possible, thus empowering them to work independently.

Methodology and Results

OCAPI-Flow is based on two ideas, the Flow-Based-Programming concept (FBP, 2024) and the concept of object capabilities as represented by the Cap'n Proto protocol (CapnProto, 2024). In a FBP data-flow Information Packets (IPs - data) travel through a set of transformation stages called processes. The semantics of FBP demand that each IP is an object with an own identity, thus can only be processed by one process at a time. Each process may receive IPs from upstream processes via input ports and send data (IPs) to downstream processes via output ports. Ports can have additional properties, like being optional or automatic.

What makes OCAPI-Flow different to some of the existing data-flow systems is that processes are connected by small Cap'n Proto programs which represent unidirectional channels. A process can read from or write to a channel only by holding a reference to a remote object representing the channel's read or write capability. The data-flow is initialized by starting all necessary channels and processes. Upon start, a process receives capabilities to its connected input and output channels. This results in the data-flow wiring itself and, once complete, starts running.

All communication within the data-flow happens via Cap'n Proto interfaces (a channel's remote read/write objects). This allows for potential distribution of a data-flow across multiple machines if necessary. Contrary to our earlier approach using ZeroMQ as the communication layer, Cap'n Proto allows us to create a capability secured system, as well as allow the use of remote Cap'n Proto services. This includes transparent forwarding and access of remote objects across system boundaries, as long as communication between objects can be established. Thus, OCAPI-Flow has the potential to create data-flows across institutional infrastructures and because of its capability secure foundation allows for a realistic implementation of the Principle Of Least Authority (POLA), which alleviates the need for centralized authorities.

Conclusions

OCAPI-Flow is still a work in progress. It is designed to integrate into our ongoing efforts to build a capability secured model and simulation infrastructure, which must support many ways of interaction and execution of models and simulation setups. We hope that an increasing part of simulation setups within CASSIS will use OCAPI-Flow and allow for a positive feedback loop where free resources can be put into extending and improving the general OCAPI-Flow system.

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Modelling to Quantify Field-Scale Carbon Dioxide Removal Across Land Resource Regions

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Summary

Through five program cycles over 2.5 years, we quantified net carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e) removal from 4,159 farm fields (132,564 ha.) across 14 Land Resource Regions (LRRs) in the United States using the COMET-Farm version of the DayCent agroecosystem model. Practice change included reduced tillage, cover crops, and reducing nitrogen inputs. Quantification involved modelling practice change netCO₂e and subtracting blended baseline CO₂e modelled through the practice change period. The modelling workflow entailed collecting inputs from retailer network carbon program participants, applying semi-automated data quality checks, provisioning model input files, calibrating the model, running final simulations, quality checking and remediating results, and delivering results to next steps in the program workflow. Lacking sufficient field data for regional validation, except for the last cycle, we calibrated the model for each field to soil organic carbon, crop yield, and nitrous oxide targets. Modelled annual net CO₂e removed with practice change averaged 71.9 grams per square meter per year across 15,694 season years.

Introduction

Private sector agricultural product and service delivery has only recently used agroecosystem models to quantify environmental benefits on cultivated land at scale across large regions. Public interest in agricultural supply chain sustainability and the opportunity to sequester carbon and reduce greenhouse gas emissions has motivated increasing their integration in a credible and efficient workflow. Here we discuss one effort by a large organization to integrate agroecosystem modelling of netCO₂e removal through agricultural practice change into their program workflows.

Methodology and Results

Truterra, the sustainability business of Land O'Lakes, provides a farmer-driven food and agricultural sustainability program through its network to advance and accelerate stewardship on 26,000 fields in 19 states across 14 Land Resource Regions in the United States, partnering with farmers, value chain companies, conservation organizations, and agricultural (ag) retailers. During 2021, the company collaborated with Colorado State University to create a modelling workflow enabling the quantification of carbon dioxide removals (CDRs) through cover crops, lowering tillage intensity, and optimizing nitrogen applications by participating farms. The workflow required methods and capacity to process inputs, provision data, calibrate model parameters, run simulations, quality check results, and process reports on 5,000 fields each crop season. The project also required the modelling platform and methods be extensible to model more fields as the program increased in scope.

The first step in the workflow involved collecting field specific inputs necessary for model simulation, a process made more complex by differences in data management across the ag retailer and supply chain network. The Truterra Sustainability Tool (TST) provided a central node for aggregating and quality checking inputs. Following the crop season as a farm field's data inputs passed quality check, TST generated a JSON request payload and posted with other field requests as a batch to a daily queue for CDR quantification. The JSON payload contained farm field geometry and management events for three baseline season years and 1 to 7 practice change years. Management events included dates, identifiers, and as applicable amounts, for tillage, planting, winter crop, summer crop, fertilizer application, and harvest/termination.

As a further pre-processing step for each daily batch of requests, we applied Python scripts to verify readiness for modelling and group valid requests by LRR and crop mix. For CDR quantification, we chose the COMET-Farm version of the DayCent agroecosystem model (December 2016 executable) accessible as a model web service and followed a modelling approach derived partially from Parton (2015). A data input/output processing web service consumed the JSON request, fetched and as necessary processed location-specific soil, weather, crop history, and model parameter sets into input files required by the model. The service then fed inputs to the DayCent model service which ran the model for each valid soil in the farm field for the practice change and three baseline threads producing a practice change minus blended baseline netCO₂e result. The model service returned these and other results to the input/output service which post-processed to a JSON response containing the output required by the CDR program.

Using a multi-group approach to particle swarm optimization, for four of the five cycles prior to final simulation we calibrated the model for each field using parameter and objective function grouping and a stepwise procedure. Calibration targets included (1) soil organic carbon (SOC) sampled within or nearby the field for the dominant soil component, (2) SOC at breakout cultivation estimated as 1.3x sampled SOC, (3) USDA-NASS county average yields for representative historical crop periods, (4) crop yields in the JSON request, and (5) IPCC Tier 1 calculated N₂O estimates for the baseline period in the JSON request. The fifth cycle used parameter values derived from calibrated parameter distributions from the prior cycles. Calibrated parameters included those determined to be sensitive in the literature, e.g. Necpalova et al. (2015), and our own sensitivity analyses. We designed the calibration approach to produce a reasonably realistic SOC “glide path” from pre-ag carbon pool stabilization through breakout cultivation, bottoming out during the first half of the 1900s, then rebounding with increasing crop cultivar biomass, fertilizers, and gradually reduced tillage to the first baseline year and sampled SOC target.

Crops modelled included corn grain/silage, soybeans, sorghum grain/hay/silage, winter wheat grain/silage/baleage, alfalfa hay/baleage, dry beans, sunflower, cotton, peanuts, canola, sugarbeets, peas, barley, rye, triticale, grass and legume hay/pasture. DayCent-based modelling results removed an average 71.9 grams per square meter netCO₂e with practice change across all fields and season years, with 71.4% season years and 76.6% fields having positive netCO₂e removed, and 95% netCO₂e between -262.4 and 582.3 grams/square meter. Reduced tillage effects often were modest because baseline-condition fields already involved few tillage passes to grow a crop. Cover crop benefit depended on whether cover was seeded early in the fall and kept growing through the spring flush, with late seeding and early termination producing minimal to no netCO₂e gain. Wide variation in nutrient management revealed opportunity to reduce N₂O emission and optimize carbon source production.

Conclusions

Modelling credibility and efficiency requires emphasis on data quality and management through all steps in the workflow. Most steps in the modelling workflow can be automated for relatively high throughput and batch processing. Automated over-night calibration at the field scale proved feasible. Among others, edge cases needing attention include farmed pivot irrigation corners having uncertain soil moisture, dairy feed crops with high manure application rates, and fields with uncertain residual nitrogen. Access to sufficiently consistent field data with adequate coverage across agricultural areas for model calibration and validation cannot come soon enough.

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AQUATOX DOT NET: Using Cloud-Based Data and Models to Link Water Quality and Ecology

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Summary

AQUATOX DOT NET integrates multiple cloud-based and web-based data sources and models to provide a generalized link between land use, water quality, and aquatic ecology. The modeling system integrates spatial data describing the configuration of stream segments, lakes, and reservoirs from NHD Plus V2 (Moore & Dewald, 2016) with flow data from the National Water Model web service (Cosgrove et al., 2024). It also incorporates nutrient, sediment, and organic matter data from the cloud-based HAWQS - a national watershed and water quality model (Yen et al., 2016). These combined data inputs are used to power AQUATOX, an EPA model focused on assessing the effects of nutrients and organic chemicals on the ecology of rivers and lakes (U.S. EPA, 2018). A map-based graphical interface lets the user define a spatial domain within the continental United States and model results are then produced via automated model linkage.

Methodology and Results

Understanding the linkage between land use, water quality, and ecological outcomes remains a high priority for policymakers world wide. However, the provision of driving data for aquatic plant and food web models is generally discontinuous in space and time. When linking models, challenges include limited availability of water quality outputs, and the significant effort required to spatially integrate data and properly convert units. The AQUATOX DOT NET modeling product enables a user to bypass many of these difficulties by providing an off-the-shelf modeling system relevant to the continental United States. Model inputs are derived from web services and cloud-based models and data sets. Because of this, as driving models improve and extend their temporal or spatial domain, updated results will be available to AQUATOX DOT NET without requiring significant software updates.

The modeling process starts with the spatial setup, which is driven by web-based data sets as rendered using Leaflet, an open-source JavaScript library. The user can view NHD Plus stream segments, lakes and reservoirs, and USGS HUC boundaries (Hydrologic Unit Codes defining a watershed) over a variety of base maps. To select a stream network, upstream and downstream segments can be defined for linkage, or the code can also traverse up river and create a relevant network of inflow segments for a defined “pour point.” If there are lakes or reservoirs in the stream network they are included in the model as 0-D segments. A single lake or reservoir may also be selected as the model’s domain.

After the model domain has been selected, two modeling options become available. One option is to exclusively work with the National Water Model for provision of water flows. In this case, point source, non-point source, and boundary condition nutrient and organic matter loadings must be input manually based on local gauges. A second option is to work with a HAWQS/SWAT model linkage, which is incorporated using a new HAWQS REST API capability (release pending). In this case, water flows, sediments, and nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus), water temperatures, chlorophyll a, and dissolved oxygen can be imported after automating an appropriate run of the water quality model. This linkage will provide nutrient and organic matter data as inflow boundary conditions, overland flows, and as point source loadings.

When HAWQS is selected, the modeling system will define the appropriate HAWQS domain, generally limited to the HUC8 drainage basins that are relevant to the model's setup. AQUATOX DOT NET traverses up stream segments to the HUC8 boundaries, defines which upstream basins to simulate, and produces output for basins that are relevant to the rivers and lakes in the model domain. The REST API call is then automatically generated and sent to the HAWQS modeling system, displaying the model run progress to the user. If inflow data are required at HUC8 boundaries, water flows are taken from the National Water Model, and water quality data are provided from existing HAWQS simulations that were run at the HUC8 spatial resolution. Following this, HAWQS model results are disaggregated to provide boundary condition inflow data and overland flow water quality data for each stream segment, lake, or reservoir in the model simulation.

After this setup process, a 2-D AQUATOX model can be executed. Model compartments within these simulations can range from simple (nutrients only) to complex (a fully populated food web with dozens of state variables.) Parallel processing is used to optimize runs when stream segments can be modeled simultaneously. Model outputs can be graphed across all segments or within each individual stream/reservoir segment.

Conclusions

AQUATOX DOT NET creates a framework that uses cloud-based data sources and models to automatically produce spatially and temporally continuous data across the continental U.S. Because of this, as nationwide models and data sources improve, only minimal updates to this system should be required to incorporate these upgrades. Furthermore, as the tool is used in various modeling studies, it should help highlight the strengths and weaknesses of nationwide models and data. This insight can guide enhancements to national models, focusing on those outputs that affect the ecological endpoints most important to decision-makers.

Work has already started to add estuarine segments to this framework. This includes defining estuaries adjacent to stream networks, and defining the linkage between NHD Plus stream segments and those estuaries, so that the impact of freshwater nutrients on estuarine ecology can be modelled.

Acknowledgements

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Facilitating Environmental Model Calibration Using Cloud Enabled Multi-group Particle Swarm Optimization

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Summary

This paper presents the development of an extensible user interface designed to facilitate model calibration using multi-group Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). It operates on cloud platforms or deploys a Minikube cluster locally, providing functionalities to define calibration parameters, perform data analysis, and visualize results. The present design is customized for the Agricultural Ecosystem Services (Ages) watershed model-as-a-service.

Introduction

The spatially-distributed Ages watershed model has been developed to assess and model ecosystem attributes, in particular those impacted by changes in water availability, land use, agricultural management practices, and climate (Ascough et al., 2015). We are developing an extensible user interface to orchestrate parallel cloud computing resources to calibrate the Ages model in less time and with lower cost using a new multi-group Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) technique (David et al., this issue). It will facilitate the application of PSO to be leveraged for Ages and other models supported by the Cloud Services Integration Platform (CSIP) (David, 2016). Ultimately, our goal is to improve accessibility of PSO for model calibration broadly.

Methodology

The application provides an intuitive user interface to calibrate, test, and visualise the results of multi-group PSO calibration. It is a cross-platform application compatible with all major operating systems. To get started, simply install Python and the MG-PSO-GUI Python application (Cordingly, 2024).

The application is comprised of three primary elements, the *Platform*, *Setup*, and *Results* tabs:

Platform Tab

The user interface can orchestrate multi-group PSO calibration on existing deployed infrastructure, either on a cloud platform (such as Amazon Web Services or Google Cloud Platform), or it can automatically deploy a Minikube cluster (Minikube, 2024). It interfaces with backend infrastructure using the Cloud Services Integration Platform (David, 2016). This tab functions as a control center for managing the local Minikube environment or monitoring and verifying the status of external infrastructure.

The interface includes deep integration with Minikube. Minikube clusters can be created, initialised, or destroyed with a single click, offering a simple and easy to use environment for testing. These features enable a cluster to be created locally and for the model calibration process to be defined in the Setup tab before moving the cluster to a cloud service provider. This workflow greatly reduces costs as cloud infrastructure only needs to be utilised when calibration takes place.

Setup Tab

The setup tab provides the functionality needed to define all calibration parameters. This tab consists of two main elements: the Group Editor and the Global Parameter Editor. The Group editor enables users to define the individual groups used in the multi-group PSO calibration, the parameters used, bounds, objective functions, data types, and datasets used. It automatically retrieves default values, suggested limits for bounds, and provides a description of each parameter from the service, enabling the user to make informed decisions for their

hyperparameters. Bounds can have a wide variety of different data types including complex arrays of values, so the Group Editor integrates with spreadsheet applications such as Microsoft Excel to enable easy importing of lists of values. Lastly, the Global Parameter Editor enables configuring various static and calibration parameters that apply to all groups. Every interface in this tab is designed to be extensible for a diverse range of different calibration processes and models.

Results Tab

On any tab, the calibration process can be started from the footer toolbar which includes a variety of controls and progress indicators. Conversely, the Results tab focuses on more detailed visualisation of the calibration process and results. While calibration is running, the Results tab generates figures to show the improvement in model costs and updates in real time. The Results tab has a variety of different options for plotting data including multiple figures, tables, and CSV visualisation. Figures are interactive, and with a single click can be opened inside a web browser to enable further analysis.

Conclusions

This new graphical user interface for multi-group PSO facilitates parallelized calibration of the Ages model-as-a-service using the MG-PSO CSIP services. The back-end methods will be demonstrated and provided to interested users in an iEMSs congress workshop using the graphical interface. New functionality is also in-progress for parameter sampling and sensitivity analysis.

Acknowledgements

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Multiscale Application, Cloud Computing and Parallelized Calibration of a Spatially Explicit Hydrologic Model For Agricultural Systems: *Ages*

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Summary

The *Ages* model (v. 1.0) is a Java-based spatially distributed model which implements agricultural, ecological, hydrologic and water quality simulation components using two coupled environmental modeling frameworks. We applied *Ages* to simulate streamflow and water quality in the Midwest USA where tile drainage affects nitrogen transport. The purpose of this scaling study was to assess the model performance for streamflow at the watershed outlet using four different resolutions of hydrologic response units, numbers and groupings of model parameters, and parallelized calibration approaches running at different widths. For each calibration scheme, we explored runtime metrics and costs of calibration.

Introduction

In this study, we explore the combined scalability of a distributed watershed model and a new implementation of Particle Swarm Optimization. Trade-offs between model resolution, parameter complexity and optimization effort are generally unknown or difficult to quantify. Even so, a standard approach to calibrating the parameters of a complex spatial and temporal model is based on prior experience and perceived intuition about the complexity needed to address the problem at hand. In this case, we started with a very high spatial resolution and asked the following questions concerning simulation of daily streamflow at the outlet of a large watershed:

1. How does coarsening the model resolution (reducing the number of hydrological response units, HRUs) affect model performance?
2. How does the number of the most influential parameters (based on prior model sensitivity analysis) and their groupings in a stepwise calibration scheme affect model performance and parameter values?
3. How does the calibration width (number of particles run in parallel) times the parallelization width of the model itself affect total runtime, clock time, and costs?

Methodology and Results

Ages simulates hydrology, dynamic plant growth, evapotranspiration, partitioning of precipitation between rain and snow, snowmelt, and nitrogen cycling and transport at a daily timestep. *Ages* simulates plant-soil-water-nutrient interactions with dynamic plant development and growth based on the Unified Plant Growth Model (UPGM) and layered soils in each HRU, driven by daily meteorological data, computed snowmelt, and specified land management (e.g., crop rotation). Water and solutes are routed laterally among HRUs and stream reaches based on the landscape topography delineated with *Cadel* (Kipka et al., 2024, this issue). The *Ages* model-as-a-service is parallelized to run on a specified number of computational threads. Likewise, the calibration method, Multi-Group Particle Swarm Optimization or MG-PSO (David et al., 2024, this issue) runs parallel model executions based on the MG-PSO hyperparameters (number of particles).

The South Fork Iowa River Watershed (581 km²) was simulated at field-scale resolution using 3012 HRUs and applications of mineral fertilizer and/or swine manure to estimate daily nitrogen loads. Cropping systems in the SFIR Watershed are typically based on corn (maize) and soybean. This high-resolution model was then scaled up (aggregated) to 300, 30, and 3 HRUs, which were recalibrated using the 4 to 12 of the most sensitive parameters.

Each parameter set was calibrated all together in one “swarm” or in 2 to 4 groups of parameters calibrated sequentially and in multiple rounds (up to 10).

We designed a set of 66 calibration schemes for each of the 4 model resolutions based on the approach above. These were comprised of the combinations of Ages parameters, their groupings, and PSO hyperparameters (particles & iterations) – see Table 1. Over the course of this experiment, different schemes were run on either a local server (managed by Colorado State University) or a proprietary cloud service. Thus, direct comparisons of runtime, clock time, and computational cost are not feasible, but the total number of model runs could be assessed across calibration schemes. As a rule of thumb, the runtime for each Ages execution (or PSO particle) is proportional to the number of HRUs plus a startup time.

Table 1. MG-PSO calibration schemes were applied to each Ages model resolution (3, 30, or 300) and a limited set of selected schemes for the 3012-HRU resolution to date.

Number of Ages parameters	2	4	6	12	Total
Number of parameter groups	1 & 2	1 & 2	1 & 3	1 & 4	
Number of PSO Particles per iteration	10, 20, 40	10, 20, 40	10, 20, 40	10, 20, 40	
Number of PSO Iterations per group	10, 20	10, 20, 40	20, 40, 80	20, 40, 80	
Combined number of calibrations	12	18	18	18	

Results of these calibration experiments show the following. For up to 12 Ages parameters, multiple groups added substantial computational costs (number of model executions) with very little improvement in model performance. The total run time relates to the number of PSO particles (P) times the number of iterations (I). Across all calibrations, the best fit did not improve beyond a total $P \times I = 800$, corresponding to $P=20, I=40$. There is also a trade-off between the number of particles and the number of threads used by Ages. These and other results of our numerical experiments will be discussed.

Conclusions

This multiscale model calibration experiment helps inform future efforts toward parallel computing for calibration of complex and runtime-intensive models for environmental assessment. Additional testing using more than 12 parameters is needed to assess potential benefits of using multiple groups. Currently, Ages is simulating effects of wildfires on hydrologic responses in the western USA. A new subdaily version will provide multi-temporal discretization, and future work will include calibration at multiple temporal scales.

Acknowledgements

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Environmental Model Geo-Spatial Data Representation Using a Cloud Enabled Catchment Delineation Tool (Cadel)

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Summary

Cadel is open source, freely available to the scientific community, and implemented using Catena, an emerging platform based on the Environmental Resource Assessment and Management System (eRAMS2), and Cloud Services Integration Platform (CSIP) frameworks providing scalable geospatial analyses, collaboration, and model service capabilities. Seamless integration of generating spatial model parameters and providing input data is implemented with a strong focus on streamlining the workflow in Catena.

Introduction

Delineating a watershed area into discrete areas (*e.g.* Hydrological Response Units HRUs) with parameter attribute tables is essential to generate input parameter sets for distributed hydrological models. This presentation will introduce a generic methodology of such a delineation process and services workflow for the Agricultural Ecosystems Services (Ages) watershed model.

Here, Digital Elevation Model raster data are processed for the topology of flow paths, then combined with raster layers of land use, soils, and hydrogeology to generate HRU patterns for a watershed area. Based on the pattern of HRUs, the web service analyzes a topological routing scheme that allows multiple-flow directions and interactions between neighboring HRUs. The resulting HRU information is used to automatically generate input files for the Ages distributed watershed model. The tool is providing scalable geospatial analyses, collaboration, and model service capabilities. Seamless integration of (1) generating spatial model parameters, (2) connecting input data, (3) executing the model, and (4) analyzing model results will be presented with a strong focus on the workflow aspect of Catena. The HRU delineation tool can be adapted to any HRU-based hydrologic model.

Methodology

Cadel provides a workflow of up to 8 steps to delineate a watershed and its HRUs (Figure 1). All geospatial operations described here are done by using methods and routines provided by GDAL, also known as GDAL/OGR, is a library of tools used for manipulating geospatial data, GRASS GIS software suite and/or from the Terrain Analysis Using Digital Elevation Models (TauDEM, Tarboton 1997).

The legacy **Step 1** provides a feature, where the user can upload a custom Digital Elevation Model (DEM), with a custom resolution. Current improvements will skip this step for the contiguous United States, with available DEMs provided by the United States Geological Survey (USGS), with resolutions of 1, 3, 10 and meters. Additionally in this step the user has to provide at least one outlet point or geospatial gauging location (point(s) or a line). Also, in this step the user can upload optional raster layers like soils, land-use or land-cover and hydro-geology maps, used for spatially variable groundwater units.

Figure 1. Cadel workflow

Step 4 subdivides the watershed into subcatchments based on the flow accumulation, by applying a user-provided minimal area for the sub-catchment area size. Cadel then generates the resulting stream reach network.

Step 5 overlays raster maps of all user-selected layers. Often used maps to overlay are subcatchments, reclassified DEM, slope and aspect, soils, land-use and hydro-geology maps. The resulting raw HRU layer will contain small areas that need to be further adjusted.

Step 6 generates the final HRU pattern based on the user provided minimum HRU size. This is achieved by dissolving and merging small areas with neighboring HRUs.

Step 7 determines the final HRU pattern with the neighborhood relations between individual HRUs. By using the final pattern overlaid with the flow accumulation raster, Cadel generates surface and subsurface water flow linkages between all HRUs regarding the flow accumulation, and if the HRU is intersected by a stream reach.

Step 8 generates Ages model structure input files that provide all geospatial information. This information is a topology routing schema. These data are essential for a fully distributed hydrological and/or water-quality model.

CSIP services and Graphical interface

Each of the Cadel steps is set up as a CSIP service in Catena. Catena is a framework that is an additional layer on top of the programming experience of eRAMS. Catena is used as a graphical interface, wherein CSIP is used to run the geospatial analysis and computational workload. The Cadel CSIP services are available as server endpoint applications and can be run using JAVA or Python scripts.

Conclusions

The workflow and Cadel delineation results will be presented for mountainous watersheds in Colorado and agriculture dominated watersheds in Colorado, Iowa and Missouri.

Acknowledgements

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Automating Evapotranspiration Forecasts Through the Canopeo App and Serverless Cloud Computing

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Summary

Evapotranspiration (ET) is a major part of the hydrologic cycle, therefore, ET forecasts can play a key role in water management, especially in agriculture. This presentation will describe the development of a proof-of-concept digital framework for short-term ET forecasts for crops. The framework consists of three key components: 1) a mobile app, Canopeo, 2) a mechanistic ET model, and 3) cloud computing services. While still in the prototyping phase, the design should allow anyone with a smart phone to receive an ET forecast for their particular plant in their particular location globally, thus providing critical information for water management decisions.

Introduction

Evapotranspiration (ET) information is critical for climate-smart irrigation practices, but local crop ET forecasts are currently unavailable for most farmers. ET is closely tied to crop water use and a good ET estimate can inform optimum irrigation decisions (Allen et al., 1998). Given its importance, efforts to make ET information available have developed such as OpenET (Melton et al., 2022) and the Forecast Reference ET (FRET) (US Department of Commerce, 2024). These efforts, however, are geographically limited - to the United States (US) for FRET and to the western US for OpenET. Furthermore, the FRET forecasts are not adjusted for crop type or conditions and are thus not well-suited for irrigation management. The OpenET data is only retrospective, with lags of days to weeks also severely limiting its usefulness for irrigation management. A related effort, not limited geographically, is the Canopeo mobile app (Patrignani & Ochsner, 2015), which estimates percent canopy (highly correlated to crop ET) from a top-down crop image taken from a smart phone. Despite the recognized importance of ET information, there is currently no globally available method to generate site-specific crop ET forecasts for irrigation management. Therefore, there is a critical need to research and develop a system that will provide producers worldwide with ET forecasts that are tailored to their crop, expected local weather, and local soil moisture conditions. Without such a tool, farmers will lack needed information to help them manage their water resources in a climate-smart way. This presentation will describe the development of a proof-of-concept digital framework for locally tailored, globally available short-term ET forecasts for crops.

Methodology and Results

The proof-of-concept framework that we are developing for locally tailored, globally available crop ET forecasts is based around three main components (Figure 1): 1) a mobile app, Canopeo, 2) cloud computing services, and 3) a mechanistic ET model.

Figure 1. Overview of Crop ET Forecast Framework

The Canopeo App

The existing Canopeo app was designed to analyze photos taken by users and estimate green canopy cover. This app has thousands of users worldwide. In addition to calculating green canopy cover, the app collects other relevant information including location (lat, long), crop height, and user email address. In our expansion of the Canopeo app, the calculated data and the data collected from the user is passed from the app to the cloud computing infrastructure. This data is used to tailor the ET forecast to the users location and crop.

Cloud Computing Infrastructure

The cloud computing infrastructure is a set of services that handles incoming data from the Canopeo users and communicates the ET forecast. We are using Amazon Web Services (AWS) cloud products. AWS Lambda is the main AWS service we are using. The AWS Lambda function that we have developed performs all of the computational parts of the workflow: parsing the information from the user, fetching the ET forecast for the specific location, adjusting the reference ET forecast to the crop, and sending the forecast to the user. The ET forecast is provided by the free and open-source meteorological service, Open-Meteo (<https://open-meteo.com/>). Because AWS Lambda is a serverless service, the computing is done only on-demand, making the infrastructure extremely cost effective.

ET Mechanistic Model

The reference ET forecast itself is calculated based on the Penman-Monteith equation (Allen et al., 1998). The forecast is further tailored to the farmer's particular crop using an established method informed by the percent canopy cover and the crop height reported by Canopeo (Pereira et al., 2020).

Conclusions

Our ET forecast system, though still in development phases, will combine the Canopeo mobile application and the cloud-computing services. We anticipate that this will allow any user with a smart phone, anywhere in the world, to receive a forecast of ET for their particular plant in their particular location, thus providing critical information for water management decisions.

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Improving Data Acquisition and Automation for VELMA Initialization and Modeling Workflow

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Summary

This research focuses on automation for batch collection of the digital elevation model, climate drivers, and surface runoff across the United States to initialize the Visualizing Ecosystem and Land Management Assessment model (VELMA). Using a gridded digital elevation model for any area of interest, acquisition of a single location or gridded network of weather drivers and stream runoff data were developed. This was accomplished using the US EPA's Hydrologic Micro Services (HMS) Representation State Transfer (REST) application programming interface (API) and the Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (GDAL) with Python. This innovation allows VELMA users to initialize simulations more efficiently.

Introduction

Cultivating stakeholder engagement within the management of complexities involving socio-ecological systems impacts outcomes for best practices, policy design, and interventions through interaction and access to easily understandable models (Asif et al., 2023). The development of a synergistic system that enables dynamic logistics and collection of data assists in increasing precision in analysis and model predictions (Ouyang, et al., 2007). Our group focused on addressing pre- and post-fire wildfire impacts on water quality. While sparse spatial and temporal observed data were limited from prior research conducted in our region, we were tasked with utilizing aggregated modeled data and satellite retrievals to initialize and analyze the environmental and eco-hydrologic conditions which impair water quality post-fire. Previous methodology for initialization of VELMA (Abdelnour et al., 2011) and Land Surface Models (LSMs) requires multiple data retrieval locations and methods for capturing the digital elevation model (DEM), climate drivers, and surface runoff. This takes expertise in resolving the gridded data indices to latitude and longitude coordinates with the use of licensed geospatial software (McKane et al., 2014) and errors can arise due to improperly matched spatial objects limiting retrieval efficiency (Yang et al., 2024). Prior methods for VELMA data aggregate initialization can curate human errors and result in additional time to accurately collect, organize, and implement the simulations. Where limited long-term records exist, adequate identification of the connections across different temporal scales are only possible within watershed boundaries (Golden et al., 2014). This new data collection workflow creates the ability for other researchers to overcome the problem of reproducibility which is a necessity for scientific advancement (Choi et al., 2021).

Methodology and Results

We have created a repository, including a Jupyter Notebook and data outputs, surrounding the GEE/GDAL/HMS/VELMA acquisition workflow integration. This code assists in the formatting and acquisition of data necessary for inputs in VELMA for any location of a given AOI by latitude, longitude, and cell index from the DEM and JPDEM Outlet points for a watershed within a rectangular bounded region. With this code and gridded network translation, we can acquire data from a variety of sources to quickly obtain climate, hydrologic, and terrain data for anyone in the US. Users can obtain random samples of indices or curated lists of locations without extreme computing power and reliance on open-sourced software. Our efforts assist in acquisition of large collections of data for multiple locations within gridded data products without the

understand the coding language. Due to the REST API accessibility, users are able to obtain large amounts of data for multiple locations and large time spans (>20 years).

Conclusions

The GEE/GDAL/HMS/VELMA acquisition workflow within a Jupyter Notebook provides greater efficiency, minimizes model initialization time, reduces manual processing errors, and facilitates reusable science for other modeling studies. We developed a database of usable modeled NLDAS climate and surface records within the mountainous terrain of the Front Range in Colorado translated through GDAL's transformation projected coordinates of grid cell indices, latitude, and longitude through updating the JSON response requests in the HMS REST API. Our workflow allows novice users to explore, customize to their area of interest, automate data acquisition, perform preprocessing, and produce aggregations within VELMA. This advancement will encourage more users to easily deploy VELMA and LSMS, thus accelerating validation of VELMA for implementation as a decision support tool.

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Modelling to evaluate outcomes of environmental watering

Land and Water Use Dynamics in Southern Indus Basin: Implications for Sustainable Groundwater Use and Environmental Flows

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Summary

The Indus Basin Irrigation System (IBIS) is vital for Pakistan's food and water security. Increasing reliance on irrigated agriculture to achieve food security is leading to unsustainable cropping and irrigation practices, which are resulting in mining of fresh groundwater resources and reductions in environmental river flows to the sea. To address this, policymakers need quantified information on irrigation dynamics. This paper showcases the remote sensing methods—MODIS-Landsat blending, CMRSET, and machine learning mapping using the phenologies—to assess land use changes from 2010 to 2020 and their impact on water use at 10-day intervals. Findings underscore the need for tailored water management strategies, including managed aquifer recharge, land use policies, and improved irrigation efficiency, to sustain agricultural productivity in the region and not exacerbate negative impacts on environmental flows.

Introduction

The Indus Basin Irrigated System (IBIS) is the world's largest contiguous irrigation system, supplying controlled irrigation to 16 million hectares across 48 canal commands in Pakistan. It provides food security to 225 million people. Growing groundwater reliance raises sustainability concerns, leading to declining levels in fresh groundwater areas and increasing risk of expansion of saline groundwater pockets into fresh groundwater quality areas. This is particularly the case in the fertile semi-arid region of southern Punjab, where surface water supply shortfalls have increased groundwater use, resulting in deep and rapidly declining groundwater levels.

The aim of this paper is to examine the recent land and water use dynamics in selected canal commands, Sidhna, Lower Mailsi, and Lower Pakpattan, in the south of Punjab province roughly (from north to south) in the middle section of the IBIS to understand the implications of land use and water use for the sustainability of irrigated agriculture in Pakistan. Cropping practices and water use were assessed through the development of remotely sensed timeseries of actual evapotranspiration (ET_a) and seasonal crop maps, at frequencies (10-day for ET_a and seasonal maps, respectively) and spatial resolution (30 m) that are amenable for informing decision and policymaking at the sub-canal command scale.

The specific objectives are to (1) assess the extent and location of main wet summer 'Kharif' (April to September) crops and main dry winter 'Rabi' (October to March) crops; (2) estimate their water use (i.e. actual evapotranspiration, ET_a); and (3) investigate the changes in cropping practices and water supply-use relations.

Methodology and Results

To produce 30 m spatial resolution remote sensing (RS) actual evapotranspiration (ET_a) estimates at 10-day frequencies and seasonal land cover maps (including main crops) from 2010–2020, the following state-of-the-art remote sensing approaches were adopted:

- The ET_a estimates were computed by scaling potential Priestley-Taylor evapotranspiration (E_0) using the vegetation index (VI)-derived scaling coefficient obtained from the CMRSET (CSIRO MODIS ReScaled EvapoTranspiration) Landsat V2.2 model at the Landsat native spatial resolution of 30 m. The 10-day frequency was achieved by taking advantage of the daily frequency VIs from the daily Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), which were subsequently blended with Landsat VIs using a method

capable of detecting gradual (i.e. phenological) or abrupt (e.g. floods) land cover changes. More details are provided in Ahmad et al (2023) and Peña-Arancibia et al (2023).

- Seasonal land cover maps were produced using a semi-supervised approach using ML methods. A ML learner Random Forest (Breiman, 2001) model was trained using a ‘big’ training dataset created by ascribing phenological patterns matching crop calendars (e.g. NAC, 2023) to 10-day EVI/GVMI timeseries clustered using K-means (Lloyd, 1982). This approach overcomes the challenges of obtaining representative in situ training data by identifying patterns obtained from timeseries describing land cover phenologies identified through expert elicitation. Mapping results for main crops were satisfactorily evaluated against crop survey statistics.

Remotely sensed ET_a estimates from the CMRSET model were evaluated against two locally calibrated ET_a estimates, showing reasonable agreement both temporally and spatially. Seasonal crop maps, obtained through a Random Forest Mapping model, were evaluated against remotely sensed mapping and agricultural survey statistics on main crop areas, showing reasonable agreement. The 30 m spatial detail of both ET_a and crop maps provided important insights into the dynamics of cropping practices and water use. The detailed analysis and results are provided under Peña-Arancibia et al. (2023).

The analysis revealed, even though ET_a showed relatively low variability from season to season, there were substantial shifts from cotton to rice, other crops, and fish farming. Nonetheless, the total cultivated area within each canal command remained relatively consistent. During Rabi, ET_a and crop area variation were relatively less compared to Kharif. Again, the total cropped area within each canal command remained relatively stable, with winter cereals being the dominant crop in Rabi season. The analysis revealed that in south Punjab canal commands, ET_a is generally higher than canal supplies, potentially resulting in increased groundwater use for agriculture and aquaculture (fish farms). The gap between ET_a is substantially higher during Rabi than during Kharif, which is one of the main contributors for groundwater decline. To address the issues of mismatch between supply and consumption, and to halt the groundwater decline and environmental degradation, potential water management options include: (i) managed aquifer recharge in fresh and declining groundwater areas, (ii) on- and off-farm storages to store intermittent surplus rainfall and canal water supplies, thus reducing groundwater pumping, and (iii) agricultural policy adjustments to promote low water requirement land uses.

Conclusions

The key learning arising from this analysis is that despite the challenges, there are opportunities for Pakistan to achieve sustainable water and food security while ensuring environmental protection. It appears that no single strategy will suffice; both supply side and demand side policies and management are needed.

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Evaluating the Australian Government's Environmental Watering Program in the Murray–Darling Basin Against Legislated Objectives

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Summary

The Australian government's Flow-MER (monitoring, evaluation and reporting) program evaluates the annual and cumulative ecological outcomes of its environmental waterings in the Murray–Darling Basin. The evaluations address legislated objectives to protect, restore and/or enhance the Basin's hydrological regime, vegetation, native fish, species and ecosystem diversity, foodwebs and water quality. Evaluation approaches vary – influenced by disciplinary preference, quality/quantity of input data, and ability and confidence to infer attribution of observed change to the watering actions. Modelling approaches and evaluation indicators used and some results for the 2022–23 water year (a wet year) and cumulative since 2014–15 will be presented.

Introduction

The Murray–Darling Basin is Australia's largest food bowl. The late 19th and early–mid 20th century saw the waters of its rivers diverted for irrigation. By the 1970s, the river system was in serious decline – algal blooms, dry river beds, dying riparian vegetation. While water is constitutionally the responsibility of the States, the Australian government intervened and legislated a reform package, setting biophysical, economic and social objectives for the recovery of the Basin. Water in the Basin is bought and traded as a commodity. To return water to the environment (from irrigation), the Australian government purchases water on the open market. It established the (Commonwealth) Environmental Water Holder (CEWH) to manage its water holdings. The CEWH plans watering actions each year. Its Flow Monitoring, Evaluation and Research (Flow-MER) Program monitors and evaluates the outcomes of those watering actions. Most of the Program is outsourced – the Basin-scale evaluation component is a consortium of researchers and practitioners, led by CSIRO. The monitoring is undertaken separately by Area-scale teams, managed by the CEWH. Basin-scale and Area-scale teams also conduct a range of complementary research activities, designed to inform evaluation and/or adaptive management of Commonwealth environmental water.

To the best of our knowledge, the Flow-MER Program is globally unique – its duration, the breadth of and harmony within its partnerships, its scale and ecological coverage, its delivery processes that support the production of a new set of evaluations and evaluation reports each year, managing through changes in institutions, policy amendments, and now delivering key evidence to the 2025–26 Evaluation and Review of the Basin Plan itself.

How environmental water is ordered and delivered is not covered in this paper, except to note that the CEWH works through and with the water managers in each jurisdiction to deliver Commonwealth environmental water (CEW). Depending on the objective/s of the watering (e.g. to maintain refugia during drought, or extend a spring pulse), the CEW may be delivered in partnership with jurisdiction's environmental water. When delivered with other water (including natural floodwaters), apportioning of outcome to CEW is challenging and is reporting as contributing to, or supporting, the environmental outcome of the watering action.

Methodology and Results

Basin-scale evaluations are conducted for 6 themes – hydrology, vegetation, native fish, species diversity, ecosystem diversity, foodwebs and water quality – in February–June every year, for the previous water year

(1 July–30 June) and cumulative since 2014–15. Reports are prepared and published, and the cycle is repeated annually. Evaluation of the contribution of CEW to observed environmental outcomes is dependent on the data available. The multi-year Hydrology (instream), Fish and Vegetation themes have sufficient data to model and compare environmental outcomes both with and without CEW (counterfactual modelling), and also infer outcomes outside of monitored areas. Ecosystem Diversity, Species Diversity and Vegetation themes identify environmental responses in locations that received CEW (often in conjunction with other sources of environmental or non-environmental water) and, where feasible, compare with areas that did not receive CEW. Hydrology (inundation) and Food Webs and Water Quality themes use flow and water quality metrics to infer likely outcomes. Fish (annual), Vegetation (annual) and Food Webs and Water Quality themes summarise findings across Selected Areas.

Theme analyses, evaluations and reports are prepared each year, and key findings are distilled into an annual synthesis report (e.g. 2021–22 water year in Flett et al., 2023). Results from that report will be presented.

Conclusions

The production of 6 annual and cumulative evaluations requires an enormous commitment each year. Modest improvements in evaluation approaches and presentation of results continue to provide the CEWH with annually updated, evidence-based reporting of outcomes of their watering program. This reporting supports adaptive management of key assets within the Basin and assists the CEWH in fulfilling its legislative requirements under the Basin Plan. The need for quantification of outcomes and inference beyond monitored sites is tempered by the paucity of data, both in terms of spatial coverage and density of sampling, requiring careful consideration of confidence in and attribution of effects. Overall, our teams have found that it is better to provide qualitative assessment of outcomes, than compromise scientific integrity. This is the tightrope that the evaluation teams walk and dictates the style of modelling and presentation of results.

The Flow-MER program is extremely important to the future of the Murray–Darling Basin, and a further 5-year program is in the planning phase (commencing on 1 July 2024). The new program has an expanded spatial footprint (and thus more data being collected) and a reduced number of themes (flows and connectivity, waterbirds, native vegetation, fish) with a strong emphasis on embedding First Nations knowledge and science in the program.

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A Framework to Describe the ‘Readiness’ of Indicators to Evaluate Outcomes of Environmental Watering

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Summary

Environmental watering is a term used to describe the planned release of river water to achieve one or more ecological objectives, e.g. extending a natural flow event to support waterbird breeding. Evaluation of the outcome of the watering often relies on biophysical and/or numeric indicators (e.g. change in habitat condition; number of waterbird nests). We have devised a framework to describe an indicator’s ‘readiness’ as an evaluation indicator. The utility of the framework to assist evaluators select appropriate indicators is under trial with promising results which will be presented.

Introduction

In the Australian government’s Flow-MER program (Cuddy et al., 2024), different approaches and indicators are used to infer annual and cumulative (over time) ecological outcomes for six ecosystem themes (fish, vegetation, species diversity, ecosystem diversity, hydrological regime, food webs and water quality) from watering actions, designed to meet an ecological objective/s (e.g. enhance fish habitat). Outcomes are reported annually for the most recent water year (July–June) and cumulatively since the start of the program. How objectives are set differ between themes. This makes it difficult to provide a Basin-scale synthesis of outcomes, and can also lead to comparison of evaluation methods that downplay the realities of what can be achieved based on the available data. This has led us to devise a framework to assess the ‘readiness’ of an indicator to serve as an evaluation indicator. We have chosen the term ‘readiness’ to avoid implying any judgement on the appropriateness of the indicator. The framework is based on the concept of maturity models, but is not intended to judge the maturity of an indicator - rather it is to provide modellers and evaluators with a rational and logical approach to selecting indicators that are appropriate for addressing the issue at hand. We are trialling the framework on the Flow-MER program and preliminary results (not yet peer-reviewed) will be presented and critiqued.

Methodology and Results

The framework is an adaptation of the maturity model concept, with 5 levels of ‘readiness’. Unlike industry-standard maturity models (e.g. the Capability Maturity Model, CMU 1994) which are designed to drive organisational process and/or capability improvement, our ‘readiness’ framework does not assume an orderly progression ‘up’ the maturity ladder or imply that one level is better than another.

In constructing the framework, we have identified a number of common phases (levels) through which an indicator matures: A Trial, B Repeatable, C Performing, D Adaptive and E Integrated. The 5 readiness principles that we have identified are 1 Science integrity; 2 Fit for purpose; 3 Quantitative and evidence-based; 4 Collaborative arrangements; 5 Improved through research. Table 1 provides an example of mapping a principle across the 5 evaluation maturity phases. The framework can then be used to characterise evaluation indicators. Results for 3 hypothetical evaluation indicators are provided in Table 2.

Table 1. Mapping the 3 key criteria of principle 1 Science integrity across the 5 readiness phases

Key criteria	A Trial	B Repeatable	C Performing	D Adaptive	E Integrated
Defensible, robust methods	Test indicator	Repeatable method	Quantitative methods	Modelled scenarios	High predictive power
Methods quantitative	Qualitative methods	Semi-quantitative	Quantitative methods	Modelled data	Scenarios / prediction
Confidence estimates	Low confidence	Known confidence	Known confidence	High confidence	High confidence and trusted

Colour key: yellow – new science, low confidence, qualified reporting; pale green – sound science, known confidence, reliable reporting; darker green – strong science base, high confidence, reporting informs adaptive management.

Table 2. Results from using the framework to assess the readiness of 3 hypothetical evaluation indicators

Principle	Evaluation indicator maturity		
	Indicator 1	Indicator 2	Indicator 3
1	E Integrated	A Trial	B Repeatable
2	D Adaptive	B Repeatable	C Performing
3	D Adaptive	A Trial	C Performing
4	C Performing	C Performing	C Performing
5	C Performing	B Repeatable	B Repeatable
Average overall rating	3.8	1.8	2.6

Conclusions

We have devised an indicator ‘readiness’ framework that we believe addresses a gap in the environmental assessment literature. Rather than focus on critiquing evaluation models and methods (and the indicators they use), we provide a framework for describing (and selecting) evaluation indicators that is non-judgemental and seeks to make a positive contribution to the science of evaluation.

Our trial using the (draft) framework to describe the readiness of the indicators used in the Flow-MER program has shown that the framework not only provides a logical approach to selecting indicators, it can help in communicating why a particular indicator has been selected, in eliciting indicator characteristics that are of importance to the issue at hand, in gathering user (client) requirements and to manage expectations. It can assist users in selecting a level of indicator that is sufficiently ‘ready’ for the job at hand.

We are keen to continue developing the framework. It brings a level of pragmatism to the modelling of environmental outcomes and contributes to the iEMSs conference theme of addressing environmental challenges through intelligent modelling.

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Exploring the Synergy: AI, ML, and Process-Based Modelling Action

Machine Education Approach for Country Scale High-Resolution Air Pollution Modelling

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Summary

Accurate dense pollution maps constitute the first step toward better understanding and mitigating air pollution. However, sensing is mostly sparse, and thus either mathematical methodologies or physicochemical dispersion models are utilized for the interpolation. Models, however, provide unsatisfactory performances, while mathematical tools require a significant amount of data. Here a *machine education* approach, which fuses both physicochemical model and machine learning is presented for producing dense air pollution maps on a national scale. In this way the need for tremendous amount of data is alleviated and the accuracy of the physicochemical model is improved.

Introduction

While possessing inherent limitations, for decades physicochemical models have been to describe environmental phenomena. In recent years data analysis methods have been suggested to compensate for the models' limitations. In recent years data analysis has increasingly relied on machine learning methodologies. Since machines implement mathematical algorithms without knowing the physical nature of the problem, they may be accurate but lack the flexibility to move across different domains. To alleviate this problem, a *machine-education* approach, where a machine is equipped with a physical model, universal building blocks, and an unlabelled dataset from which it derives its decision criteria is presented (Kendler et al. 2022). The educated machine is accurate, and its generalization capabilities outperform classical machines.

Here, we utilize a machine education approach that capitalizes on a physicochemical countrywide model as a first estimate of dense pollution maps and Machine and Deep Learning (M&DL) algorithms, for its correction. Specifically, the CHIMERE model (Menut et al. 2013) is used as the physicochemical predictive model. CHIMERE estimates the concentrations of pollutants in the atmosphere by physicochemical calculations using meteorological inputs, pollutants emission fluxes and chemical boundary conditions. When comparing the estimations of the model with the AQM stations' actual monitored pollutants concentrations, the model has consistently shown spatially limited performance across all geographical regions. Moreover, previous studies have documented significant biases of CHIMERE when compared to monitored measurements, encompassing both gaseous and particulate chemical species, including NO₂ and PM_{2.5} (Ferreyra, Curci, and Lanfri 2016). To cope with the shortcomings of the CHIMERE model, Bessagnet et al., (2019) have suggested a surrogate metamodel for the CHIMERE rather than correcting its output. By doing so, they essentially disassociated the problem from its physicochemical context. Thus, arises the need for an implementation of a correction method to CHIMERE, intending to enhance its performance and accuracy while preserving the association to the physics that governs the pollution system.

Methodology and Results

Machine learning (ML) can capture complex nonlinear relationships and learn intricate patterns in data. However, these models disregard the physical nature of the problem and need a lot of data. Machine education integrates a physicochemical model with ML methods to alleviate these hurdles. Thus, the machine is given insights about the physical nature of the problem instead of inferring the connections only from the data.

The physicochemical model reduces the need for data and simplifies the ML methodology. Decision trees-based algorithms, such as eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) and Random Forest (RF) were chosen as simple ML

methods for their ensemble learning and diverse data handling. The input for the ML algorithms includes the CHIMERE's estimation. Thus, estimating the error is equivalent of estimating the true value (Chimere estimation and estimated error superimposed). This allows for a smaller search space and simpler NN architecture.

NO₂ and PM_{2.5} timeseries are investigated. The NO₂ dataset contained 39,148 samples from January 1st, 2018, to December 23rd, 2020. The PM_{2.5} contained 18,826 samples. The units of measurement for the pollutants' concentrations are *ppb* and $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for NO₂ and PM_{2.5} respectively. The input also includes other pollutants concentrations, meteorological, geographical and topographical variables, and hour of the day.

Table 1 shows the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Fractional Bias (MFB) of AQM measurements and Chimere's outputs before and after correction using NN, RF and XGB. MFB values range between -2 to +2, where 0 is ideal and indicates no bias, positive and negative values indicate underestimation and overestimation, respectively. Fig. 1 shows the Error before and after correction. Thus it is evident that the machine education approach outperforms the physicochemical model with less data than ML methods.

Table 1. Chimere, NN, RF and XGB

Conclusions

The study presents a machine education approach, in which the CHIMERE physicochemical model's NO₂ and PM_{2.5} estimates are improved by integrating M&DL methods into the process. The methodologies used are Neural Networks, Random Forest and XGBoost for bias correction methods on top of the CHIMERE, a deployed physicochemical model estimating concentrations of air pollutants across Israel. The results show the great potential of the machine education approach, as the model's error (MAE) and bias (MFB) have been mitigated.

Figure 1. CDF of all models, constructed of all NO₂ AQM stations.

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Investigate the Fate and Behaviour of *Lyngbya majuscula*: Australian Case Study

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Summary

This research aims to monitor, predict, and create risk assessment scenarios for the cyanobacteria *Lyngbya majuscula* in the Broadwater, Gold Coast, Australia. The first recorded appearance of *L. majuscula* in the Broadwater dates to early 2018. However, the precise causes behind these blooms and their specific locations remain uncertain, raising concerns about potential reoccurrences. Advanced data collection strategies, coupled with the development of an effective data-driven model integrated with a hydrodynamic model, will allow to understand the spatial and temporal distribution of *L. majuscula* and will be used to assess scenarios related to climate change and urbanisation of the catchment area.

Introduction

Harmful cyanobacterial blooms have drawn the attention of governments and water utilities because of their potential to harm water resources. It is also expected that these events will increase in both frequency and magnitude in the future due to the effects of climate change. Since the 1990s, Australia began experiencing seasonal *L. majuscula* blooms, which is a toxic cyanobacteria species with rapid growth and areal expansion. These blooms exert multifaceted impacts on the environment, economy, and human health. The *L. majuscula* bloom appear to be linked to a complex system of biological and environmental factors, which are aggravated by human activities (Watkinson, O'Neil, & Dennison, 2005).

Occurrences of *L. majuscula* blooms have been observed in multiple coastal locations across Queensland (Albert et al., 2005). Broadwater is approximately 25km in length (north-south), and has high ecological, economic, cultural importance and community values for the Gold Coast region (Dunn et al., 2022). The catchment is intensely urbanised, as a result of that, the Broadwater is likely receiving significant nutrient loads from urban/agricultural sources (Burton, Phillips, & Hawker, 2004). With the ongoing population growth within the catchment (Dunn et al., 2022), there is a potential for increased nutrient discharge in the area. Furthermore, considering the projected increase in temperatures, the occurrence of extreme precipitation events, and its history of past blooms, Broadwater is emerging as a vulnerable area for *L. majuscula* blooms.

In view of the serious impacts caused by *L. majuscula* and the vulnerability of the study area to this cyanobacteria appearance, it is crucial to develop management strategies that aim to prevent or minimize the risk of future blooms and their expansion. To achieve this goal, understanding its spatial and temporal distribution is fundamental, as well as the variables that influence its occurrence.

Methodology and Results

This is an ongoing PhD project, and the methodology consists in an innovative data collection utilizing two different types of drones: the aerial drone DJI Mini Pro 3 and the underwater drone Deep Trekker Revolution ROV. For efficient monitoring of *L. majuscula*, it is necessary to use the underwater drone since *Lyngbya* begins to form at the bottom of the water body. The aerial drone is essential because, towards the end of its cycle, *Lyngbya* can form mats that float on the water's surface. The high resolution of both drones enables the monitoring and consequent data collection of *Lyngbya* in Broadwater, also they allow identify the spot of its appearance. Whenever *Lyngbya* is detected, a water sample will be collected to check the water quality parameters on that day.

Due to the complex nature of the relationships among the variables involved in the appearance process of *L. majuscula*, more sophisticated modelling approaches are necessary to accurately capture and predict the

dynamics of this ecosystem. The hydrodynamic model MIKE 21 serves as a potent tool for comprehending water movement.

MIKE 21 will initially be employed to predict chlorophyll-a concentrations. This choice is based on the greater availability of data concerning chlorophyll-a compared to *L. majuscula*. Consequently, it will be feasible to calibrate the model for simulations in Broadwaters. The presence of *L. majuscula* will be inferred from the chlorophyll-a data. However, due to limited knowledge about Lyngbya, its prediction will rely on a fully data-driven model integrated with the outputs of the hydrodynamic model MIKE 21.

After linking the hydrodynamic model MIKE 21 with the data-driven model to predict Lyngbya, scenarios involving climate change and land use change will be conducted. To represent climate change, global circulation model projections for two Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) emission scenarios will be utilized as inputs for the MIKE 21 model. The selected scenarios are RCP 4.5, representing a moderate/positive scenario, and RCP 8.5, representing a more severe/negative scenario. As for land use changes, variations in nutrient concentrations will be incorporated and used as inputs in the model.

The novelty of this research lies in its endeavour to predict the presence of *L. majuscula* in Broadwater, a task that has not been previously undertaken. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there have been no attempts to integrate a process-based spatially explicit hydrodynamic model with a *L. majuscula* bloom prediction model. Therefore, conducting research to monitor and predict this cyanobacterium by utilising integrated numerical models can be considered a significant advancement in the field. Additionally, the drones utilized in this research for data collection are considered innovative technological devices, offering high-resolution capabilities for data collection.

Conclusions

As this is an ongoing PhD project, results have not yet been generated. However, the expected outcomes include:

- determine the optimal conditions for the appearance of *L. majuscula* in Broadwater, based on the correlations between chlorophyll-a and abiotic factors necessary for *L. majuscula* growth;
- calibrating the MIKE 21 model to simulate conditions in Broadwater;
- development of a data-driven model linked to MIKE 21 to predict *L. majuscula*;
- identify the spatial and temporal distribution of *L. majuscula* and represent it on maps;
- identify the future pattern of *L. majuscula* through the creation of risk assessment scenarios based on climate change and land use change;
- identify whether *L. majuscula* has been growing over the years.

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Extracting Hydrologic Laws From Data Via Machine Learning

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Summary

ML applications in hydrology have largely evolved in isolation from the mechanistic, process-based modelling (PBM) paradigms, which have historically been the cornerstone of scientific discovery and policy support. To address this gap, we frame a new modelling framework that is both ML-powered and process-equipped, for new knowledge discovery from big, complex, and high-dimensional geospatial data. This framework can directly derive and synthesize new differential (ordinary or partial) and other types of equations across various hydro-climatic and socio-economic settings, at scales from small headwater catchments to large multi-jurisdictional watersheds. We test this framework using a comprehensive dataset encompassing numerous watersheds across the contiguous United States. Our findings reveal potential deficiencies in the representation of certain processes within conventional process-based hydrologic models.

Follow the Faeces: Understanding *Clostridioides difficile* Infection Dynamics Across Human, Animal, and Environmental Systems

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Summary

Clostridioides difficile infection (CDI) poses a significant global health threat, with over 8,500 cases annually in Australia alone. While traditionally linked to healthcare settings, community-acquired cases are rising, possibly due to zoonotic transmission via contaminated food and surfaces. Using a “One Health” approach, researchers aim to model CDI dynamics across human, animal, and environmental systems. This participatory Systems approach integrates diverse data and stakeholder input, aiming to identify key drivers of CDI transmission and intervention strategies’ effectiveness. The study pioneers systems modelling in understanding CDI transmission, potentially informing evidence-based policies and broader infectious disease control efforts.

Introduction

CDI is a global public health threat, recognized as a leading cause of infectious diarrhea and a prevalent healthcare-acquired infection. In Australia alone, over 8,500 cases of CDI occur annually (ACSQHC, 2022), placing a significant burden on both healthcare systems and individuals. While traditionally considered a problem within healthcare facilities, there has been a notable rise in community-associated CDI (CA-CDI) cases in Australia, with a recent ACSQHC report suggesting that >80% of CDI in Australia is now CA and with overall costs of over AU\$100 million annually. However, the sources/origins of CA-CDI remain unclear, suggesting potential sources beyond hospitals (ACSQHC, 2023). Leveraging the “One Health” paradigm, which recognises the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health, we hypothesise that zoonotic transmission, particularly through contaminated food and household surfaces, plays a significant role in *C. difficile* dissemination. Furthermore, human behaviour patterns and socioeconomic factors may also influence *C. difficile* spread. Our overarching research aim is to employ a participatory Systems approach to model the intricate dynamics of *C. difficile* multiplication and transfer within, and between, different sub-systems. This systems modelling focuses on revealing: the behavioural and socioeconomic factors influencing *C. difficile* dissemination; the environmental pathways of transmission; and the potential role of zoonotic transmission in CA-CDI cases. By elucidating the key drivers of *C. difficile* dissemination and their interplay, the model will offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of various intervention strategies aimed at mitigating human CDI incidence, such as improved hygiene protocols and antimicrobial stewardship programs in healthcare settings.

Methodology and Results

Our methodology leverages a novel participatory Systems approach (Sterman, 2000; Ghaffarzadegan et al., 2011), integrating diverse data sources and stakeholder input to construct a comprehensive Systems model of *C. difficile* transmission dynamics. This approach stands in contrast to traditional research methods (Eckhardt et al., 2020) that often focus on isolated aspects of the transmission cycle. The value of the Systems approach has been increasingly evidenced in health care and public health applications to investigate intervention strategies (Sharareh et al., 2017; Cepoiu-Martin & Bischak, 2018; Sahin et al., 2020; Dhirasasna et al., 2021). Central to this methodology is the assembly of a transdisciplinary team (including epidemiologists, microbiologists, environmental scientists, veterinary medicine specialists, social scientists, and public health policymakers). This diverse group will ensure a holistic approach to model development.

We draw upon a wealth of data sources, including: CDI case records; environmental and animal sampling results; genomic sequencing data; and qualitative input from key stakeholders (patients, healthcare workers, veterinarians). Through collaborative workshops and consultations, we have developed a Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) that captures the complex interdependencies among key variables driving *C. difficile* transmission. This CLD was refined iteratively to represent the underlying causal mechanisms governing *C. difficile* dissemination, incorporating both direct and indirect pathways of transmission. Positive and negative links within the CLD delineate the directionality of relationships between variables, allowing for the identification of reinforcing and balancing feedback loops that drive system behaviour. Our research aims to yield a robust Systems model that provides a nuanced understanding of *C. difficile* transmission dynamics across human, animal, and environmental systems. By elucidating the key drivers and their interplay, the final dynamic simulation model will offer valuable insights for: The effectiveness of various intervention strategies in mitigating human CDI incidence; and the economic implications associated with different intervention approaches, facilitating cost-benefit analysis for policymakers and healthcare stakeholders. Through scenario analysis and sensitivity testing, we anticipate identifying optimal intervention points and strategies for reducing *C. difficile* transmission. This will contribute to improved public health outcomes, resource allocation, and potentially healthcare cost savings.

Conclusions

This study represents a pioneering effort in applying Systems modelling techniques to investigate the transmission dynamics of *C. difficile*. By adopting a holistic “One Health” perspective and engaging diverse stakeholders, we aim to advance our understanding of the complex interactions underlying *C. difficile* dissemination. Through interdisciplinary collaboration and data integration, our research has the potential to inform targeted interventions aimed at curbing CDI incidence rates and mitigating associated economic burdens. Ultimately, the insights assembled from this study not only hold immense promise for informing evidence-based policy decisions and public health strategies to combat CDI, but also have the potential to contribute to the broader fight against infectious diseases by improving our understanding of transmission dynamics across human, animal, and environmental interfaces.

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Towards a Sustainable Future for Rare Earth Elements: A System Dynamics Approach to Supply Chain Diversification and Environmental Stewardship

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Summary

This paper presents a system dynamics (SD) model to evaluate policy measures for diversifying the global rare earth elements (REEs) supply chain, while balancing economic, environmental, and social factors. The model provides insights for informed decision-making to meet the growing demand for Neodymium sustainably.

Introduction

Rare earth elements (REEs) are critical for various industries, particularly green technologies such as electric vehicles and wind turbines (Alves Dias et al., 2021; Barthelmie and Pryor, 2021). However, the global REEs supply chain is heavily reliant on China, introducing significant geopolitical risks (Riddle et al., 2021; Sprecher et al., 2017). To mitigate these risks and enhance supply security, it is crucial to diversify the supply of REEs among countries outside China, referred to as the “Rest of the World” (RoW) countries (Smith et al., 2022). This paper presents a novel decision-support model based on System Dynamics (SD) to evaluate policy measures for achieving this goal while considering the environmental impacts associated with different REEs deposit types (Verrier et al., 2022; Lee and Wen, 2017).

Methodology and Results

The SD model developed in this study consists of seven interconnected sectors: Current Capacity, Indicated Capacity, Pricing, Demand, Neodymium Market, Physical Structure, and Recycling. Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs) were used to map out the relationships between key variables in each sector, and the quantitative model was implemented using stock and flow diagrams in AnyLogic software (Sterman, 2000; Richardson, 2011).

Through simulation experiments, the effectiveness of individual policies and their combinations was evaluated based on their ability to enhance RoW’s market share, minimize environmental impacts, and meet the growing demand for Neodymium. The results showed that direct government interventions, particularly those focused on expanding mining and recycling capacities, significantly increased RoW’s market share and decreased unmet Neodymium demand. Environmental regulations were found to be important for promoting sustainable mining practices, leading to considerable environmental benefits despite slightly constraining market share growth. The most effective policy combination included capacity expansion, recycling, and international cooperation, resulting in a substantial increase in RoW market share and a notable reduction in unmet demand.

The model also evaluated the potential of recovering REEs from non-traditional sources, such as coal ash, as a promising strategy for diversifying supply and reducing environmental impacts. However, the limitations of existing recycling infrastructure were noted, highlighting the need for further investment in this area.

Conclusions

The SD model developed in this study provides a novel decision-support tool for policymakers to evaluate REEs supply chain policies comprehensively. By balancing supply diversification and environmental impacts, the model contributes to the discourse on sustainable supply chain management for critical minerals. The findings underscore the importance of a holistic approach that considers economic, environmental, and social factors in REEs policy-making.

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The LSG Model: A New Hybrid Model for Fast and Accurate Flood Inundation Simulation

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Summary

High-fidelity 2D hydrodynamic models are commonly used for flood inundation modelling to inform emergence responses or flood mitigation decisions. However, they are computationally expensive, which prevents their use in real-time flood forecasting, where real-time response is needed or flood infrastructure design under uncertainty, where hundreds or thousands of model runs are required. We address this challenge by developing a hybrid model - the LSG model, based on both coarse resolution hydrodynamic models and data-driven techniques. The LSG model can speed up the traditional flood inundation modelling process by over 1000 times, while maintaining accuracy that is comparable to the original 2D high-fidelity hydraulic models.

Introduction

Floods are one of the most frequent and devastating natural disasters for human communities. Currently, 2D hydrodynamic models are commonly used for flood response management worldwide. These models can accurately simulate complex flow patterns of flood events and provide crucial information on flood risks. However, the computational demand of 2D hydrodynamic models scales with their resolution and complexity (Chu et al., 2020; Xie et al., 2021). This means accurate high-resolution (i.e. high-fidelity) models cannot be directly used for real-time flood inundation forecasting over large domains or for situations where models need to be run repeatedly to evaluate and update meteorological forecasts and dam operation options to account for uncertainty (Zhou et al., 2021). We introduce a new modelling approach that supercharges hydrodynamic models for speed while maintaining high accuracy.

Methodology and Results

It has been found in our study (Fraehr et al., 2022; 2023a) that spatial-temporal patterns of flood inundation simulated using an extremely simplified (and hence super-fast) hydrodynamic (i.e. low-fidelity) model can be mathematically transformed to reproduce similar results as a high-fidelity model. The mathematical transformation consists of three steps: i) using Empirical Orthogonal Function (EOF) analysis to reduce the dimensionality of the low-fidelity data to just a few key features, ii) using pre-trained Sparse Gaussian Process models to convert the key features to high-fidelity features; and iii) to reconstruct the flood inundation information from the high-fidelity features using a reverse EOF analysis. This new modelling approach is called the hybrid Low-fidelity, Spatial analysis, and Gaussian Process Learning (LSG) model (Fraehr et al., 2022). By integrating a low-fidelity process-based model and a data-driven model, the LSG model can incorporate spatial-temporal correlations between flood drivers and flood responses, and simulate the entire dynamic evolution of flood inundation in an efficient manner.

To demonstrate the application of the LSG model, we simulated historic flood events for two distinctively different river reaches in Australia: the Chowilla floodplain of Murray River and Burnett River in coastal Queensland. The study sites were chosen due to their distinctively different topography and flow patterns - the Chowilla floodplain has a flat and complex topography resulting in slow-moving water, whereas the Burnett River is a steep, coastal river with rapid flows. The LSG model leads to a significant reduction in computational demand for both sites compared to conventional 2D hydrodynamic models, predicting flood inundation more than three orders of magnitude faster while still maintaining high accuracy (Fraehr et al., 2023b). The high accuracy is demonstrated by a Critical Success Index of 0.98 and 0.95 for the maximum inundation extent, and a Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of 0.999 and 0.997 for the maximum water depth in the Chowilla floodplain and the Burnett

River, respectfully. The results demonstrate that the LSG model can evaluate flood inundation accurately, rapidly, and repeatedly as events unfold - a capability required for active decision-making during flood emergencies to save lives and protect assets (Fraehr et al., 2024).

Conclusions

In this study, we developed a fast and accurate model for flood inundation modelling – the LSG model. This can serve as an efficient alternative to commonly used high-fidelity 2D hydraulic models for various applications requiring accurate flood inundation information with time.

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Development of a Machine Learning Model to Support Low Cost Realtime *Legionella* Monitoring in Premise Plumbing Systems

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Summary

Legionella pneumophila (*L. pneumophila*) is a type of bacteria primarily known for causing Legionnaires' disease with severe outcomes. With caseloads continuing to increase, further research to understand optimized sampling schema and safe limits of *L. pneumophila*, improved treatment options and realistic population-level risk modeling, particularly in healthcare and other high-risk locations are reinforced needs. This project aims to present insights into the water quality in public drinking water systems and explores its capability of acting as a means of preliminary identification and prevention for *L. pneumophila* infection or potential outbreak. Physiochemical surveillance is a simple, fast tool to estimate the contamination level and this risk assessment method of *L. pneumophila* may replace the traditional one for *L. pneumophila* management and control, to mitigate the risk to public Health.

Introduction

Opportunistic premise plumbing pathogens (OPPPs) are a class of waterborne pathogens that survive in biofilms due in part to the ecological support of the biofilm to the pathogens lifecycle, and to avoid residual disinfection treatment of water distribution systems. *Legionella pneumophila* (*Legionella*) is a type of OPPPs primarily known for causing Legionnaires' disease which contributed 98.1% hospitalization rates of OPPPs (Collier et al, 2021). With caseloads continuing to increase, further research to understand optimized sampling schema and safe limits of *Legionella*, improved treatment options and realistic population-level risk modeling, particularly in healthcare and other high-risk locations are reinforced needs. To assess the risk of *Legionella*, the enumeration of *Legionella* contamination people exposed to is crucial. Currently, Culture-based methods or biochemical methods like Legiolert act as the main approach on *Legionella* monitoring and control determining although they are time-consuming. (Reischl, et al 2002). Also, the true *L. pneumophila* cell counts can't be assessed precisely for the sake of over and under counting problems (Bopp et al, 1981; Hussong et al, 1987; Chang et al, 2009). Another alternative is qPCR and it becomes popular owing to quick detection and high specificity. But all the three methods incur substantial monetary and person-time costs when placed in socioeconomically and racially disadvantaged locations, like environmental justice communities, exacerbating the issues of equality of water quality access in the USA (Pierce & Jimenez, 2015; Morello-Frosch et al, 2011; McDonald & Jones, 2018). Contrastingly, physiochemical parameters like pH, total suspended solids, oxidation reduction potential among others, all can be measured in high volumes and assessed in real-time for a fraction of the financial costs of microbial monitoring. Incorporating these substantial data sources with intelligent machine learning (ML) method can support real-time low-cost monitoring.

Methodology and Results

Using data from a COVID-19 induced stagnation period to the College of Public Health at University of Michigan, water samples from drinking fountain and bathroom taps were taken. These samples were then assayed for *Legionella*, three amoeba hosts: *Acanthamoeba*, *Hartmenella* and *Naegleria fowleri*. General and specific water quality parameters were also measured grouped as physiochemical parameters these: pH, turbidity, temperature,

electrical conductivity, oxidation reduction potential, and residual chlorine concentration. These sample results were used to develop a ML workflow and model to estimate a range of *Legionella* concentration based on physiochemical parameters more associated with both *Legionella* and its host cells. The ML model demonstrates good predictive power using internal verification. The model outputs a logistic regression of the range of concentration that can be expected under specific physiochemical conditions and host cell ratios. We also demonstrate that not only is *Naegleria fowleri* a significant health concern as a pathogenic amoeba but also as the most impactful host cell information for predicting *Legionella* occurrence and high concentration events. This is in agreement with the microbiology and current state of drinking water science of its importance in *Legionella* proliferation and survival. These results will be expanded to a greater set of computational tools to make more informed and system specific *Legionella* control measures for Ohio and the nation.

Conclusions

ML model provides a dependable estimate of *Legionella*'s instantaneous concentration, offering a valuable basis for informed decision-making in controlling occupant risks. A remarkable advantage of the surveillance methodology lies in its capacity for real-time monitoring facilitated by sensors that provide instantaneous physiochemical parameter readings.

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Computational Intelligence and AI Systems for scientific computing in water resources

Regional-Scale Integrative Modeling for Nature-Based Flood Adaptation Solutions

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Summary

Nature-based solutions (NBS) are crucial for flood risk management, offering both flood mitigation and improved water quality. The effectiveness of NBS is scale-dependent, with regional implementations significantly reducing downstream flood risks and enhancing water quality. We developed an “Integrated Flood-Nutrient Framework” using high-resolution ecohydrologic and hydrodynamic models based on the Soil Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) and LISFLOOD-FP at the NHDPlus scale, optimized for computational efficiency through parallel and high-performance computing. This approach improves the precision of regional-scale ‘what-if’ scenarios and decision-making, quantifying water quality co-benefits to enhance the benefit-cost ratio of NBS, promoting their adoption in comprehensive flood risk management.

Introduction

Climate change is intensifying the frequency and severity of floods, resulting in considerable economic and ecological ramifications. Agricultural watersheds are particularly vulnerable, where the increased occurrence of floods accelerates nutrient runoff and soil erosion, severely disrupting ecosystems and degrading water quality. In the United States, regions like the Chesapeake Bay and the Gulf of Mexico are experiencing significant eutrophication.

In response to these escalating challenges, a paradigm shift toward multifunctional, nature-based flood risk management strategies is gaining momentum. Highlighted at the 27th Conference of the Parties (COP27), this shift signifies a move away from traditional (gray) engineering-focused flood infrastructure, such as levees, which often relocate flood risks, to more holistic approaches (hybrid=blue+green+gray). These practices prioritize natural flood storage, diversion, and infiltration, aiming to achieve not just flood mitigation but also broader environmental and social benefits. Particularly in agricultural watersheds, the adoption of these nature-based flood adaptation strategies provide opportunity to improve water quality as a co-benefit. However, despite their potential, the task of comprehensively quantifying the co-benefits of such nature-based solutions to facilitate their broader implementation remains a significant hurdle. The effectiveness of these solutions is inherently scale-dependent, and the complexities involved in their strategic regional application add an additional layer of challenge, emphasizing the critical need for regional-scale, integrative modeling.

Recognizing the pressing need to address both flood risk management and water quality, our research aims to fill the gap in comprehensive, integrated modeling approaches. Specifically, we introduce the “Integrated Flood-Nutrient Framework” to:

- I. Investigate “flood teleconnections” (Ansari et al., 2024) to understand how upstream management practices influence downstream flood risk.
- II. Evaluate nature-based flood adaptation strategies' effectiveness at a regional scale.
- III. Quantify water quality co-benefits of nature-based flood adaptation strategies for wider implementation.
- IV. Integrate SWAT and LISFLOOD-FP with NHDPlus for detailed “what-if” scenario analysis.
- V. Utilize parallel processing to facilitate “what-if” scenario analysis under varied climate and land management conditions.

Methodology and Results

Our research introduces the “Integrated Flood-Nutrient Framework,” a novel approach designed to address flood risk and nutrient management simultaneously. The study was conducted in the Susquehanna River Basin, the major contributor to the Chesapeake Bay with a catchment area of 71,000 km². The methodology synergizes the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT, Arnold et al. 1998) with the LISFLOOD-FP hydrodynamic model (Bates, 2010), enhancing the capability to simulate complex watershed dynamics and floodplain delineation with precision. This integrated framework enables the evaluation of climate and management scenarios' impacts on streamflow, sediment transport, and nutrient fluxes. To fully capture and understand the outcomes of flood adaptation strategies and their water quality co-benefits, our framework is divided into four critical components: the Landscape Component, the Routing Component, the Hydrodynamic Component, and the Parallel Processing capability.

Landscape component utilizes SWAT for simulating landscape hydrology and nutrient dynamics, offering an expansive view of hydrological processes across varied terrains and agricultural practices. Land scape simulation models such as APEX, AnnAGNPS, Mike-SHE could also be used for landscape component.

Routing Component advances water, sediment, and nutrients through a complex network of water bodies and channels. This includes in-stream process, reservoir and wetland routing and pond storage. The component also enhances the interaction between channel and riparian wetlands (Liu et al, 2008), acknowledging their crucial roles in flood mitigation and water quality improvement.

Hydrodynamic Component employs LISFLOOD-FP model to simulate 2D floodplain dynamics, integrating digital elevation models and land cover data for accurate flood risk assessment. The model’s configuration respects the existing river network and existing flood control infrastructures, ensuring realistic floodplain delineation.

Parallel Processing operates on high performance computing servers execute parallel simulations across the watershed. This approach enables the spatial units within the landscape, routing, and hydrodynamic modeling components to be processed concurrently. By parallelizing the computations of these spatial units, the framework significantly reduces computational time, allowing for efficient and detailed regional-scale modeling.

Conclusion

The “Integrated Flood-Nutrient Framework” marks a pivotal advancement in watershed management, merging high-resolution ecohydrologic and hydrodynamic modeling with parallel computing for enhanced precision in evaluating nature-based solutions (NBS). By integrating the Soil Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) and LISFLOOD-FP at the NHDPlus scale, this approach not only fine-tunes the accuracy of “what-if” scenarios and enriches decision-making but also effectively quantifies the co-benefits of NBS, fostering their broader implementation in flood risk management.

Acknowledgements

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On Weighted Ensembles and Hydrological Signatures

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Summary

Optimisation of ensembles using model averaging has been gaining traction. We evaluate how simple methods with varying complexity affect the overall performance the ensemble streamflow against the observed timeseries as well as how hydrological signatures are influenced by the methods both in-situ and regionalisation context. We find that simple constrained alternatives are more reliable than flexible methods for overall performance and for most of the hydrological signatures assessed. We strongly recommend applying bias correction independently before model averaging and note that leveraging dynamic weighting schemes is required to make the most of the ensembles.

Introduction

As a science riddled with numerous unknowns and a lack of comprehensive ground observations, environmental modelling is increasingly turning towards the use of ensembles – collections of estimates from various combinations of models, parameters and input data – to quantify uncertainties. The outputs of ensembles can be optimized with different model averaging methods and existing research has shown that they can considerably improve predictions obtained from an ensemble.

In hydrological sciences, comparisons of model averaging methods have thus far focused on overall performance of the estimates for streamflow and generally do not assess their influence on specific parts of the hydrograph (i.e. hydrological signatures). Furthermore, most studies focus on point observations and only a few studies consider regionalisation of the optimal model averaging weights.

In this study we optimise weighted ensembles using linear regression with various constraints on the coefficients using catchments in the CARAVAN dataset (Kratzert et al., 2022). The optimised ensembles are assessed over a few simple hydrological signatures (flow quantiles Q5, Q25, Q50, Q75 and Q95, coefficient of variation, and 1- and 7- day autocorrelation) as well as their overall performance.

Methodology and Results

We construct ensembles by using global regionalised model parameters for HBV at 5 arc-minute resolution (Beck et al., 2020) falling within the CARAVAN catchments. The resulting ensembles vary between 2 and 980 members in size. Each ensemble is optimised with the methods shown in Table 1 using a training period consisting of the first 50% of available observed timesteps, and assessed in a testing period consisting of the latter half of the available timeseries. The optimised weights are also regionalised using clustering and regression-based techniques.

When the ensembles are strongly biased, performance of the methods with implicit bias correction (i.e. the methods where coefficients are not required to add to 1 or which include an intercept) is considerably better than methods without bias corrective property. Rather unexpectedly however, when the ensemble is unbiased, the methods with stronger constraints perform more consistently, and more flexible methods show very poor performance in some catchments (i.e., overfitting). Methods which constrain the weights to strictly positive do not show the same tendency. Furthermore, the methods which allow negative regression coefficients or an intercept (which may be negative), result in significant amount of negative streamflow predictions with their proportion increasing with increasing ensemble size. This is undesirable for any variable for which negative values make no physical sense.

Table 1. Model averaging methods based on linear regression $y = \alpha + \beta X + \varepsilon$ and their varying coefficient constraints. α is the intercept, β is the regression coefficients, X represents the data matrix and ε is the error term.

Method	Coefficient constraints			Note
	$\alpha = 0$	$\beta \geq 0$	$\sum \beta = 1$	
EM	-	-	-	Ensemble (arithmetic) mean
Best	-	-	-	Best ensemble member according to RMSE
CLS	Yes	Yes	Yes	Constrained Least Squares
NNLS	Yes	Yes	No	Non-Negative Least Squares
NNLS2	No	Yes	No	Non-Negative Least Squares with an intercept
GRB	Yes	No	Yes	Granger-Ramanathan method B
GRA	Yes	No	No	Granger-Ramanathan method A
GRC	No	No	No	Granger-Ramanathan method C (Ordinary Least Squares)

We further find that CLS, NNLS, and NNLS2 use on average less than ten members in an ensemble regardless of its size, and for which there is little gain from ensemble sizes larger than 10-15 members. The other methods (GRA, GRB, and GRC) generally utilize >90% of all members in the ensemble, and increasing ensemble size gradually improves coefficient of variation and autocorrelation, but high flows begin to show erratic behaviour with larger ensembles.

The preliminary results also show that weighted ensembles with constant weights over the entire timeseries do not significantly outperform the simple ensemble mean benchmark when the performance is assessed over the entire timeseries. However, the ensemble mean is clearly inferior to the constrained methods (CLS, NNLS and NNLS2) in its ability to reproduce hydrological signatures.

The preliminary results further suggest that common parameter regionalisation methods generally fail to produce good results in ungauged settings and we therefore recommend caution in any application where an optimised ensemble is used in locations where validation is not possible. Dynamic weighting seems the most promising avenue forward.

Conclusions

The outcome of this work points that flexible model averaging methods do not consistently beat alternatives with constraints on the weights for overall performance and most of the hydrological signatures assessed. We strongly recommend first bias correcting the ensembles and subsequently applying model averaging with constraints on the weights, particularly if the weights are to be used in ungauged catchments. We further recommend the use of dynamic weighting schemes to leverage the strengths of the ensemble members in different hydrological conditions, as constant model averaging weights cannot make use of the strengths of the ensemble members in particular environmental conditions.

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Flood Gauge Height Prediction Using Advanced Deep Learning Approaches

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Summary

This paper compares the performance of recent deep learning models e.g. Neural Hierarchical Interpolation for Time Series Forecasting (N-HiTS) (Challu et al., 2022), against the traditional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model for flood gauge height forecasting. The study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of these models at different forecast horizons and assess the impact of parameters like prior rainfall, relative humidity, and temperature on forecast accuracy. The models are trained and evaluated using flood gauge height data from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) station on the Chattahoochee River in Atlanta (USGS 02336000).

Introduction

Accurate short-term prediction of river gauge height is crucial for various aspects of water resource management, flood prevention, and overall societal well-being. Researchers have employed both physical modelling tools and data-driven models to address this problem. While physical models require extensive data on watershed characteristics, data-driven models can learn complex relationships directly from the past data. Neural networks have been increasingly used for time series forecasting, with recent architectures like N-HiTS model that showed promising results for time series simulation. However, this type of models has not been extensively studied in the context of flood simulation. In this paper we apply these models to forecast the flood gauge height and compare results with LSTM.

Methodology and Results

The study compares the performance of recently published state of the art time series analysis models including N-HiTS, and LSTM models for gauge height forecasting. The models are trained and evaluated using data from the USGS gauging station on the Chattahoochee River (USGS 02336000). The effectiveness of the models is assessed at different forecast horizons (1, 3, 6 and 12 hours), and the impact of parameters like prior rainfall, relative humidity, and temperature on forecast accuracy is examined. Our methodology employs Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) and Weighted Absolute Percentage Error (WAPE) for evaluation. The forecasted results for both N-HiTS and LSTM are shown in Figure 1.

Conclusions

The results showed that for short-term forecasting, there is no significant difference in the accuracy of the models. However, for slightly longer-term forecasts, the transformer-based model outperforms both LSTM and MLP-based models like N-HiTS. Additionally, for similar parameter sizes, the MLP-based models like N-HiTS perform better than the LSTM model. Similarly, we demonstrate that model outcome does not depend significantly on the past parameters like precipitation, relative humidity, and temperature. The study concludes that recent deep learning models such as N-HiTS show promise for river gauge height forecasting and warrant further investigation in the field of hydrology.

Figure 1. The test results of the N-HITS model(left), and the LSTM model (right). Both models were evaluated using a 24-hour lookback period and a 6-hour forecasting horizon. Over a dataset spanning one year, the N-HITS model showed Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) of 75%, whereas the LSTM model showed NSE of 68% for 6 hr horizon. Note that the height values presented in these results have been normalized.

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Deep Learning Interpretability in Rainfall-runoff Modeling: What, Why, and How

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Summary

Broad consensus exists on the importance of interpretability for data-driven modeling. While there has been an increasing influx of research on interpretable deep neural networks (DNNs), the importance of interpretability is not nearly as widely appreciated in data-driven hydrologic modeling as it should be. Developers and users often build models that aren't interpretable, cannot correct bias thoroughly, and do not provide a fair explanation as to how DNNs inherently emerge from the black box model to conceptually (symbolically) reflect what the model learned. This talk will discuss a Transformer architecture for interpretable rainfall-runoff modeling that is coupled with an uncertainty and error quantification algorithm. Quantile regression was adopted to multi-horizon forecasting setting, outputting the 10th, 50th, and 90th percentiles at each time step. The proposed interpretable architecture identifies persistent temporal patterns to correct bias in the network's decision rationale. This architecture is accompanied by an example of its potential use in daily streamflow simulation across the continental US.

Introduction

Many cutting-edge approaches rely on Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs) architectures to simulate rainfall-runoff processes across various contexts. However, the structure of LSTMs does not facilitate direct connections between nonadjacent segments of a time series. Vaswani et al. (2017) introduced Transformers, which rely on attention modules for input and output representations, bypassing the need for sequence-aligned recurrent networks. Transformers employ self-attention modules to directly connect arbitrary positions in a time series, offering greater flexibility compared to LSTM-based models. This study aims to bridge a gap in the use of deep neural network (DNN) for rainfall-runoff modeling, focusing on Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT), applied to rainfall-runoff modeling across the continental United States (CONUS). We incorporated physical parameters into TFT models during training, to ensure physical consistency in modeling. We also address uncertainty by coupling TFT with a quantile regression approach.

Methodology and Results

Experimental data were collected from the openly accessible CAMELS dataset. The CAMELS dataset encompasses information on 671 catchments distributed throughout CONUS, varying in size from 4 to 25,000 square kilometres. We also used CAMELS physical parameter sand incorporated them into TFT model. The TFT model represents an advanced deep learning architecture tailored for temporal forecasting tasks, particularly well-suited for applications in hydrology, such as streamflow prediction. TFT seamlessly integrates key components of two prominent neural network architectures: the Transformer and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks. This fusion enables the TFT model to harness the strengths of both attention mechanisms and recurrent connections for enhanced predictive capabilities.

TFT calibration and training were performed using data from 1 October 1989 through 30 September 1999. TFT and benchmark evaluations were performed using data from 1 October 1999 through 30 September 2008. There were

several catchments with very low NSE values, particularly in the Great Plains. This was expected as the major portion of the 531 catchments were distributed on the east and west coasts. The TFT model faced inherent limitations in accessing sufficient information for cases situated in the central part of the CONUS, thereby resulting in suboptimal performance within these specific catchments. As previously mentioned, the core architecture of the TFT model is based on the transformer framework. Consequently, it incorporates an innovative multi-head attention mechanism that, upon examination, offers valuable insights into the sensitivity (degree of importance) of various features, enhancing the model's interpretability. Each catchment is labeled based on its respective highly sensitive static and dynamic features, as determined from the outcomes of the TFT model.

Figure 1. The most sensitive static and dynamic features of each catchment driven from the TFT.

Considering all the catchments, uncertainty metrics (median over CONUS) revealed that the 95PPU interval of TFT bracketed most of the observed streamflow data (> 95%). Accordingly, quantile regression was efficient in quantifying the average width of the uncertainty band for most of the catchments including shown in Figure 2. By including catchment physical parameters, TFT not only enhanced the performance but also provided crucial interpretability, offering insights into the role of each feature in daily streamflow generation.

Figure 2. Observed, simulated and 95PPU band along with probability plots for USGS08271000.

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Integrated Harmful Algal Bloom Early Warning Systems can Quantify the Impact of Early vs. Delayed Policy Actions for Building Climate Resilience

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Summary

Many sustainability challenges arise due to lags, inertia and phase-transitions in smaller scale systems (e.g. shallow freshwater lakes) stemming from cascading impacts from larger scale systems (e.g. global climate change). Coupled natural and human systems models, co-designed with stakeholders, can be configured as multi-hazard early warning systems to inform anticipatory policy action for building climate resilience. This study presents an Integrated Harmful Algal Bloom Early Warning System (I-HABEWS), co-designed with stakeholders, to project the likelihood of Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) from 2000-2050 in the shallow Missisquoi Bay of transboundary Lake Champlain Basin under alternate climate change and nutrient management scenarios.

Introduction

Significant advancements have been made in recent decades to monitor the spatial incidence, severity and duration of Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in freshwater lakes and estuaries through in-situ sensors and satellite remote sensing. However, the design and deployment of HAB Early Warning Systems (HABEWS) at long-term (climatic) forecast lead times still lags far behind. This paper presents an I-HABEWS that can quantify and project the impact of early versus delayed nutrient management actions under alternate land management and climate change scenarios. The I-HABEWS is built on a modular Pegasus computational workflow, originally designed as an Integrated Assessment Model (Zia et al. 2016, 2022, Hecht et al. 2020). We piloted this I-HABEWS in the context of Clean Water Act mandated Total Maximum Daily Load policies guiding the management of water quality in Missisquoi Bay of Lake Champlain and increasing concerns among stakeholders and policy makers about the adverse impacts of global climate change induced variability and shifting intensities and frequencies of extreme events.

Methodology and Results

The I-HABEWS simulates the cascading impacts of global climate change and early vs. delayed nutrient management interventions in transboundary Missisquoi watershed from 2000 through 2050. Twelve future climate simulations (4 global climate models (GCMs) x 3 emissions scenarios) and 11 early versus delayed nutrient reduction scenarios drive a distributed hydrological model (the Regional Hydro-Ecologic Simulation System - RHESys) that simulates 132 daily time series of riverine discharge and nutrient loads entering Missisquoi Bay of Lake Champlain. A high-resolution system of biogeochemistry and hydrodynamic lake models simulates water quality, including four phytoplankton groups, in the shallow bay.

From the analysis of 132 scenario outcomes estimated through I-HABEWS, we found that early action will avoid phase transitions in summer and shoulder season months (eutrophic to hyper-eutrophic and mesotrophic to eutrophic respectively), as shown in Figure 1. A delayed action embedded in the current nutrient management policy regime, coupled with climate change driven high water temperatures, on the other hand, will steer the lake in the domain of eutrophic to hypereutrophic phase spaces that promote cyanobacteria dominance (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Projected Basins of Attraction in ChIA Concentrations under six nutrient management scenarios for two climate scenarios [RCP4.5 and RCP8.5] averaged for 2001–2015, 2016–2030 and 2031–2045 simulated conditions derived from warm GCM

Conclusions

The incorporation of cross-scale coupled natural and human system dynamics, thresholds, lags and phase transitions in computational models can advance the science policy interface in challenging management decision-making processes by setting more realistic expectations about the changes in water quality. While numerous studies have identified the limits of adaptation to climate change for managing water quantity in the face of changing global scale induced temperature and precipitation patterns, this study highlights the sustainability challenges that arise in water quality management due to lags, inertia and phase transitions in smaller scale systems due to cascading effects from large scale systems. Freshwater lakes and bays, specifically, face severe challenges to adaptation and even a best-case global climate change scenario (RCP45) will require significant nutrient reductions to overcome the lags and inertia associated with internal loading from benthic Phosphorus. Targeting low emission greenhouse gas trajectories at planetary scale is necessary, but not sufficient, to avoid undesirable trophic state shifts in shallow bays like Missisquoi Bay and similar freshwater lakes. Early policy action can counter the adverse effects of global climate change on freshwater lakes.

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CIROH 1: Modelling and framework advances in the U.S. National Water Model and similar large scale modeling

Evaluation of the National Water Model's Retrospective Evapotranspiration Using Eddy-Covariance Flux Tower Measurements Across the Continental United States

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Summary

The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) National Water Model (NWM) is a key continental-scale hydrologic model for forecasting streamflow across the Continental United States (CONUS), which also provides simulations of land surface variables like evapotranspiration (ET). In this study, we assessed the ET outputs from the NWM Version 3.0 (NWM V3) Retrospective, using monthly ET measurements from 71 AmeriFlux controlled eddy-covariance towers across the CONUS by categorizing it based on the National Weather Service (NWS) River Forecast Center (RFC) regions, land cover types, elevation levels, and climate zones. The findings suggest a need for improvement in ET simulations, particularly in the California-Nevada region.

Introduction

70% of the precipitation that occurs inside the CONUS is returned to the atmosphere in the form of ET, demonstrating its significant role in the hydrological cycle (Reitz et al., 2017; Velpuri & Senay, 2017). Despite its importance for modelling, it is difficult to have accurate measurements for ET due to insufficiency of ET monitoring stations globally. With an attempt to capture the ground heterogeneity, state-of-the-art methods like Remote Sensing and Land Surface Models (LSM) are used globally to simulate ET in spatial grids. In the United States, the NOAA NWM, a continental-scale hydrologic model based on the WRF-Hydro modelling architecture provides streamflow forecasts along with the land surface simulations including ET across a 1 km rectilinear grid for the CONUS among other regions (Cosgrove et al., 2024; David Gochis et al., 2020). In this study, we have addressed the following key research question: How effectively does the NWM V3 simulate ET compared to eddy-covariance tower measurements across the CONUS? The eddy-covariance towers are at present the best-established option for ground-truth validation of ET measurements on daily and monthly scales (Aubinet et al., 2012; Reitz et al., 2017).

Methodology and Results

NWM V3 Retrospective datasets are available on the Amazon Web Services (Retrieved December 25, 2023, from <https://noaa-nwm-retrospective-3-0-pds.s3.amazonaws.com/index.html>). We extracted the accumulated evapotranspiration (ACCET) data stored in the Zarr format, a cloud friendly format, using a Python script (<https://www.hydroshare.org/resource/9690fe3dfc194b7f81e8e715bf5214dc/>). The data was extracted for those grids where the AmeriFlux towers used in this study were located. The ACCET data is available at three-hour intervals, with the accumulation period spanning three months. Latent heat flux (LE, W/m²) data from 2019 and 2020 were obtained for 71 AmeriFlux eddy-covariance towers across the CONUS from the AmeriFlux network website (Retrieved December 24, 2023, from <https://ameriflux.lbl.gov/>). Tower locations were strategically selected to represent diverse hydroclimatic and land use contexts across the CONUS. The monthly latent heat of flux values were converted into monthly ET (mm/month) using a standard energy-to-depth conversion factor:

$$ET = LE / \rho l_v,$$

Where l_v is the latent heat of vaporization (J/kg); LE is in W/m²; ρ is the density of water (kg/m³) and ET is in mm/month. ρ and l_v varies according to the temperature of water.

To incorporate the diverse hydroclimatic context, our analysis is structured by categorizing CONUS according to the National Weather Service (NWS) River Forecast Centers (RFCs), land use categories from the National Land

Cover Database (NLCD) 2019, elevation bands, and Köppen-Geiger climate zones. The performance of NWM ET was evaluated against the tower measurements using the following metrics: Coefficient of correlation (R^2), Root mean squared error (RRMSE), Relative root mean squared error (RRMSE), and Kling-Gupta efficiency (KGE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE). Paired t-tests were conducted to quantify statistically significant differences.

The analysis across RFCs within the CONUS yielded notable spatial variability. The NERFC region shows strong model performance in estimating ET, with high scores in key metrics (KGE=0.89, NSE=0.8). Other regions like LMRFC, NCRFC, and ORFC also demonstrate good agreement, with varying levels of accuracy and slight tendencies towards overestimation. SERFC, MBRFC, NWRFC, WGRFC, MARFC, and ARBRFC show moderate accuracy, often overestimating ET, especially in extreme values. In contrast, CNRFC performs poorly, with significant underestimation and failure to capture variability. Paired t-tests reveal significant differences (p -value < 0.05) between NWM estimates and tower ET data for ARBRFC, CNRFC, CBRFC, LMRFC, MARFC, MBRFC, NCRFC, SERFC, and WGRFC. Conversely, no significant difference (p -value > 0.05) was found for NERFC and ORFC. Overall, the NWM tends to overestimate ET in most regions, except for CNRFC and CBRFC, which show underestimation.

Conclusions

Our findings suggest a critical need for improvement in ET simulations of the NWM, particularly in the California-Nevada RFC region. While we did not directly investigate meteorological forcings or calibration discrepancies, these factors are likely significant for future model accuracy and should be thoroughly examined. Our forthcoming study will explore the usability of machine learning and deep learning techniques for bias-correcting or post-processing NWM ET forecasts, to develop a product with enhanced reliability for predicting ET across the CONUS for future periods ranging from 7 to 30 days.

Acknowledgements

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Modeling Breach Development in Earthen Dams with a Top Layer of Biopolymer-Treated Sand

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Summary

Numerical modeling of breach development in layered dams is challenging because of spatially varying material properties. A novel numerical model of breach evolution in layered dams is presented. A finite-difference approach is used to solve the depth-averaged mass and momentum flow equations along with sediment-mass conservation equation with a slumping failure module. The slumping failure module is characterized by a threshold failure angle of the breach channel side slope that allows breach widening. The numerical model assigns different bedload transport coefficients, and soil porosity to different layers to capture different breaching behavior.

Introduction

Almost 86% of dams in the United States are constructed with earthen material (soil and rock) (Froehlich, 2016). The most common cause of earthen dam failure is overtopping (Foster et al. 2000). During overtopping, flowing water starts to erode the the downstream dam slope if the hydraulic shear stress exceeds a critical threshold. Reducing dam erodibility can give emergency managers more time to organize flood response and can thus help reduce loss of human life and property.

Recent research proved the biopolymers are eco-friendly materials that can reduce the erodibility of earthen dams (Ko and Kang, 2018 and Ko and Kang, 2020). Research is in progress to determine if biopolymers can be considered an eco-friendly alternative to traditional soil additives because they do not have negative impacts on water quality and are produced with minimum greenhouse gas emission compared to cement. Experiments on breach development in earthen dams revealed that failure time significantly increased when the embankment was covered with a top-layer of biopolymer-treated sand as compared to untreated sand embankments (Ko and Kang, 2018 and Ko and Kang, 2020). It remains, however, unknown how to numerically model the breach evolution in this layered dam.

A novel numerical model describing breach development in layered embankment dams is presented here. The model is applied to simulate breach evolution in a 20 cm sand dam and a 15 cm sand dam covered by a 5 cm-thick layer of biopolymer-treated sand. Both dams were compacted to a maximum dry density. The model is based on the solution of the depth-averaged flow equations and a sediment-mass conservation equation with a slumping failure module to account for channel slope destabilization during breaching. Different bedload transport coefficients, soil porosity, and failure angle are used to model the different breaching of both dams.

Methodology and Results

The numerical model presented here uses a finite-difference approach to integrate the depth-averaged mass and momentum flow equations (Chaudhry 2022) along with sediment-mass conservation equation with a slumping failure module (Elalfy et al. 2018). The slumping failure module is based on a threshold failure angle which allows the breach to widen. The failure angle of biopolymer-treated sand is higher than that of homogenous sand. Laboratory experiments show that in biopolymer-treated sand dams breach evolves only in the vertical direction, while in case of homogenous sand, the breach develops in the vertical and horizontal directions concurrently due to mass destabilizations of breach sides (Czapiga et al. 2024). To account for the lower erodibility of biopolymer-treated sand relative to homogeneous sand, the coefficient of the sediment

transport relation is reduced. Soil porosity is also lower in the case of biopolymer-treated sand as compared to untreated sand due to the formation of a water-biopolymer matrix in the pores (Czapiga et al. 2024).

Figure 1 shows a comparison of simulated breach development at the middle of dam crest for untreated sand dam (Figure 1a) and sand dam treated by biopolymer-sand mixture for the top 5 cm (Figure 1b). The figure clearly shows that the time to erode the sediment till the dam bottom is increased four times in case of the treated dam as compared to the untreated dam. Also, the figure shows that the model can capture the steep breach side slopes in case of the treated dam as compared to the untreated dam.

Figure 1. Time variation of breach development: (a) untreated sand dam, and (b) dam with a 5 cm top layer of biopolymer-treated sand

Conclusions

Breach development in layered earthen dams of optimally compacted non-cohesive sediment covered by a biopolymer-sand mixture can be modeled using the depth-averaged model introduced herein. The model can capture the different breaching behaviors between different layers, as well as the increase in failure time in biopolymer treated dams. The model can be utilized to draw relations between the thickness of different layers and breach characteristics, such as widening rate, deepening rate, breach formation time, breach peak outflow discharge, and downstream flood inundation due to dam failure.

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Post-Processing National Water Model Output to Forecast Water Quality for Management Applications in Diverse Watersheds

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Summary

As water quality monitoring continues to expand globally, freely accessible, process-based forecasting models have improved anticipation of flow events, enabling data-driven models of water quality to be coupled to streamflow projections to forecast water quality at broad scales. Here we develop machine learning (ML) models of water quality in two heterogeneous watersheds in the northeastern USA and combine them with streamflow forecasts from the U.S. National Water Model (NWM). Results suggest that interpretable, flexible ML models forced by NWM outputs can provide robust forecasts of contaminant concentration in a given watershed and enhance process understanding of water quality drivers.

Introduction

Global concerns over water quality impairment have spurred increased consideration, regulation, and management of the concentrations and fluxes of various constituents. As a result, many waterbodies are now closely supervised, and enhanced ability to predict future concentrations and loading across flow events or range of hydrological conditions has substantial utility for the active management of aquatic systems.

One potential avenue to improve predictions of concentration is the construction of higher-order models of concentration (or flux) based on additional parameters beyond simply at-a-point discharge magnitude, the derivation of which can be greatly enhanced by the collection of high-frequency hydrologic and water quality data using field-deployed sensors (Kirchner et al., 2004; Rode et al., 2016). When this type of data is paired with machine learning/artificial intelligence (ML) approaches – unbound by assumptions of linearity inherent in traditional techniques and capable of parsing large quantities of data – enhanced estimation of concentrations and fluxes is possible (Zhong et al., 2021). This is especially true of late: as monitoring networks continue to enrich our ability to predict water quality, enhanced streamflow forecasts such as the U.S. National Water Model (Cosgrove et al., 2024) have become increasingly available and accessible, and the time thus is ripe to leverage these capabilities to produce robust water quality forecasts at actionable spatial and temporal scales (e.g., Wade et al., 2024). This is the approach we have taken here.

In this application, we combine data-driven models of turbidity, phosphorus, and nitrogen with streamflow forecasts from the US National Water Model (NWM), to build forecasts of these constituents in a) a New York City drinking water supply watershed (Esopus Creek) where reservoir operations are frequently impacted by elevated turbidity and b) the large, diverse Lake Champlain watershed, where downstream aquatic ecosystems are often impaired by elevated phosphorus concentrations that drive harmful cyanobacteria blooms. Overall, we aim to demonstrate the capabilities of data-driven models to generate skilful water quality forecasts from the NWM and illustrate the value added when flexible, nonlinear ML approaches are used in addition to more commonly employed extensions of linear techniques.

Methodology and Results

In the Esopus Creek watershed in the Catskill Mountains of southeastern New York, USA, we used hourly streamflow and turbidity data over a seven-year period to build two gradient-boosted decision tree (LightGBM) (Ke et al., 2017) models and compare their performance to a quantile regression quadratic model (Mukundan et

al., 2018). The gradient-boosted models consistently offer improvements for turbidity prediction over the linear quantile method, especially during high flow events, and the more spatially complex ML model may yield better results at longer forecast lead times.

In our second use case, the Lake Champlain basin of Vermont and New York, we used daily streamflow data in combination with various watershed attributes (land-use, topography, etc.) and 30 years of discrete water quality samples to build LightGBM models of total phosphorus, dissolved phosphorus, and total nitrogen for 18 major tributary watersheds. Model performance for total phosphorus scales inversely with forest cover and directly with drainage area and hydrologic peakiness; for dissolved phosphorus, inversely with forest cover and drainage density; and for total nitrogen, directly with hydrologic peakiness. Additionally, watershed-specific models built on hydrological features alone are sometimes more capable of skilful forecasts than a single lumped model trained on hydrological and geospatial data from all basins. Results underscore the value of interpretable ML algorithms like LightGBM for expanding process understanding and again emphasize the capabilities of ML approaches for robust water quality forecasts.

Conclusions

Study findings have both use-case specific and generalizable implications. For the Esopus Creek watershed, interpretation of feature weights within ML models indicates that increased connectivity with glacial legacy deposits catalyzed by large storm events that expose and erode into such deposits can drive elevated turbidity concentrations for a given discharge, underlining the influence of erosional processes in specific sub-basins on catchment-scale turbidity behavior. Additionally, ML models consistently offer improvements for turbidity prediction over linear methods, emphasizing their capabilities as forecasting tools. In the Lake Champlain basin, results indicate that both watershed-specific models and lumped models should be tested to determine the most appropriate model for a given basin. Model skill appears in general to be inversely related to the dynamicity of hydrology (i.e., peakiness), suggesting that water quality in basins where high flow conditions are marked departures from average behavior is harder to predict. Basin-specific models offer improvements over the lumped approach as basins get wetter and less agricultural, suggesting either that harder-to-capture water quality drivers (e.g., seasonal impacts) have a greater influence in wet basins or that monitoring is skewed towards drier, agricultural watersheds. The approach delineated, with flexible, efficient LightGBM models that are readily interpretable, can potentially inform efforts to design and improve models of water quality in basins throughout the country and globe. Taken together, these results clearly demonstrate the broad utility of the NWM as a water quality forecasting tool, which, when coupled with robust long-term or high frequency water quality monitoring data, can provide water quality forecasts at stakeholder relevant timescales across the country. Study findings overall underline the potential to couple any large-scale process-based model to data-driven models to produce robust water quality forecasts for contaminant(s) of concern.

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A Multi-Region, Multi-Year Analysis of Flood Timing, Magnitude, and Severity as Measured Compared to National Water Model Predictions

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Summary

The National Oceanic Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) has been operational since August 2016, providing near real-time continuous hydrologic forecasts across the Continental United States (CONUS). This study evaluates the effectiveness of NWM Version 2.1 in predicting floods from extreme short-duration rainfall across diverse regions and scales within the CONUS for the years 2021-2022. It considers NWM short-range forecast configurations and various lead times. By comparing NWM forecasts with USGS observational streamflow data, the study assesses performance under different temporal and spatial conditions. The insights gained will enhance flood prediction, benefiting both researchers and decision makers.

Introduction

Flooding, a major global hazard, causes significant human and infrastructure loss annually (Balica et al., 2013). Flash floods from intense precipitation are particularly destructive (Zanchetta & Coulibaly, 2020) leaving little time for response (Coelho et al., 2022). Robust real-time flood forecast systems enables taking in-time and effective response measures to prevent or reduce the adverse impacts of such horrific events in at-risk areas (Trošelj et al., 2023). In the United States, the NOAA National Weather Service (NWS) Office of Predictions (OWP) has developed the NWM producing near real-time streamflow forecasts along with the land surface simulations. While existing research has evaluated the NWM's accuracy for retrospective (Abdelkader et al., 2023; Cosgrove et al., 2024; Johnson et al., 2023) and forecast streamflow outputs (Cosgrove et al., 2024; Viterbo et al., 2020), none has conducted a comprehensive assessment of its utility in predicting floods from intense precipitation events. In this study, we aim to assess NWM short-range flood forecast performance across various basin characteristics (landscape and meteorological), lead times, and seasonal variations.

Methodology and Results

We identified 20 major flash flood events in CONUS from 2021-2022, primarily in urban areas. Using the NWM client subpackage from the NOAA OWP hydrotools Python module (Regina & Raney, 2021) to access Google Cloud Bucket data (<https://console.cloud.google.com/marketplace/prod-uct/noaa-public/national-water-model>), we compared NWM historical forecasts with USGS streamflow data, employing performance metrics like modified Kling–Gupta efficiency (KGE). Additionally, we evaluated peak flow magnitude, timing, and their relation with flood forecast lead time. To delineate basins and gather their characteristics, for most watersheds, we utilized the USGS StreamStats Batch Processing Tool. In cases where data was unavailable, an ArcGIS Pro workflow that uses USGS National Map DEM (<https://apps.nationalmap.gov/downloader/>) data was developed. We finally show relation between the basin characteristics and flood forecast performance metrics. The study's workflows are shared as Jupyter notebooks and accessible as a HydroShare resource (Maghami et al., 2024). While the notebooks are mostly complete, final results are pending, anticipated by the conference.

Conclusions

The forthcoming research aims to elucidate the conditions under which the NWM short-range streamflow forecasts exhibit robust performance, thereby instilling trust in their utility for flood forecasting purposes. Conversely, areas where the model demonstrates inadequacy will serve as focal points for future

enhancements. Future investigations will delve into the influence of meteorological forcing inputs, enabling a comprehensive hydrometeorological assessment of forecast accuracy. Moreover, attention will extend to the medium- and long-range flood forecast configurations within the NWM framework, fostering a holistic understanding to advance flood prediction capabilities. While definitive results are pending, these anticipated avenues of inquiry hold promise for both researchers and decision-makers alike.

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A Machine Learning Approach for Enhancing National Water Model Streamflow Forecasts in Montane Headwater Catchments

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Summary

Accurate streamflow predictions are essential for water management activities and flood mitigation. Hydrological forecasting models are crucial in ensuring the reliability of these predictions, however, substantial discrepancies between observed and forecasted streamflow often exist. This study focuses on developing a machine learning correction model to enhance the performance of the National Water Model in predicting streamflow in montane headwater streams. The proposed model offers advantages such as interpretability and ease of use, making it suitable for practical implementation by decision-makers in local communities. Furthermore, insights for its application to forecasts are provided.

Introduction

The National Water Model (NWM; Crosgrove et al., 2024) provides hourly streamflow forecasts across the contiguous United States. Since its creation in 2016, it has gone through several updates improving its performance. However, as evidenced in various studies (Garousi-Nejad and Tarboton, 2021, Johnson et al., 2023, and Abdelkader et al., 2023), discrepancies between observed and forecasted streamflow persist. The NWM has particularly struggled to accurately predict flows in montane headwater settings (Johnson et al., 2019). Montane headwater streams play a crucial role in maintaining water quality, quantity, flood generation, and nutrient mobility. However, they are often overlooked and present challenges for streamflow prediction due to complex topography, highly variable rainfall-runoff patterns, and limited gaging infrastructure to develop and inform models. Inaccurate forecasts in these low-order streams, which cover 70-80% of the river network, can contribute to extensive damage to local communities as illustrated by recent catastrophic floods in Vermont in July of 2023. The NWM coverage of all stream reaches offers significant potential benefits for numerous communities if practical methods can be developed to improve forecast accuracy. ML techniques have the potential to provide more accurate predictions, quicker training and execution times, and the ability to capture nonlinear connections between various factors, showing promise in improving forecasting skills. In particular, physics-informed ML techniques leverage insights from process-based models to enhance the strengths of data-driven ML models, and this approach has been tested in enhancing the NWM (Frame et al., 2021). This study addresses a gap in forecasting by focusing on the NWM's performance in headwater catchments and using an easy-to-implement post-processing correction model that leverages physics-informed ML technique to enhance its accuracy for predicting hourly streamflow – a crucial need for rapid warning, planning and response to floods within these catchments.

Methodology and Results

The NWM retrospective dataset's performance was evaluated in headwater catchments in the northeastern United States and, considering the discrepancies found, a ML correction model was developed to improve NWM performance in predicting hourly streamflow in these low-order streams. The post-processing correction model was developed using a physics-informed Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM; Ke et al., 2017) by combining hourly estimated precipitation from the Analysis of Record for Calibration (AORC) and NWM streamflow estimations with observations of antecedent hourly water-level, daily precipitation, snow depth, snow water equivalent (SWE), maximum temperature, and minimum temperature. This allows the physics

knowledge encoded in the NWM simulation of streamflow to be transferred to our ML correction model through ingesting NWM predictions as one of the inputs. Preliminary results show a dramatic improvement in the model's predictive performance relative to observations based on commonly used metrics such as Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE), Kling-Gupta efficiency (KGE), Pearson correlation, and percent bias. We take the lessons learned from the retrospective case and applied them to develop a general framework that could be applied to improve model performance in medium-range streamflow forecasts. The advantages of this approach allow for practical implementation by decision-makers in local communities and provide an alternative for future operational applications.

Conclusions

The post-processing ML correction model developed dramatically improved hourly streamflow prediction performance relative to observations. Including water level measurements, even from relatively distant sites, greatly improved model performance. This demonstrates the potential to improve forecasts by deploying low-cost water level sensors in ungaged basins of interest, without the need for timely and costly rating curve development. Our study indicates that while the current version of the NWM does not perform particularly well in montane watersheds, hourly streamflow prediction performance can be dramatically enhanced using ML tools and a ML correction model informed by low-cost sensor based monitoring. This approach and the general framework presented for its application in medium-range forecasts offer advantages such as interpretability and ease of use, enabling widespread adoption. The approach outlined here by design is model agnostic and also quite malleable making it suitable for integration into the NextGen framework of the NWM to improve performance as model development continues for the foreseeable future.

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Enhancing LSTM-Based Streamflow Prediction with a Spatially Distributed Approach

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Summary

We introduce the Spatially Recursive (SR) model, that integrates a lumped long short-term memory (LSTM) network seamlessly with a physics-based hydrological routing simulation for enhanced streamflow prediction in large basins. The SR model involves applying the trained LSTM at the subbasin scale for local streamflow predictions which are then translated to the basin outlet by an uncalibrated hydrological routing model. The SR model was able to predict streamflow much more accurately on large testing basins than the LSTM alone. Overall, the SR model demonstrates how to generate accurate LSTM-based streamflow predictions for large basins by considering finer resolution spatial heterogeneity.

Introduction and Methodology

Lumped LSTM models of streamflow predictions have shown excellent and typically superior performance to process-based, traditional hydrological models (e.g., see Kratzert et al., 2018; Arsenault et al., 2023; Mai et al., 2022). Although studies such as Mai et al. (2022) show that lumped LSTMs can produce superior quality hydrographs for small basins, typically for most basins less than 2000 km², they often struggle to generate realistic hydrographs on the largest basins in the study.

Our study highlighted here (Yu et al., 2024) aims to identify a generalizable, regional-scale, easy-to-implement methodology to utilize spatially-distributed inputs to improve upon lumped data-driven streamflow prediction in large ungauged basins. Our proposed Spatially Recursive (SR) model first employs a lumped data-driven prediction model (regionally-trained on a large sample of basins) to predict local streamflow at subbasins discretized from the basin of interest. Then, it utilizes a semi-distributed hydrologic routing-only model, capable of explicit lake simulation, to route subbasin streamflow to the basin outlet. The data-driven prediction model is considered spatially recursive because it is trained at the basin scale and further re-applied at the smaller subbasin scale to incorporate finer-resolution forcing data and subbasin attributes.

The lumped LSTM was trained on the basin-averaged meteorological and hydrological variables in the Great Lakes region of North America following the approach and case study watersheds in Mai et al. (2022). The lumped LSTM component of the SR model is the only trained or calibrated part of the SR model. The LSTM was trained using 141 calibration basins while the testing of the LSTM and the SR model was conducted via spatial validation and spatio-temporal validation on 71 other basins. In addition, 8 new large basins were added to the testing dataset that were never simulated before by the lumped LSTM model or the SR model.

Results and Conclusions

The SR model exhibits substantial streamflow prediction improvements in large basins (>2000 km²). The performance improvement over the lumped LSTM is most significant in a prediction in ungauged basins context. For the 15 large validation basins in Mai et al. (2022), the median KGE levels over the 10-year training period (spatial validation) and the 7-year testing period (spatio-temporal validation), are 0.11 and 0.08 KGE units higher, respectively, than those of the lumped LSTM. Out-of-sample testing of the SR model in 8 additional large basins (2343 km² to 6760 km²) showed that the SR model was substantially better than the lumped LSTM for 7 of 8 basins by an average of 0.16 KGE units, over the 17-year period. Additional new tests beyond Yu et al. (2024) also demonstrate the advantages of the SR model for prediction in large basins.

Our SR modelling approach is novel in three important ways. First, it considers the spatial variability of input variables by having smaller response units than the lumped LSTM training dataset. Second, it integrates a physically-based lake and river hydrological routing approach with data-driven learning to form a demonstrated generalizable (regional) modelling approach for improved streamflow prediction in large basins not used in training. Finally, it functions without the need for further fine-tuning, parameter transfer, or training/calibration, given the trained lumped LSTM is available.

Acknowledgements

All code used to implement and validate the models will be available in a dedicated GitHub repository (<https://github.com/glenyuyuyu/SR-LSTM>). The GRIP-GL calibration data are made available on the Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR; <https://doi.org/10.20383/103.0598>) and the access procedure for GRIP-GL validation data is also described there. The BasinMaker library used here for lake and river routing network delineation from Han et al. (2023) is available at <https://hydrology.uwaterloo.ca/basinmaker/>. The Raven hydrologic modelling framework (Craig et al., 2021) used as the hydrological routing model is available at <https://raven.uwaterloo.ca>. This research has been supported by an Environment and Climate Change Canada G&C grant and a Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada Discovery grant to the first author, as well as the Global Water Futures (GWF) Project.

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Analysis of Baseflow Signatures and Streamflow Error Metrics Across CONUS Using an Optimized Digital Filter

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Summary

In this study, we estimated baseflow for 1,462 reference-quality gages across CONUS using a digital filter method with a single input parameter, β . We fine-tuned the β parameter by evaluating the estimated baseflow values from the digital filter against the time series of the 10th non-exceedance probability of streamflow for each Julian day. We then computed the average monthly baseflow index (BFI, the baseflow proportion of total streamflow) for each gage and performed clustering analysis on these signatures. The clustering analysis identified 11 distinct BFI trends across CONUS. We also demonstrated how clusters of baseflow correspond to predictive ability of streamflow prediction models across CONUS and the Colorado River Basin.

Introduction

Groundwater and surface water are interconnected in most climatic regions. Baseflow, the contribution of streamflow not directly associated with precipitation forcing, is a critical component of streamflow prediction and water resource allocation. Baseflow is often considered to be a low-frequency component of streamflow and many of the methods for estimating it are based on this premise.

Baseflow estimates are often presented as annual averages. However, we know that many of the factors indirectly or directly contributing to baseflow (i.e., precipitation, snowmelt, surface runoff, groundwater levels, etc.) vary seasonally and, thus, the contribution of baseflow to total streamflow is expected to vary as well. Rigorous estimates of baseflow on a fine temporal scale may prove crucial to improving streamflow model estimates, especially for streamflow models such as the National Water Model (NWM) that make daily predictions.

Methodology and Results

We estimated baseflow using a version of the digital filter proposed by Nathan and McMahon (1990). The filter has only one input parameter, β , which determines the intensity of the filtering effect. While a recommended range for values of β exists, a method for systematically determining an appropriate value for β is critical because of the significant effect the parameter has on the resulting baseflow estimate and BFI.

To estimate β , we applied a Variable Threshold Method (VTM) to daily streamflow records for 1,462 reference quality gages across the CONUS from the USGS GAGES-II data set; each gage contained at least 20 years of complete daily streamflow measurements. The VTM approach applies a non-exceedance percentile (NEP) computed based on the distribution of flow recorded at a stream gage over a given time frame (i.e., daily, monthly, seasonally) throughout the complete record of measurement. We computed the 10th NEP for each Julian Day at all 1,462 gages and used optimization to determine a value for β that resulted in the minimal error between the filtered baseflow and the daily 10th NEP flow values.

The results indicate that an appropriate value for β depends on the characteristics of the streamflow timeseries being analyzed. Trends in baseflow and BFI vary across CONUS; some gages exhibit consistent BFI values throughout the year, while others show considerable seasonal fluctuations in BFI. K-Means clustering revealed that the BFI trends fall into 11 unique clusters.

To explore potential links between streamflow prediction error metrics and BFI trends identified through clustering, we began by examining the model error metrics of the National Water Model (NWM) for gages

across CONUS and comparing them with BFI trends at those gages. Afterward, we conducted a similar analysis of the model error metrics of the USGS streamflow prediction model for gages in the Colorado River Basin. Initial findings suggested that baseflow may be impacting the predictive performance of both models.

Conclusions

This study developed a method for estimating baseflow at a daily time step using a digital filter optimized based on long-term streamflow records at a large set of gages. Clusters formed from monthly average BFI signatures show considerably different trends and seasonality. Clusters generally show strong regionalization across CONUS. Some clusters show strong seasonal fluctuations and others show almost no seasonal variation, which may be linked to the climatic and physiographic attributes of the drainage basin and region. This suggests that rigorous estimates of baseflow may be critical to accuracy of streamflow predictions in some regions, and less critical in others.

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CIROH 2: Data and hydroinformatics advances in the U.S. National Water Model and large scale modeling systems

Design and Implementation of a Big Query Dataset and Application Programmer Interface (API) for the U.S. National Water Model

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Summary

We introduce an open-source web-based Application Programming Interface (API) developed within a representational state transfer (REST) architecture framework that provides access to the operational streamflow forecasts from the U.S. National Water Model (NWM). We built this API within the Google Cloud infrastructure, taking advantage of Google's API Gateway, BigQuery, and Google Cloud Run. We ran a data transformation from netCDF to tabular formation then ingested data into BigQuery using Apache Beam parallel processing technology. The API activates functions deployed to a Cloud Run server instance that executes SQL queries within the BigQuery data warehouse. The API gives users granular control to specify queries based on forecast type, reference datetime, stream segment specifics, and forecast ensemble members. This API greatly simplifies access and use of current and historic NWM forecasts, an otherwise arduous task due to the large volume of data and unwieldy storage methods. Retrieved forecast data can be used for many critical water management applications providing actionable intelligence for, e.g., flood management, safety, recreation, agriculture, and related uses.

Introduction

The U.S. National Water Model (NWM) (Cosgrove et al., 2024) is a hydrologic modeling framework developed by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) at the National Water Center in Tuscaloosa, Alabama. The NWM simulates streamflow across the continental United States (CONUS), southern Alaska, Hawaii, Puerto Rico, and the U.S. Virgin Islands. The NWM provides comprehensive streamflow forecasts by mathematically modeling various processes such as rainfall, snowmelt, infiltration, water movement through soil layers, overland flow, and river routing. This complex model accounts for factors like elevation, soil types, vegetation, and other variables that influence streamflow. Our objective in this work was to research, design, develop, and deploy a comprehensive cloud-based data workflow that manages and provides tools to effectively use the terabytes of operational forecast data generated by the NWM.

Methodology and Results

We took advantage of Google's BigQuery cloud database to restructure the data into a queryable dataset and to design and implement a REST-based API for querying and retrieving these operational forecast data. We processed the NWM NetCDF file data into a tabular format, then stored the tabular data in a Parquet file format on Google Cloud Storage and in Google BigQuery in long-table format. We used Apache Beam, an open-source tool for parallel data processing pipelines that simplifies large-scale data processing dynamics, to define the transformation pipeline. We used the Google internal execution engine Flume to run the processing pipeline. We selected the Parquet file format to store the data because it is open source, good at storing large volumes of data, is efficient for analytical queries, and is easily ingested directly into BigQuery. The Parquet files are written to Cloud Storage where users can directly access the data. BigQuery has a serverless architecture with distributed analytical processing that facilitates queries and processing of terabytes of data in seconds and petabytes in minutes using a Structured Query Language (SQL) interface. By storing the NWM data in a structured table format

rather than the raw NetCDF format, the data is made accessible using various queries based on logical filters (e.g., reach ID and time) and returned in a time series format, rather than users accessing spatial formatted data where large number of files are needed to be read and queried for processing, scientific analysis, or to be used for additional services.

We also developed a cloud-based service that provides a REST API to facilitate easy access to the NWM datasets for researchers and other software systems. We built the REST API with functions and processes to query and access publicly available NWM datasets stored in BigQuery tables. The API provides common data access patterns using simple HTTP requests rather than complex SQL queries typically required to access and select data in large databases. We wrote the API server using the FastAPI framework which acts as the service that manages user requests and dispatching queries to BigQuery. We packaged the FastAPI server as a Docker container image for easy deployment and dependency management. The service is deployed on Cloud Run, a serverless compute platform that enables the execution of containers. We used Google's API Gateway service as the authentication and management layer for the API. When contacted by the client, the API Gateway directs the request to the Cloud Run service and returns the results to the user or client. For deployment, we use Google Cloud Build to automatically build and deploy the Docker image. We deployed Google's Artifact Registry service to store the resulting built Docker Image and the container on Cloud Run.

Conclusions

The results of a benchmarking process illustrate the efficiency of leveraging the reformatted data for the different queries in the benchmark. Using the original NetCDF files and reading them natively from cloud storage, like how a user might do on a local machine, is the least efficient across all queries. Using technologies like Kerchunk along with the original NetCDF data improves speed compared to the native file access, however, this pattern is still less efficient compared to using the transformed Parquet files and BigQuery. Accessing the data using Parquet and DuckDB showed improvements over using NetCDF whereas accessing the data using BigQuery or the API was the most efficient. Accessing the data via the API or directly on BigQuery provides significant performance gains compared to traditional methods used to access the NWM data.

The API accesses the data directly on BigQuery which consistently yielded the most efficient query time across the different methods. The query runtimes were consistent across the different methods with a mean runtime of around 2.5s for each, no matter which query was run. This shows that different types of queries do not affect performance, they all run in about the same amount of time. While the API and BigQuery times were comparable, there was a slight increase in runtime (less than 0.5s) with using the API. This is most likely caused by authentication through the API gateway, URL routing of the API, and/or logic to transform results into formats requested.

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Data Acquisition Framework Design for Environmental Modelling Input Data

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Summary

Thoughtful construction of data acquisition and preparation workflows for environmental model input data allows for greater flexibility in future research directions, quicker and more efficient changes between input datasets, and enables code reuse. This work presents a modular data acquisition framework that supports hydrological and meteorological data acquisition from several observation and forecast products for use in water resources forecasting applications. The framework organizes acquired data in a standardized data structure which can then be written out to model-specific input formats making the framework generalizable to future modelling efforts.

Introduction

Writing modelling workflows that are tightly integrated with specific input data sources often results in an operational modelling system relatively quickly. However, future delays can then develop when (1) additional / different input data sources need to be explored or (2) the core model is replaced and input data has to be formatted to a different model. Alternatively, the use of modular software components designed to standardize data acquisition from a diversity of sources makes the modelling workflow more flexible, easing the implementation of future changes to the workflow and thus preventing these future delays.

Modular software development can be a higher upfront investment in terms of time and energy but yields payoffs of reduced effort and coding time in the long-term (Baldwin & Clark, 2000; Clemins, Turnbull, Rodgers & Zia, 2020; Knoben et al, 2022). In the context of environmental modelling, this trade-off is worthwhile if a researcher intends to run a given model with many configurations. This is because any given model usually requires a variety of structured input data and these data must be aggregated and processed from individually unique sources. Despite the field's best efforts at standardizing meteorological and hydrological data formats (i.e. GRIB, NetCDF), in practice, these data almost always require significant pre-processing before they are ready to be utilized by a model. This pre-processing commonly includes standardizing sampling rates, time zones, variable units, and data structures. While manageable for a single model configuration, these data pre-processing tasks can become prohibitively extensive as the complexity of an experiment increases. For instance, when a researcher wants to run a variety of environmental models with inputs provided by the same set of data sources, or conversely, run a single model iteratively with differing data sources, the task of formatting data for such experiments can become untenable for many researchers. In these cases, pursuing modularity becomes a necessary goal.

Methodology and Results

We designed our data acquisition modules based on two central principles: (1) each module should return data in a readable, standardized data structure, and (2) each module should have the same generalized parameters. With these design principles in mind, we built Python modules to fetch and process meteorological and hydrological data from five unique data sources. Meteorological sources include the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Association (NOAA) Global Forecast System (GFS), the NOAA Local Climatological Dataset (LCD), and the Forest Ecosystem Monitoring Cooperative (FEMC) Quality-Controlled Colchester Reef Meteorological Data. Hydrological data sources include the NOAA National Water Model (NWM) and the United States Geological Survey (USGS) Instantaneous Values Service (IVS). These sources were chosen based on the needs of researchers funded under the Cooperative Institute for Research to Operations in Hydrology (CIROH) at UVM.

Initially, researchers requested assistance acquiring data from these sources, and in many cases, provided initial code for us to adapt and build upon. We then modified these crowdsourced code fragments into a standardized function within each module, one for each data source. Each of these functions share the same basic structure; they load the data given the provided parameters, process the data to isolate the desired variables and standardize time series indices, and then restructure the data into a consistent format. Exactly how much data to load, which variables to isolate, and other specifications are determined by a standardized set of function parameters. Fundamentally, these parameters include start and end datetimes, locations at which to return data, and variables of interest. Based on how data is made available for a given data source, additional optional parameters are necessary for certain modules. Modules that provide raw data files for downloading, such as GFS and NWM, implement a directory parameter so that a user can specify where the data should be stored. Modules that access data via an API, such as IVS or LCD, can load data directly into a Python data structure without having to use local system storage. The FEMC module requires a hybrid of these approaches; FEMC provides a dynamically updated and downloadable CSV file with the last thirty days of data that is then merged with a locally cached CSV containing historical data.

The consistent structure of our data acquisition modules makes reconfiguring data sources within a modeling workflow expeditious and efficient. Our work was integral to the launch of an experiment designed to investigate the accuracy of an harmful algal bloom forecast system across a number of model configurations. Fourteen different model configurations, using a variety of datasets for model inputs, were evaluated. Because of our modular data acquisition workflow, we were able to configure and launch the experimental runs in a fraction of the time it would have taken to reconfigure the model inputs manually for each run, thus significantly decreasing the time to complete the experiment.

Conclusions

This modular data acquisition workflow has allowed our researchers to broaden the scope of their model experiments by enabling them to cleanly and efficiently interchange a model's sources of meteorological and hydrological data. This workflow has already saved dozens of hours of work that would normally be required to rewrite a typical data acquisition script to fit new model inputs. This workflow is robust to future changes as well, such as the need to acquire new data sources or to change the variables of interest for a current data source.

In the future, we will continue to improve the modularity of these current data acquisition modules by expanding the range of locations and variables that each module supports. In addition, as new modules for additional data sources are requested, we will continue to build new acquisition modules that follow the same design structure described here. By providing accessible and standardized methods of data acquisition, we are making progress towards our goal of improving the efficiency and pace of environmental research and modelling.

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Simulating Water and Air Flow in Stormwater Networks

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Summary

Flow in stormwater networks can be complex due to the interaction between water and air above water level. In this study, an unsteady flow model that accounts for the presence of air in stormwater mains headspace and air shafts is tested against field data from the literature. The model employs the finite-difference Lax-diffusive scheme for water flow calculations and three different compressibility methods for airflow simulation. The comparison between model results and field data shows that the model can be used to simulate main pressurization in the real world. Future research could focus on optimizing air shaft design based on these findings.

Introduction

Stormwater networks usually comprise pipes, tunnels and open-channel sections for water conveyance and air shafts for ventilation. Studying the interaction between water and air flows in stormwater systems has critical operational implications for various issues such as pipe bursts and corrosion, manhole geysers, control of noise and odor resulting from airflow in tunnels and through air vents, and displacement of manhole covers. Proper management of such issues is critical to guaranteeing and improving the safety and efficiency of stormwater networks.

Most stormwater models do not fully integrate water and air calculations nor consider air compressibility, which is critical for pressurization during floods. This work tests an integrated model called CHANNEL (Computer Applications, 2002) that simulates the concurrent spatiotemporal variability of water flow and airflow in stormwater mains against field data. The model can handle dendritic networks, considering a main channel with incoming and/or outgoing channels, and includes a comprehensive set of intermediate and end boundary conditions such as gates, weirs, reservoirs, and inflow and outflow hydrographs. Mains pressurization is modeled with Preissmann slot if the water flow exceeds pipe conveyance capacity. Three methods are used to simulate airflow in terms of its compressibility: incompressible, pseudo-compressible, and compressible.

Methodology and Results

CHANNEL is a one-dimensional (1D) model that accounts for changes in water flow and airflow conditions. The model first reads the input file containing information on network configuration, that is data on the main channel, branching channels, and air shaft number, size, and location. The same input file also contains data on initial water levels and channel geometry. Boundary conditions may be specified in terms of fixed-head reservoirs, sluice gates, weirs, and inflow and outflow hydrographs. The model solves the 1D Saint-Venant equations to calculate unsteady water depths using the explicit finite-difference Lax-diffusive scheme within a prespecified simulation time while satisfying Courant condition for stability in each time step. The model uses Preissmann slot method by prespecifying a fixed value for slot width in the input file to handle mains pressurization.

CHANNEL calculates air volume above the water depths in selected tunnels to obtain air pressure, velocity, and flow direction. Three options are available for such airflow calculations. The first handles air as an incompressible fluid with a fixed density and gets air velocity and pressure directly from the updated air volume difference between each two subsequent time steps. The second is a pseudo-compressible treatment of airflow by computing 1) air velocity and direction in terms of the difference between modeled and incompressible air pressure while assuming subsonic airflow only and 2) changes in air mass and the corresponding pressure, considering the coefficient of air shaft discharge and following the ideal gas assumption. The third method comprehensively describes air compressibility by defining airflow status according to the ratio between modeled

and atmospheric air pressure. It depicts four statuses for airflow: i) choked inflow when this ratio is less than 0.53, ii) subsonic inflow when the ratio lies between 0.53 and 1.00, iii) subsonic outflow when the ratio lies between 1.00 and 1.89, and iv) choked outflow when the ratio is more than 1.89. An iterative correction is made to the modeled air mass and pressure value until a prespecified tolerance for the pressure correction is reached. Afterward, airflow velocity is calculated with respect to final air mass and pressure.

The model is validated using the measured air pressure in one of the air shafts located in the middle of the sewer trunk in Edmonton City, Alberta, Canada. Preliminary results show that simulated compressible airflow most agreed with measured air pressure, while incompressible and pseudo-compressible flow could not track air pressure variation (Fig. 1). The simulated compressible air pressure can capture most of the highest and lowest pressure timings with a mean error of ± 0.05 Psi in pressure values.

Figure 1. Variation of simulated and measured air pressure in air shaft T5 located in the sewer trunk of the southwest area of Edmonton City, Alberta, Canada, from June 16 to June 22, 2016

Conclusions

The comparison between results of the unsteady flow model CHANNEL that explicitly accounts for the interaction between water and air in mains headspace is presented. Three methods are used to describe the compressibility of air. These methods were compared to field data from the literature, and a good agreement was found between the field measures and simulation results for the fully compressible airflow only, while the incompressible and pseudo-compressible airflow methods could not trace air pressure variations. Further work may include applying the developed model to other real-world stormwater networks and optimizing the design of the size, number, and location of air shafts along such networks.

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FloodSim Sandbox: Leveraging Realtime Fluid Simulation in Flood Visualization

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Summary

Urban flooding remains a critical challenge, yet there is a significant gap in accessible tools that can both educate and facilitate research on effective mitigation strategies. Addressing this gap, FloodSim Sandbox utilizes Unreal Engine along with plugins like Fluid Flux and Skycreator to provide a simulation environment for both educational and research purposes. It offers an interactive experience where users can explore flood dynamics and mitigation strategies through. The platform serves as a testbed for validating flood models, featuring real-time simulation, intuitive interfaces, and damage estimations. This dual-purpose tool aims to enhance learning and contribute to urban flood resilience research.

Introduction

The integration of immersive technologies in educational settings has been recognized for its potential to enhance learning through increased engagement and interaction (Sermet & Demir, 2020; Bower et al., 2014). Particularly in the domain of environmental education, the use of serious games and simulations has been shown to offer rich, experiential learning environments that can significantly impact learners' understanding and preparedness for real-world challenges, like natural disasters (Sermet & Demir, 2022). FloodSim Sandbox utilizes advanced simulation and visualization technologies to provide a realistic and interactive experience of flood scenarios. This application aligns with cognitive theories suggesting that multimodal learning environments enhance the processing of information and facilitate deeper learning. Moreover, the importance of visualizing complex data such as spatial flood risk predictions has been emphasized in geographical information science, highlighting the need for tools that can simplify and convey intricate data to users effectively (Ahlqvist et al., 2015). By enabling users to manipulate and observe flood dynamics and mitigation strategies within a simulated urban environment, FloodSim Sandbox aims to foster a comprehensive understanding of flood impacts, echoing the educational potential of innovative, interactive learning tools.

Methodology and Results

FloodSim Sandbox was developed using Unreal Engine 5.3.2 to create an immersive simulation environment tailored for both educational and research purposes. The core simulation functionality is powered by the Fluid Flux plugin, which facilitates real-time fluid dynamics simulations within a detailed model of Iowa City. The simulation environment is further enhanced with visual elements controlled via a user interface, including adjustable factors such as simulation time of day, fog intensity, and precipitation. These elements, while primarily aesthetic, contribute to a more immersive user experience without affecting the hydrological accuracy of the simulation.

The user interface is designed to be intuitive, providing users with the ability to interact with the simulation dynamically. Users can input specific volumes of water to simulate flood events, and control the simulation through functions like play, pause, and reset, allowing detailed inspection of flood scenarios as they unfold. This direct manipulation of the simulation parameters is crucial for both educational demonstrations and research experiments.

The urban environment within the simulation is constructed using data imported from ESRI's CityEngine, enriched with metadata from OpenStreetMap (OSM). This integration allows for a realistic representation of

Iowa City, where buildings within the simulation are not only visually accurate but also interactive. Users can click on individual buildings to view relevant metadata in a screen-rendered information panel, which includes data such as building usage, structural details, and historical value.

A significant feature of FloodSim Sandbox is its capability to estimate property damage due to flooding. This is achieved by a component attached to each building model that reads the local simulation water height and compares it to the physical height of the building within the simulation. The relative water height is then used to calculate potential damage by applying a ratio to the building's pre-assigned property value. These individual damage estimates are aggregated to provide a comprehensive view of the financial impact of the flood event across the entire simulated city area.

Conclusions

FloodSim Sandbox adeptly merges the realms of education and research through a sophisticated simulation platform that offers in-depth insights into flood dynamics and urban flood mitigation strategies. The tool provides a realistic and controllable environment tailored to the needs of both learners and researchers. The application's detailed and interactive simulation environment enhances user engagement and learning by allowing manipulation of flood parameters and observing the resultant impacts in a digital twin. This hands-on approach aids in the comprehension of complex flood dynamics and the effectiveness of various mitigation strategies, aligning with educational theories that emphasize active learning and engagement for deeper understanding. Moreover, the tool's capacity to simulate detailed flood scenarios and generate actionable data supports its application in urban planning and disaster management research. By providing a platform where theoretical models can be tested and refined based on empirical data and visual feedback, FloodSim Sandbox contributes significantly to the advancement of knowledge in flood risk management and urban resilience planning.

In conclusion, FloodSim Sandbox demonstrates substantial potential to both educate and advance scientific understanding in the field of urban flooding. Moving forward, continued evaluation and development of this tool are essential to maximize its educational impact and to further enhance its capabilities as a research instrument for supporting resilient urban planning against flooding challenges. Further studies and collaborations are recommended to explore its scalability and applicability in different urban contexts and to integrate more comprehensive environmental factors into the simulation.

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The Canadian Lake and River Hydrofabric v1.0

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Summary

We produce a high-resolution, vector-based lake and river routing GIS product over Canada called the Canadian Lake and River Hydrofabric (CLRH). The CLRH supplies all the necessary spatially distributed hydrological routing model inputs, including network topology, subbasin geometry, channel characteristics, and lake characteristics. All lakes in Canada that are 10 ha and greater in surface area are fully integrated into CLRH allowing for their explicit representation in hydrological models. A key aspect of CLRH is the inclusion of various types of points of interest that are included as explicit subbasin outlets and these include national and provincial hydrometric stations as well as some USGS stations and points along the international border between Canada and the United States.

Introduction and Methodology

Except for some of the largest lakes in a watershed, lakes are often not explicitly simulated in hydrologic modelling studies. This is presumably due to the difficulty in integrating them into the drainage network. The CLRH and the preceding work by Han et al. (2023) to create software for delineating routing networks with lakes correctly alleviate this difficulty.

The core of CLRH is a Pan-Canadian, enhanced 30 m flow direction raster (FDR) recently developed by Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC) that aligns mapped flow directions from Natural Resources Canada's National Hydro Network with DEM-derived flow directions. The target ECCC hydrometric station drainage area polygons we aimed to match as precisely as possible (and discretize further) are available at <https://collaboration.cmc.ec.gc.ca/cmc/hydrometrics/www/HydrometricNetworkBasinPolygons/>.

Lake polygons and data for CLRH are from the HydroLakes database (Messenger et al., 2016). The BasinMaker library is the basis for the lake and river routing network delineation workflow (Han et al., 2023). CLRH production required some BasinMaker updates. We compare the superior quality of CLRH to other global hydrofabrics or global datasets that provide WSC hydrometric station drainage areas.

Results and Conclusions

The open access CLRH is archived in ESRI-shapefile format and can be downloaded by hydrometric gauge ID using a convenient online map interface (<https://hydrology.uwaterloo.ca/CLRH/Hydrofabric.html>). In addition, a set of cloud-based Python GIS post-processing tools are available for customizing the resolution of the hydrometric station routing networks.

All Water Survey of Canada (WSC) hydrometric stations with drainage area boundaries updated by Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC) in 2022/2023 (7000+ stations) are included as explicit subbasin outlets in CLRH. The vast majority of active WSC hydrometric stations are delineated in the CLRH to have drainage areas within 0.1% of ECCC's pre-release hydrometric station polygons drainage areas. Hundreds of provincially operated hydrometric stations and hundreds of United States Geological Survey (USGS) hydrometric stations close to the international border are also included as subbasin outlets in CLRH. While the CLRH delineated area includes small parts of the United States along the international border, CLRH includes almost 1000 points of interest along the international border to enable the intelligent stitching together of

CLRH with any US-based hydrofabric covering the continental US. The resultant hydrofabric has nearly 500,000 lakes explicitly represented and an average subbasin area of just under 5 km².

The CLRH provides an excellent starting point for studies in Canada interested in lake and river network connectivity or watershed delineation and discretization and does so without requiring complex geospatial data processing. Importantly, the discretization explicitly includes all lakes over 10 ha in surface area, thus opening up the ability to integrate the new SWOT satellite mission lake monitoring data into hydrologic models. Our BasinMaker software in Han et al. (2023) enables users to simplify and customize the routing network to lower resolutions and even better, a set of cloud-based Python GIS post-processing tools enabling this functionality is also available. Both of these tools also provide users the ultimate flexibility in extracting their watershed(s) of interest as well as a function that directly translates extracted (and simplified) CLRH network ESRI-shapefiles into the corresponding Raven Hydrological Modelling Framework software (Craig et al., 2020) input files.

Acknowledgements

The BasinMaker library used here for lake and river routing network delineation from Han et al. (2023) is available at <https://hydrology.uwaterloo.ca/basinmaker/>. This research has been supported by Environment and Climate Change Canada G&C grants to Dr James Craig.

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Development and evaluation of surrogate models using machine learning to emulate results of calibrated process models

Process-Based Aggregation Reduces Dimensionality and Enables Surrogate Model Development: An Application to Wildfire Simulation Modelling

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Summary

We use process-based aggregation to reduce the dimensionality of spatial inputs and enable the development of surrogate models that can predict burn probability (a measure of wildfire risk). A surrogate model developed using these aggregated inputs was highly accurate (+/- 10% MAE) in an Australian case study, much more computationally efficient than the original simulation model (0.6% computational run time) and offered insights into how the process-based aggregated inputs affect burn probability across different spatial scales. The computationally efficient surrogate model can be used in computationally demanding studies, such as uncertainty analysis and optimisation of decision making for risk reduction.

Introduction

Wildfires can be destructive processes that pose significant and increasing risks to communities and the environment. Managing wildfire risk is often supported using computational wildfire risk models that can quantify risk and evaluate the effectiveness of different management strategies (Parisien et al., 2019).

Wildfire risk models typically involve simulating many thousands of wildfire events using fire event simulation models. These many fire events correspond to the many different locations from which a wildfire ignition may occur, and the different weather conditions under which a fire may spread. Unfortunately, using fire event simulation models in this way is computationally expensive, even for generating a single map of burn probability estimates.

For this reason, practitioners currently have limited ability to explore the uncertainties in burn probability that stem from modelling choices or test different strategies of landscape management that may help to reduce wildfire risk.

Developing surrogate models presents an opportunity to overcoming the computational expense of traditional wildfire risk models. However, as fire event simulation models represent fire spread using high resolution inputs (e.g., 30 m² raster inputs) across large areas (> 100,000,000 m²), the input dimensionality of burn probability models is very large (i.e. 100, 000s of inputs), which restricts our ability to develop surrogate models. While aggregation is a common approach for reducing input dimensionality (Castelletti et al., 2012), surrogate models have not been developed to predict burn probability before and so no guidance for aggregation exists in the context of emulating burn probability.

Methodology and Results

To overcome challenges of dimensionality and develop surrogate models that can emulate burn probability outputs, we introduce and use a process-based approach to aggregate spatial inputs in a way that allows artificial neural network (ANN) surrogate models to capture and represent patterns in fire spread and burn probability.

The process-based aggregation of inputs involves transforming raw model inputs into representative measures of fire spread (e.g., potential rate of spread or intensity) and then spatially aggregating these measures using “neighbourhood” regions (Radford et al., 2024) which are defined relative to (i) the position at which burn probability is to be predicted, and (ii) the prevailing wind direction, which governs the dominant direction of fire spread. Several neighbourhood sizes and shapes represent different possible scales of fire spread, for example,

longer, narrower neighbourhoods represent fire spread over larger distances under more severe conditions and/or shorter, more circular neighbourhoods represent fire spread over smaller distances.

An input variable selection algorithm is used to identify which neighbourhood-aggregated inputs are most uniquely relevant to representing burn probability, and these inputs are used to develop a surrogate model using ANNs that can predict burn probability.

The surrogate model, calibrated for a case study in the Adelaide Hills & Fleurieu regions of South Australia, can predict burn probability within +/- 10% Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and achieves this prediction of burn probability with a fraction of the computational effort (0.6% of the computational run time) when compared with simulation-based models. To achieve this, the surrogate model uses only 17 inputs which have been aggregated using neighbourhoods, suggesting that the process-based aggregation for reducing dimensionality was extremely successful.

Our interrogation of the ANN's structure suggests that the relationships captured between fire spread across different spatial neighbourhood scales and the resulting burn probability are structurally valid. Furthermore, the relationships captured in the ANN structure provide evidence to support theories of multi-scaled, contagious and emergent patterns of wildfire likelihood (Newman et al., 2019).

Given that the surrogate model is both computationally efficient and accurate, it can be used in problem contexts that require many evaluations of burn probability that were infeasible using the original simulation-based models. For example, the surrogate model can be used in optimisation algorithms to identify effective landscape management strategies for reducing wildfire spread. These types of real-world use cases present opportunities for the surrogate modelling approach to improve the way that society manages landscapes and balances trade-offs associated with wildfire risk.

Conclusions

We propose process-based approaches to aggregating spatial inputs in a way that reduces input dimensionality and enables surrogate modelling of the burn probability outputs of fire simulation models. The reduction in the input dimensionality of the fire simulation models achieved by the process-based aggregation was significant (in the order of 10, 000 times) and the resulting surrogate model was both accurate (+/- 10% MAE) and computationally efficient (0.6% runtime) when evaluated against the original fire simulation model in the South Australian case study area.

While surrogate modelling is new in the space of wildfire risk modelling, we believe that surrogate models offer significant opportunity to improve the way in which wildfire risks are managed. Further work will improve the application of surrogate models to wildfires, but we believe that this work holds valuable findings that may be translated to other fields of surrogate modelling affected by the challenge of high spatial input dimensionality.

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A Machine Learning-Based System for Incorporating Air Quality Assessment in Integrated Assessment Models

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Summary

Air quality impacts from climate policies is an important yet under-addressed part of integrated assessment modelling. From a set of high-fidelity global air quality model simulations, we train a machine learning model to emulate the response of ozone and PM_{2.5} to changes in air pollutant emissions, atmospheric CH₄ level and climate (parameterized as atmospheric CO₂ level). Combining with an existing pollutant emission model (TAPS), our system can rapidly translate global changes in sector-specific fuel usages and CO₂ level into spatially resolved changes in air quality outcomes, which can be used to estimate the corresponding effects on public health and economy.

Introduction

Climate policies do not only contribute to climate mitigation, but also improve air quality since greenhouse gases are often co-emitted with air pollutants (e.g. NO_x, SO_x). Air quality impacts from any policy interventions are typically studied by applying pollutant emissions from counterfactual scenarios to air quality models, from which the changes in pollutant concentration can be simulated and applied to estimate the impacts on public health metrics (e.g. premature mortality, morbidity). Such changes directly affect economic dynamics through pathways like healthcare cost and labor availability, which warrant the use of integrated assessment models (Nam et al., 2010).

The air quality co-benefits from climate change mitigation are relatively well-researched, and often found to be comparable with climate mitigation cost (Karlsson et al., 2020). Despite their importance, however, air quality has yet to be a routine part of climate-related integrated assessments. Air quality modelling has significant barrier of entry due to skill and computing power requirements, which motivates the development of reduced-form air quality models (Van Dingenen et al., 2018).

Current reduced-form air quality models are highly linearized and do not account for the direct effect of climate change on air quality. Under typical global change scenarios, climate and pollutant emissions change simultaneously and interact with each other, potentially invalidating the underlying assumptions of the linearization since the chemistry of secondary air pollutant formation is non-linear. In addition, translating outputs from integrated assessment models (e.g. fuel consumption changes) to a format digestible for air quality models is not trivial. These motivate us to build a modern, user-friendly, accurate and computationally efficient air quality modelling workflow specifically tailored towards global integrated assessments.

Methodology and Results

Figure 1. Description of the proposed workflow

We draw from a previously-developed tool (TAPS) (Atkinson et al., 2022) to translate integrated assessment model output into air pollutant emissions. Here we focus on describing the machine learning model emulating the response of O_3 and $PM_{2.5}$ levels to changes in air pollutant emissions (SO_2 , NO_x , NH_3 , Black Carbon (BC), Organic Carbon (OC), Non-Methane Volatile Organic Compounds (NMVOC) and CO), atmospheric CH_4 level and climate. We generate training data from a set of 120 perturbation experiments of a state-of-the-art global air quality model (GEOS-Chem High Performance, GCHP), following a Latin Hypercube design. At each perturbation experiment, different scaling factors are applied to individual pollutants (0 to 2) and atmospheric CH_4 level (0.5 to 2.5). The atmospheric CO_2 level (400 – 900 ppm) and corresponding future meteorological fields (Eastham et al., 2023) are used to drive the air quality model.

Figure 2. Emulator (GP vs Linear) errors in regional population-weighted $PM_{2.5}$ ($\mu g m^{-3}$) and O_3 (ppb) levels. Dot size represents the population of the region.

We run another 10 sets of GCHP simulations with random scaling factors and climate to test our model. We find our GP model satisfactorily emulate the changes in global population-weighted O_3 (MAE = 29%) and $PM_{2.5}$ (MAE = 8%), and significantly outperforms the linear model at both global (O_3 MAE = 47%, $PM_{2.5}$ MAE = 26%) and regional (fig. 2) scale.

Conclusions

We develop a GP-based emulator to estimate O_3 and $PM_{2.5}$ response to climate and pollutant emission changes, which outperforms the linear models. Future work includes fine tuning the emulator, evaluating the emulator with global change scenarios, and building the impact assessment part of the workflow.

Acknowledgements

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Open modeling and simulation

Design of Ecological Flow (E-Flow) Considering Watershed Status Using Watershed and Physical Habitat Models

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Summary

E-flow should be determined while considering the overall status of the watershed, including the hydrological cycle, hydraulic facility operation, and stream ecology. The coupled modelling between watershed model and habitat model can help to determine E-flow considering overall watershed status.

Introduction

When determining ecological flow (E-flow), it should be done considering all components of the natural watershed, as well as the relationship between hydrology, ecology, and morphological aspects. Generally, the E-flow have been estimated by hydrological method or habitat simulation method such as physical habitat simulation system (PHABSIM) (Leone et al., 2023). In the past, instream flow (IF) and E-flow have been regarded as the same concept. However, now that E-flow is encompassed within the concept of IF, it should be estimated considering the overall watershed status including the hydrologic cycle, operation at hydraulic facilities, and so on (European Commission, 2012). To complement these points, one needs to link habitat model with a model that can simulate long-term streamflow and consider overall watershed status.

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) is basically composed land use/cover and soil maps and can consider the overall watershed status such as dam and sewage treatment plant operation. If SWAT coupled with PHABSIM using these advantages, E-flow will be estimated considering the overall watershed status.

The main objectives of this study are: (1) to perform coupled modeling between SWAT and PHABIM using the flow duration results of SWAT, and (2) to determine the optimal E-flow considering overall watershed status.

Methodology and Results

To link with two models, the calibrated streamflow of SWAT was used to determine discharge boundary conditions of PHABSIM. The initial boundary conditions of the water surface's elevation and velocity were established using the calibrated streamflow of the target stream and cross-section data. Normal and dry boundary conditions, derived from the flow duration analysis results for nine years (2012-2020), were applied to estimate the E-flow considering the overall watershed status.

In this study, the Gudam upstream basin (GDUB, 4,584.8 km²) in South Korea was set up as study area and its main stream (410.0 m) was set up as target stream. The watershed outlet of GDUB has a Gudam streamflow gauging station (GD) and an IF notification spot named Jibo (JB), which is managed by the Ministry of the Environment (ME) in South Korea.

SWAT was established for GDUB considering 2 multi-purpose dams and sewage treatment plants using GIS spatial data, observed meteorological, and hydrological data (1975-2020). In case of PHABSIM, PHABSIM was established for main stream of GDUB including GD as 410.0 m using field survey data including water depth, velocity, stream topographic, streamflow and fish. The hydraulic data were provided by MOLIT (MOLIT, 2009). The field survey was conducted 4 times. Fishes were collected to construct habitat suitability index (HSI) using casting net and skimming net.

SWAT was calibrated and validated for 9 years (2012-2020) to assess its capability to simulate the watershed hydrology considering the overall watershed status. The average of R^2 , NSE, RMSE, and PBIAS were 0.62, 0.57, 1.68 mm/day, and -16.6% showing satisfactory results (Moriassi et al., 2015). After SWAT calibration, flow duration analysis was performed to determine the discharge boundary condition of PHABSIM using both observed and calibrated data from GD during 2012-2020. The average of mid-range flow (Q_{185}) showed a slight difference of 0.5 m³/s compared to the average of observed Q_{185} . For dry condition (Q_{275}), the simulated Q_{275} in 2015 was overestimated with a difference of +7.0 m³/s but it has smaller variability and reflected streamflow trends well compared with observed streamflow.

The dominant fish species was selected to determine HSI using the field survey. The number of fish individuals sampled was 203 in 12 species of five families. Among them, the relative abundance of *Zacco platypus* was assessed as 54.2% with a total 110 individuals indicating highly relative abundances. The HSI ranges (depth, velocity, and substrate) of *Zacco platypus* are 0.25-0.85 m, 0.05-1.05 m/s, and sand-fine gravel.

The applicability of the SWAT model for providing PHABSIM input data was evaluated by simulating PHABSIM using the observed and SWAT-simulated streamflow and comparing the results of water surface elevation and velocity. For the PHABSIM discharge boundary condition, the averages of the observed Q_{185} (36.5 m³/s) and Q_{275} (23.8 m³/s) were applied to calibration discharges, and the averages of simulated Q_{185} (36.0 m³/s) and Q_{275} (23.8 m³/s) were applied to simulation discharges. As a result of the water surface elevation and velocity simulations, the differences of water surface elevation simulation were -0.12 m and 0.00 m at Q_{185} and Q_{275} and the differences of velocity simulation were -0.03 m/s and -0.04 m/s at Q_{185} and Q_{275} . Despite the error in the hydraulic model simulation, the water surface elevation and velocity were simulated effectively within an acceptable range.

PHABSIM calculates weighted usable area (WUA) and defines the flow that secures the largest WUA as the optimal E-flow. The optimal E-flow of the target stream was estimated at 11.2 m³/s, with an area of 61,955.3 m²/1000 m as the largest WUA. The IF of JB downstream of PHABSIM modeling was reported to be 20.8 m³/s by ME. This means that the E-flow estimated by SWAT-PHABSIM coupled modeling was in an appropriate range compared to the notified IF, and that the modeling coupled with watershed and habitat models yielded effective simulations.

Conclusions

This study performed coupled modeling, using watershed and physical habitat models SWAT and PHABSIM, and estimated the optimal E-flow for a target stream. The optimal E-flow was estimated as 11.2 m³/s via coupled modeling, which is lower than that given by IF (20.8 m³/s), as notified by the government for the JB location. These results show that the applicability of coupled modeling using watershed and physical habitat models was high. Comparing the IF and estimated E-flow shows that the IF could be used as an effective tool to determine whether the E-flow has been estimated appropriately.

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Laying the Foundation for Developing Modeling Standards: Exploration of Definitions and Principles

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Summary

To enhance the utility of modeling in learning and decision processes, embracing agreed standards is necessary. Analysis of 80+ modeling standards revealed three key goals: (1) 'minimum quality standards', (2) 'good modelling practices' and (3) 'compliance to rules or systems'. Key principles encompass (1) interoperability, (2) transparency, (3) findability, (4) reproducibility, (5) flexibility and (6) credibility. Two main themes revolve around (1) facilitating the adoption of modeling standards and (2) ensuring the development of quality models. By identifying principles and relationships, this study lays the groundwork for developing common standards in environmental modeling, with potential transferability across related disciplinary fields.

Introduction

Modeling standards are important for ensuring the quality of processes throughout the lifecycle of models, contributing to outcomes such as sharing designs and supporting collaboration, learning across disciplinary fields and domain space, and informing decision-making processes. Considerable efforts have been put into the establishment of standardized modeling practices, spanning from model building to performance evaluation, with major advances including standardized protocols such as the ODD (Overview, Design concepts, Details) by Grimm et al. (2006), as well as high-integrity mechanisms such as ISO norms to support the adoption and enforcement of modeling standards across organizations (Deissenboeck et al., 2009).

However, a main challenge for modeling standards is the lack of consensus within the scientific community on how to define, develop and implement modeling standards, mainly explained by dynamic changes in sciences, technology and society and associated influence on worldviews, relevant approaches and requirements (e.g., Laakso & Kiviniemi, 2012; Araújo et al., 2019). This lack of consensus impedes our ability to compare models and assess their reliability (Araújo et al., 2019), and restricts their accessibility, reusability and interoperability.

To contribute to the establishment and effective implementation of general modeling standards for environmental modeling, we reviewed a broad range of 'modeling standards', including from computing, finance, earth sciences, engineering, ecology and defense, and identified overarching definitions and emerging principles.

Methodology and Results

Through reviewing the literature, we initially identified over eighty 'modeling standards'. These have three different kinds of goals: (1) 'minimum quality standards', (2) 'good modelling practices' and (3) 'compliance to rules or systems'. We examined the goals, scope, features, key principles (or desired outcomes or qualities of modeling), commonalities and differences among a selected subset of these in more detail. The most prevalent

principles emerging from our review were related to the: (1) interoperability, (2) transparency, (3) findability, (4) reproducibility, (5) flexibility and (6) credibility of models. Using an inductive thematic analysis, two main themes associated with these principles emerged: 1) facilitating the adoption and effective implementation of modeling standards at the organisational or institutional level and (2) ensuring the development of models, at the project level, perceived as valuable by users and addressing their requirements in terms of usability and functionality, among others.

By mapping the identified principles at both organizational and project levels, we uncovered specificities, overlaps and interdependencies. While some principles were equally distributed across both levels, others exhibited a greater prevalence at one level compared to the other. For example, 'interoperability' was generally influential on project level for sharing data among models. As for 'transparency', it was identified at both levels and linked to 'traceability' at the organisational level and to 'reproducibility' at project level. The mapping of modeling standard principles suggests the co-existence of hierarchical standards, with common and complementary principles aiming at achieving quality processes and tools to enhance modeling outcomes.

Conclusions

The principles for modeling standards identified in this research cover technical, communication and process-based factors which influence the quality of model design and model uptake. These principles appear to play a dual role, influencing the adoption and implementation of modeling standards at the organization level and, by applying them at the project level, the development and uptake of models. Additionally, shared principles between these two levels highlight some interdependencies between modeling standards and tools. This suggests that modeling standards may undergo dynamic evolution, adapting to external factors affecting the lifecycle of modeling tools, such as rapid technological advancements and evolving user demands for model functionalities. Therefore, future research should explore how present and future external factors may impact the achievement of modeling standard principles, informing potential requirements for and development of modeling standards.

Through the comparative analysis of numerous modeling standards, this study identifies the common modeling standard principles applicable across various modeling types, disciplines and problem domains. By doing so, it lays the groundwork for the development of a common set of modeling standards for environmental modelling and beyond.

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Comparative Analysis of EPA’s New Environmental Source Apportionment Toolkit and Positive Matrix Factorization 5 Models

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Summary

Source apportionment methods are a multivariate factor analysis tool that quantitatively estimate source profiles and contributions of speciated sample data. We present a comparative analysis of the EPA’s new Environmental Source Apportionment Toolkit (ESAT) with those generated from an older model called the Positive Matrix Factorization 5 (PMF5) application (Brown 2015) to showcase ESAT’s functionality. ESAT is open-source using modern software capabilities, while PMF5 has dataset size limitations and is no longer actively supported. We demonstrate that ESAT is capable of producing solutions that are highly correlated, comparable, and computationally efficient relative to PMF5.

Introduction

The EPA’s PMF5 application provides source apportionment estimations while considering data uncertainty. PMF5 also contains error estimation methods and post-processing analytics to evaluate the efficacy of solutions (Paatero 1998). The application has seen widespread use internationally for environmental source apportionment projects but is no longer maintained and relies on a proprietary solver. The EPA has developed ESAT to provide a modern, open-source replacement for PMF5. The first stage of development focused on a Python package (*esat*), with complete documentation and demonstration via Jupyter notebooks providing code use examples. ESAT offers all the pre- and post-processing analysis tools, error estimation methods, and customized constraint features found in PMF5 (Paatero 2014).

Here we provide the results of a comparative analysis of solutions produced by PMF5 and those from the two algorithms available in ESAT, least-squares non-negative matrix factorization (LS-NMF) and weighted semi non-negative matrix factorization (WS-NMF). The solution of non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) algorithms are generally in the form of two source matrices (W and H) whose product form the solution estimate for the input data matrix (V). These two matrices are the basis for source apportionment using NMF and contain the factor/source information. The standard NMF algorithm minimizes the loss function by updating the source matrices. In PMF5 and ESAT, data uncertainty is included in both the update algorithm and the loss function.

A variation of mean squared error is used as the loss function in both PMF5 and ESAT. The loss (Q) is the squared difference between the input data V and the solution WH divided by the uncertainty matrix U . The number of factors is defined as K .

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \left[\frac{V_{ij} - \sum_{k=1}^K W_{ik} H_{kj}}{U_{ij}} \right]^2$$

The W and H matrices generated from these update algorithms can vary significantly (dependent on initialization method and initial random seed values) and often require multiple independent output for determining possible real world applicable factor solutions. We compared output matrices produced by PMF5 and ESAT, showing how mapped factors were strongly correlated between the solutions. We also conducted a loss and runtime analysis of PMF5 and ESAT, showing several different implementations and optimizations.

Methodology and Results

The solution space for most NMF algorithms is infinite and the algorithms operate by minimizing the loss function through alternating least squares updates to the W and H matrices, or by some other update algorithm. No known solver can guarantee a solution is the global minimum, and there are no known methods for confirming a solution is a global minimum. Additionally, the order of the factors is not guaranteed to be consistent between multiple solutions, requiring consideration of the factor orders when making comparisons. Because of this, our comparisons were based on the coefficient of determination of each ESAT solution profile relative to the PMF5 profiles from a specific solution. Comparability of the ESAT results were based on the highest average coefficient of determination between the mapped factor profiles and mapped factor contributions.

Two other metrics were also compared: 1) the runtime of ESAT and PMF5 algorithms for computing N solutions when the resulting loss values were equivalent, and 2) a comparison of ESAT and PMF5 loss values when the solution runtimes were equivalent, ensured by tuning of convergence criteria parameters. We found that one of the ESAT algorithms consistently and significantly outperformed PMF5 in runtime and optimal result loss value, with the other being comparable to PMF5 in both runtime and loss value.

Across three available sample datasets in PMF5, and testing across a number of factors (3 to 9), we found that the ESAT algorithms produced highly correlated solutions to PMF5. The loss of the best-performing PMF5 solution typically fell within the first and third quartiles of the ESAT loss values and was often larger than the best-performing ESAT result. The two ESAT algorithms include a standard NMF algorithm which is computationally efficient and significantly faster than PMF5, and a semi-NMF algorithm that permits small negative values in the contribution matrix; its runtime was comparable to PMF5.

Conclusions

The comparative analysis demonstrated that ESAT is a suitable replacement for PMF5, generating output with an averaged lower loss value, comparable factor profiles, and options for more computationally efficient algorithms. Specifically, the factor profiles showed high correlations across all three datasets and the tested factor range. Our analysis also showed that ESAT produces output in the same loss value range as PMF5 and is now primed for use as a general source apportionment application. Additional comparative analyses will be conducted during alpha and beta testing with additional datasets, as well as applying ESAT to known source studies and synthetic datasets.

Disclaimer

Mention of any trade names, products, or services does not convey, and should not be interpreted as conveying, official EPA approval, endorsement, or recommendation. The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views or policies of the US EPA.

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OpenGMS-Based Interoperability Engine Design for Reusing Geo-Analysis Models

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Summary

Sharing geo-analysis models globally for reuse has become prevalent, offering significant savings in funds and time. However, their heterogeneous origins result in challenges hindering effective reuse. Diverse reuse's requirements, from system integration to application coupling, often go unmet by shared models. This research consolidates extensive literature on model interoperability and develops a novel interoperability engine, implemented through OpenGMS. The engine streamlines deployment, resource access, and data conversion. A case study on watershed flow simulation demonstrates the engine's effectiveness in facilitating model reuse for geographic and environmental problem-solving, contributing to collaboration and innovation in geographic research.

Introduction

The development of diverse geo-analysis models has revolutionized our ability to simulate massive geographic phenomena in various domains such as atmosphere, ecology, and hydrology (Belete et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2020; Laniak et al., 2013). Sharing these models for reuse has become a global trend, which can save a lot of funds and time consuming. To date, international efforts have focused on designing kinds of web-based sharing approaches for different domains (e.g. CSDMS, CoMSES.net, HydroShare, and OpenGMS) (Chen et al., 2020; Gan et al., 2020; Janssen et al., 2008; Overeem et al., 2013). However, due to their origins from different groups or individuals, these models exhibit heterogeneity in type, invoking, and data exchange protocols, still posing challenges for effective reuse. Furthermore, diverse user requirements for model reuse, ranging from system integration to application coupling, often remain unmet by shared models. To address these challenges, geo-analysis models need to enhance their interoperability for model reuse.

Methodology and Results

This research consolidates extensive literature on model interoperability and investigates the requirements and mechanisms underlying it. We designed and developed a novel model interoperability engine, implemented through OpenGMS standard. The engine facilitates seamless deployment, resource access, and data conversion, among other functionalities. A case study focusing on watershed flow simulation demonstrates the effectiveness of the interoperability engine in enabling model reuse for solving geographic and environmental challenges.

Conclusions

This study reviews relevant interoperability research and explores the interoperability content and methods in model reuse. This study designs and develop an interoperability engine that contributes to advancing the interoperability of geo-analysis models, thereby fostering collaboration and innovation in geographic research and problem-solving.

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Advances in Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence for environmental modelling and decision support

Streamlining Streamflow: Post-Processing National Water Model Long-Range Forecasts with Machine Learning

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Summary

Correcting bias in streamflow forecasts is crucial for better flood mitigation. Many hydrologic models exist for runoff simulation, yet errors persist, leading to uncertainty in flood warning systems. Bias correction is essential to enhance model predictive performance. We used machine learning techniques, specifically random forest regression, to correct bias in streamflow predictions from the National Water Model (NWM) against U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) gauge station observed measurements of actual streamflow. We assessed effectiveness of the bias correction technique through error metrics including RMSE to gauge improvement. Post-processing NWM forecasts through bias correction will elevate accuracy and trust in the NWM, amplifying its efficacy in flood management efforts.

Introduction

Accurate prediction of streamflow is crucial for water resource management, flood forecasting, and environmental planning. However, long-range forecasts from the NWM often lack precision, leading to challenges in making informed decisions based on these forecasts before the last minute. Long-range forecasts from the NWM are 30 days long with streamflow predictions every 6 hours. The longer a forecast period the more inaccurate it becomes. As the forecast gets further and further away from measured data, naturally the predictions will lose precision. Post-processing the long-range forecasts from the NWM with machine learning techniques will help correct the forecast to more closely follow actual gauge measured values. With a more accurate long-range forecast, decision-makers will have more time to react and inform the public about possible dangers. The purpose of this study is to explore opportunities for using machine learning random forest regression to improve the accuracy of streamflow predictions based on long-range NWM forecasts. The need for this research arises from the critical importance of reliable streamflow predictions for various stakeholders, including water managers, policymakers, and environmental agencies. More accurate streamflow predictions will reduce loss of life and cost from flood damage with a greater reaction time for the effects of excess runoff. Hales et al (2023) present techniques to bias correct global hydrologic model outputs of the GEOGLOWS model, noting that predicted streamflow is often inaccurate and the need to post-process the output to better match actual flows helps create trust in the models being used. We recognized the need to do this for any hydrologic model, as discussed by Wu (2018). In Han and Morrison (2022) and Gauch (2020), machine learning techniques are described as novel approaches to understanding and correcting errors made by these models. In Dion, Martel, and Arsenault (2021), they bring to light the need for multiple models to increase accuracy and dependability within streamflow forecasting. With this background, this study aims to bias correct the streamflow output from the NWM long-range forecast to follow the USGS gauge measurements more accurately for streamflow using multiple different machine learning models to maximize accuracy. Like the GEOGLOWS model, the NWM was developed as a continental scale model with a focus on spatial resolution over hydrologic accuracy (Johnson, J. M., 2023) and hence is a strong candidate for post-processing bias correction. To explore this area thoroughly, this study aims to apply multiple machine learning approaches to best select a post-processing model streamflow adjuster. While there has been quite a bit of work in streamflow prediction and machine learning, there has been limited attention given to analyzing long-range NWM forecast outputs and correcting them using machine learning. This study aims to bridge this gap by providing a case study in leveraging ensemble forecasting techniques with machine learning to enhance the accuracy of streamflow predictions for the NWM long-range forecasts.

Methodology and Results

We used one year of historical NWM forecast data and corresponding observed streamflow data for model training and validation. We acquired historical NWM forecasts and USGS gauge values by accessing a Google BigQuery database through the cloud. This BigQuery database holds past NWM forecasts and USGS observed values for cloud access. The BigQuery method greatly reduces the data download and processing time when compared to traditional methods of data access. Once the BigQuery data has been queried to the user's parameters (Time frame, Forecast Type, etc.), we format the data into a workable dataframe for applying a machine learning model within the cloud. In the script, four lags will be created for each member and those will be put into the dataframe as column names to capture the time series nature of the data for the ML model. The data will be separated into predictive features and the target values. The target being the USGS observed values and the forecasts being the features to aid in prediction. After using 80% of the data to train and setting aside 20% for testing, we implement the random forest regression algorithm and then each of the other models as desired using Python's scikit-learn library. Next, we conduct feature selection and hyperparameter tuning to optimize model performance. Then, we evaluate model performance using metrics such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) to determine the most apt model for NWM long-range streamflow forecast correction.

The random forest regression technique using 10 folds in the kfold function has shown the best results, approximating the streamflow close to the USGS observed values. The RMSE of the model has been reduced down to around 65 and more data, more iterations, and more tweaking of the hyperparameters hope to reduce the error even further when testing the untrained values.

Conclusions

This novel method for bias correction of streamflow model outputs can help improve NWM model outputs across all regions. There is significant evidence that suggests that this machine learning model corrects NWM long-range forecasts to follow observed streamflow more closely with minimal error. The limitations of the model include only being able to predict streamflow for one location at a time. Once the model is trained, it can predict streamflow for that location only because it's been trained on data specific to that location. Future work includes expanding the number of locations used for analysis, using this method on different types of hydrologic model outputs, and experimenting with more machine learning model types.

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Enhancing Dam Hourly Inflow Prediction Performance Using Improved Inflow Data Preprocessing and LSTM: Integration of Event Identification & Exponential Smoothing (IE²S)-LSTM

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Summary

The performance of LSTMs in analyzing rainfall-runoff dynamics has demonstrated better performance over the physically-based hydrological models. However, data quality remains crucial to further improve the performance of LSTM. In this study, we applied the Integration of Event Identification & Exponential Smoothing (IE²S) method to reduce the fluctuations in inflow, which are typically estimated by the Simple Water Balance method. The preprocessed inflow data was then used to train a LSTM, demonstrating a noticeable improvement in reliability and variability for hourly inflow prediction. This research presents not only new deep learning methods but also data-centric research that is critical to improving the performance of deep learning as an example of rainfall-runoff analysis.

Introduction

Deep learning has emerged as an important approach to improving the performance of rainfall-runoff analysis (Kratzert et al., 2018). However, the accuracy of natural observational data such as stream flows and dam inflows remain a tedious challenge (Sessions & Valtorta, 2006). In particular, the estimation of inflow through the existing Simple Water Balance (SWB) method (Fenton, 1992) often fails to accurately reflect the actual inflow well due to uncertainties caused by fluctuations in dam water levels (Deng et al., 2015), and these can lead to a degradation of performance for applications of deep learning such as Long Short Term Memory (LSTM), which has recently demonstrated the improved performance in rainfall-runoff analysis compared to physically based models. However, there is a lack of studies on improving the data quality while existing studies are mainly focusing on developing new deep learning models to improve prediction performance. Therefore, this study first introduced an IE²S method to improve the data quality of hourly inflow by both minimizing data fluctuation and preserving the scale of peak inflows after preprocessing. Next, we applied 12 scenarios to demonstrate the improvements in the performance of hourly inflow prediction using LSTM.

Methodology and Results

1) Integration of events identification and exponential smoothing (IE²S) method

Currently, the SWB method has been mainly used to estimate dam inflow and applied the Exponential Smoothing (EA) or Moving Average (MA) method to remove inflow fluctuation. Yet, it is difficult to find optimal coefficients for the EA and MA methods because of different scales of inflow during flood and drought periods. In addition, in the case of traditional approaches such as developing and applying physically based models, the fluctuation of inflow was not relatively critical. However, in the case of data-driven approaches such as deep learning, data quality is important because deep learning models are trained using the data itself. Therefore, the current hourly inflow is an important issue when applying for LSTM. In this section, the IE²S method was developed to apply Event Identification to distinguish the scale of inflow and Exponential Smoothing to apply appropriate exponential coefficient values according to the scale of inflow. As a result, this approach was able to smooth low inflow, which has frequent fluctuation, and preserve peak inflow to predict flood exactly based on observation.

2) Case study area and scenario description

This study is applied to the Yongdam dam basin(930.4km²) in South Korea. For training of LSTM, Basin Average Rainfall (B.A.R), and 8 rainfall stations (8 sta.) as input features, and hourly inflow: 1) raw data(preprocessing of missing data and outlier), 2) 2hr and 3hr MA, 3) IE²S method as target variables for 20 years ('03.10.1~'23.9.30) were collected. Then, a total of 12 scenarios were applied through a combination of input features and target variables, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. 12 Application Scenarios for Evaluation of LSTM Performance Improvement

Cases	Case 1-1	Case 1-2	Case 1-3	Case 2-1	Case 2-2	Case 2-3	Case 2-4	Case 2-5	Case 2-6	Case 3-1	Case 3-2	Case 3-3
Input Features	B.A.R	8 sta.	B.A.R + 8 sta.	B.A.R	8 sta.	B.A.R	8 sta.	B.A.R + 8 sta.	B.A.R	8 sta.	B.A.R + 8 sta.	
Target Variables	Preprocessing of Missing Data and Outlier from Hourly Inflow			2hr MA	3hr MA	2hr MA	3hr MA	2hr MA	3hr MA	IE ² S Method		

1) B.A.R: Basin Average Rainfall, 2) 8 sta.: 8 Rainfall Stations, 3) B.A.R + 8 sta.: 1) + 2), MA: Moving Average

3) Application and performance evaluation of LSTM

To compare the performance and properties of 12 scenarios using LSTM, we used 9 performance metrics: 3 metrics (NSE, KGE, Pearson-r) for efficiency and correlation, 3 metrics (MSE, RMSE, Peak-MAPE) for error, and 3 metrics (FHV, FMS, FLV) for bias. In the case of different types of input features application, the overall performance of the four scenarios (Case-1-1, Case-2-1, Case-2-2, and Case-3-1), which used only basin average rainfall, was outperformed. Based on these results, considering different types of target variable applications, Case-2-1, Case-2-2, and Case-3-1 performed relatively well. However, Case-2-1(2-hour MA) and 2-2 (3-hour MA) reduced the peak hourly inflow to a relatively larger than IE²S methods because these approaches arithmetically average inflow data around it. As a result, the application of basin average rainfall and IE²S-LSTM showed the best performance. In addition, this approach solved both the problems of reduction of peak inflow and fluctuation of inflow (Table 2).

Table 2. Performance Results of LSTM using Raw Data (Case-1), MA (Case-2), IE²S (Case-3)

Years	[1]		[2]		[3]		[4]		Obs-Preprocessed (m ³ /s)			Ratio of Obs-Preprocessed Value (%)			Performance						
	Inflow (m ³ /s) (Obs:Max)	Inflow (m ³ /s) (IE ² S:Max)	Inflow (m ³ /s) (3hr MA:Max)	Inflow (m ³ /s) (3hr MA:Max)	[2]-[1]	[3]-[1]	[4]-[1]	[2]-[1]	[3]-[1]	[4]-[1]	((2)-[1])/([1])*100	((3)-[1])/([1])*100	((4)-[1])/([1])*100	NSE	Case-1-1	Case-2-1	Case-2-2	Case-2-3	Case-2-4	Case-3-1	
2006	1,355	1,348	1,350	1,291	8	5	64	0	0	0	0.6%	0.4%	4.7%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		
2007	1,755	1,748	1,746	1,711	7	9	44	7	9	44	0.4%	0.5%	2.5%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		
2008	851	811	828	817	37	26	34	37	26	34	6.6%	5.0%	6.6%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		
2009	2,327	2,326	2,305	2,275	1	22	52	1	22	52	0.0%	1.0%	2.2%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		
2010	2,575	2,573	2,467	2,294	2	108	281	2	108	281	0.1%	4.2%	10.9%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		
2016	832	774	778	662	58	114	170	58	114	170	7.0%	14.7%	22.0%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		
2017	341	335	341	341	7	0	0	7	0	0	2.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		
2018	2,193	2,158	2,089	2,034	35	104	159	35	104	159	1.6%	4.8%	7.3%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		
2019	1,124	1,072	982	935	52	142	189	52	142	189	4.7%	13.3%	17.6%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		
2020	4,395	4,388	4,266	3,985	7	129	410	7	129	410	0.2%	2.9%	9.3%	0.897	0.919	0.942	0.87	0.767	0.92		

Yearly peak inflow comparison using different pre-processing approaches

Performance Results of LSTM

Conclusions

Data quality is important for further improving dam inflow prediction using deep learning models. Firstly, this research presented the IE²S method for preprocessing the hourly dam inflow. Then, LSTM models were evaluated with 12 different scenarios to demonstrate enhancement of inflow prediction through 9 performance metrics. From this research, we suggest that for continuous and rapid improvement of deep learning performance, both new deep learning approaches and data-centric control will be conducted simultaneously in the future.

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Machine Learning for Hindcasting Nitrate Concentration Data

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Summary

Nitrate concentration data is a critical indicator of stream health, but it's often limited to weekly or biweekly in-situ water sample measurements. High-frequency nitrate sensor measurements could provide critical insights into the catchment's nitrate dynamics, which could be used to hindcast the nitrate concentration data for periods with in-situ water sample measurements. We developed a machine-learning framework for nitrate concentration hindcasting using historic in-situ sample nitrate data, sensor-based nitrate data, discharge, and biophysical characteristics of the catchment. This approach provides a deeper understanding of nitrate dynamics in the region and offers opportunities for generating spatially and temporally continuous nitrate data.

Introduction

Stream nitrate monitoring is conducted using in-situ water samples, typically at coarse temporal (weekly or bi-weekly) resolution. In the United States, agencies started collecting high-frequency (5-60 min intervals) nitrate data using optical sensors in the last decade. These sensor-based high-frequency stream nitrate concentrations could provide valuable information on the nutrient dynamics of the region, which could be used to understand historic nitrate trends and stream health in the region. This study hypothesized that the nitrate dynamics information available in the high-frequency stream nitrate monitoring sites could be used to hindcast nitrate concentration at other low-frequency monitoring locations in the region.

Methodology and Results

We developed a machine learning framework using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) to estimate continuous daily stream nitrate. The modeling framework utilized biophysical characteristics such as climate, land use, fertilization, topography, and soil characteristics data as inputs during the model development. The hypothesis was tested in the watersheds of Iowa, USA since the region had more high-frequency nitrate monitoring sites with long-term data.

The results indicated a high potential for the framework for hindcasting spatially and temporally continuous nitrate data. For daily nitrate concentration prediction, 50% of the sites were simulated with Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) of greater than 0.75, and 75% of the sites were simulated with NSE greater than 0.5.

Conclusions

The hypothesis testing indicated a high potential for the machine learning framework for hindcasting nitrate concentration data. An expanded study area with more high-frequency nitrate data and increasing length of data availability could significantly improve the model performance. Temporally continuous long-term nitrate concentration data could provide critical insights into stream health and nutrient dynamics of a region and could help with designing adaptation strategies.

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Evolutionary Multi-Criterion Optimization and Decision-Making for Land Use Management in New Zealand

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Summary

Many complex societal and industrial problem-solving tasks require simultaneous consideration of more than one, and often conflicting, objectives. In this talk, we discuss a solution procedure of two-party land use management of a 1500-ha farm divided into 315 paddocks from New Zealand in possession of local Maori tribes. The problem was formulated with 14 objectives (maximizing sawlog production, pulpwood production, milk-solids, beef, sheep meat, wool, carbon sequestration, water production, income and earnings before interest and tax; and minimizing costs, nitrate leaching, phosphorus loss and sedimentation). We addressed the problem by formulating a 14-objective optimization task and solved using a recently proposed computational intelligence procedure. It resulted in 100 different Pareto solutions trading off all 14 objectives. They were presented to Maori and local government policy-makers using virtual reality gadgets and also through innovative visualization methods. The final choice a single preferred solution was achieved through the analytical hierarchy process.

Introduction

Complex societal problems involve a few pragmatic characteristics, which are often not considered in theoretical and academic research, but are critical to include in any practical solution. In this talk, we consider a complex land use management problem from New Zealand. The land under discussion is possessed by local Maori tribe and any decision related to the land is decided by the senior Maori leaders. On the other hand, since the piece of land is connected in many way with neighbouring localities owned by private citizens and like, the local government is concerned about the well-being of the environment in and around the land under question. Thus, clearly there are two separate entities which have a stake in deciding how the Maori land must be utilized for various purposes.

Our approach is human-centric, in which a computer algorithm finds a set of alternate solutions trading-off different key objectives through a multi-criterion formulation of the problem, so human decision-makers (DMs) can review them and choose a single preferred solution from the set. This brings humans into the driver's seat for complex problem solving tasks and allowing computer algorithms to take the blunt of number crunching through multiple models. However, there exist a number of problem-specific complications which must be ironed out to make the approach practical. First, the problem involves 14 conflicting criteria arising from three main aspects: (i) maximizing productivity (diary, sawlog, etc.), (ii) minimizing cost of land use changes (transition cost, interest rates, etc.), and (iii) minimizing environmental effects (carbon, nitrogen, etc.). Second, the land use management requires a multi-year implementation ensuring practicality and sustainability. This requires that costs of products and interest rates be known for future years, involving an accurate predicable model from past data. Third, any acceptable solution to the multi-criteria and multi-year problem must be vetted by two apparently polarized group of stake-holders, thereby requiring an interactive, transparent and easy-to-understand computational system. Fourth, the search space to find solutions from is astronomically large, thereby demanding a scalable optimization procedure. In this study, we have obtained agricultural, hydrological, and economical models from the local forest department, as this study was executed in cooperation of them. The local government has also allowed to us interact with the local Maori senior leaders and local governmental policy-makers, who acted as decision-makers, to come up with a single preferred solution.

Methodology and Results

First, mathematical models, obtained through collected data from the past, for 14 objective functions are obtained from the local department of forestry. A solution represents 10 yearly changes in 315 paddocks, each

having one of 100 land use options. This created an astronomical search space with $100^{315^{10}}$ or 10^{3150} solutions (note that there are only 10^{82} atoms in the universe). All 14 models are evaluated for a total of 50 years from the start year to fully estimate each objective’s true sustainable effects over multiple years. A customized evolutionary multi-criterion optimization (EMO) algorithm – reference point based non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (R-NSGA-II) (Chikumbo, Goodman, & Deb, 2015) – is developed. R-NSGA-II is shown to extend to solve up to 100-objective problems better than any other known EMO algorithm. The customization is made to ensure that geographical contiguity of land uses are maintained. This required fundamental changes in the R-NSGA-II operators.

After a few hours of execution, the R-NSGA-II finds 100 alternate solutions with a trade-off in all 14 objectives. To facilitate a clear understanding of the solutions, we grouped them into three overall criterion – productivity, profitability and environmental effects. The solutions are plotted in time-varying maps of land use changes over 10 years. While finding 100 different trade-off solutions for a complex and large-scale problem was a computational challenge, choosing a single preferred solution for implementation was a human challenge which must be addressed in solving any societal problem. We followed a two-tier decision-making process. First, we begin showing 100 solutions to each group of DMs sorted in their increasing preference order. Fortunately, we found that there were only four (out of 100) solutions which would be acceptable to both DM groups, but one group could not be persuaded to choose the other group’s best choice. Hence, in the second level of decision-making, we have used the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) (Saaty, 2001) with pair-wise comparisons of four solutions and 3 clusters of objectives, involving a total of nine pair-wise comparisons, each involving about 90 to 120 minutes. This process resulted in a single winner. All 100 solutions and chosen four solutions including the winner are shown in the figure.

Figure 1. Multi-criterion optimization and two-tier decision-making are illustrated on NZ land use management problem. Two specific solutions from 100 optimized trade-off solutions at the end of 10 years are shown.

Conclusions

This study has formulated a real-world land use optimization problem into a 14-criterion problem involving triple bottom-line consideration – productivity, profitability and environment – and employed an evolutionary multi-criterion optimization problem with a two-tier decision-making aspects to reduce an astronomically large search space into a single preferred solution. The methodology can be generically applied to solve other large-scale complex problems from practice.

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Conversational AI, Digital Twins, and Metaverse in Water Resources Research, Education, and Operations

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Summary

The transformative potential of Conversational AI systems like ChatGPT, coupled with Digital Twin (DT) and Metaverse paradigms, is ushering in a new era of education, research, and operational functionalities in the hydrology and water resources domain. These advanced technologies can bridge knowledge gaps, foster immersive learning experiences, and promote real-time, dynamic interactions. Whether it's enhancing disaster communication, addressing water quality pollution concerns, or fostering climate awareness, the combination of these systems can provide unprecedented precision and engagement. This confluence of technologies is poised to redefine how we approach hydrological challenges in the 21st century.

Introduction

The integration of advanced technological paradigms such as Conversational Artificial Intelligence (AI), Digital Twins, and Metaverse has the potential to significantly transform the field of hydrology and water resources management (Sajja et al., 2023). These technologies not only promise to enhance educational and operational aspects but also aim to revolutionize research methodologies in tackling hydrological challenges (Gourbesville et al., 2023). The pressing issues of climate change, increasing water scarcity, and frequent extreme weather events necessitate the adoption of innovative solutions that can provide enhanced predictive capabilities, real-time data interaction, and more immersive educational tools (Demir et al., 2022). This study explores the application of these technologies in creating highly detailed, interactive models of water systems, facilitating both operational decision-making and educational outreach, thereby improving the responsiveness and adaptability to hydrological disasters (UNESCO, 2023).

Methodology and Results

To explore the transformative impact of integrating the aforementioned technologies in the domain of water resources, we adopted a multifaceted approach as detailed below.

Conversational AI Implementation: Conversational AI technologies such as ChatGPT have been leveraged to interact seamlessly with DT and Metaverse platforms, enhancing both user interaction and analytical capabilities. These AI systems, trained on comprehensive hydrological datasets, provide instant responses to complex queries and facilitate dynamic scenario simulations. Notably, operational agents like Floodplain Manager AI assistants specialize in managing floodplain resources efficiently, offering expert advice on flood mitigation and response strategies based on simulated outcomes from DT. Similarly, Hydrological Analytics AI experts aid in deciphering intricate water quality and supply data, thus enabling precise pollution tracking and resource management.

Furthermore, the implementation of AI agent hubs has the potential to improve decision-making processes. These hubs host multiple AI agents, each representing different operational roles or stakeholder perspectives, creating a robust environment for holistic analysis. Through interactive discussions within these hubs, AI agents collaboratively analyze data, propose solutions, and predict outcomes of various water management scenarios. This collaborative AI environment ensures a comprehensive evaluation of potential strategies, facilitating consensus among community stakeholders on critical water-related issues. The integration of AI in these capacities significantly enhances decision-making speed and accuracy, while also broadening the scope for adaptive water resource management (WRM) strategies.

Development of Digital Twins: DT of water resource systems are developed by creating virtual replicas of physical water bodies, including rivers, lakes, and water treatment facilities. These models are continuously updated with real-time data from IoT sensors and satellite imagery, providing a current and accurate representation of their physical counterparts. The DT serve as test beds for simulating various hydrological models and disaster scenarios, such as flooding, contaminant dispersion, and resource management, without the risks associated with real-world testing.

Metaverse Integration: Metaverse platforms are utilized to create immersive environments where stakeholders including scientists, policymakers, and the general public can interact with the DT. Users can navigate through virtual environments that mimic real-world water systems, experience the outcomes of different water management strategies, and understand complex hydrological data through intuitive visualizations. This immersive experience is facilitated by VR headsets and spatial computing devices, enhancing the educational and operational understanding of WRM.

Conclusions

The combination of Conversational AI, DT, and Metaverse technologies provides a transformative approach to water resource education, research, and management. This integration offers several benefits:

- Enhanced Decision-Making Capabilities: The real-time data and interactive models allow for quicker and more informed decision-making in managing water resources and responding to hydrological events.
- Immersive Educational Tools: By leveraging the Metaverse for educational purposes, complex hydrological concepts and management strategies can be taught in a more engaging and understandable manner.
- Increased Engagement and Accessibility: These technologies make hydrological data and simulations accessible to a broader audience, fostering greater public involvement and awareness in WRM issues.

Future research should focus on refining AI algorithms for better accuracy in unstructured environments, enhancing the scalability of DT for global water systems, and improving the user interface in Metaverse platforms to be more intuitive. Additionally, interdisciplinary collaboration will be crucial in advancing these technologies to address the complex challenges of modern hydrology and WRM effectively. Additionally, the further development of advanced user interfaces in hydroinformatics should be explored to enhance user interaction and accessibility. This includes expanding the capabilities of gesture-based control systems for more intuitive manipulation of hydrological data, enabling broader accessibility, including for individuals with disabilities. Additionally, the potential of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) should be investigated to facilitate direct interaction through cognitive commands, which could revolutionize decision-making and data analysis in WRM. Furthermore, the design and integration of multimodal interfaces that combine voice, touch, and motion should be refined to provide a seamless and immersive experience that meets diverse user preferences and enhances the comprehensibility of complex hydrological information. These advancements will ensure that hydroinformatics tools are not only more effective but also more inclusive and adaptable to various user needs.

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A New Wave in Hydrological Modelling: Transformer Models for Extended Streamflow Prediction

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Summary

This study evaluates the efficacy of a Transformer model for 120-hour streamflow prediction across 125 diverse locations in Iowa, USA. Using data from the preceding 72 hours, including precipitation, evapotranspiration, and discharge, we developed a generalized model that significantly outperforms traditional location-specific models. Our analysis demonstrates the Transformer model's superior capabilities by maintaining higher median Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) and Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE) scores, and exhibiting the lowest Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE). These results highlight the Transformer's potential as an advanced, adaptable tool in hydrological modelling, offering notable improvements over existing forecasting methods.

Introduction

The escalating trend in natural disasters, driven by climate change, has made the frequency and severity of flooding events a global concern, resulting in substantial economic and human losses (World Meteorological Organization, 2021; Munich Re, 2022). These changes require advanced forecasting tools capable of effectively predicting and managing such events. Streamflow prediction is particularly critical as it directly influences flood management strategies, impacting both emergency response actions and long-term planning (WMO, 2021). Despite the crucial role of accurate streamflow forecasting, traditional models often fail to capture the complex interdependencies and dynamic variations within hydrological systems, especially under changing climatic conditions (Sit et al., 2020).

This study introduces the use of a Transformer model, a sophisticated machine learning approach initially designed for natural language processing but adapted for the temporal dynamics of hydrological data. We apply this model to 120-hour streamflow prediction across multiple locations in Iowa, US, evaluating its effectiveness against both traditional models and other advanced machine learning techniques. Our goal is to demonstrate that the Transformer model not only enhances prediction accuracy but also offers scalability and adaptability across different geographical and environmental conditions. Through this research, we aim to showcase the potential of advanced machine learning models in revolutionizing hydrological forecasting and contributing to more resilient water resource management strategies in the face of ongoing climate change.

Methodology and Results

In this study, we employed a Transformer-based model, designed to leverage its advanced machine learning capabilities for sequential data analysis. The model was trained on a comprehensive dataset, Waterbench-Iowa (Demir et al., 2022), including 72-hour historical records of precipitation, evapotranspiration, and discharge, collected from 125 different locations across Iowa. This approach allowed the model to learn from a broad range of hydrological conditions, enhancing its predictive accuracy across diverse environments.

The methodology involved preprocessing the dataset to normalize the input features and splitting it into training, validation, and testing subsets. The Transformer model was then trained to predict streamflow for a 120-hour future period, using a combination of self-attention mechanisms to effectively handle the temporal dependencies in the data. Comparative models included LSTM, GRU, Seq2Seq, and a baseline Persistence approach, all benchmarked against the Transformer to evaluate performance comprehensively.

Table 1. Comparative performance summary of different models for 120-hour streamflow prediction on unified 125 stations

	NSE			
Persistence	0.864	0.922	0.931	0.824
SeqSeq	0.921	0.867	0.962	0.612
GRU	0.884	0.932	0.945	0.735
LSTM	0.864	0.903	0.939	0.793
Transformer	0.926	0.945	0.964	0.583

The results demonstrated that the Transformer model outperformed all other models in terms of Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE), Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE), Pearson’s r, and Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE). Specifically, the Transformer model maintained higher median NSE and KGE scores and exhibited the lowest NRMSE values, indicating its superior capability to accurately simulate and predict streamflow. Additionally, it showed a strong ability to adapt to varying hydrological conditions and geographical variances, underlining its potential as an advanced tool in hydrological modelling.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates the efficacy of Transformer models in significantly enhancing the accuracy and adaptability of streamflow predictions over a 120-hour horizon across 125 diverse locations in Iowa. By outperforming both traditional hydrological forecasting methods and other advanced machine learning models such as LSTM, GRU, and Seq2Seq, the Transformer model has proven its exceptional capability to handle complex, multi-temporal hydrological data. The model’s robust performance across various metrics highlights its potential as a transformative tool for improving flood management strategies and water resource management.

Looking ahead, the scalability and adaptability of Transformer models suggest substantial potential for broader applications. Future research should focus on expanding the application of these models to include longer prediction timelines and a wider range of environmental variables. This would test the model’s limits and provide insights into its full potential in hydrological forecasting. Additionally, integrating Transformer models with real-time data acquisition systems could lead to the development of more dynamic and responsive hydrological forecasting systems. Another promising direction is incorporating climate change projections into the training process, which could enhance the model’s utility under anticipated future conditions, ensuring that water resource management strategies remain robust in the face of changing global climates.

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Urban Air-Quality Estimation Using Visual Cues

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Summary

Monitoring air pollution via mobile means encounters obstacles due to immature technology, and thus, hindering comprehensive assessments. To address this, surrogate methods like videos and images have been proposed. This study focuses on leveraging deep learning techniques to estimate on-road pollutant levels from dashboard camera videos. Analysing data from Bengaluru, India, the study employs convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to infer pollutant concentrations based on object identification and motion detection in video frames. Results demonstrate that this approach is able to assess CO₂ concentration, offering rapid analysis in real-time using readily available dashboard cameras, thus advancing mobile monitoring capabilities.

Introduction

Air pollution is a problem that must be solved to sustain the modern way of life. Effective monitoring is the first line of defence. However, the monitoring costs limit the sensor networks' spatial and temporal coverage. This study presents an air quality estimation method, based on video footage from a dashboard camera, to infer traffic-related air pollution in locations with no sensors. In the first stage pollution-related cues, specifically pixel motion field and semantic segmentation, are extracted from video frames. Then, the extracted information is organized in a multi-channel image and flows through a regression convolutional neural network (CNN), to deduce the ambient air-pollution level. The methodology has been applied to a mobile-sensing database, containing air pollution measurements and video footage, recorded by a car equipped with air-quality sensors and a dashboard camera.

Methodology and Results

Data were collected using a commercial dashboard camera alongside GPS and air pollution instrumentation mounted on a car. The instruments measured fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), black carbon (BC), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and particle concentration. The monitoring campaign, conducted from May 2019 to March 2020, involved 43 measurement days covering various routes within Bengaluru, revealing high pollutant concentrations on major roads compared to residential areas. The setup ensured accurate data collection with minimal interference from the car's exhaust, employing portable, battery-operated, and factory-calibrated instruments.

Data from videos were sampled at a constant rate of 1 frame every 5 seconds to avoid redundancy and smooth out noisy readings. Pixel motion fields and labels were extracted from each frame and concatenated with the original frame to create a multichannel image associated with air pollution measurements. Motion estimation was done using the Horn–Schunk optical flow algorithm, while pixel labeling utilized image semantic segmentation. Various data train-validation-split strategies were employed, including temporal and geographic divisions, to evaluate model generalization capabilities. The deep-convolutional neural network (Deep-CNN) model architecture was based on Resnet-50 with a few changes to fit the current problem.

The Deep-CNN model proved most effective in identifying CO₂-related features. The model's predictions for the most highly polluted areas are mostly main roads with heavy traffic, whereas the cleaner areas are open one-lane roads with little activity.

Conclusions

This study presents a novel cue-based approach utilizing video features to infer air pollution levels, leveraging the capabilities of CNNs for enhanced accuracy and real-time estimation. By integrating dynamic factors such

as traffic emissions and meteorological conditions, the method offers a significant advancement over existing models, particularly in urban environments. The results demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of this approach in capturing air pollution dynamics, paving the way for its widespread deployment in monitoring and managing air quality. With the potential integration into autonomous vehicle technology, this methodology holds promise for comprehensive and efficient air pollution monitoring on a large scale. Future research directions may focus on further optimizing the model architecture and incorporating additional data sources to enhance its accuracy and applicability in diverse environmental settings.

Increasing Trust and Confidence in Artificial Neural Networks by Using Good Model Development Practice

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Summary

While the potential of artificial neural networks (ANNs) is unquestioned, they are surrounded by an air of mystery and intrigue, leading to a lack of understanding of their inner workings. This has led to the perpetuation of a number of myths, resulting in the misconception that applying ANNs involves “throwing” a large amount of data at “black-box” software packages. To address these issues, this presentation explodes a number of the common myths surrounding the use of ANNs and outlines state-of-the-art approaches to developing ANNs that enable them to be applied with confidence in practice.

Introduction

Despite their widespread application, the inner workings of artificial neural networks (ANNs) are often not well understood by environmental modellers, who are generally quite content to repeat the rhetoric commonly associated with the use of these types of models, such as “ANNs work well because they learn from examples”, “complex ANNs are better able to deal with large amounts of information”, “ANNs are black boxes” and “ANNs need large amounts of data”. While some of these statements are valid in their original computer science context, they are often misleading, or even untrue, in the context of environmental modelling. As a result of the perpetuation of these myths, the principles and level of rigor commonly applied to the development of other types of environmental models are generally not applied to the development of ANNs. Examples include the lack of consideration of the selection of appropriate model inputs, the way the available data should be divided into the subsets needed for model development, how to select an appropriate number of hidden nodes, how to deal with the issue of parameter identifiability, how to obtain confidence limits on predictions, how ANN models should be validated and how models should be deployed in operational environments. This can have a detrimental impact on the quality and usefulness of the resulting models, potentially misleading users. It also makes it difficult to assess and compare research findings and to make significant research progress on the use of ANNs for environmental modelling.

Methodology and Results

In order to address the above issues, the purpose of this presentation is to shed light on the inner workings of ANNs by exploding some of the common myths that exist about them and to present a state-of-the-art approach to their development. In many applications of ANNs in environmental modelling, the primary focus is on the choice of model architecture, structure and “training” (calibration), at the expense of the consideration of the other steps in the model development process. This is likely to have significant negative consequences on the performance of the resulting model, as, for a given model architecture, structure and optimisation (training) algorithm, which model is ultimately developed (i.e. which set of model parameters is selected as part of the

calibration process) is a function of the characteristics of the error surface, the selected inputs, and how the available data are split into their calibration, testing and validation subsets.

Determination of appropriate model parameters (e.g. connection weights and biases) involves the interaction between an optimisation algorithm (e.g. back-propagation) and the error surface, which represents how the calibration (training) error varies with changes in model parameters. The optimisation algorithm navigates through the error surface in order to identify the combination of parameters that corresponds to the lowest error. However, how successful the optimisation algorithm is in achieving this depends on the searching behaviour of the algorithm (e.g. gradient descent or global search) and the characteristics of the error surface (e.g. smooth with one optimum or rough with many local optima). While significant attention is paid to the optimisation algorithm side of this equation, the characteristics of the error surface are often ignored. However, this is vitally important, as the characteristics of the error surface not only influence the ability of the optimisation algorithm to find a nearly globally optimal solution in this surface, but also what parameter combinations these correspond to and how well these are defined.

So, how do we maximise our chances that the error surface is as “nicely behaved” as possible – that it contains a single, clearly-defined optimum and that this optimum is easy-to-find by the selected optimisation algorithm? In order to answer this question, we need to understand what factors affect the characteristics of the error surface. As the error surface shows how calibration errors vary with changes in model parameters, the dimension of the space the optimisation algorithm has to search is equal to the number model parameters (i.e. the number of axes in the error surface is equal to the number of model parameters), as well as the bounds on the values the model parameters can take (i.e. their maximum and minimum values). Consequently, there is a significant incentive to reduce the number of model parameters, which can be achieved by using state-of-the-art input variable selection techniques to ensure only relevant, non-redundant model inputs are included.

Apart from dimensionality, the characteristics of the error surface are also a function of the error values themselves, which are a function of the selected input variables and how they are processed, the selected performance (error) metric, the selected model architecture and structure and which data are used to calculate the error (i.e. the calibration data). The characteristics of the error surface are therefore directly related to the Data Processing, Input Selection, Data Splitting and Performance Metric Selection steps of ANN model development. Consequently, there is a need to adopt state-of-the-art approaches at each step of the model development process.

We believe the adoption of such approaches will assist those who are apprehensive and sceptical about using ANNs, those who are curious about using ANNs and those who have already used ANNs extensively, but have done so “blindly” without “looking under the hood” to fully understand how ANNs work and what potential implications this might have. This increased understanding and guidance is expected to overcome some of the perceived barriers to the adoption of ANNs and increase trust and confidence in their use and the results they produce.

Conclusions

ANNs were considered a “novelty item” by industry 20-30 years ago, primarily confining their application to the research domain. However, this is certainly not the case anymore. Today, many businesses are familiar with ANNs and their capability, and often employ machine learning experts. While the potential of ANNs is clear, they are still surrounded by an air of mystery and intrigue, leading to a lack of understanding of their inner workings. This has led to the perpetuation of a number of myths, resulting in the misconception that the application of ANNs primarily involves “throwing” a large amount of data at a “black-box” software package. While this is certainly a convenient way to side-step the principles and level of rigor applied to the development of many other types of environmental models, this comes at significant cost in terms of the validity and usefulness of the resulting models, the ability to assess and compare research findings and the ability to progress research efforts. In order to address these issues, this presentation explodes a number of the common myths surrounding the use of ANNs for the prediction and forecasting of environmental systems and outlines state-of-the-art approaches to developing ANN models that enable them to be applied with confidence in practice.

Agricultural Modelling Is Not Quite Ready for the Artificial Intelligence Revolution

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Summary

Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, including machine learning, are crucial for monitoring and mitigating human impact on the environment and making agriculture efficient and resilient. Agricultural modelling is ill-prepared for the AI revolution because of fragmentation of data and research practices. Challenges are related to data availability and quality, open and community-driven research and stakeholder requirements. Even then, the convergence of remote sensing, crop modelling and machine learning provides opportunities to address these challenges. Progress has been made in areas where researchers can work on their own; more effort is required in areas that involve cross-domain collaboration or interactions with stakeholders.

Introduction

Applications of machine learning to crop yield forecasting and agriculture suffer from fragmentation in terms of selected data sources, methods for preprocessing and feature design, models or architectures and evaluation metrics. Such fragmentation, coupled with limited sharing of code implementation and data, makes it difficult to reproduce and intercompare research. Some of the fragmentation can be attributed to the size and quality of available data (including statistics, crop masks and predictors), spatial heterogeneity and differences across spatial scales. Another factor is the diversity of research objectives and modelling practices focusing on specific contexts. Such research suffers from concerns about the rigour of validation and generalizability to different settings.

Methodology and Results

We critically reflect on the current state of data and research practices, and identify challenges in taking advantage of the artificial intelligence revolution. Similarly, we identify key trends and opportunities that could make machine learning more beneficial to agricultural applications. In addition, we provide specific recommendations to make agricultural modelling more reproducible, comparable and generalizable.

Gaps and challenges in agricultural modelling fall into three main categories: (i) data availability and quality, (ii) open and community-driven research practices, (iii) end-user or stakeholder engagement. Data may be unavailable or, when available, size and quality may not meet modelling requirements. Agricultural systems modelling will remain fragmented in the absence of clear guidelines for data selection, preparation and modelling, software tools to automate the guidelines and benchmarks to intercompare models. This fragmentation can be addressed by open community-driven research practices powered by shared best practices, standardised datasets and benchmarks and interactions with the artificial intelligence and machine learning research communities. Similarly, current research efforts are limited to performance comparison among models with standard metrics (e.g. root mean squared error). Agricultural modelling must move from “supply-driven”, in which researchers develop models for system understanding, to “demand-driven” or “user-driven”, in which decision-making needs of end-users are front and centre.

Conclusions

When looking at the bigger picture, ML and DL methods are providing benefits to agricultural applications, including crop yield forecasting, but gaps and challenges remain in making models intercomparable and useful to end-users. Even then, the convergence of knowledge-based methods, remote sensing and machine learning, and emergence of causal and interpretable machine learning provide opportunities to address many of these challenges. Significant progress has been made in areas where researchers can work on their own; more effort is required in areas that involve cross-domain collaboration or interactions with stakeholders.

A Comprehensive Comparison of Multimodal Large Language Models (MLLMs) in Hydrology

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Summary

This study evaluates the effectiveness of Multimodal Large Language Models (MLLMs) in hydrology, focusing on models such as Multimodal-GPT, GPT-4 Vision, Gemini, and LLaVA. These models are assessed for their capability to synthesize visual and textual data to address challenges in flood management, water pollution control, and agricultural water discharge. GPT-4 Vision is highlighted for its superior performance in visual data interpretation, demonstrating significant potential in enhancing hydrological research and applications. The insights derived from this analysis aim to contribute to the advancement of AI applications in environmental and resource management.

Introduction

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) with hydrology is revolutionizing the understanding and management of water resources (Pursnani et al., 2023). Hydrology, which examines the distribution and movement of water on Earth, significantly benefits from AI advancements, particularly through the application of MLLMs. These sophisticated models, capable of processing both textual and visual information, provide a dynamic toolset for enhancing data analysis and decision-making in environmental science (Sajja et al., 2023). MLLMs are a specialized subset of machine learning models distinguished by their ability to interpret and synthesize information from diverse data sources, such as text, images, and occasionally audio. This capability is crucial in hydrology, a field characterized by its reliance on varied data formats including satellite imagery, sensor data, textual reports, and real-time environmental monitoring systems. The seamless integration and analysis of these disparate data types by MLLMs enable a more nuanced understanding of water-related phenomena (Slater et al., 2023).

The deployment of MLLMs in hydrology signifies more than a mere technological enhancement—it marks a paradigm shift in how data are leveraged to inform critical decisions regarding water management, disaster preparedness, and environmental protection. For example, MLLMs can simultaneously analyze satellite imagery and textual weather predictions to deliver more precise and timely flood forecasts. Similarly, these models can optimize water use in agriculture by integrating data from soil moisture sensors with meteorological information, thereby promoting more sustainable irrigation practices (Herath et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2022).

This paper evaluates the effectiveness of prominent MLLMs, including Multimodal-GPT, GPT-4 Vision, Gemini, and LLaVA, in processing complex hydrological data for real-time environmental management. By investigating the performance of MLLMs across a range of scenarios designed to replicate real-world conditions, this paper aims to reveal the strengths and limitations of these advanced AI models in enhancing hydrological research and applications. Through this exploration, we seek to provide valuable insights that could shape future developments in hydrology, expanding the possibilities for how AI can be employed to manage and safeguard one of our most vital resources: water.

Methodology and Results

Four prominent MLLMs were selected for analysis based on their ability to handle multimodal inputs: Multimodal-GPT, GPT-4 Vision, Gemini, and LLaVA. Each model differs in core architecture and specialization, with GPT-4 Vision, for example, excelling in visual data processing alongside textual analysis, potentially suiting it for spatially rich hydrological applications. Various hydrological scenarios were designed to test each model's

responsiveness and accuracy. These included flood events, river discharge levels, and pollution incidents, featuring visual elements like on-site photographs, and textual descriptions providing context or posing queries about the visual data.

Data collection comprised both synthetic and real-world datasets, integrating images from sensor data with textual weather reports, historical hydrological data, and emergency response records. Models were evaluated based on the accuracy, relevance, and integration of their responses, measuring how effectively they could generate accurate and contextually relevant responses to multimodal prompts and integrate visual and textual data into coherent outputs.

The results indicated varying performance levels among the models. GPT-4 Vision consistently provided the most accurate interpretations of visual data and best integrated these with textual analyses in complex scenarios involving detailed image backgrounds and subtle water-related features. LLaVA also demonstrated strong performance, particularly in textual integration, though it was less consistent in purely visual tasks. Multimodal-GPT and Gemini, while effective overall, were less adept in scenarios requiring intricate visual recognition.

GPT-4 Vision's ability to accurately identify and interpret features such as flood extents and pollution levels is notably superior, even under challenging conditions such as cloud cover or shadows in the imagery. This capability underscores the potential utility of MLLMs in real-time monitoring systems for environmental management, such as flood management and pollution control. The quick processing and interpretation of complex datasets by these models could significantly enhance decision-making processes in hydrology.

Conclusions

This exploration into the use of MLLMs in hydrology underscores their potential to significantly enhance our understanding and management of hydrological phenomena. The superior capabilities of models like GPT-4 Vision in integrating and interpreting multimodal data suggest a promising future for their application in improving predictive models and real-time response systems in hydrology. Future research should aim at refining these models to boost accuracy, broaden their application in environmental science, and address challenges such as data biases and model interpretability to ensure their effective and ethical use.

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Enhancing Efficiency and Objectivity in Environmental Academic Peer Review Processes Through Artificial Intelligence

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Summary

The peer-review system, essential for maintaining academic integrity, is increasingly burdened by inefficiencies and subjectivity, impacting the dissemination of research. This study introduces an artificial intelligence (AI)-based framework designed to support the peer-review process by enhancing the accuracy, consistency, and timeliness of reviews. Our methodology leverages machine learning techniques to assess scientific manuscripts and grant proposals, aligning evaluations with domain-specific standards. Preliminary results indicate a potential reduction in review times and an increase in the objectivity of evaluations.

Introduction

The integrity of scientific discourse and the advancement of knowledge heavily rely on the peer-review process, a fundamental mechanism within academic publishing and grant funding frameworks (Tennant et al., 2017). This process serves as a gatekeeper for quality, ensuring that only research which meets specific scientific standards is disseminated and funded. Despite its pivotal role, the peer-review system faces significant challenges that undermine its effectiveness and efficiency (Horbach and Halfman, 2018). These challenges include prolonged review times, potential reviewer bias, and a frequent scarcity of expertise, particularly pronounced in interdisciplinary and rapidly evolving fields such as environmental modeling and software development (United Nations, 2023).

The increasing volume and complexity of submissions across scientific disciplines exacerbate these issues, placing a considerable burden on the traditional peer-review system. Reviewers often handle multiple articles simultaneously, leading to cognitive overload and potential oversights. Furthermore, the subjective nature of human evaluations can introduce inconsistencies in review outcomes, influenced by individual perspectives, expertise levels, and even unconscious biases. These factors collectively contribute to delays and variability in review quality, which can impede the timely dissemination of crucial scientific findings.

A significant knowledge gap exists in the application of advanced technologies to mitigate these inefficiencies and enhance the objectivity of the peer-review process (Dwivedi et al., 2023). While some automated tools and platforms offer rudimentary checks, few harness the power of artificial intelligence (AI) in a way that profoundly transforms the review process. Specifically, there is a lack of sophisticated AI systems that can understand and evaluate the complexity and nuance of high-level scientific content, particularly in specialized domains such as environmental science and related software tools (Pursnani et al., 2023).

This research aims to address these challenges by introducing an AI-driven framework designed to support and augment the human peer-review process. By leveraging machine learning and natural language processing, this framework aims to enhance the accuracy, consistency, and timeliness of reviews. Our approach focuses on automating the initial assessment of manuscripts and grant proposals to identify major strengths and weaknesses in alignment with domain-specific criteria. This support aims not only to streamline the review process but also to raise the overall quality of academic outputs by providing more structured and objective feedback to authors and grant applicants.

Methodology and Results

Our methodology integrates the development of a comprehensive review rubric, an advanced evaluation workflow, a robust training dataset, sophisticated AI models, and a user-friendly platform prototype.

A technical rubric was developed, encompassing over 100 specific evaluation criteria tailored to scrutinize scientific validity, methodology, novelty, and relevance within environmental modeling and software disciplines. This rubric supports a multimodal evaluation workflow, where both textual and visual content of submissions are systematically assessed. A scoring algorithm quantifies various dimensions of the review, providing a structured and quantifiable output that guides further human expert analysis.

To ensure the effectiveness of the AI, a diverse training dataset was curated, featuring a wide range of peer-reviewed articles and funded grant proposals. Importantly, we incorporated peer review data from European Geosciences Union (EGU) journals, which publish their peer review process and reviewer comments, providing a rich source of real-world evaluation feedback. This dataset was utilized to train both open-source and proprietary AI models, which were fine-tuned to adapt to the intricacies of environmental and software-related academic works. The fine-tuning process focused on optimizing the models for higher accuracy, precision, and recall in identifying key elements and potential issues in submissions.

The culmination of this research is embodied in a platform prototype designed with an emphasis on usability. This prototype facilitates easy interaction with AI-generated insights, allowing reviewers and editors to efficiently navigate through evaluations, manage review tasks, and communicate effectively within the academic community. Initial results from the deployment of this system indicate a reduction in review times, with improvements noted in the consistency and depth of reviews, highlighting the potential of AI to enhance the peer-review process significantly.

Conclusions

The integration of artificial intelligence into the peer-review process represents a transformative advancement with the potential to significantly enhance both the efficiency and objectivity of academic evaluations. The AI-enhanced framework developed in this study demonstrates a viable pathway for reducing the workload on human reviewers while simultaneously improving the consistency of the reviews provided. This is particularly critical in the fields of environmental modeling and software development, where the complexity and specialized nature of content require high levels of expertise and discernment.

Our findings suggest that the AI system can effectively perform initial manuscript and grant proposal assessments, accurately identifying key thematic and methodological elements. This capability allows reviewers to focus their efforts on deeper, more critical analyses, potentially leading to a more thorough and insightful review process. As a result, the overall quality of scholarly publications and funded research is expected to improve, fostering a more robust scientific discourse and facilitating faster dissemination of important findings.

The implications of this research extend beyond immediate improvements in review processes. By setting a precedent for the use of AI in academic evaluations, this study opens avenues for further technological enhancements and encourages a shift towards more digital, data-driven approaches in scholarly publishing and research funding. Future research will aim to refine the AI algorithms used, expanding their applicability to a broader range of scientific disciplines and exploring their integration with various publishing platforms.

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Enhancing Microclimate Control in Greenhouses Through Optimized Sensor Deployment Using Advanced Machine Learning Techniques

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Summary

Our study aimed to optimize microclimate sensor deployment in greenhouses for ideal plant growth conditions, minimizing unnecessary sensor use. Over four months and all seasons, we utilized 56 dual sensors for temperature and humidity in a high-tech greenhouse. Our method combined KMeans++ clustering for spatial distribution and gradient boosting for predictive accuracy. We innovatively applied the sine cosine algorithm (SCA) to enhance sensor placement optimization. Validated with LR, SVM, and XGBoost models, SCA, especially with XGBoost, outperformed, significantly improving microclimate control precision. This approach shows promise for resource efficiency and sustainability in Controlled Environment Agriculture.

Introduction

Automated systems have transformed industries by offering precision, continuous operation, and minimal human intervention. In agriculture, automated greenhouses play a crucial role in addressing challenges like climate change and labor scarcity while ensuring sustainability. Greenhouses control environmental factors precisely (Gurban & Andreescu, 2018), promoting faster plant growth and extending growing seasons (Lin & Chiu, 2005). Optimal sensor placement within greenhouses is essential for accurate measurements and decision-making. Machine learning techniques, including clustering and gradient boosting, help identify sensor locations effectively (Uyeh et al., 2022). This study introduces the Sine Cosine Algorithm (SCA) to optimize sensor placement by synthesizing insights from clustering and predictive models. The SCA efficiently explores sensor combinations, leading to near-optimal solutions and improved accuracy. Integration of SCA enhances the efficiency and interpretability of sensor placement, combining the strengths of ensemble techniques and optimization algorithms. The paper details the background, motivation, methodology, and results, emphasizing the importance of optimized sensor placement in automated greenhouse systems for precision agriculture.

Methodology and Result

Optimizing sensor placement is critical for efficiently managing automated greenhouses, ensuring precise data collection on environmental variables like temperature and humidity. Conventional methods often lead to inefficient monitoring. This study aims to develop a comprehensive approach for optimal sensor placement, addressing challenges like identifying optimal sensor locations and improving prediction accuracy. We combined machine learning techniques, such as K-means++ clustering and gradient boosting, and introduced the Sine Cosine Algorithm (SCA) for feature selection. The SCA efficiently explores sensor combinations, enhancing prediction accuracy. Two base models, K-means++ clustering and gradient boosting, are utilized to determine optimal sensor locations. The SCA, integrated with these models, synthesizes their outputs to achieve superior coverage and accuracy. The SCA utilizes stochastic optimization, mimicking oscillatory behavior to navigate complex search spaces.

$$x_{ij}^{t+1} = \begin{cases} x_{ij}^t + r_1 \cdot \sin(r_2) \cdot |r_3 P_j^t - x_{ij}^t| & \text{if } s \leq 0.5 \\ x_{ij}^t + r_1 \cdot \cos(r_2) \cdot |r_3 P_j^t - x_{ij}^t| & \text{if } s > 0.5 \end{cases}$$

$$r_1 = a - t \frac{a}{T_{max}}$$

The movement of search agents is determined by parameters such as r1, r2, and r3, ensuring a balance between exploration and exploitation (Mirjalili, 2016). The proposed framework emphasizes predictive performance while ensuring optimal spatial coverage, offering a balanced solution for optimal sensor placement in automated greenhouses.

Monthly analysis covered four distinct seasons: February (winter), April (spring), June (summer), and October (autumn). Temperature and humidity data were analyzed separately. Results, including base models and SCA-optimized locations, are detailed in Table 1. SCA's effectiveness is highlighted, synergistically enhancing coverage in certain months like June and October and selectively combining predictions in others. This adaptive approach highlights SCA's flexibility in optimizing sensor placements based on environmental conditions. Compared to base models, SCA consistently exhibited enhanced accuracy and precision, validating its effectiveness in optimal sensor placement. Comparative analysis with machine learning algorithms affirmed SCA's superior performance across all error metrics.

Table 1. MAE Validation results using various models

Month	Metric	KMeans++			Gradient Boost			SCA			Best Model
		LR	XGB	SVM	LR	XGB	SVM	LR	XGB	SVM	
Feb	Humidity	0.4813	0.3552	0.4020	0.6630	0.3640	0.4319	0.3833	0.2930	0.3390	SCA-XGB
	Temperature	0.1167	0.0871	0.0996	0.1666	0.0806	0.1129	0.0905	0.0603	0.0852	SCA-XGB
Apr	Humidity	0.3819	0.3664	0.3686	0.6167	0.4789	0.5337	0.3484	0.3147	0.3415	SCA-XGB
	Temperature	0.0831	0.0640	0.0710	0.3751	0.1514	0.2333	0.0772	0.0618	0.0696	SCA-XGB
June	Humidity	0.1332	0.0856	0.1114	0.3026	0.1757	0.2231	0.0971	0.0669	0.0809	SCA-XGB
	Temperature	0.1229	0.0846	0.0977	0.4741	0.3178	0.4133	0.1113	0.0739	0.0883	SCA-XGB
Oct	Humidity	0.3084	0.2431	0.2716	0.3573	0.2704	0.3194	0.2974	0.2182	0.2487	SCA-XGB
	Temperature	0.1269	0.0876	0.1091	0.2541	0.0723	0.0985	0.0911	0.0513	0.0616	SCA-XGB

Conclusion

This study introduces an advanced framework for optimizing sensor placement in automated greenhouses, integrating predictions from KMeans++ clustering and Gradient Boosting models with the SCA. Our methodology challenges conventional practices, enhancing precision and efficiency while minimizing predictive error and sensor usage. This research offers a scalable solution for sustainable management and productivity improvement in Controlled Environment Agriculture.

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Harnessing Choice Experiments to Elicit Preferred Configurations of Trustworthy AI augmented Decision Support Systems (AI-DSS) for Crop Certified Advisors

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Summary

Increasing diffusion of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and sensor data driven Precision Agriculture (PA) technologies have shown the promise of AI and PA technologies to improve efficiencies in agricultural production systems and decrease adverse impacts of agriculture on environment compared to traditional approaches. Yet, many complex trade-offs surrounding the design and configuration of trustworthy AI augmented decision support systems (AI-DSS) for advancing responsible and ethical PA have recently surfaced, e.g. data ownership, transparency, accuracy, precision, and accountability dimensions of AI-DSS. This study harnesses choice experiments to elicit stated preferences of crop certified advisors for informing the design and configurations of trustworthy AI-DSS.

Introduction

Process-based models have been traditionally used to provide decision support to the farmers and watershed/environmental managers for managing multiple competing goals such as maximizing farmer net profits and crop yields while minimizing the environmental impacts of agriculture on water quality, climate change, air quality and biodiversity loss. The accuracy and precision of AI-DSS in PA applications is however outperforming traditional approaches in some cropping and livestock systems. Yet, data ownership challenges and cost of AI-DSS has created new set of inequities and privacy challenges (Gardezi et al. 2024). Crop Certified Advisors (CCAs) serve as “canary in the coal mine” for initial update of AI-DSS in precision agricultural arena. This study aims at estimating the marginal willingness to pay of CCAs for cheaper, medium range and expensive AI-DSS with various accuracy, precision and data ownership structures. Choice experiments, supplemented with conjoint analysis, provide a well-established approach to estimate the CCA market demand for various configurations of AI-DSS, and infer the trust placed on purchasing an AI-DSS conditional upon its underlying attributes and levels of attributes.

Methodology and Results

A choice experiment survey was designed with five embedded experiments and circulated through a listserv of ~2600 CCAs with a lottery based incentive. We received responses from 771 participants. The choice experiment was framed as follows: “Imagine comparing between artificial intelligence decision support systems (AI-DSS) that can help you decide what and when to plant, how much to irrigate & fertilize, and when to harvest. In the next five questions, you will have a choice between three AI-DSS that all use artificial intelligence, but they differ in their cost, accuracy, precision, and data ownership attributes.” The choice experimental data was analyzed by using three alternate models: (a) Standard (McFadden) Logit Model; (b) Random Utility Mixed Logit Model and (c) Latent Class Analysis (Holmes et al. 2017). Table 1 presents results from all three models. All three models provide comparable results; however, Latent Class Analysis provides most robust estimates. We find that 48.44% of CCAs opt out (Class One) and 51.55% prefer one of the three AI-DSS configural designs. We estimate that CCAs are willing to pay \$3.76/acre/year for each percentage point

improvement in the accuracy of AI-DSS; \$0.88/meter² improvement in precision (smaller is better); and \$0.12 for data ownership by CCAs, farmers and AI-DSS companies.

Table 1. Estimated coefficients from choice experiments. *** shows significance at 99% level, ** at 95% level and * at 90% level. Marginal willingness to pay for each attribute are estimated from the imputed costs.

Attributes of AI-DSS	M1: Standard McFadden Logit (s.e.)	M1: Marginal Willingness to Pay (US\$) (s.e.)	M2: Random Utility Mixed Logit (s.e.)	M2: Marginal Willingness to Pay (US\$) (s.e.)	M3: Latent Class Analysis of Class 1 (s.e.)	M3: Marginal Willingness to Pay of Class 1 (US\$) (s.e.)	M3: Latent Class Analysis of Class 2 (s.e.)	M3: Marginal Willingness to Pay of Class 2 (US\$) (s.e.)
Accuracy (%)	0.0311*** (0.0070)	1.1669*** (0.2624)	0.0297*** (0.0072)	0.9764*** (0.2369)	70*** (0.1352)	1.06E+18 (2.05E+15)	82.1907*** (0.1310)	3.7665*** (0.0060)
Precision (meter ²)	-0.0077* (0.0043)	-0.2906* (0.1639)	-0.0103** (0.0048)	-0.3401** (0.1578)	100*** (0.1622)	1.52E+18 (2.46E+15)	19.3220*** (0.1572)	0.8854*** (0.0072)
Data Ownership	0.1036 (0.1728)	3.8826 (6.4745)	0.0206 (0.1835)	0.6778 (6.0292)	1*** (0.0080)	1.52E+16 (1.22E+14)	2.6326*** (0.0077)	0.1206*** (0.0003)
Cost (US\$)	-0.0267*** (0.0031)		-0.0304*** (0.0044)		6.60E-17 (0.4251)		21.8214*** (0.4121)	
Random Utility/ Normal sd(cost)			0.0123 (0.0059)	0.4042 (0.1938)				
ASC* (for Opt Out alternative)	(base)		(base)		0.5372*** (0.0080)	8.14E+15 (1.22E+14)	4.27E-25 (0.0078)	1.96E-26 (0.0003)
ASC (AI-DSS1)	0.2135** (0.0799)	7.9992** (2.9955)	0.2115** (0.0799)	6.9482** (2.6258)	0.4627*** (0.0115)	7.01E+15 (1.75E+14)	0.4495*** (0.0112)	0.0205*** (0.0005)
ASC (AI-DSS2)	-0.9181*** (0.2030)	-34.3850*** (7.6047)	-0.9408*** (0.2057)	-30.9013*** (6.7586)	1.27E-21 (0.0080)	1.92E-05 (1.22E+14)	0.3673*** (0.0077)	0.0168*** (0.0003)
ASC (AI-DSS3)	-0.8431*** (0.2104)	-31.5757*** (7.8819)	-0.8799*** (0.2152)	-28.9016*** (7.0710)	4.32E-35 (0.0064)	6.55E-19 (9.78E+13)	0.1831*** (0.0062)	0.0083*** (0.0002)
ASC(AI-DSS) [†]					(base)		0.0622** (0.0323)	0.0028** (0.0014)
Wald chi2(4)	189.84		162.96					
Log (pseudo)likelihood	-4665.327		-4664.927		-51599.565		-51599.565	
No of observations	15,292		15,292					
No of cases	3,823		3,823		3823		3823	
No of participants	771		771		771		771	

*ASC= Alternative Specific Constant; [†]Latent Variable (AI-DSS);

Conclusions

We present an empirical choice experimental methodology to ascertain stated preferences of stakeholders (CCAs, in this study) for configuring different levels of attributes associated with variable costs for trustworthy AI-DSS. We discover that 51% of the CCA sampled participants have statistically significant willingness to pay and adopt AI-DSS. Improvements in accuracy and precision of AI-DSS, complemented with privacy enhancing data ownership design of AI-DSS will have the largest potential for scaling up AI-DSS to improve agricultural yields while lowering their adverse environmental impacts. Our team is launching similar choice experiments for farmers and urban gardeners in agricultural systems arena. Further, similar choice experiments are being designed to test AI-DSS configurations in water resources and climate change mitigation and adaptation policy designs.

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Artificial Intelligence Tools and Software Libraries for environmental modeling, computing and communication

Development of a Communication Library for Large-Scale Data Processing and Transfer in the Hydrological Domain

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Summary

The library presented (HydroRTC) addresses the challenge of managing and distributing the exponential volume of hydrological data by introducing a web-based communication library. Leveraging advanced web technologies like WebSockets, WebRTC, and Node.js, HydroRTC facilitates large-scale data sharing and analysis through peer-to-peer communication. It enables smart data transmission and streaming of large datasets in real-time. Three use cases highlight its versatility: server-to-peer with intelligent data scheduling, peer-to-peer data sharing, and peer-to-server data exchange. HydroRTC enhances research efficiency and collaboration capabilities in the hydrological and environmental domain by enabling real-time, high-throughput data sharing and transfer.

Introduction

In earth sciences, the vast amount of information generated exceeds researchers' and data collectors' capacity for easy ingestion and digestion. This challenge is particularly evident in hydrology, encompassing remote sensing, reanalysis data, sensor data, and various other sources. Governmental agencies, research institutions, and diverse organizations primarily manage this data, conducting comprehensive analyses across various metrics, covering flood extents, rainfall distributions, resource allocation, humidity, and temperature conditions, crucial for informed decision-making processes (Ames et al., 2012). Understanding how this data is used is key to leveraging new technological advancements, especially in terms of web technologies and systems. These steps not only enable more efficient data management but also enhance overall functionality and utility, significantly contributing to the progression of earth sciences. Conventional methods of managing, storing, and distributing data often revolve around server-based architectures, primarily growing through horizontal scaling. Data hosted on servers is accessible through various mechanisms, typically employing TCP/IP services over the internet. Despite their utility, centralized systems face several challenges, leading to server overload, performance degradation, and potential data loss (Essawy et al., 2016). Recent technological integrations, such as node-based systems in cloud architectures, offer solutions by distributing data handling across multiple nodes. Alternative approaches, like peer-to-peer connectivity paired with server technologies, offer efficient means of managing and distributing data, moving towards data decentralization (Demir & Szczepanek, 2017).

Methodology and Results

The library addresses the challenge of managing large data volumes and facilitating connectivity between peers by aiming to reduce server requirements for robust real-time data sharing and collaboration. This framework employs two interconnected approaches: a server-side implementation responsible for facilitating peer connections, managing peer information, and enabling seamless interaction for data sharing and tasks among connected peers; and a client-side implementation connecting to the server using event listeners and handlers for user inputs. Both implementations are based on Node.js development, share commonalities in event listeners and handlers, and allow for various communication and sharing schemes. The server-side component, built on Node.js, utilizes WebSocket connections through Socket.IO to enable bidirectional communication between the server and clients. It handles event triggers, facilitating user registration, WebRTC setup, data streaming, and distributed computing tasks. The server implementation is tailored to manage various types of

data commonly found in hydrology, including large data sizes, and utilizes existing Node.js tools for data streaming and compression. On the client side, Web sockets via Socket.IO and Peer.js' WebRTC connections are employed for seamless message passing and communication channels among different clients. IndexedDB serves as client-side storage for data sourced from the server or other peers, facilitating data sharing and storage flexibility. Moreover, data handlers for commonly found formats have been added to both implementations, including HDF5, netCDF, GRIBB, GIS shapefiles, raster files, TIFF/geoTIFF, JSON, among others. Figure 1 shows the architecture of a peer-to-peer chat interface application with the aim to evaluate the data throughput at different data transfer sizes, highlighting the importance of decentralized communication real-time data sharing and analysis. Figure 1 shows the architecture of the client/server implementations, as well as the dependencies the library rely on.

Figure 1. Example result from case study for peer-to-peer data sharing

Conclusions

The HydroRTC library represents a significant advancement in facilitating streamlined data handling within hydrologic sciences. By leveraging specific server and client-side technologies, the library enables versatile use-case scenarios, including smart data transmission, direct server-client data retrieval, peer-to-peer data sharing, and distributed work capabilities. This marks a step towards employing decentralized systems for real-time and collaborative data and workflow sharing. Moving forward, integration with existing solutions such as cloud providers and institutional data solutions would allow an easy integration for the library's growth, aligning with the trend towards progressive web applications and decentralized systems. While the library harnesses cutting-edge technology for both server-side and client-side applications, challenges like data sizing limits and event blocking require further exploration. This can be further explored by creating new examples and use cases on the integration of the library for the creation of large-scale applications. In terms of security concerns, solutions such as the integration of blockchain technology could ensure secure data transfer and robust tracking of application usage. Additionally, as part of a larger scheme of tools aiming to provide a comprehensive solution for hydrological analysis on the web, the library contributes to democratizing access to information and expanding hydrological analysis tools within the contemporary web environment.

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A Platform of Monitoring Network Design for Environmental Infrastructures

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Summary

Monitoring of environmental infrastructures in the age of smart city and digital is of important. Precisely design monitoring network for environmental infrustruces such as water quality monitoring stations received many attentions. However, in many cases the basic data is very limited for designing. We develop a new algorithm for cost-effective network design without local observation of the river. A website is developed for design for any rivers.

Introduction

The Water Quality Monitoring Network (WQMN) design is most empirical in practices so far. Design parameters includes water quality indicators, monitoring sites, and sampling frequency, which are all linked to the cost. Among them, location is the most important, which directly affects the accuracy of data and the budget. Previously studies few considered the cost of monitoring stations in the optimization objectives, while means a design in practice need to meet the maximum budgets requirements. This study main considers this kind of restriction for optimize the response effective of the network as if the pollution events comes.

Methodology and Results

We propose a simple pathway for network design. The basic idea is straightforward:(1) minimizing the total cost of water quality monitoring stations and (2) minimizing the average detection time of the contamination events. The candidate sets of monitoring locations are selected by topology at first. The stations are represented by an adjacency matrix L of river network, wherein the element L_{ij} indicates whether the i -th station is adjacent to the j -th station, and if it is adjacent, the value is 1. The velocity of each river section between stations is represented by matrix V , in which the element V_{ij} represents the velocity between the i -th station and the j -th station. The velocity is obtained by Manning's formula (1).

$$V = \frac{k}{n} R_h^{2/3} \times s^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

The average detection time Tr of the network is calculated by the formula (2).

$$Tr = \sum(0.5 * \frac{D_{ij}}{V_{ij}})/N, \text{ where } L_{ij} = 1 \quad (2)$$

Where the distance of each station is represented by matrix D , in which the element D_{ij} means the distance between the i -th station and the j -th station. N means the number of river sections. The total cost of water quality monitoring stations C is calculated by the formula (3).

$$C = \alpha \times \text{Number of stations} \quad (3)$$

Where α means the cost of single station, it varies from local policy. The cost required to treat the contaminated water L is calculated by the following formula.

$$L = Tr \times \beta \times Q(v_{ij}) \quad (4)$$

$$Q(v_{ij}) = \text{width} \times \text{depth} \times \text{velocity} \quad (5)$$

Where β means the cost of sewage treatment per unit mass, $Q(v_{ij})$ means river discharge between the i -th station and the j -th station. The optimization formula F is summarized by the formula (6).

$$F = C + L \quad (6)$$

Min(F), where $Tr > T$

The F value of all potential observation stations is calculated, and the smallest F is the best site. We may also consider the risks distribution among each river reach, described by a matrix of R , according to the local knowledge on pollution sources.

Besides, it integrated a GIS-based module that can automatically identify the necessary of parameters, and calculating the optimal locations and number of monitoring sites. The process now involves the use of predefined ArcGIS script tools, developed and optimized within the ArcGIS environment to ensure efficient and accurate data handling. As the workflow progresses, predefined ArcGIS ModelBuilder combined with ArcPy scripts and other professional GIS tools supported by ESRI are utilized for complex spatial analysis and data processing. These tools, with a broad application spectrum that includes spatial interpolation, geostatistics, and network analysis, form a robust backbone for GIS analysis.

Post data analysis and processing, the end product is a visualized Water Quality Monitoring Network (WQMN) map. This map intuitively displays the distribution of water quality monitoring points and potential conditions. To achieve this, the design module must manage input variables, which often encompass various constraints such as the number and range of monitoring points. Moreover, the WQMN design module's framework must adapt to different development environments. While the core development path remains consistent across offline and web-based platforms, the tools used may vary. For web development, ArcGIS API for JavaScript or ArcGIS Online is commonly employed to create interactive web applications, allowing users to access and manipulate GIS data and maps via the internet.

In summary, the WQMN design module within the GIS toolbox framework is a sophisticated system that relies on a suite of predefined tools and scripts. This ensures a process that is efficient, accurate, and user-friendly, from data input to the final visualization of maps. We take Maozhou River in Shenzhen, China, as an example to demonstrate the usability of the WQMN design tool and algorithm. A map of monitoring network is successfully produced with the number of WQMN stations reduced to 38. The platform for global application will be online soon for testing.

Conclusions

A cost-effective based water quality monitoring network design algorithm is proposed. A WebGIS based platform for automatic data-free water quality monitoring network design is developed. It can provide services for any rivers.

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Gamifying Flood Mitigation Education: Development and Implementation of Floodcraft in Minecraft for Enhancing Youth Resilience to Flooding

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Summary

Floodcraft offers an immersive educational experience, teaching children flood mitigation techniques and showcasing decision-making in flood protection. Through interactive challenges, players simulate real-world scenarios, implementing floodwalls, sandbagging, wet floodproofing, and structure elevation. The game fosters hands-on learning, allowing students to experiment with mitigation strategies and observe their effectiveness. Floodcraft's gameplay mechanics promote deep understanding, empowering self-directed learning tailored to diverse flooding scenarios. Clear instructions, visual guidance, and NPC assistance enhance player comprehension and engagement. Integration of ChatGPT provides intelligent conversational support, further enriching the learning experience. By simulating real-world behaviors, Floodcraft facilitates intuitive learning and skill development in flood resilience.

Introduction

Flooding remains one of the most pervasive natural disasters, posing significant risks to economic stability, infrastructure, human safety, and environmental sustainability globally (Ashizawa et al., 2022). The increasing frequency and intensity of flood events, attributed to climate change and urbanization, exacerbate these challenges, necessitating effective flood risk management and community resilience strategies (Sermet and Demir, 2022). Traditional educational methods for disseminating flood risk knowledge and mitigation strategies often fail to engage younger audiences—an essential demographic for long-term community resilience planning (UNESCO, 2017). Engaging educational interventions are required to bridge this knowledge gap, particularly interventions that resonate with youth culture and learning preferences (Sajja et al., 2023). The digital nativity of the younger generation calls for an educational paradigm that integrates entertainment with learning, leveraging platforms that are both familiar and engaging to them.

Minecraft, a sandbox video game, emerges as a formidable platform in this context due to its immense popularity among children and its proven capability as an educational tool (Baek et al., 2020). The game's open-ended nature allows for the creation of dynamic, interactive learning environments where complex concepts can be explored through hands-on activities and simulation (Simpson, 2022). Previous studies have highlighted Minecraft's effectiveness in enhancing engagement and learning outcomes in various educational contexts, yet there remains a significant gap in its application specifically for flood risk education (Louis-E, 2022).

This paper introduces Floodcraft, a Minecraft-based educational game designed to fill this gap by teaching children about flood mitigation strategies through interactive gameplay. Floodcraft integrates critical flood mitigation methods such as building floodwalls, sandbagging, wet floodproofing, and elevating structures within the engaging Minecraft environment. This approach not only aims to educate but also to inspire proactive attitudes towards disaster preparedness among the youth. By doing so, Floodcraft seeks to contribute to the cultivation of a generation that is better equipped to respond to and manage flood risks, thereby enhancing community resilience over the long term.

Methodology and Results

Floodcraft was developed on Minecraft Java Edition, chosen for its compatibility and modifiability. The game's design centered on integrating flood mitigation strategies into gameplay, including floodwalls, sandbagging, wet floodproofing, and structure elevation. Mod development involved creating new blocks and entities, enhancing gameplay functionality and educational content delivery. City design utilized external structures and structure blocks to create realistic environments for flood mitigation tasks. Gameplay mechanics were implemented using command blocks to control player actions and simulate flood events. Floodcraft's gameplay mechanics enable students to actively engage with flood mitigation techniques, fostering a deep understanding of their application. Through trial-and-error experimentation, players learn to select and implement appropriate strategies, guided by NPC instructions and visual references. The integration of ChatGPT enhances the learning experience, providing personalized assistance and troubleshooting suggestions. By simulating real-world materials and behaviors, Floodcraft facilitates intuitive learning and skill development in flood resilience.

Conclusions

The development and implementation of the Floodcraft game on the Minecraft platform provides an innovative approach for educating children on critical flood protection methods. Students gain firsthand experience applying essential strategies like floodwalls, sandbagging, wet floodproofing, and elevation by interactive gameplay features simulating real-world flood mitigation techniques. To validate the pedagogical impact of Floodcraft, conducting quantitative tests on learning outcomes and qualitative surveys on user engagement becomes essential. However, existing research on serious games and Minecraft education shows the value of an experiential, simulation-based learning tool for motivating students and enhancing their understanding of complex systems.

Floodcraft can help the next generation to engage in building community resilience to flooding by using a popular and creative tool that younger people highly appreciate. Game-based education in the proposed project enhances problem-solving skills, raises environmental awareness, and encourages social responsibility regarding flood risks. Floodcraft has the potential to expand and teach additional flood-proofing techniques, safety protocols, and sustainable development practices. Overall, this project demonstrates Minecraft's potential as an engaging platform for preparing students to mitigate and adapt to climate challenges.

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Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning for RICE50+

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Summary

The Regional Integrated Climate Economy (RICE) model unrealistically simplifies the collective action dynamics of cooperation and non-cooperation among agents. To add realism to inter-agent dynamics, we reshape RICE as a partially observable stochastic game and apply multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) to obtain independently trained agents. We use the Gini coefficient of emissions control rates to compare the degrees of cooperation. Contrary to our hypothesis that MARL agents would be incentivized towards defection, we find that MARL agents are more cooperative than non-cooperative RICE agents, indicating that MARL agents may exhibit emergent cooperation.

Introduction

Integrated assessment models (IAM), such as the Regional Integrated Climate Economy (RICE) model are the standard means of modelling the collective action dynamics of cooperation and non-cooperation in climate economic systems (Nordhaus 2015). Cooperation in RICE assumes the existence of a social planner and non-assuming a fixed strategy of other agents. In reality, there is no global social planner and regions do change their strategies over time (Yang 2020). To increase realistic collective action dynamics, we reshape RICE as a partially observable stochastic game, such that multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) can be applied, allowing for learned strategic behavior between agents. In MARL, agents learn a policy function mapping observed states to actions to optimize their individual pay-off. By including the actions of other agents as observations, MARL agents can base their decisions on the observed strategies of others. We apply MARL to JUSTICE, a climate-justice-oriented implementation of RICE50+, which we will refer to as JUSTICE-MARL (Gazzotti 2022; Biswas et al. 2023). We compare JUSTICE-MARL agents to RICE50+ agents under cooperative and non-cooperative modes using the Gini coefficient of emissions control rates (ECR), indicating the degree to which the emissions reductions burden is shared. We hypothesize that agents in JUSTICE-MARL will have a higher ECR Gini coefficient than non-cooperative and cooperative RICE50+ agents within a given shared socioeconomic pathway (SSP) scenario.

Methodology and Results

We learn a policy on the JUSTICE-MARL simulation using proximal policy optimization (PPO) for an initial empirical evaluation (Schulman et al. 2017). Agent observations are net output, emissions, regional temperature, global temperature, economic damage, abatement cost, and the previous action of all other agents. The pay-off function is per capita consumption, given a degree of inequality aversion. Actions are savings rate and emissions control rate of regions.

As visible in left two graphs of the above figures, our hypothesis was unsupported. Note that the RICE50+ ECRs plummet to 0 in the final 15 years of the simulation; hence, the volatility of Gini coefficients near the end. Awareness of the actions of other agents increases the equitable distribution of ECRs in both SSPs. This indicates that a degree of cooperation is possible without the unrealistic assumption of a global social planner. It could

also be the case that our shared network PPO approach fails to differentiate between agents, thereby not learning to defect.

To control against the circumstance in which agents equitably defect, resulting in a low gini, we report the comparison of ECRs in absolute values. The right two graphs of the above figure indicate that JUSTICE-MARL agents opt for higher ECRs than non-cooperative RICE agents.

Conclusions

While not supporting our hypothesis, our findings illustrate agents who are aware of each other's actions seem to cooperate even when maximizing a private payoff. Potential causes include emergent properties of a complex adaptive system, or a model quirk derived from the use of a shared PPO model. Follow up ablation studies will be required to determine the conditions conducive to emergent cooperation. Researchers interested in applying MARL to IAMs are welcome to use our codebase (<https://github.com/pollockDeVis/JUSTICE/>).

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**Stream D. System design,
identification and uncertainty in
modelling complex environmental &
agricultural systems**

New and improved methods in agricultural systems modelling

Towards Hybrid Models Combining Deep Learning and Process-Based Components for Agricultural Modelling

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Summary

Biophysical models offer valuable insights into climate-phenology relationships in both natural and agricultural settings. However, there are substantial structural discrepancies across models, and they require site-specific recalibration, often yielding inconsistent predictions under similar climate scenarios. Machine learning methods offer data-driven solutions but often lack interpretability and alignment with existing knowledge. We present a unified framework for cherry tree phenology prediction, integrating conventional biophysical models with a neural network to address the structural disparities. We evaluate our hybrid model in an extensive case study predicting cherry tree phenology in Japan, South Korea and Switzerland. Our approach consistently outperforms traditional models in predicting blooming dates across years. Additionally, the neural network's adaptability facilitates parameter learning for specific tree varieties, enabling robust generalization to new sites without site-specific recalibration. This hybrid model leverages both biophysical constraints and data-driven flexibility, offering a promising avenue for accurate and interpretable phenology modeling.

Introduction

Phenology models generally assume the daily accumulation of temperature-dependent units towards some threshold at which a phenological transition occurs. Commonly used models, however, differ in how they relate daily temperature to their contribution towards vernalization and display differences in behaviour under the same climate scenarios (Luedeling et al, 2011; Fernandez et al, 2020). The models have typically been proposed as the simplest functions that are able to explain observations from controlled experiments on optimal chilling temperatures and effective temperature ranges, and weight their contribution accordingly. These models work well for predicting blooming dates but do not fully capture the true dynamics that are known to be more complex (Fernandez et al, 2020). The structural differences between these biophysical models, of which phenology models are a core component, are the main source of uncertainty in yield projections under climate change (Asseng et al, 2013; Wang et al, 2017). As consequence, crop models require extensive calibration to account for the specific crop dynamics of the considered site, and parameters do not generalize well to new locations (Wallach et al, 2021). Hybrid modelling (Karpatne et al, 2017) has been recently introduced as a means to improve data-efficiency and interpretability in machine learning models by constraining them to solutions that are consistent with domain knowledge and has been successfully applied in a wide variety of domains (Reichstein et al, 2019; Shen et al, 2023), but not in agricultural modelling.

Methodology and Results

We compare the proposed model with three phenology models that have been optimized using a grid search of their parameter space and find the model consistently shows an improved ability to predict blooming dates in unobserved seasons. Moreover, the flexibility of the substituted component allows the model to combine data from various sites to learn parameters specific to tree varieties which, due to its biophysical constraints, show generalization capabilities without requiring re-calibration. Figure 1 provides a schematic overview of two approaches modeling the phenological stages between dormancy initiation and flowering. The structural disagreement between different process-based model candidates (Top) is reflected in their predictions of when the chilling requirement is fulfilled. The scatter plot on the right shows the disagreement between two process-based models on the moment of dormancy release, despite roughly agreeing on the moment of bloom.

Substituting the model component showing structural disagreement with a data driven component (Bottom) improves flowering date predictions and reduces the disagreement between models.

Figure 1. A schematic overview of two approaches modeling the phenological stages between dormancy initiation and flowering

Conclusions

Machine learning models can help biophysical models (and vice versa) for improved predictions. In this case we study plant phenology by substituting the process-based function modeling temperature contribution towards vernalization by a neural network. In all considered environments, this hybrid model improves with respect to the baseline of three commonly used process-based models that were fit using an extensive grid search of their parameter space.

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High-Resolution Daily Actual Evapotranspiration Estimation in Agricultural Fields Using Cloud-Free Sentinel Imagery

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Summary

This study utilizes daily, cloud-free Sentinel-2 satellite imagery sourced from SpaceEye, a neural network-based tool that integrates multispectral and radiofrequency data to reconstruct clear daily images. Leveraging this dataset, we trained a Neural Network model to estimate Actual Evapotranspiration (ETa) at 30-meter spatial resolution and daily temporal resolution throughout the agricultural growing season. This approach enables daily estimates of ETa over the agricultural fields, even under cloudy conditions or on the days with no satellite overpass.

Introduction

Accurate estimation of ETa is vital for effective water management in agriculture and can facilitate optimal irrigation scheduling and crop yield predictions. Remote sensing serves as a valuable tool for obtaining ETa estimates by capturing data across large areas and over time; however, challenges exist due to coarse spatial resolution, low revisit frequency of satellites, and cloud cover obstruction. While satellites with higher revisit frequencies offer improved temporal resolution, they often sacrifice spatial resolution. These trade-offs pose significant constraints on obtaining precise ETa estimates at the temporal and spatial scales needed by farmers. To address this challenge, we leveraged a cloud-free satellite imagery product sourced from SpaceEye; it is a neural network-based tool capable of integrating multispectral and radiofrequency data to reconstruct daily images with the same bands and spatial resolution as Sentinel-2 imagery (Zhao et al., 2023).

Methodology and Results

We employed a simple backpropagation neural network to estimate ETa for an agricultural farm in Ferguson Township, Centre County, PA. We considered the U.S. Geological Survey Provisional ETa generated from Landsat satellite imagery (*Landsat Collection 2 Level-3 Provisional Actual Evapotranspiration Science Product courtesy of the U.S. Geological Survey*) to be the ground truth data for assessing ETa estimates (Senay, 2018; Senay et al., 2023). Raw bands and select vegetation indices (e.g., Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index; see Amani & Shafizadeh-Moghadam, (2023)) derived from the SpaceEye imagery were used as training data for the neural network model. These vegetation indices are considered to be correlated with ETa values. The agricultural farm includes three fields ranging in size from 11 to 14 hectares. All three fields were planted with silage corn. Additionally, as of 2019, two eddy covariance towers have been installed on the farm.

Preliminary findings indicate that ETa can be estimated from optical bands of the satellite imagery product with relatively good accuracy at high spatiotemporal resolution. The ETa estimates derived from optical satellite imagery showed a good match with the spatially autocorrelated ground truth data (withheld for validation) over the agricultural field.

Conclusions

This study explored the potential of optical satellite imagery to estimate ETa at a high spatiotemporal resolution using a neural network model and a cloud-free satellite imagery product to overcome some of the challenges (i.e., coarse spatial resolution, infrequent satellite revisits, and cloud cover interference) associated with remote sensing data. The findings demonstrate that ETa values can be estimated from optical bands of satellite imagery

with an acceptable degree of accuracy. While more sophisticated models could be leveraged to capture more complex relationships between optical bands and ETa values, this work presents a promising methodology for enhancing the spatial and temporal resolution of ETa estimates from optical remote sensing data.

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Reliable Decision-Making Under Uncertainty in Hierarchical Multi-criterion Problems

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Summary

Many societal and industrial problem solving tasks, including agricultural problems, are conveniently decomposed into hierarchical subproblems. In such problems, an independent decision-making process for the lower-level problem causes a deviation in the expected outcome at the upper-level problem. In this study, we provide a new and computationally efficient evolutionary approach for upper-level decision-makers to analyze the vagaries of lower-level decision-making to choose a preferred solution with a minimum deviation from their expectations. Using an evolutionary multi-objective optimization approach, we demonstrate the concept on a watershed management problem. The approach is generic and can be applied to other similar hierarchical management problems to achieve minimum deviation with a more predictive and reliable outcome.

Introduction

Many societal problems are often divided into multiple hierarchical levels for convenient management and decision-making purposes. For example, the effort to reduce pollution to the environment due to excessive use of fertilizers is divided into two hierarchical levels. At the upper level, the policy-makers attempt to come up with optimal tax rates on different fertilizer prices to minimize overall environmental effects and also maximize revenue, while at the lower level, farmers decide what and how much fertilizer to use to produce maximum crop and without paying much on taxes. There is a clear hierarchy between the two levels, as farmers must work with the given tax rates already fixed by the policy-makers. Such a hierarchical system allows both levels to have their own flexibility, rather than a big government deciding exactly what each farmer should and should not do.

When each level has multiple conflicting objectives (such as revenue versus environmental effect at the upper level and cost versus productivity at the lower level), each level produces a Pareto set of alternate trade-off solutions. One tax rate fixation at the upper level will result in several alternate solutions at the lower level.

While the models of objectives and constraints can have uncertainty in real world, this hierarchical problem introduces a new source of uncertainty, which is rarely modeled and discussed in the literature. The upper level's decision depends on the specific Pareto solution chosen by the lower level decision-makers, making the upper level problem uncertain. Therefore, it is likely that the prediction of upper-level objectives will be associated with uncertainty due to the independence of decision-making at the lower level. This talk will focus on the unavoidable uncertainty that arises in hierarchical problems and propose a reliable decision-making strategy to reduce uncertainty in upper-level predictions.

Methodology and Results

It is proposed that for every upper-level solution, the difference between the extremes of upper-level objective vectors caused by alternate Pareto solutions at the lower level is minimized. This will cause a different bi-level optimization problem than the original problem, but in the end will locate the reliable solution that will have a minimum deviation of the upper-level outcome from the predicted values. An evolutionary bi-level optimization (EBO) algorithm is employed to find a reliable solution. After demonstrating the proposed method on a two-objective upper and two-objective lower-level test problem, it is applied to the Honeyoey Creek-Pine Creek watershed in Michigan. The policy-makers announce that farmers can choose a maximum of five of 11 Best Management Practice (BMP) options to maximize their revenue per dollar of BMP implementation and maximize productivity. On the other hand, the policy-maker's goal was to minimize total subsidies and minimize sediment

loading computed by the SWAT modeling tool. Our bi-level optimization finds a specific combination of BMPs that produces a reliable prediction of upper-level goals, despite uncertainties involved in the lower-level decision-making process, demonstrating the usefulness of the proposed approach. Figure 1 shows upper-level objective values for different BMP combinations. The inset lower-level objective variation produces a small spread in objectives at the upper level, compared to the large variation by another largely uncertain BMP combination. Our approach recommends the use of “tree and shrub establishment” and “vegetative barrier” as two BMPs to achieve a reliable solution to the overall bilevel problem.

Figure 1. Our approach finds “tree and shrub establishment” and “vegetative barrier” as the most robust and reliable predictive BMPs

Conclusions

This study introduces a new source of decision-making uncertainty associated with hierarchical problems often encountered in practice. Our approach and presented results indicate that policy-makers can expect to have a better prediction of their decision-making outcomes due to better handling of uncertainties in the lower-level entities, such as policy users, farmers and local businesses, making the resulting solution reliable and less unpredictable.

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Overcoming Challenges in Agricultural Extension With AgXQA and AgRoBERTa: A New Benchmark Dataset and Domain-Specific LLM

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Summary

Several scientific fields have experienced the benefits of recent Large Language Models (LLMs), which are being adopted for their apparent reasoning and impressive generative abilities. However, few scientific domains, such as the Agricultural Extension (AE) have been slow adopters. Therefore, to address this gap, this study introduces a novel benchmark dataset called AgXQA, and a domain-specific LLM called AgRoBERTa, both tailored to solving the question-answering downstream task for AE. Upon evaluation, AgRoBERTa achieved an F1 score of 78.89% and an EM score of 55.15%. The human evaluation metrics also confirmed AgRoBERTa's consistency in matching experts' assessments 94.37% of the time.

Introduction

AE plays a vital role in educating farmers and promoting sustainable practices. However, its effectiveness is hampered by both internal and external challenges alike. For example, internally, access to real-time and precise information can be hindered by the absence of an Extension Educator (EE), outdated online resources, and declining federal funding support (Wang, 2014). Meanwhile, the external challenges are often technical; namely, the inconsistency and unstandardized nature of agricultural data lead to the lack of adequate datasets to train suitable AI models for practical use cases. Ultimately, these challenges further limit the adoption of mainstream LLMs in the AE community despite their commonplace usage and research development in other disciplines, such as biomedicine (Pampari et al., 2018). Consequently, our research presents a comprehensive approach to overcome these limitations. On the one hand, we aim to improve the quality and accessibility of AE information by creating standardized data collection and curation methods. This resulted in the **Agricultural EXtension Question Answering (AgXQA)** benchmark dataset. Furthermore, we introduce AgRoBERTa, a novel domain-specific LLM, designed specifically for AE QA tasks. Finally, we developed a pipeline to evaluate AgRoBERTa's performance against other mainstream LLMs, such as GPT 3.5, RoBERTa, and SciBERT, on the AgXQA benchmark. The strengths and weaknesses of these LLMs are also documented in a comprehensive quality error analysis.

Methodology and Results

We took a four-phase methodology to meet the objectives described above. The first consists of data curation and annotation. In other words, we downloaded 1,655 Extension documents from legitimate sources such as the Journal of Extension and major U.S. land-grant institutions. These documents were pre-processed and represent our first dataset: the non-annotated corpus. Furthermore, we extracted irrigation-related paragraphs from this corpus and annotated them following the structure of a standard question-answering dataset, thus resulting in AgXQA. The annotations were conducted and verified by two experts, before being split into training, validation, and test sets. Notably, AgXQA's test set represents the ultimate evaluation dataset against which all the baseline and proposed LLMs will be tested. The second and third phases correspond to the evaluation of the baseline LMs and the training of a specialized LM, respectively. In the former, the baseline LMs consist of two encoder-LMs (RoBERTa, SciBERT) and one decoder-LM (GPT 3.5), which underwent zero-shot learning (ZSL) experiments. In the latter, however, we conducted a series of fine-tuning (FT) experiments on AgRoBERTa, an encoder-LM, which we trained specifically on the in-domain datasets created during phase

1. We also performed an ablation study whereby the non-annotated corpus was discarded during the FT experiments. As for the F techniques, we considered three cases: fine-tuning all the layers of the encoder-LM, fine-tuning its last layer only, and fine-tuning additional model parameters via a parameter-efficient approach. Finally, the fourth phase consists of both an automated and human evaluation of all the LLMs' performances. On the one hand, we performed the automated evaluation by computing the standard metrics such as F1, EM, ROUGE, BLEU, and BERTScore. On the other hand, we introduced a new expert human score, AgEES, to capture the quality, correctness, and completeness of AgRoBERTa and GPT3.5's performance. Furthermore, they both underwent a thorough qualitative error analysis, thus enabling us to capture each other's strengths and weaknesses when evaluated on our benchmark AgXQA dataset.

The key findings of our experiments are summarized as follows. The automated metrics revealed that GPT 3.5 outperformed RoBERTa and SciBERT in the ZSL setting. However, AgRoBERTa, specifically fine-tuned on agricultural datasets, outperformed GPT 3.5 on AgXQA. For instance, AgRoBERTa's F1, EM, and BERTScore results were 78.89%, 55.15%, and 0.87 compared to 26.06%, 62.71% and 0.77 for GPT 3.5. Notably, the results of the ablation study highlighted the importance of the non-annotated corpus, which improved AgRoBERTa's final performance. Elsewhere, the human evaluation metrics showed that AgRoBERTa's performance coincides with the expert judgment 94.37% of the time, in contrast to 92.62% for GPT 3.5. Finally, the qualitative error analysis revealed GPT 3.5's superiority in generating longer answer spans and processing numerical questions better than AgRoBERTa. This is exemplified by an 86.2% success rate at producing non-erroneous answers by GPT 3.5 compared to a 56% rate for AgRoBERTa.

The importance and relevance of our work are justified by the development of the first annotated extractive QA dataset coupled with AgRoBERTa, a new fine-tuned encoder-LM in the agricultural community in general and the agricultural extension field in particular. AgRoBERTa is readily deployable as an intelligent QA system capable of serving as the backend system of any extension-based software dealing with farmers' QA.

Conclusions

Our work investigated the factors limiting the productivity of farmers-Extension Educators interactions despite the recent explosion of LLMs' extensive applications in other subdomains. We identified that high-quality in-domain datasets are lacking to train LLMs to perform well in most agricultural-related settings efficiently. We developed two datasets to address this knowledge gap: the AE corpus (for unsupervised training) and AgXQA (for supervised training). Consequently, we fine-tuned AgRoBERTa, a novel, domain-specific encoder-LM specifically tailored to AE's unique requirements of extractive QA. Our evaluation pipeline demonstrated AgRoBERTa's consistent ability to outperform other LLMs, such as GPT 3.5 or SciBERT, which were not sufficiently trained in agricultural data. Therefore, our research fosters improved information retrieval and context-aware QA capabilities, ultimately promoting sustainable agricultural practices while offering new potential enhancements to agricultural modeling software. Future efforts will focus on expanding AgXQA to other agricultural topics since it is currently limited to irrigation. Furthermore, we plan to extend our fine-tuning experiments to encoder-decoder LMs to handle heavy numerical queries efficiently.

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Sensitivity-Based Dominant Factor Mapping to Identify Drivers of Farmer Enrolment in Land Conservation Program

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Summary

This paper demonstrates how sensitivity indices, obtained using output variance decomposition, can be used to identify the drivers of farmers' decisions to enroll their land in a conservation reserve program. We use an agent-based model to simulate the process of program signup, which produces land use change maps. By overlaying the sensitivity index maps, we identify which input scores highest in a particular location, creating a dominant factor map that shows spatial patterns of the major drivers of the enrolment decision variability.

Introduction

The Conservation Reserve Program - CRP (USDA, 2024) in the United States incentivizes farmers to rent their land for environmental purposes - an effort crucial for preserving biodiversity and maintaining ecological balance. Farmers' decision to enter the program is complex and multifaceted, with numerous drivers operating within a spatially heterogeneous landscape and making the enrolment process highly variable across regions. Gaining insight into farmers' decisions can be done using agent-based modeling (ABM), which produces spatial patterns of CRP enrolment (Ligmann-Zielinska et al., 2014). Since ABM's inputs and outputs are inherently uncertain, we can apply sensitivity analysis (SA) to identify which factors (and where) contribute to output map variability.

Methodology and Results

Our ABM simulates the farmer's enrollment and the Farm Service Agency's (FSA) selection processes based on a structured CRP signup – Figure 1 (Ligmann-Zielinska et al., 2014). The ABM integrates various criteria that affect the enrollment decisions, such as farmer retirement status, land tenure, the fraction of land suitable for enrollment, the decision rule, land production, and bid – all contributing to building a land rent offer submitted to FSA. The FSA agent, in turn, evaluates all offers based on their environmental benefits, soil rental rate, and overall cost. The selected offers are passed to farmers who change their agricultural land to fallow, effectively enrolling in the CRP.

In the context of SA, variance decomposition (VD) offers a robust framework for determining the influence of various factors on model outputs to better understand the simulated complex system behavior. One of the results of VD is the total-effect index (ST), which captures both the individual and interactive contribution to output variance. When applied to spatially explicit ABM, it allows for creating one sensitivity map per factor, where the ST is calculated for each spatial unit like a raster cell. We can then overlay the ST maps and quantify which input scores the highest in a particular location, creating a dominant factor map to identify the leading drivers of the enroll/not-enroll decisions.

We use the Sobol radial sampling (Saltelli, 2010) for the nine inputs mentioned above. The results are shown in Figure 2. The map on the left depicts the standard deviation of enrollment frequency. The dominant factor map (Figure 2 – right) shows areas where a particular factor scores highest. Only four out of the nine factors drive farmer agent enrolment decisions. Also, there is a considerable spatial heterogeneity of influential factors. The value of production dominates on the eastern side of the study area, with smaller clusters of cost, whereas farmers' retirement status dominates on the western side. Interestingly, none of the four dominant factors are spatial (i.e., for a given input, alternative maps can be selected for specific model executions).

Figure 1. The CRP ABM conceptual diagram

Figure 2. ABM results for N=1024 runs (Cass County, Michigan, U.S.)

Conclusions

Our results reveal that, just like the simulated land use patterns, their drivers of change are spatially heterogeneous. Furthermore, in the case of the presented model, most CRP enrolment drivers come from individual decisions. The FSA plays a secondary role in the final land use configuration.

Apart from the input data accuracy, the significant limitations of the presented approach are high computational cost, reliance on variance as a measure of uncertainty, and poor handling of non-parametric elements (Borgonovo et al., 2022). Future research should focus on exploring measures of the overall distributions of outputs and more efficient algorithms. The presented methodology offers a powerful tool for demonstrating the interplay of factors that drive variations in model outputs, especially in the context of agricultural systems modeling, where spatial heterogeneity plays a crucial role. It allows for looking into the black box of the model mechanisms and, by extension, the processes of land use change in the target system.

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Modelling the Evolution of Territorial Agriculture: An Economics and Geography Perspective Based on the Example of the French Riviera

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Summary

The French Riviera (and more precisely the Alpes-Maritimes department) has seen the virtual disappearance of its local traditional agriculture, owing to the rapid urban development and touristic influx beginning in the second part of the 20th century. As part of an effort to understand the modalities of agricultural reterritorialization, we have developed an agent-based model based on a purely economic approach. In this presentation, we explore how such a model can be expanded in order to include a few spatial elements: difference between coast and hinterland, irreversibility of urbanisation, core-periphery dynamics and type of agriculture according to zones.

Introduction

In the context of a globalised food system that has created a “food from nowhere” regime (Shermer 2015), the development of a sustainable and nourishing agriculture at the territorial level can be thought of as a *wicked problem* (Rittel & Webber, 1973). A myriad of interlinked social, cultural, geographical, economic, environmental and technical factors has locked territories into trajectories that render the possibility of a relocation of the production of food a difficult one.

Our work is carried out in the context of a territory in Southeast France with a strong farming tradition that has seen its agriculture virtually disappear over the last 60 years. The trajectory has seen a strong division between a highly populated coastline (including the cities of Cannes and Antibes) where land has been urbanized, and a hinterland where it has been mostly left unused or kept for extensive animal husbandry. In response, the past 10 years have seen an increase in citizen's interest (and in some territories, political will) to regain a certain level of local agriculture, which has led to a number of efforts to understand the levers and blockages, as well as to implement solutions.

An important issue is the level of income that farmers obtain from their activity, which is substantially lower than that which can be earned from a different activity. In that sense, increasing farmers' income is one of the levers of reterritorialization (Gneiting & Sonenshine, 2018). Recent work has produced a model of reterritorialization that studies this variable (Lopez-Merino, Zeppini & Lazaric, 2024), offering a first insight as to how a more resilience trajectory for the food system can be achieved.

The present work is an effort to complement this, through the inclusion of spatial variables that can interact with income ones and therefore with the decision of farmers to produce. We seek to recreate not only the decline in the level of agricultural activity, but also its geographical evolution and the type of products that remain, to study where and what type of agriculture can be revitalized. The model is a co-design effort by economists and geographers.

Methodology and Results

The model we depart from uses the evolution in farmers' income in the region as compared to other activities as an input. It includes also network effects which are considered central in farming (Rasel et al., 2022), although it is silent with regards of the spatial dimensions of the evolution of agriculture, and includes full reversibility in land uses. Our intention here is first and foremost to determine how such a model can be fit to a spatial treatment, and as such is a contribution to the field of economic geography. Secondly, we seek to recreate a

stylized version of the dynamics observed in the territory under study over the past 50 years: agricultural land lost to urbanization in the southern coastal area, reduction in the overall number of farms, specialization in animal husbandry in the northern hinterland.

We introduce the following modifications to the initial model: i) Land can be urbanised, therefore becoming permanently lost to agriculture (non-reversibility). ii) Urbanisation follows a process of spatial diffusion, tending to be concentrated in coastal zones. iii) Non-urban land can have three states: vegetable agriculture, animal agriculture or unused. iii) The likelihood of each state is partially dependent on proximity to urban centers.

Figure 1 (left). Simulation grid at t=0. Figure 2 (right). Simulation grid at t=max. Gray=urban, green=vegetable agriculture, orange=animal husbandry, brown=unused land. We observe an expansion of the urban land concentrated in the lower part of the grid (akin to the coastal area), and the emergence of an agriculture specialised in animal husbandry in the upper part of the grid (akin to the hinterland).

Conclusions

The complexity of the problem of reterritorialization implies that complex approaches to its study, drawing from different disciplines and local knowledges are key to understanding how it can take place. At the same time, modelling complex systems needs to be done in a step-by-step fashion in order to avoid black-box results (Le Page, 2017). We have made an effort to include spatial considerations into an economic model, and adapt it to the observed reality of a particular territory. It is currently being used to explore potential pathways for a reterritorialisation of agriculture.

We will discuss our ongoing co-design work, lessons learnt for good modelling practice, and how our work offers a contribution to the field of territorial agricultural transitions, using an economic geography approach.

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PyCHAMP: A Crop-Hydrological-Agent Modeling Platform for Groundwater Management

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Summary

In this presentation, I introduce the Crop-Hydrological-Agent Modeling Platform (PyCHAMP), a Python-based open-source package designed for modeling agro-hydrological systems. The modular design, incorporating aquifer, crop field, groundwater well, finance, and behavior modules, enables users to simulate and analyze the interactions between human and natural systems within agricultural context, considering both environmental and socio-economic factors. This study demonstrates PyCHAMP's capabilities by simulating the dynamics in the Sheridan 6 Local Enhanced Management Area, a pilot groundwater conservation region in the High Plains Aquifer in Kansas. This presentation will demonstrate PyCHAMP's potential as a useful tool for human-water research and sustainable groundwater management.

Introduction

Motivated by the need for a more flexible and expandable platform to endogenously represent human-environmental interconnections and feedbacks within agriculture settings, we propose the Crop-Hydrological-Agent Modeling Platform (PyCHAMP). PyCHAMP is a Python-based platform designed to improve agricultural groundwater management modelling. It has a unique modular approach, encapsulating components like aquifers, crop fields, groundwater wells, and behavioral actors (i.e., farmers) into a cohesive package. This modularization affords flexibility and expandability, allowing users to customize the complexity of their models by integrating external sub-models or self-developed Python programs, ranging from established statistical relationships to sophisticated physics-based simulations, thereby enhancing control over computational cost and model output uncertainty. PyCHAMP connects created entities (e.g., actors, wells, fields, and aquifers) through a network-based structure. Furthermore, PyCHAMP supports complex decision-making rules such as optimization guided by a CONSUMAT behavioral framework with customizable behavior agents' objectives (e.g., maximizing profit) to simulate behavioral actors' decision-making process, under various scenarios.

PyCHAMP enhances both academic and applied research by improving the modeling of coupled human-natural systems. PyCHAMP enables the development and testing of social-ecological systems theories and supports sustainable groundwater management within a broader human-natural systems modeling framework. This study demonstrates PyCHAMP's application in the Sheridan 6 Local Enhanced Management Area (SD-6 LEMA) in western Kansas, highlighting its ability to simulate, analyze and evaluate water conservation policies. By bridging individual decision-making to broader environmental outcomes, PyCHAMP marks a significant advancement in environmental management and modeling.

Methodology and Results

PyCHAMP is organized into five core modules: aquifer, field, well, finance, and behavior, which together include five pivotal classes: Aquifer, Field, Well, Finance, and Behavior. Additional Optimization class is provided for enhancing flexibility in agent's programming. Users of PyCHAMP can easily adapt each module according to the data they have availability. For example, simple representation of crop growth can be represented in the field module, or a sophisticated, highly-parametrized crop model could be integrated within the PyCHAMP platform.

Decision-making within PyCHAMP is framed as an optimization problem, addressed through the Optimization class within the context of the CONSUMAT behavioral framework. CONSUMAT is a multi-theoretical behavioral framework used to understand and simulate individual and group behaviors, particularly in the context of consumer behavior. It integrates insights from psychology, sociology, and economics to explain how individuals make decisions and how these decisions can be influenced by various factors. The development of PyCHAMP is built upon the Mesa agent-based model (ABM) framework.

We showcase PyCHAMP's analytical capabilities in revealing co-evolved dynamics of human and natural systems through a case study of the SD-6 LEMA, a groundwater conservation area in the High Plains Aquifer region of northwestern Kansas. Through this case study, we demonstrate how PyCHAMP can be used to investigate the environmental and socio-economic factors that contribute to the effectiveness, adaptability, and resilience of groundwater conservation policies. We performed a local calibration and validation of our model. We also designed a series of numerical experiments aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of water conservation policies, incorporating both environmental and socio-economic factors, and understanding how these factors influence farming decisions and water conservation behaviors.

Overall, the model successfully represented the general trends observed in the SD-6 LEMA for key variables, such as saturated thickness, groundwater withdrawal, and crop plantings. The versatility of PyCHAMP was further highlighted through its capability to output additional dynamics, such as energy usage, profit, and CONSUMAT state ratios. The findings revealed that profit per irrigated depth improved during the second water conservation period, coinciding with an increase in rainfed fields, while the energy required for water pumping stabilized alongside the saturated thickness during the second conservation period.

Our findings illustrate the pivotal role of endogenously simulating human decision-making in evaluating the effectiveness of water conservation policies. The local sensitivity analysis further illuminates the significant influence of behavioral parameters on the modeling outcomes. Additionally, we explore how each CONSUMAT state affects farmers' decision-making dynamics. Our analysis also demonstrates that, during dry periods, farmers managing three fields achieve higher profits and more equitable earnings compared to the scenario where farmers manage a single field. These numerical experiments demonstrate how PyCHAMP's network-based structure can facilitate scenario-based analysis.

Conclusions

In this presentation, I introduce the open-source Python-based Crop-Hydrological-Agent Modeling Platform (PyCHAMP). PyCHAMP is able to represent the complexities of human-water systems and is designed to support agricultural water management and policy modeling. The modular design of PyCHAMP offers great flexibility and adaptability for custom applications. This generalizability provides several advantages over existing tools. First, PyCHAMP offers the flexibility to tailor model complexity to align with the user's specific research needs, data availability, and computational capabilities. Second, PyCHAMP supports the exploration of social-behavioral theories and the quantification of structural uncertainty in human model design. Our experiments demonstrated how the CONSUMAT behavioral framework significantly influenced modeling outcomes. Third, PyCHAMP's network-based structure, as opposed to grid-based models, enables applying multiple spatial resolutions to different sub-models and components. In the SD-6 LEMA case study, we use PyCHAMP to build the SD-6 Model, successfully capturing observed dynamics in saturated thickness, groundwater withdrawal, and crop plantings. This presentation highlights the ability of PyCHAMP to evaluate a variety of different policies, water management strategies, and behavioral scenarios.

Acknowledgements

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Development of an Agroecosystem Model to Promote Prairies in the Midwest

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Summary

Establishing prairies in the Midwest could have numerous environmental benefits. Yet, the adoption of prairies is sparse. Adoption may increase if the ability to estimate economic and environmental tradeoffs improves. Thus, there is a need to better estimate their site-specific potential for biomass production and environmental outcomes. Here we develop a prairie model based on APSIM's AgPasture framework with the goal to better estimate their biomass production, soil carbon and nitrogen dynamics and other environmental outcomes. Preliminary results are encouraging but point to the need for improvements in model parameterization and highlight the need for additional observations and experimentation.

Introduction

Establishing prairies on farmland in the Midwest could have numerous environmental, economic, and ecological benefits, including improvements in water quality, reduced nitrate-N leaching, increase in farm profit, and an increase in native species in the landscape. Furthermore, one of the most compelling potential economic opportunities for adopting prairies is as a feedstock for renewable natural gas production from anaerobic digestion potentially coupled with ecosystem service and climate regulation payments. Still, the adoption of prairies is sparse due to the uncertainty regarding environmental and economic trade-offs. Reducing this uncertainty could increase the adoption of prairies in areas of low-yielding land under existing row crop production. Therefore, it is important to have accurate and precise modeling to quantify the potential benefits of prairie. This research aims to develop and test a prairie model using APSIM's AgPasture framework with the goal of reducing uncertainty regarding yield and nitrate leaching produced from prairies by quantifying the economic and environmental benefits of prairie's compared to a traditional row-crop system.

Methodology and Results

For the development of our model, we use the AgPasture framework in. Within the AgPasture model we use the grasses ryegrass, rhodes, and red clover, as examples of C3, C4, and legumes respectively, that would grow within a typical prairie landscape. Parameterization of the model parameters is based off of data collected at Iowa State University field site Comparison of Biofuel Cropping Systems (COBS) in Boone, Iowa. COBS aims to compare biomass production, fossil fuel replacement values, and environmental impacts for various crops. COBS consists of 24 plots, which are 27 m by 61 m in dimensions, where there are four replications of each of the following crop sequences: continuous corn grown for grain and stover with (CCW) and without (CC), a winter rye cover crop, fertilized prairie, unfertilized prairie, and a corn-soybean rotation (Iowa State University, 2023). The prairie plots are fertilized with 85 kg/ha of nitrogen per year on each plot. To calibrate the model, we will use both the fertilized and unfertilized prairie data collected at COBS for 2008-2022. Data collected for the harvests includes harvested weight (kg), sample weight in grams (g), sample dry weight in grams (g), moisture percent, biomass standing dry weight in grams (g) and biomass litter in grams (g). Samples were taken in each plot's northeast, northwest, southeast, and southwest quadrants, with each sample being 0.28 meters squared. Data was also collected for annual nitrate leaching at the site, measured in kg/ha.

Environmental inputs required by APSIM include weather and soil data. Weather data from NWS CO-OP stations and NASA POWER will be used to generate a weather file for APSIM. Soil data implemented in the model will combine data from the Soil Survey Geographic Database (SSURGO) and data collected at the field site. SSURGO will serve as a baseline and be replaced where field data is available. The following variables were collected at the field site: pH and texture (sand, silt, clay) at 0-15 centimeters and 15-30 centimeters.

After a sensitivity analysis was completed, values of the following values were changed since they had the largest impact of the performance of the model: reference photosynthesis rate, nitrogen optimum concentration, nitrogen minimum concentration. Furthermore, the following parameters were changed based off APSIM documentation: maximum rooting depth, root elongation, and photosynthetic efficiency. Initial results of the parameterization of the fertilized model indicate that the model is under-representing biomass and over-representing nitrate leaching compared to observations at COBS. We are currently in the process of determining optimal parameter combinations and performing more comprehensive sensitivity analyses and tests. A comprehensive parameterization and testing of the model are currently limited by the scarcity of field observations.

Conclusions

A preliminary version of the model shows promise for capturing the carbon and nitrogen dynamics of a prairie agro-ecosystem. Conclusions drawn from initial parametrization of the model indicate that optimization of parameters regarding phenological development and the nitrogen cycle needs to occur to move onto the next stage of model development, which is model calibration and testing. We will use these results of the optimization of the model to identify potential issues with the model. Further work will occur to parameterize the model to gain the statistical significance of model output compared to observations.

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Formalizing the Theory of Planned Behaviour in Agent-Based Models; Literature review

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Summary

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) offers a valuable framework for understanding humans decision-making. This paper explores how Agent-Based Models (ABMs) utilize TPB to investigate the interplay between social interactions, individual perceptions, and feedback from the environment in shaping behavior. We reviewed a selected collection of studies that utilize TPB within ABMs, focusing on how they formalize and operationalize this statistical model in a dynamic form. Our analysis reveals a diversity in approaches, which researchers implemented to handle this issue based on their research questions and available data. In most of the reviewed models, the dynamic nature emanates from evolution of Attitude or Subjective norm. To account for social influence of agents and internal dynamics of the Subjective norm or Attitude, few researchers used Relative Agreement Model of opinion dynamics. Additionally, the review highlights various methods for translating intention into behavior within ABMs, ranging from threshold-based approaches to regression-based model. We conclude by proposing future directions for research, including incorporating dynamic updates for TPB constructs and exploring the Decomposed Theory of Planned Behavior. By addressing these considerations, researchers can develop more powerful ABMs for understanding complex social dynamics and decision-making processes.

Introduction

Psychological theories play a particularly significant role in shaping the decision-making rules that govern agent behavior within ABMs. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) proposed by Ajzen (1991) has emerged as a prominent framework within the agent-based literature on human decision-making (Constantino et al., 2021; Githinji et al., 2023; Groeneveld et al., 2017; Schlüter et al., 2017). The TPB extends the understanding of human decision-making beyond bounded rationality by incorporating the influence of socio-psychological factors. It posits that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control interact to determine an individual's behavioral intentions (Githinji et al., 2023). Attitude (ATT) refers to an individual's evaluation of a behavior, considering it favourable or unfavourable. Subjective norm (SN) reflects the perceived social pressure to perform a behavior. Finally, perceived behavioral control (PBC) captures the perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behavior, influenced by past experiences and anticipated obstacles (Ajzen, 1991; Fishbein & Ajzen, 2011). While utilizing psychological theories such as TPB in ABMs offers advantages, modellers face the challenge of translating these abstract concepts into concrete code. This process, known as operationalization, requires creativity to transform psychological notions into specific model elements (Muelder & Filatova, 2018; Schwarz et al., 2020). This paper conducts a critical review of few existing literature, exploring how researchers have integrated the TPB within ABMs with a specific focus on innovation diffusion and socio-environmental systems.

Methodology and Results

This paper conducts a preliminary review of few existing literature, exploring how researchers have integrated the TPB within ABMs with a specific focus on innovation diffusion and socio-environmental systems. The reviewed studies illustrate diverse and effective applications of TPB in ABMs. One of the important issues in initialization of artificial societies is capturing the real-world social networks in the model. In reviewed papers, studies utilized different revised version of small-world networks to depict artificial society's relation in their ABMs (Kaufmann et al., 2009; Kniveton et al., 2012; Rai and Robinson, 2015; Schwarz and Ernst, 2009; Sopha et al., 2013). Also, our review identified a limited application of the Relative Agreement Model (RAM) within the examined studies. Only two out of eight reviewed studies Kaufmann et al. (2009) and Rai and Robinson (2015) utilized RAM to explore how social interactions shaped agent internal dispositions which lead to change their

behaviours. Furthermore, these studies demonstrate the flexibility of ABMs in capturing the interplay between ATT, PBC, SN, and social influence within the TPB framework. The specific implementation of these factors varied based on the research question and the complexity of the decision-making process being modelled. In general, modelling ATT and PBC in these ABMs resembles the Decomposed Theory of Planned Behavior (DTPB) (Taylor & Todd, 1995), drawing upon constructs from the innovation characteristics literature. The reviewed studies reveal a spectrum of approaches to address how researchers translate an agent's intention into concrete behavior. Different researchers have employed various criteria for translating intentions into agent behavior within their models.

Conclusions

This review explored how ABMs leverage TPB to understand humans decision-making processes. The studies highlight the role of SN, capturing social pressure, in shaping intention. Social network structures and information exchange mechanisms can influence how SN evolves within a social network. Moreover, there is a diversity in how researchers model ATT, PBC, and SN. While some models capture these constructs as static functions of various factors, others acknowledge the potential for them to evolve dynamically based on experiences and social interactions. The reviewed studies showed various approaches for translating intention into behavior within ABMs. These approaches range from threshold-based methods to regression-based models, each with its own strengths and limitations. Moving beyond static models, future ABMs could incorporate mechanisms for ATT, PBC, and SN to evolve based on social interactions. Further, a deeper exploration of the DTPB holds promise to add more dynamic to the model. By incorporating the specific factors outlined in DTPB and allowing them to evolve dynamically, researchers can create more fine-grained models that capture the complexities of human decision-making within social and environmental contexts. By addressing these considerations, researchers can develop ABMs that offer a more comprehensive understanding of how social interactions and individual perceptions influence behavior in complex systems. These advancements can empower researchers to explore a wider range of real-world scenarios involving social influence and decision-making, ultimately leading to more informed interventions and policies.

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Meta-Regression Analysis of Resilience Measurements Among Senegalese Farmers

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Summary

In recent years, disasters from climate change and COVID-19 have greatly threatened the resilience of farmers' livelihoods in Senegal. In this study, We performed a meta-regression analysis to determine how different study characteristics affect reported resilience levels. From the selected peer-reviewed papers, we extracted indices representing farmers' resilience in Senegal from nine of 34 studies, yielding 54 observations for the resilience index and explanatory variables. Our results indicated that study sample size, crop type, project-based studies, and focus on food security significantly and positively affect reported resilience levels.

Introduction

Resilience is "the capacity to prepare for types of disruption, recover from shocks, and grow from a disruptive experience" (World Bank, 2021). The dependence of Senegalese farmers on agricultural activities amplifies the critical need to develop adaptive strategies against socioeconomic and climate-related disturbances (Moller et al., 2024). As a result, several studies explore the various dimensions of resilience among farmers in Senegal. Meanwhile, a meta-regression analysis can help determine variations affecting farmers' resilience indicators across Senegal.

Methodology

Following, we described details of regression estimations, variables, and data:

Meta-data generation: We selected 34 studies among more than 1600 studies on farmers' resilience in Senegal published in Elsevier, Emerald, and Willey. Reviewing the selected articles, we filtered interesting indices representing the farmers' resilience from nine studies, generating 54 observations for the resilience index and control variables.

Fractional regression model: We applied the fractional regression model as the resilience index ranged between 0 and 1. The fractional regression model is introduced for regression estimation, including fractional values for the dependent variable (Wooldridge, 2010).

Meta-regression equation estimation: As Equation 1 shows, the regression equation includes the resilience index (R_i), as a dependent variable, and characteristics of selected studies in terms of sample size (SS), gender discrimination (GE), crop specification (CR), COVID-19 consideration (CO), shock sources (SH), project-based study (PR), publication year (PY), type of resilience index (RI), and single-country studies (SC):

$$R_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot SS_i + \beta_2 \cdot GE_i + \beta_3 \cdot CR_i + \beta_4 \cdot CO_i + \beta_5 \cdot SH_i + \beta_6 \cdot PR_i + \beta_7 \cdot PY_i + \beta_8 \cdot RI_i + \beta_9 \cdot SC_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where, β_0 to β_9 and ε_i are parameters and residuals, respectively, and subscript i represents the observations. We estimated the parameters using Stata software (Version 17).

Variables and Data Description: Table 1 provides the data description of variables.

Table 1. Variables and data description

Symbol	Description	Kind of variable	Min	Max	Mean	Mode
R_i	Resilience index measured by the selected studies	Continues	0.02	1	0.45	-
SS_i	A sample size specified by the selected studies	Integer	49	976	-	49
GE_i	If the selected study considers gender discrimination, GE = 1; otherwise, GE = 0	Dummy	0	1	-	1
CR_i	If the selected study considers the crop types, CR = 1; otherwise, CR = 0	Dummy	0	1	-	0
CO_i	If the selected study considers the COVID-19, CO = 1; otherwise, CO = 0	Dummy	0	1	-	1
SH_i	Main shock sources affecting the farmers' resilience specified by the selected study: 1: COVID-19; 2: Climate; 3: Others (e.g. input, price, etc)	Discriminant	1	3	-	3
PR_i	If the selected study was conducted to assess a specific development project, PR = 1; otherwise, PR = 0	Dummy	0	1	-	0
PY_i	Publication year of the selected study	Integer	2018	2023	-	2023
RI_i	If the selected study considers a dimension of food security representing the resilience index, RI = 1; otherwise, RI = 0	Dummy	0	1	-	0
SC_i	If the selected study considers only Senegal, SC = 1; otherwise, SC = 0	Dummy	0	1	-	1

Source: Study results.

Results

Table 2 presents the estimations of the meta-fractional regression model. These results showed that i) increasing sample size positively affected the levels of reported resilience; ii) Studies evaluating specific crop types and targeted project implementations, reported higher resilience levels; iii) considering the gender discrimination and COVID-19 infection led to a lower level of reported resilience; iv) The shift in shock sources from COVID-19 to climate factors, such as temperature and rainfall, lowered resilience levels, while shifts to other sources like input availability and price fluctuations did not significantly affect resilience; v) studies prioritizing the food security concluded more improvement in resilience; vi) the level of resilience worsened in the recent studies; vii) and the effect of multi-country investigation on resilience was not significant statistically.

Table 2. Results of meta-fractional regression estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Z-statistic	Variable	Coefficient	Z-statistic
SS	2.82E-3***	4.85	SH (if SH= Others)	2.14E-4	-0.00
GE	-1.23***	-6.34	PR	8.33E-1*	1.74
CR	1.60***	4.48	PY	-1.28E-1*	-1.72
CO	-1.32***	-3.87	RI	7.04E-1***	6.35
SH (if SH= Climate)	-1.65***	-4.25	SC	-1.62E-1	-0.30

Source: Study results

Conclusions

In this study, we identified the factors influencing the structure of research on the resilience index for farming systems in Senegal. We concluded that the resilience index in Senegal is sensitive to the sample size, and the data acquisition restriction could potentially lead to a misspecification of resilience interpretation. We also suggested that the upcoming studies need to remarkably extend the methodological approach to detect the shocks derived from the climate factors on the resilience index and its consequences on cropping systems.

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Transition-Based Unified Modeling Framework for Heterogeneous Agro-environmental Systems

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Summary

Synergistic combination of a new non-conventional modeling and simulation (M&S) framework with its declarative implementation is discussed in the context of environmental and agricultural modeling. The structure- and transition-based method of Programmable Process Structures can contribute to the holistic modeling of heterogeneous agro-environmental systems. The flexible generation of the extensible set of model elements and the respective locally executable, editable program prototypes are supported by the unification and list processing capabilities of the applied declarative logical programming language. The modeling framework provides the analysis and stepwise elimination of the associated lack of knowledge.

Introduction

Nowadays, increasing need for model-supported analysis, design, planning and operation of environmental and agricultural systems meet the fast-developing methods and tools of Information Technology. Global environmental monitoring and local precise operation of agricultural processes is supported by affordable remote sensing and *in situ* sensors, as well as by intelligent data analytics of the increasingly available data. Many detailed, sophisticated modeling tools can be used for the development of different sectors of agronomy, livestock farming, etc. In addition to the integration of these specific models, comprehensive tools, focusing on specific areas, like SWAT (Gassman et al., 2007) on all of the soil related processes, as well as unified frameworks like APSIM (Holzworth et al., 2018) for modelling of various agricultural systems offer promising solutions. Moreover, there are rigorous and heuristic upper-level optimizers, embedding simplified models to support the systemic decisions.

However, needs for modeling and simulation of holistic, spatially and temporally changing heterogeneous agro-environmental systems still inspires the development and testing of new approaches. Actual challenges are the convenient horizontal coupling amongst the models of holistically interlinked systems, as well as the vertical coupling between the upper-level decision support and the lower-level data analytics. In addition, new frameworks have to assist in the analysis and elimination of lack of true knowledge in the complex models.

The key aspect of this methodological research is to address the above challenges by providing a solution for fast generation and flexible use of unified, causally transparent dynamic material and energy balance models with medium complexity.

Methodology and Results

Having studied several systems from various disciplines and inspired by the (chemical) process engineering way of thinking, the non-conventional M&S methodology of Programmable Process Structures (PPS, Varga & Csukás, 2022) has been developing for the general class of process systems. In recently upgraded framework of PPS, the model structure is declared in sense of General Net Theory (Petri, 1980). Functional description of the (e.g. material, energy, signal representing) state and (e.g. transformation, transportation, rule representing) transition elements is motivated by the two basic functions in Mathematical Theory of Systems (Kalman et al, 1967). In "transition-based knowledge representation", in contrary to the "horizontal" describing of state changes by (e.g. differential) balance equations, the model is organized by the "vertically arranged" mappings of transitions, determining the interconnected partial changes of the given elementary process, together.

State and transition elements (describing the case-specific data and parameters) are associated with one of the reusably general, but editable program prototypes, containing the locally executable distributed code for

calculations. To provide the integrity and extensibility for the generation and execution of models, all of the case-specific elements and programmed prototypes are derived from the same two “empty” meta-elements. The transition-based architecture makes possible the inherently common representation of the extensive / intensive properties and functionalities for (conservation law-based) quantitative balances, with the qualitative and quantitative signals and rules. The model elements have a spatial identifier and a timing capability that (combined with optional rules) support the time- and/or event-driven simulation of multi-scale models.

Regarding software implementation, the “mother tongue” of PPS is the declarative, logical SWI-Prolog language (Wielemaker et al., 2011). The unification capabilities of Prolog support data transfer between the case-specific, data containing standardized model elements and the problem-specific code containing standardized, locally executable program elements. The extensibility and reusability of the models are enhanced by list structures and list processing.

Considering the actual challenges in environmental and agricultural modeling, the fast generation and robust execution of spatially varying, heterogeneous and temporally changing complex production systems can be emphasized. The consideration and stepwise elimination of the lack of true knowledge in design and identification of these complex systems is achieved by the transition-based knowledge representation. It makes possible the localized improvement, by implementing experimentally simplified (e.g. efficiency-based or rule-based) and stepwise improved local programs. On the other hand, the transparent representation of process structure helps to study the transferring and cyclic flux and influence pathways for assessment of systemic impacts in context of circularity. Moreover, the comprehensive utilization of the changing or constant stoichiometric composition allows to build models of medium complexity, in between the simple mass balance-based and the detailed biochemical and biogeochemical components-based models.

Conclusions

Programmable Process Structures may afford a possible solution to the holistic modeling of heterogeneous agro-environmental systems. The easy generation and robust execution of the extensible models can be solved by the unification and list processing capabilities of the applied declarative logical programming language. The transparent process structure and the transition-based model representation helps the analysis and the elimination of the possible lack of true knowledge. In future work, PPS can develop further toward a generally usable M&S tool and/or toward a horizontal and vertical coupling model of medium details. Both cases would need collaboration with the internationally leading M&S initiatives. The implementation of the method in other programming environment is another future question.

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Harmful Algae Blooms (HAB) research and development in the Great Lakes Region and beyond

New Multi-Constituent Nutrient and Harmful Algal Blooms Model for River Networks With Online State Estimation

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Summary

Water managers are recognizing an increasing need for a novel water quality model that enables real-time monitoring, prediction, and prediction of various constituents. In this study, we develop a new multi-constituent water quality model based on a fully dynamic hydraulics and unsteady advection-diffusion equation, which includes a major eutrophication process with algal growth. As a case study, the proposed model is calibrated and validated with the observed data in a large river network in South Korea. Additionally, we examine the data assimilation capabilities to estimate the multiple constituents in the model. The results show that the model can estimate the water quality states more effectively and accurately than the model-only case.

Introduction

Water quality impairment of surface water systems fed by urban and natural drainage networks has become a crucial challenge in recent decades due to urbanization and climate change. Dynamic models to predict water quality have crucial roles in coping with water quality threats such as Harmful algal blooms, toxicants in drinking water, and ecosystem degradation. Despite its significance, most existing physics-based water quality models for river networks are struggling with representing diffusive contaminant transport under fully unsteady hydraulics, a lack of data assimilation capabilities, or limited extensibility due to closed-source code. To overcome these limitations, we propose a new water quality model for river networks with multi-constituent state estimation.

Methodology and Results

In the previous work, we developed Pipedream-WQ, a novel water quality model for natural and urban drainage networks based on the unsteady advection-reaction-diffusion (ARD) equation and featuring real-time data assimilation using a Kalman Filtering scheme. Designed specifically for real-time applications and large-networked drainage systems, the model features a novel implicit solver scheme based on the SUPERLINK algorithm that ensures numerical stability and scalability to large networks (Kim & Bartos, 2024). In this study, we extend the model to represent multi-constituent water quality dynamics with complex reactions for the algal bloom prediction in river networks.

Based on a literature review of widely used existing models (QUAL2K, EFDC, CAEDYM, and CE-QUAL-W2), the most essential constituents such as temperature, dissolved oxygen, organic and inorganic nutrients (N, P, C), and algal groups (green, diatom, and cyanobacteria) are considered in the proposed model as follows.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the model development process and reaction kinetics of our new model

To validate the proposed solver, we construct a model for a real river network—the Nakdong River in South Korea—and validate using a large set of hydraulic and water quality measurement data. This is the second largest watershed (23,384 km²) in South Korea, consisting of a highly-regulated river network (11 multi-purpose dams and 8 large weirs in the mainstream) and many developed areas (13 million people and several industrial complexes).

Figure 2. Model calibration results for 3 years (2020–2022)

Multi-constituent multi-point state estimation is implemented using a Kalman Filtering approach. In addition, we analyze spatial and inter-constituent correlations using historical measurement data to improve model performance by specifying an estimate of the process noise covariance matrix that incorporates prior knowledge of the system. We examine the model’s performance and its capability to predict major water quality constituents using state estimation. Using a spatial holdout assessment, we show that we can effectively estimate the whole networked system’s state based on a spatially limited number of measurement data.

Figure 3. State estimation results by a spatial hold-out assessment

Conclusions

We expect that the proposed model will provide an effective decision-making tool for operators to respond to water quality threats in river networks. In future research, we will explore how forecasts of harmful algal blooms are improved using assimilation of in-situ water quality sensor data, and how state estimation can help to predict hard-to-measure constituents (like phosphorus) by combining in-situ sensor measurements with a physics-based process model.

Acknowledgements

The measurement data is opened to public by NIER of Korea and can be obtained from <https://water.nier.or.kr>.

Composite Red Tide Vulnerability Index (CRTVI): Assessing and Communicating Vulnerability of Coastal Communities to Red Tide in Florida

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Summary

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) caused by *Karenia brevis*, commonly known as red tide, are a recurring natural phenomenon along Florida's coastline. In addition to affecting water quality and ecosystems, red tide has shown severe impacts to human health, tourism, fisheries, and other economic structures. However, existing studies largely represent measurements of the impacts to specific human activities from individual red tide events and do not yet provide a framework for consistent, comparable measurements across years. This study creates a Composite Red Tide Vulnerability Index (CRTVI) for Florida to measure community vulnerability to the socio-economic impacts of red tide events.

Introduction

Red tide events have persistently occurred in Florida since its initial documentation in 1844 and are most frequently observed along the Southwestern peninsula. While still not yet fully understood, the initiation, progress, termination, and ecosystem effects of red tide events have been observed and studied for decades. More recently, red tide events have been shown to influence human activity, resulting in significant impacts to human health, tourism, fisheries, marine activities, and other socio-economic domains. The scope and severity of these impacts to human activity in a given region are not only dependent on the size, intensity, distance to, and duration of the red tide bloom itself, but also the demographics, economic structure, and relationship to other regions of the state and world (e.g., through visitation and trade). However, existing studies largely represent measurements of the impacts to specific human activities from individual red tide events and do not yet provide a framework for consistent, comparable measurements across years. There are critical needs to build upon this information towards consistent, comparable measurements across years and to quantify the vulnerability of coastal communities in Florida to the impacts of red tide events, which can both inform decision-making processes related to preparing for, mitigating, or preventing the negative impacts of red tide events.

Methodology and Results

In this study, we have developed a Composite Red Tide Vulnerability Index (CRTVI) for coastal communities in Florida for measuring community vulnerability to the impacts of red tide events. By "vulnerability", we specifically refer to the degree to which a community is susceptible to and struggles to cope with the adverse effects of red tide on social, and economic systems.

First, through a thorough literature review and focus group discussions, we identified four primary domains relevant to the impacts of red tide events in Florida, including human health, tourism, fisheries and marine activities, and socioeconomic vulnerability. In addition, a red tide exposure indicator was also included when designing CRTVI. Then, we selected metrics and measurements deemed consistent and comparable in each domain. With selected metrics, the following steps were conducted to construct the CRTVI: collect relevant data, construct a composite indicator for each domain, identify weights for each indicator, and assess community level vulnerability. Figure 1 shows the conceptual diagram of steps used to develop the CRTVI.

Figure 1. CRTVI development diagram

Then, we developed an interactive web platform to offer comprehensive data visualization of the results (shown as Figure 2). A usability test was conducted with both experts and the general public to enhance the performance of the web platform and ensure it fit their needs.

Figure 2. Florida Red Tide Vulnerability Index Dashboard

Conclusions

This study identified consistent and comparable metrics and measurements relevant to the socio-economic impacts of red tide events in Florida and created indicators across domains of human health, tourism, fisheries and marine activities, and socio-economic vulnerability. With an indicator of red tide exposure, a Composite Red Tide Vulnerability Index was constructed with chosen indicators and weights to quantify county-level socio-economic vulnerability to red tide events in Florida. An interactive web application was developed with a usability test to enhance the accessibility of the study results for policymakers, stakeholders, and the public. The CRTVI can significantly enhance how policymakers and stakeholders understand and manage the effects of red tide events and support red tide preparedness and mitigation efforts, potentially reducing the adverse effects on human health, local economies, and tourism. Moreover, the efforts and outcomes can inform ongoing regional-, state-, and national-level discussions related to preparing for, mitigating, or preventing the negative impacts of Red Tide events.

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An Agent-Based Model to Simulate and Assess Dynamic Vulnerability in a Coupled Human and Environment System of Lake Erie Harmful Algae Blooms

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Summary

The concept of coupled human and natural systems (CHANS) features complex human-environment interactions and provides a holistic perspective to address questions in environmental science and policy studies. In this paper, we report on an integrated agent-based model and multicriteria evaluation framework to calculate social vulnerability and evaluate the risks of people in CHANS facing disturbances. While accounting for CHANS dynamics, this framework aims to quantify and assess community vulnerability using spatially explicit model outputs. We applied Lake Erie's harmful algal blooms as our case study. The modeling results can inform policy decisions to support targeted communities and provide insights to understand vulnerabilities in CHANS.

Introduction

Coupled human and natural systems (CHANS) involve complex interactions between human behavior and the environment. This framework features many complexities and provides a holistic perspective to describe real-world linked human and environmental problems (Liu et al., 2007). CHANS can be exposed to disturbances causing harm to human/environmental systems. Environmental hazards, as a type of natural disturbance, can damage humans, whereas vulnerability is a concept that describes the risks people have when facing disturbances. Disasters occur when hazards meet vulnerability (Raju et al., 2022). Therefore, it is essential to quantify and assess social vulnerability to environmental hazards to assist policies to manage CHANS and identify high-risk populations to provide targeted support.

Social vulnerability index is a widely adopted metric that quantifies and assesses group vulnerability to various threats. Current studies face two main challenges when assessing social vulnerability to environmental hazards: 1) how to define the specific indicators of vulnerability and 2) how to account for the dynamics of vulnerability. Several indices have been developed and implemented in risk assessments and emergency management, but each includes very different indicators. So far, they have not covered the dynamics of social vulnerability due to the intrinsic complexity of CHANS. Therefore, this research aims to develop a framework to address these deficiencies. The results of the quantitative vulnerability index include simplified but significant indicators of vulnerability dynamics. The framework and the resulting index may assist in understanding social vulnerability in CHANS and identify populations for targeted environmental policy design.

Lake Erie's harmful algal blooms (HABs) have long drawn public attention. The severe conditions of HABs in Lake Erie are due to its geographic characteristics and the massive amount of agricultural runoff from its surrounding areas (Lake Erie LaMP, 2011). At the same time, HABs have negatively affected the neighboring population, which treats the lake as an essential natural resource. We used this complex system as a case study and applied our framework to evaluate the vulnerability levels of different communities in the Toledo metropolitan area.

Methodology and Results

We developed an agent-based model (ABM) named Algae Vulnerability Simulation (AVUS) to simulate the behaviors of residents and the interactions between the behaviors and the HAB severity in Lake Erie projected by the amount of nutrients from agricultural input delivered to the lake. The simulated dynamics are driven by community income, HAB severity, surface water dependence, and distance to the lake. We followed the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change recommendations to characterize social vulnerability (McCarthy et

al., 2001). The factors were adopted in a multicriteria evaluation (MCE) model to calculate a HAB dynamic vulnerability index (HAB-DVI). This integrated framework is shown in Figure 1. We further utilized a Monte Carlo-based uncertainty analysis and visualized the statistical results of the simulations to indicate the variability and reliability of the HAB-DVI.

Figure 1. Model framework

Our spatial results point to two categories of low versus high-vulnerability populations. For example, ten census tracts in Fulton County scored low on HAB-DVI, marking the whole county as low vulnerable to the Lake Erie HAB events. On the other hand, most of the highly vulnerable census tract populations are in Lucas County, which is relatively close to the lake. The highly vulnerable communities near the lake usually have higher population density and lower income levels. Uncertainty analysis also shows that most high HAB-DVI scores have low standard deviation, confirming that populations in such locations are very likely to be vulnerable to HABs. At the same time, most tracts in Wood County score medium to high on the HAB-DVI spectrum, which also points to significant variability in the results of the simulations.

Conclusions

We designed an integrated agent-based and MCE modeling framework to investigate social vulnerability in systems facing environmental disturbances. The results of our case study of Lake Erie HAB events indicate that the dynamic social vulnerability index at a census tract level is especially useful when the system has been exposed to the disturbance for years. The results suggest prioritizing supportive policies to help the communities adapt and build resilience to environmental hazards. At the same time, this research provides insights by looking at the topic of dynamic social vulnerability from the perspective of CHANS.

The presented framework is versatile enough to be adopted to study different geographic regions facing environmental hazards. The next step in the research is to evaluate the results for policy analysis to provide suggestions for prioritizing supportive management strategies when distributing government resources. Moreover, improvements in the selected factors used for the MCE analysis can further contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of dynamic social vulnerability.

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Good modelling practice for better social and environmental outcomes

Justifying Decisions in the Modeling Cycle With Illustration for an Eco-Hydrological Model

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Summary

Decisions made in the modeling process matter and the number to be considered expands substantially in accordance with the complexity of the problem, issues and perspectives. We provide a framework that links choices to decision points in five phases of the modeling cycle, and suggest invoking a fitness-for-purpose concept to support those, mostly upfront, decisions that can be justified qualitatively. We recommend that other decision choices, typically technical, need evaluation, or at least justification, amongst alternatives for their effects on outcomes. The justification framework is illustrated with an eco-hydrological model to support environmental watering in the Narran Lakes, Australia.

Introduction

Modeling is an iterative process with elements that enter the various model development and phases. The elements are determined based on model decisions made among candidate alternatives. Model decisions can have a profound impact on final outcomes. The undesirable outcomes of model choices might include: (i) a model is poorly designed without basic quality assurance; (ii) a model is well-designed, but end users might not consider it if it is too complicated to understand, or it is not robust under, for example, changing climate; or (iii) a model is used to support decisions even though it has significant flaws because no other information is available.

There is increasing awareness of the need for transparency via documenting modeling choices (Schmolke et al. 2010). But good practice also calls for critical justification of choices to promote credibility of the process, as it is increasingly recognised that the process is vital when dealing with wicked problems. We present the foundations of a framework for justifying decision choices in the modelling cycle. We propose invoking a fitness-for-purpose concept (Hamilton et al., 2022) to support decision choices, especially those in the scoping and conceptualization phases, which can be justified qualitatively through discussion with funders and other stakeholders and experts. We recommend that, wherever possible, other decision choices, typically technical, need evaluation, or at least thoughtful justification, amongst alternatives for their effects on outcomes. The framework is illustrated with an eco-hydrological model to support environmental watering in the Narran Lakes, Australia.

Methodology and Results

The five modelling phases – scoping, conceptualization, development, application and perpetuation (Badham et al., 2019, Hamilton et al., 2015) – assist us in recognising alternatives at the various decision points. Our framework uses fitness-for-purpose to connect the intended functional use and contexts to the modelling choices. Fitness-for-purpose has three requirements that can guide the modeling choices – usefulness, addressing the needs of the end user; reliability, obtaining an adequate level of certainty or trust; and feasibility, ensuring the modeling is within practical constraints of the project (Hamilton et al., 2022).

For some decisions the fitness-for-purpose framework may lead directly to an appropriate choice whereas in others there may need to be evaluation of choices among alternatives. We list a set of choices in the modelling cycle for an eco-hydrological model under development as a case study.

- a. Model purpose: research model to simulate hydrology-vegetation response relationship
- b. System boundaries: hydrological boundary of the nature reserve

- c. Variables: model inputs (rainfall, inflow, evapotranspiration, storage curve); model outputs (inundation extent, leaf area index of the lignum community)
- d. Processes/relationships: hydrology-vegetation interactions; flow, inundation and soil moisture provide water to vegetation
- e. Scales: spatial resolution (one lake storage for inundation, two landscapes for vegetation response); temporal resolution (hydrology/daily, vegetation/monthly)
- f. Selection of approach: hybrid approach composed of two parts, hydrological module including inundation extent and soil moisture simulation; ecological module for leaf area index simulation based on precipitation, inundation, soil moisture and evapotranspiration over the two landscapes
- g. Model structure: inundation (water balance in the lake storage); conceptual hydrological model (IHACRES-CMD) for soil moisture accounting, and statistical approach or other alternatives such as carbon assimilation approach for the vegetation dynamics module
- h. Parameterisation: optimize the objective function of inundation extent and leaf area index using Shuffled Complex Evolution method
- i. Model testing & evaluation: cross-validation; comparison with individual datasets such as habitat suitability from existing research
- J. Uncertainty analysis: compare model structure alternatives (comparison of alternative model families for soil moisture accounting, vegetation dynamics model).

Using the proposed framework, the choices b, c, and e were associated with data availability (i.e. feasibility). For example, the data requirements for the hydrological module such as flow are easily met, whereas for the vegetation, remote sensing data was considered most suitable due to a lack of long-term ground-truth data. This limited data availability means we need to do more evaluation in i to improve model reliability, as there are scale mismatches between satellite data and the ground survey, and temporal gaps in satellite data with site-based observations. For f, g, h, i, and j, we chose modelling approaches based on model purpose (a), selected relationships (d), prior knowledge from historical monitoring and research, previous studies in similar wetlands such as Macquarie Marshes, and time to implement the analysis. The biophysical processes included in the model (d), such as inundation, evapotranspiration, rainfall and soil moisture, were selected based on a literature review on semi-arid wetlands. Integrating sub-models involving these drivers and tailoring them to key eco-hydrological processes were considered crucial for model reliability. The chosen approaches represent our conceptualization of the wetland system, which was in some ways biased towards addressing the feasibility of the modeling, highlighting the need to test alternative structures to contribute to the coupled model's reliability.

Conclusions

The justification of modeling decisions is paramount for promoting the credibility of the modeling process and specific model outcomes. Here we present the foundations of a framework using a fitness-for-purpose concept to justify what are mostly less technical modeling decisions. Wherever possible, we advocate comprehensive assessment and inter-comparison of the more technical model choices such as model structure, variables to include, process detail and scales.

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Confronting the Elephant in the Room: The Importance of How Data are Used for Model Development and Evaluation

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Summary

Data are essential for the development and evaluation of environmental models. Depending on model type, they are used to determine the values of unknown model parameters and the structure of the model itself, as well as for the assessment of the performance of the developed model. Which data we use for these purposes can therefore have a significant impact on both the final model and the perceived performance of this model. It is therefore critical that we consider the implications of how data are used for model development and evaluation. However, this issue is too often ignored – the elephant in the room.

Introduction

Environmental models are used extensively to help us to better understand environmental systems and to support decision-making. How well these models perform and how useful they are is dependent on which data are available for model development and how the available data is used. While the former is generally beyond the control of modellers, the latter is not and usually involves decisions about how the available data are split into calibration (model development) and validation (model evaluation) subsets.

Such partitioning is required because the available data have to be used for both model parameter tuning and structure selection (model development) and to understand how well models can be expected to perform when actually applied in practice (model evaluation). The manner in which the available data are assigned to these subsets (hereafter we will refer to this by the imperfect term “data-splitting”) has a direct impact on the resulting model, and its perceived performance.

Although data-splitting can have a significant impact on model performance, the optimal way to achieve this has been largely ignored in literature. The consequences are far reaching, resulting in models with reduced generalization ability, a misleading assessment of the absolute and relative performance of models, and suboptimal decisions based on the outputs of these models.

Methodology and Results

To address the elephant in the room, this presentation (i) articulates why a careful choice of how data are partitioned into development and evaluation subsets is critical, (ii) outlines problems with both traditional and state-of-the-art data splitting approaches, and (iii) provides a roadmap and call to action. These are based on Maier et al. (2023). We hope that this presentation will stimulate discussion on what role data play in the model development process, what the purpose of model calibration and validation actually is and how we should

evaluate the performance of models. We are hopeful that the outcome is the development of improved approaches to using the available data, and hence model development.

Specifically, we call on the modelling and research communities to focus on the following courses of action:

1) Increase Awareness and Adoption. Researchers and modelers need to become more aware of the widespread impact the way the available data are split into development and evaluation subsets has on the resulting model and its perceived performance.

2) Perform Comparison and Evaluation. Researchers and modelers need to quantify the impact of data-splitting relative to that of other steps in the model development process.

3) Develop Improved Data-Splitting Approaches. Research is required to improve a number of aspects of data-splitting approaches, including:

a. Addressing the bias-variance dilemma. While some efforts have been made to develop data-splitting methods that minimize the bias-variance dilemma for data with different characteristics, further work is required to ensure the “best” possible models, given the available data, are developed. This is particularly the case when dealing with noisy data, extreme events and data with underlying trends and patterns that are associated with changing conditions (such as climate).

b. Improving the applicability of data-splitting methods to physically-based (PB) models. Existing data-splitting methods generally do not address the need to maintain the underlying time structure of the data, and hence cannot be applied directly to PB models that require time-consecutive observations as inputs. Consequently, efforts need to be intensified to develop strategies that enable the application of data-splitting methods to PB model development.

c. Accounting for data scale and data sampling variability. No matter how long the observational record, the available data are generally a particular realization of the underlying physic process. Therefore, the issue of data sampling variability (DSV) inevitably exists and again this issue is largely ignored in the modelling community. Consequently, when using the available data to develop models, it is necessary to account for DSV.

d. Improving out-of-sample performance. While this presentation focuses on new methods to improve “in-sample” model performance, future work should also address the need to better use the available data to enhance out-of-sample model performance.

Conclusions

When it comes to developing Earth and environmental system models, the impact of how data are used for model development and evaluation is undoubtedly the elephant in the room. Even though decisions on how to use the available data for model development and evaluation occurs near the beginning of the model development process, and therefore impacts *all* subsequent processes, this impact is largely ignored, with little to no justification of why the available data are used in the way they are and seemingly no understanding of, or interest in, the potential impacts of these choices. This is despite the fact that the way the data are used determines what model we end up with, how we assess its performance, the resulting uncertainty in model outputs and, ultimately, what decisions we make based on these model outputs. This is extremely surprising, given the large amount of attention that is paid to other model development processes, such as calibration, evaluation and uncertainty analysis, and the significantly greater degree of scrutiny these are subjected to, even though the outcomes of these processes are *all* contingent on how the available data are used. This is analogous to focusing on the noise, while ignoring the signal. Consequently, greater attention needs to be paid to this issue and we are hopeful that this presentation will raise awareness of this issue and will start discussions that will lead to improved outcomes.

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Multi-Scale Forecast Skill Evaluation Framework for Integrated Early Warning Systems

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Summary

Integrated early warning systems (IEWS) are increasingly being used to help protect freshwater quality and public health, particularly amidst the growing number of cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms (cyanoHABs) linked to human-induced nutrient overload. These blooms pose global threats to health, ecosystems, and economies, necessitating accurate prediction and prevention measures. Evaluation frameworks, like the multi-scale assessment discussed, are pivotal in ensuring the effectiveness of early warning systems. This framework evaluates the forecast performance by drawing from approaches like the variational ensemble streamflow prediction assessment. The study, focused on Lake Champlain, Vermont, demonstrates the utility of this assessment approach by comparing different scenarios generated with observed and predicted data, helping to understand the spatial and temporal variations in forecast skill and identify the importance of accurate future forcings in IEWS.

Introduction

Integrated Early Warning Systems (IEWS) for freshwater quality are essential for safeguarding water resources and public health. The occurrence of potentially harmful cyanobacteria blooms (cyanoHABs) in freshwater systems, exacerbated by human-induced excess nutrient loadings, has global implications, affecting human health, ecosystems, and economies. The prediction and prevention of these cyanoHABs outbreaks are critical for managing water quality and mitigating their impacts (Hecht et al., 2022; Ho & Michalak, 2017; Zia et al., 2016). The forecasting ability of such models for cyanoHAB early warning depends on the quantity and frequency of available data (Wang et al., 2018), and frameworks for evaluating these model forecasts are essential for ensuring the effectiveness of these systems to provide timely and accurate alerts. This paper presents a multi-scale evaluation framework for cyanoHABs IEWS designed to produce a 7-day cyanoHAB forecast every day. It comprises a process-based integrated assessment model (Hecht et al., 2022; Zia et al., 2016) that simulates Lake Champlains' Inland Sea physical processes, including the hydrology of contributing basins and their management, and the respective Bay's water quality dynamics.

Methodology and Results

The cyanoHAB early warning system developed for the northeastern part of Lake Champlain, Vermont, is an integrated assessment model that includes climatic, hydrological, and lake systems components. It is designed as a loosely coupled system to prioritize modularity and flexibility in interchanging the component models. The hydrological part of the Integrated Early Warning System used for weekly cHABs forecasting is configured to include the National Water Model (NWM) Medium Range Blend Forecast that uses the NOAA Global Forecast System (GFS) model to produce a 10-day streamflow forecast for CONUS (Cosgrove et al., 2024) and the corresponding GFS forcing meteorological data. The Inland Sea subsystem, including Missisquoi Bay and St Albans Bay, is simulated with the AEM3D hydrodynamic and water quality model. In this study, the retrospective weekly forecast is spanning 2018–2023 from June 1st through October 31st. To perform our experiment, we utilized the Bluemoon high-performance computing (HPC) cluster hosted by the Vermont Advanced Computing Center (VACC).

A comprehensive framework for evaluating forecast skill is essential to ensure the reliability and robustness of integrated early warning systems. Such a framework includes data quality assessment, model performance analysis, and validation against observed outcomes. A notable example of a forecast skill evaluation framework in hydrology is the variational ensemble streamflow prediction assessment (VESPA) approach (Arnal et al., 2017; Wood et al., 2016). The proposed framework draws from VESPA's philosophy as its direct implementation to IEWS, due to the challenges posed when coupling models. The developed scenario-based evaluation framework is closer to the traditional ensemble prediction methodology since observed retrospective meteorological data are used in the IEWS' spin-up period to generate realistic initial conditions for the Lake just before the short-term forecast period. The true forecast skill of the baseline scenario is determined against observed datasets. This comparison to observed datasets is essential to evaluate inherent modeling errors. The evaluation is conducted in locations where long-term water sampling-derived and remotely sensed satellite-derived observational data are available to assess forecast skill both temporally and spatially. The IEWS output for the baseline scenario is driven by observed weather and hydrological data in the spin-up and the short-term forecast periods. In order to evaluate the importance of accurate information about future forcings, the remaining scenarios are generated using the inputs of different ensemble members; they are used to drive only the simulation of the forecast period and compared against the baseline scenario, thus disregarding the relative effect of modeling errors.

Conclusions

The proposed framework serves as a critical tool in the continuous improvement of IEWS, enabling them to adapt to evolving environmental conditions and inform communities about the impacts of hazards on ecosystems. The forecast skill evaluation framework for IWES encompasses the use of ensemble forecasting members for assessing, in multiple scales, the forecast capacity of integrated physical-based models. This paper focuses more on the forecast capacity due to imperfect predicted meteorological and hydrological information, as well as to pinpoint limitations due to modeling and potential further improvements.

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Impacts of Nitrogen Fertilizer Regulations on Household Food Security

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Summary

In this study, we investigated the impact of nitrogen regulatory policy (NRP) scenarios on households' food security in the Zayandeh-Rud River basin, Iran. We applied the procedure of the Aggregate Household Food Security Index (AHFSI) to explore the impact of calorie variations due to NRP scenarios on food security status. The results showed that the households' food security was in the range of serious food insecurity and low food security for poor-protein and medium-protein diets, respectively. We also showed that the changes in NRP scenarios did not affect the AHFSI significantly. These results highlighted the nitrogen fertilizer application rate revision as an effective solution for satisfying the nitrogen losses in the Zayandeh-Rud River basin without variations in the produced calories.

Introduction

The results from global investigations overlooked the impact of mitigation measures related to nitrogen fertilizer use. Specifically, they did not consider how sharing calorie sources from livestock and non-livestock diets affects the vulnerability of nutritional security. Therefore, the impact of calorie variations on nutritional insecurity should be studied separately for different calorie sources. For instance, cereals and livestock contribute to 51 and 8.7 percent of the human global calorie supply, respectively (World Calories- Total, 2023). The goal of this research is to examine the effects of three nitrogen regulatory policy (NRP) scenarios—low, moderate, and high nitrogen fertilizer application—as climate change mitigation measures on household food security in the Zayandeh-Rud River basin, Iran.

Methodology

To achieve the research objectives, we used the Decision Support System for Agrotechnology Transfer (DSSAT) (Version 4.7.5.0) (Hoogenboom et al., 2019) to simulate wheat crop yields under various NRP scenarios. We then adjusted the yields of potatoes, barley, alfalfa, and forage corn based on the simulated wheat yields for nine subregions located at the Zayandeh-Rud River basin, Iran. Then, we measured the average of the Aggregate Household Food Security Index (AHFSI), introduced by FAO (FAO, 1996), through Equations 1, 2, and 3 for four diet components (q: wheat, potatoes, meat, and dairy) and two dietary preferences (q: poor-protein and medium-protein diets) in the region. The transformation of crop yields to diet components and the detection of dietary preferences were followed as a procedure developed by Tirgariseraji et al. (2024). AHFSI represents the households' food security based on the share of the population under malnutrition (ρ), calorie shortfall (G), inequality in calorie distribution among households (I), and coefficient of variation in dietary energy supplies (CV). The calorie shortfall is the share of the difference between the "average calorie requirement normally" (C_{req}) (kcal) and "average availability of calories" (C_{ava}) (kcal) to "average calorie availability from the reference diet" (C_{ref}) (kcal).

$$AHFSI_{d,r}^{S,q} = 1 - [\rho(G + (1 - G)I) + \frac{1}{2}CV_{d,r}^{S,q}(1 - \rho(G + (1 - G)I))] \quad (1)$$

$$G = \rho \cdot \left(\frac{C_{req} - C_{ava}}{C_{ref}} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\overline{AHFSI}_d^{s,q} = \frac{\sum_{r=1}^n AHFSI_{q,r}^{s,q}}{n} \tag{3}$$

where, *d*, *q*, *r*, and *S* represent the diet components (*d*: wheat, potatoes, meat, and dairy), dietary preferences (*q*: poor-protein and medium-protein diets), subregions (*r*: 1, ..., *n*=9), and NRP scenarios (*S*: low, moderate, and high NRP scenarios), respectively. In Equation 3, *n* is the number of subregions. The ranges of AHFSI determine the status of food security such as i) $\overline{AHFSI}_d^S \leq 0.65$: serious food insecurity; ii) $0.65 < \overline{AHFSI}_d^S \leq 0.75$: low food security; iii) $0.75 < \overline{AHFSI}_d^S \leq 0.85$: sustainable food security; iv) and, $0.85 < \overline{AHFSI}_d^S \leq 1.00$: high food security (Thomson and Metz, 1999).

Results

According to the results of AHFSI reported in Table 1, the food security status associated with the poor-protein diet ranges in the ‘serious food insecurity’ for all diet components as $\overline{AHFSI}_d^S \leq 0.65$. The status of AHFSI for a medium-protein diet varies from serious food insecurity for potatoes to low food security for wheat, meat, and dairy. The comparison of values of AHFSI for wheat across scenarios showed more alteration for the medium-protein diet due to NRP variations than for the poor-protein diet.

Table 1. Aggregate Household Food Security Index (AHFSI) for poor-protein (PPD) and medium-protein (MPD) dietary preferences

Diet components	Low NRP scenario		Moderate NRP scenario		High NRP scenario	
	Poor-protein diet	Medium-protein diet	Poor-protein diet	Medium-protein diet	Poor-protein diet	Medium-protein diet
Wheat	0.519	0.701	0.517	0.699	0.514	0.694
Potato	0.415	0.618	0.414	0.617	0.415	0.618
Meat	0.100	0.706	0.100	0.708	0.100	0.709
Dairy	0.220	0.727	0.221	0.730	0.221	0.731

Source: Research findings.

Conclusions

This study investigated the consequences of three NRP scenarios on households’ food security status by four main diet components, i.e., wheat, potatoes, meat, and dairy. We discovered significant food insecurity across all dietary components in a protein-deficient diet, with the most severe impacts observed in meat and dairy consumption. Our findings indicate that alterations in calories from domestic production, due to changes in nitrogen fertilizer rates, had minimal impact on household food security in our study region.

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Modeling food and agricultural systems for a circular bioeconomy

Introducing a Novel Resilience Approach in the Assessment of Agricultural Interventions

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Summary

Agriculture plays a critical role in the livelihoods of Senegal's population. Yet, its productivity faces notable challenges due to occurrences of extreme events like floods, droughts, and heat waves. This study presents a novel resilience approach for evaluating agricultural interventions. Specifically, the focus is on smallholder farmers in Senegal's Groundnut Basin who practice mixed farming, combining crop cultivation with livestock rearing. The proposed holistic approach encompasses demographics, economics, consumption behavior, and farm operations and is adaptable to farmers of varying characteristics across different regions.

Introduction

Climate change and variability, extreme events (e.g., drought and floods), major natural disasters, political instability, civil unrest, and mass pandemics have profoundly impacted global food and nutrition security. These events compromise global access, availability, and stability in nutritious food supplies. Therefore, it is imperative to enhance the resilience of communities, households, and individuals to better cope with unforeseen events. While no consensus exists on measuring resilience, this paper defines it as farmers' ability to meet their nutritional and economic needs with minimal risk.

Methodology and Results

The approach outlined in this study assesses resilience by utilizing a comprehensive framework. Here, we employed two distinct models (APSIM, Agricultural Production Systems Simulator (Holzworth et al., 2018); and FARMSIM, Farm Simulation Model (developed by Texas A&M in 2023)) to gather essential data on nutrition, economics, and risk factors. Given its prominence in Senegal's agricultural landscape, APSIM was utilized to simulate millet yield. FARMSIM was used to model crops and livestock together, reflecting the conditions of smallholder farmers in Africa (Chikafa et al., 2023).

This study seeks to investigate the influence of different nitrogen fertilizer rates, planting dates, and plant densities on millet production and their implications for the resilience of smallholder farmers amidst severe drought conditions. The alternative scenarios encompass six nitrogen fertilizer rates, three planting dates, and three plant densities, totaling 54 management scenarios alongside their respective baselines per district for a total of 324 simulations.

This study established resilience when nutritional and economic conditions were met with minimal risk to the farmer. Regarding nutrition, this involved an optimization analysis to meet the minimum human nutritional needs (Objective 1). A multi-objective optimization was utilized to meet the minimum nutrition requirements of farmers while ensuring a healthy, balanced diet at the lowest cost. For Objective 1, alternative scenarios were ranked based on achieving a nutritionally balanced diet at the lowest cost. Once the households' nutritional

requirements were met, an economic analysis was conducted to identify economically viable solutions. The process began by filtering out economically unfeasible alternatives (Objective 2). Solutions with negative internal rates of return (IRR) were eliminated. Subsequently, the remaining options were evaluated using three economic indicators: ending cash reserves (EC), net present value (NPV), and net cash farm income (NCFI). Ultimately, two risk factors, risk premium (RP) and certainty equivalent (CE), were used to assess the economically feasible alternatives and determine the most resilient alternatives (Objective 3). Table 1 illustrates the final ranking from the nutrition, economic, and risk analyses.

Table 1. The top four rankings of alternatives for all districts in the study region, based on nutrition, economic, and risk analyses, are summarized. The alternative scenarios are labeled by planting date_plant density_nitrogen fertilizer rate (adapted from Moller et al., 2023).

Rank	Nutrition analysis	Economic analysis	Risk analysis
1	Early_3.3_40	Late_3.3_40	Late_3.3_40
2	Late_3.3_20	Medium_6.6_20	Medium_6.6_100
3	Medium_3.3_20	Medium_6.6_100	Medium_6.6_80
4	Late_3.3_40	Late_6.6_100	Late_6.6_100

Conclusions

Current metrics for measuring resilience adopt a holistic framework covering social, environmental, nutritional, and economic dimensions. However, there is no assurance that a top-ranking method adequately addresses population needs across these domains. Furthermore, many resilience metrics overlook the element of risk. Thus, the approach adopted in this study endeavors to remedy these deficiencies, enhancing its robustness. Moreover, we developed an innovative and qualitative approach that employs integrated crop-livestock models instead of arbitrary weighted metrics. These adaptable models can be calibrated for other regions, conditions, climates, technologies, and practices. This paper introduces a pioneering approach for assessing farmer resilience to climate extremes. The comprehensive methodology utilized in this study provides an intricate and multi-faceted evaluation of farmers' resilience to climatic challenges. Consequently, it is imperative that this approach be acknowledged and adopted by stakeholders so they can effectively address farmers' nutritional needs within budget limitations while mitigating farmer risks.

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Routes to Sustainability: How Global Trade Can Facilitate Circular Agriculture

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Summary

This study proposes an analytical framework to assess the merits and feasibility of global circular economy initiatives in agriculture by evaluating the transportation time, logistics costs, and environmental impacts of exchanging underutilized materials between countries, enabling informed decision-making for sustainable, circular practices worldwide.

Introduction

With the global agricultural sector facing mounting pressures to enhance its sustainability, reduce waste, and improve resource efficiency, increasing attention is being paid to the viability of embracing circular bio-economy practices. The sector produces a wealth of residual materials, by-products, and co-products that hold immense potential for circular reuse. However, there is often spatial mismatch between the supply of these resources and demand for them. Geographical heterogeneity in farming practices, industrial infrastructure, and consumer preferences contribute to this, underscoring the vital importance of connecting underutilised resources in one location with the appropriate processing or end-use capabilities in other parts of the world. While the global exchange of agricultural residue streams and co-products holds promise, the practical realities of long-range transportation can introduce countervailing environmental and economic factors that risk undermining the case for circularity. Logistical expenses, transportation externalities, and challenges in preserving material integrity over extended transit times must be carefully evaluated against the potential value recovery from these underutilised resources in order to determine the merits of engaging in such activities.

Recognising both the promise and the practical realities of circulating underutilised agricultural materials across international borders, this study aims to establish an analytical framework that can inform subsequent assessments of the merits and feasibility of global circular economy initiatives in the agricultural sector. We set out a means of identifying potential trade routes for exchanging materials between countries, evaluating the transportation time, logistics costs, and environmental impacts associated with moving resources along the identified pathways. By providing a standardised approach to quantifying the key operational and environmental factors influencing the viability of cross-border flows, this approach can enable more informed decision-making by policymakers, industry stakeholders, and supply chain actors seeking to implement sustainable, circular practices globally.

Methodology and Results

Drax Power Station, located in Selby, England, is the United Kingdom's largest electricity generator. In recent years it has transitioned from using coal as its primary fuel source to biomass. The biomass fuel used at Drax primarily consists of compressed wood pellets made from sawmill refuse and other wood-based by-products, though the plant also utilizes a small percentage agricultural residues as part of its biomass inputs (Drax, 2023). These biomass inputs are sourced globally, with the majority coming from the United States, Canada, Latvia, and Brazil (Drax, 2023). As such, Drax Power Station represents an example of the circular bio-economy operating across international borders, albeit a somewhat imperfect one. Drax's reporting means information is readily available on its biomass sources, the ports it uses, and the transportation methods utilised. This makes it an ideal initial case study to use in developing a methodology for assessing the environmental footprint and economics of a global circular bio-economy enterprise with links to agriculture.

Using the detailed information provided in Drax's Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Performance Report (2023), we are able to infer likely trade routes for the company's biomass pellets using a novel multi-modal route optimisation tool. This allows us to calculate the total tonne-kilometres travelled by each mode of transportation—including rail, sea, and road—across Drax's globally dispersed supply chain. Applying unit-based coefficients for time, emissions (BEIS, 2021), and logistics costs (UNCTAD, 2021; BTS, 2023) to these tonne-kilometre figures then allows a rough estimation of the time, emissions, and costs associated with the transportation components of Drax's biomass supply chain. The approach also makes it possible to calculate the share of pellets that pass through particular pinch points such as the Panama Canal (8.49%) and Bosphorus (0.21%), providing additional insights into supply chain vulnerabilities. The results are shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Pellet production locations and their inferred routes to Drax Power Station in the UK. Estimates of transportation time, emissions, and cost are set out for each production region, along with the share of pellets that pass through the Panama Canal and Bosphorus.

Conclusions

We have demonstrated a means of assessing some of the transportation frictions involved in circulating underutilised agricultural materials globally, an important step in determining the merits of such activities. The approach can be readily applied to other materials and scenarios as long as data on potential sources, sinks, and volumes, plus other activity-relevant parameters can be compiled. Future refinements will include taking better account of uncertainty and adding handling frictions into the calculations.

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Evaluating the Feasibility of Greenhouse Farming in Vermont, United States

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Summary

The agriculture sector represents a major economic and cultural driver in the State of Vermont. Dairy operations make up about half of all farms in the State and despite the \$35 million spent on subsidies each year, they are struggling to survive the escalating social and climatic disruptions when their return on assets is about 1% each year. Supporting these and other farms across the State in diversifying operations and removing crops from high-risk areas such as flood zones is critical to their long-term resilience. This project evaluates one pathway towards diversification and risk reduction, the addition of a year-round greenhouse paired with on-site generation. Using Monte Carlo simulations, this project evaluates net present value of farm profits for three scenarios in which a greenhouse is paired with various on-site energy systems.

Introduction

Controlled environment agriculture has the capacity for the expansion of local food production in currently untenable conditions like urban communities and cold climates. Renewable combined heat and power systems could fill critical gaps in the renewable energy grid of the future. Examples outside the United States have demonstrated that these technologies operate well in combination and have the potential to provide significant benefits to society including greater food security and decarbonization of the electric grid. This paper first seeks to evaluate several greenhouse + CHP systems against traditional energy generation systems and in comparison to the traditional US agricultural model to clarify the benefits and drawbacks of these technologies.

Despite the expected benefits of greenhouse + CHP systems, they are not being developed in the United States at the same rate or scale as in other countries. Leaders in this space suggest that they are not currently being developed in the United States due to financial and educational burdens of the technology and the disconnection of benefits. The benefits do not accrue to individual owners of the technology, but to society as a whole, leaving little incentive for investment. Therefore, this paper also seeks to identify actionable policies that would allow for private enterprise to adopt controlled environment agriculture (CEA) and combined heat and power (CHP) systems specifically in the context of Vermont.

Methodology and Results

We develop a Monte Carlo simulation model that combines engineering and scientific data with economic forecasting based on historical data to evaluate the long-run profitability of greenhouse farming in the state of Vermont, United States. Our initial results show that without significant subsidies, such a farming system is unlikely to generate profits. We find that current subsidies received by dairy farms have the potential to be repurposed towards greenhouse farming, thereby stabilizing farm incomes and making them less susceptible to natural shocks.

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Water infrastructure system modelling and optimization for a sustainable future

Adapting a Watershed Model to Urban Watersheds

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Summary

The VELMA model is a framework for creating ecohydrological models. This talk discusses additions to VELMA to support models that include urban areas.

Introduction

VELMA—visualizing ecosystem land management assessments—is a framework for creating ecohydrological models. VELMA was designed to work in a variety of watersheds but increasing urban areas have created challenges for creating accurate models. We have added a number of new features to support modelling in areas where waterflow is not determined solely by slope, where permeability may vary due to man-made structures, and evaporation is not solely determined by plant ground cover.

Methodology and Results

The following features were added to the VELMA modeling framework: pipes and drains, to allow the movement of surface water in a way not governed by slope, a permeability fraction to control how surface water moves into the soil layers, and a new evaporation model for surface water, independent of ground cover. These features have been applied to urban areas, in particular to the Longfellow Creek area of West Seattle. Calibrating the model using these features resulted in significantly better hydrographs and Nash Sutcliffe values.

Conclusions

Hydrological modelling in urban areas can be challenging given that man-made changes to the landscape control how and where water moves. Models such as SWMM are designed for urban areas but are difficult to set up and calibrate and do not handle natural areas of the watershed well. Some fairly simple additions to the VELMA model allow the simulation of both natural and urban areas. Using the new features is straight-forward to add and calibrate and results in significantly better hydrologic results in watersheds with urban areas.

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Challenges of Using Robustness Metrics for Water Resources System Management Under Uncertainty

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Summary

Uncertainty about future conditions presents a challenge to the effective management of water resources systems. To consider this uncertainty robustness metrics have been widely used to find solutions that can perform consistently well under plausible future conditions. However, the selection of robustness metrics assumes a particular risk tolerance level and hence presents an additional challenge for decision-makers. This study investigates how different metrics can lead to the selection of different management options, affecting the confidence in decision-making. A real-world reservoir system has been used as the case study to demonstrate challenges of using robustness metrics. This study presents the challenges of selecting appropriate robustness metrics to guide water management decisions under uncertainty, which further highlights the need for a new systematic approach to assist decision-making.

Introduction

Effective management of water resources systems is important for the sustainable development of our society. However, it is a challenging task due to uncertainty. For example, natural variability in system inputs and climate change can have a significant impact on the effectiveness of management decisions. To address this challenge, the concept of robustness has been introduced to identify solutions that provide acceptable performance for a range of uncertain conditions. In order to quantify the robustness of different decision alternatives, different robustness metrics have been developed, which include expected values (Wald, 1950) and regrets-based metrics (Savage, 1951), with each metric capturing different aspects of uncertainty (e.g., risk tolerance levels). Consequently, different metrics can lead to very different solutions that may lead to unexpected management outcomes as found in past studies (Giuliani & Castelletti, 2016; Herman et al., 2015; Quinn et al., 2017). This adds another layer of uncertainty to the decision-making process, reducing the confidence of decision-makers in relation to the performance of their decisions. In this study, different robustness metrics have been compared systematically for a real-world reservoir system, and their impacts on water resources management under uncertainty have been investigated. This provides insights into the challenges of selecting appropriate robustness metrics, potentially highlighting the need for a more systematic approach for effective water resources management under uncertainty.

Methodology and Results

A real-world reservoir management problem from China has been used as the case study. Input uncertainty was considered using an ensemble of 100 inflow timeseries generated from historical data (Wu et al., 2022). Five robustness metrics were selected to investigate the impact of different metrics, based on a guidance framework (McPhail et al., 2021). Results show that different robustness metrics result in different results as demonstrated by variation in performance. Besides, due to the implicit assumption of risk tolerance levels in the metric selection process, robustness metrics focusing on similar risk tolerance levels can also give very different results and solution rankings. This can lead to the selection of different management options, reducing confidence in the optimal management of the system.

Conclusions

This research explores the challenges of selecting suitable robustness metrics for effective water resources system management under uncertainty. A reservoir system has been used to demonstrate the potential impacts of selecting different robustness metrics on system performance, and their implications to real-world management decision-making. This study highlights the challenges of selecting appropriate robustness metrics, which further emphasizes the need for a new systematic approach to assist decision-making for water resources system management under uncertainty.

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A Multi-Objective Optimization-Based Framework for Maximizing Water Infrastructure System Service Life Under Deep Uncertainty

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Summary

In the context of climate and water demand change, the future conditions under which water infrastructure systems are managed are deeply uncertain. To maintain the service of these systems over time, traditional strategies such as physical capacity expansion or water demand reduction are expensive or disruptive. To address this issue, this study introduces a multi-objective optimization-based framework to extend the service life of water infrastructure systems under deeply uncertain future conditions. The application of the framework to a hypothetical reservoir system in Northern Australia shows the service life can be extended by up to 40 years; and it also provides valuable insights for developing long-term management strategies.

Introduction

Water infrastructure systems are vital for ensuring water supply reliability and security. Climate change and the resulting shifts in water availability and demand patterns pose a continual challenge to manage these systems sustainably. Traditionally, water resources managers attempt to extend the service life of existing water infrastructure systems through expansion of physical capacity or reduction of water demand. However, these adaptation strategies can be costly and disruptive to service to water users. Therefore, there is a need to find a low-cost and less disruptive alternatives for maximizing the service life of existing water infrastructure systems. Adaptation of operation policies over time is investigated as an alternative option in this study.

Methodology and Results

In this study, we developed a multi-objective optimization-based framework to (1) maximise water infrastructure service life through the adaptation of operation policies and (2) estimate the extent to which the service life can be extended under uncertainty. This is done by re-optimizing operation policies to accommodate potential changes and uncertainties in future water availability and demand conditions. The framework enables the full potential of existing water infrastructure systems to be utilised, thereby extending their service life without requiring expensive or disruptive strategies.

To demonstrate the application of the framework, it was applied to a hypothetical reservoir system in Northern Australia. Results show that the service life of this system can be extended by up to 40 years, despite the uncertainties associated with future water availability and demand. Moreover, crucial changes in operation policies and system responses over time were explored. For example, water releases will initially rise to meet the growing water demand, but will eventually decrease to enhance water supply security in response to potential future reductions in water availability.

Conclusions

In this study, a comprehensive framework for maximizing the utility of existing water infrastructure under deep uncertainty was developed, thereby postponing or even avoiding expensive and disruptive strategies. The insights gained from the changes in operation policies and system responses over time can offer valuable guidance for developing reservoir management strategies in the deeply uncertain future. In addition, the

framework can also be used to estimate the time when the existing reservoir system can no longer perform satisfactorily, informing other adaptation strategies.

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How Do We Consider Cyber-Security as an Objective in the Sustainable Management of Water Infrastructure?

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Summary

Cyber risk to water infrastructure is growing and must be managed for the sustainable future of these systems. We utilise and adapt an approach to assessing and quantifying the cyber risk of water infrastructure in an effort to enable cyber-security to be included as an objective for the planning, design and operation of water distribution systems. The approach quantifies cyber risk at different scales, and testing indicates the potential for this to accompany typical objectives for decision making regarding water infrastructure.

Introduction

Water supply infrastructure, particularly water distribution systems (WDSs), are incredibly important, and their continued operation supports society by way of supply for industrial water use, agricultural and residential needs. To ensure these complex networks can function sustainably into the future, their planning, design and operation need to consider a number of competing objectives, requiring the development of appropriate quantitative modelling, simulation and optimisation approaches. Although there have been efforts to quantify carbon, and energy use of the water-energy nexus (Wu, Maier, & Simpson, 2013), the primary focus of these quantitative methods are cost and reliability (Farmani, Savic, & Walters, 2005).

However, there is another important factor that has been largely ignored in the decision-making process for the planning, design and operation of WDSs – cyber security. The need to consider cyber security arises from the fact that WDSs are increasingly connected to complex control networks (cyber networks), creating cyber-physical systems. This connection introduces a cyber risk to WDSs, namely that of a cyber-attack that can cause a physical impact due to disrupted control of the infrastructure.

As these cyber networks, that are essential in ensuring that supply systems can achieve their desired outcomes, are increasing in scale and their threats are increasing (Stouffer et al., 2022), there is an urgent need to manage the cyber risks of WDSs into the future to achieve sustainable outcomes.

Methodology and Results

In this study, an approach is developed to enable the cyber risk to WDSs to be quantified such that cyber-security can be considered alongside other objectives for their planning, design and operation. This approach builds on the approach of (Keenan, Maier, van Delden, & Zecchin, 2024), which overcomes the current cyber-physical divide in the assessment of the cyber-physical risk of WDSs. This divide exists because cyber risk is generally only quantified within the cyber domain, without consideration of what that cyber component failure may have an impact on in the physical domain. Likewise, as stated above, quantitative approaches to modelling and simulation of water supply systems are generally only based on cost and reliability, without consideration of this cyber risk.

In order to cross this divide, a modified version of the approach of Keenan et al. (2024), (Figure 1) is used to quantify the cybersecurity of WDSs. Utilising this approach quantifies the cyber risk of all physical assets of interest within the WDS network, as well as the level of contribution to risk for each cyber component. In order to enable a single overall cyber risk value for WDSs to be obtained, the cyber risk values at individual physical assets are aggregated in this study using a weighted sum approach.

Figure 1. Crossing the cyber-physical divide in risk assessment (adapted from Keenan et al., 2024)

This approach to quantifying cyber risk was used as it provides multiple benefits. As the cyber risk is quantified for each physical asset, it provides multiple decision points for optimisation of design, or mitigation measures within the physical network. Likewise, the contribution to risk of each cyber component is quantified, providing a similar resolution for the same management options within the cyber network. Furthermore, as mentioned above, by aggregating the risk values with a weighted sum, the design and structure of the networks as a whole can be quantified and assessed.

Our results of testing this approach demonstrate that the cyber risk of WDSs can be quantified at the scale of individual assets, but also network wide. Subsequent to this, these values can be used alongside other performance metrics (cost, hydraulics, reliability, carbon, energy, etc.) in multi-objective problems to effectively measure cyber security in the planning, design and operation of WDSs. This aids the sustainable function of WDSs into the future, as their cyber risks increase.

Conclusions

We utilise and adapt an approach that allows for the quantification of cyber risk to water infrastructure, allowing cyber security to be included as an objective in the planning, design and operation of water infrastructure. Results indicate this is an effective approach at understanding risk at various scales, making it useable in decision making for the WDS.

This is a step in understanding how the connectivity and network design of the connected water infrastructure effects the cyber security of the network. Further work aims to use this approach to investigate further the trade-offs in connectivity and risk, to develop a methodology to manage the cyber security objective of the WDS and ensure the sustainable future of water infrastructure.

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Exploring the Benefits of Integrated Energy-Water Management in Reducing Economic and Ecological Trade-Offs

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Summary

Understanding how hydropower operations should adapt to manage competing goals under a decarbonizing grid requires an integrated model of the water-energy system. This requires an economic model of electricity prices and their financial impacts on power producers, as well as a network flow model of the power sector to calculate fossil fuel emissions. This study introduces an integrated water-energy optimization model for this purpose, using the Columbia River Basin (CRB) and Mid-Columbia energy market as a case study. Our work illustrates the multi-objective benefits of integrated water-energy management, while also elucidating remaining trade-offs in their joint operation.

Introduction

Designing multi-reservoir operating policies to balance competing socioeconomic and ecological objectives is a challenging, multi-objective control problem. Multipurpose reservoirs provide water for clean energy, recreation, navigation and flood protection. However, dams also have detrimental ecological impacts, altering the natural flow of water, sediment and nutrients, impeding fish migration, and impairing water quality. Balancing these trade-offs could become increasingly challenging for power producers as the role of hydropower in meeting electricity demands changes with decarbonization of the grid. Understanding how hydropower operations should adapt to manage these competing goals requires an integrated model of the water-energy system, including an economic model of electricity prices and their financial impacts on power producers, and a network flow model of the power sector to calculate fossil fuel emissions. Yet, such integrated models are lacking in the literature. This study introduces an integrated water-energy optimization model for this purpose.

Methodology and Results

We evaluate the economic and ecological benefits of integrated management of the water and electricity sector using the Columbia River Basin (CRB) and Mid-Columbia electricity market as a case study. This model couples a simulation model of 46 CRB reservoirs and a unit commitment/economic dispatch model of the California and West Coast Power system (CAPOW). We use a model-free, closed loop optimal control method called Direct Policy Search (DPS) to design reservoir operations at four of the system reservoirs in conjunction with the dispatch of non-hydropower energy sources (wind, natural gas, and in California, solar). We couple DPS with a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm (MOEA) to optimize four objectives simultaneously: maximize economic benefits from electricity production, minimize electricity generation from fossil fuels, minimize environmental flow violations, and minimize peak flood levels. We find the system can improve performance on all objectives simultaneously compared to the current operating rules, yet trade-offs remain between prioritizing clean energy production and utility revenue vs. environmental flows, as well as between clean energy production and flood protection.

Conclusions

Our work illustrates the multi-objective benefits of integrated water-energy management, while also elucidating remaining trade-offs decision-makers must weigh in, in designing their joint operations.

Turbidity Source Apportionment of the Urban Lakeside River Network

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Summary

With the rapid economic growth and land use/cover change, turbidity impairment of water bodies has increasingly become a global concern. Various turbidity sources of Huzhou urban river network were quantified by a new framework integrating in-situ water sampling, vessel volume monitoring, RS, export coefficients, and scenarios simulation of the MIKE 11-based TSS model. This framework specifically considered the flow reversal from the turbid lake, navigation effect, and urban non-point source, which were critical processes in the urban river network neighboring the lake. The Huzhou turbidity problem was largely SIM-driven, which constituted 58% of the average turbidity at the Huancheng River, the remaining 42% included SOM (19%) and dissolved colored organic compounds and colloids (23%). Tiaoxi River and busy shipping were the two largest contributors to the total TSS load of Huancheng River, with the same percentage of 34%. Turbid Lake Taihu was another important source of TSS load, contributing 31% of the total TSS load. Urban non-point sources only contributed no more than 1%. The shipping and Tiaoxi River sources decreased dramatically during the COVID-19 lockdown and Spring Festival holiday. The aquatic plant restoration near the Tiaoxi River estuary, shipping restriction and rerouting, and integrated catchment management are three potential measures to mitigate the urban river network turbidity.

Water Distribution System Design Under Long-Term Uncertainty Considering Solar Energy as a Supplementary Energy Source

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Summary

This study focuses on the design of water distribution systems (WDSs) and on-site solar systems, considering uncertain future water demand growth and the potential development of solar energy generation technology. The impact of solar integration on the design of sustainable and resilient WDSs considering changing future water demand growth has been investigated. It has been found that solar integration improves WDS's resilience across different water demand change conditions. Furthermore, solar integration and its technology development can reduce the capital cost for pipes and postpone WDS rehabilitation by maintaining its energy efficiency over time.

Introduction

Water distribution systems (WDSs) are important water supply infrastructure. To provide the required pressure head to water consumers, a significant amount of energy is consumed by WDSs due to pump operation during its service lifetime. Due to the increasing awareness of climate change and the impact of emissions associated with energy consumption, the energy efficiency of WDSs becomes an important consideration when designing the system for the future. On-site solar energy generation has been considered as one potential source of supplementary energy supply for WDSs. Compared to the traditional source of energy from the centralised grid, on-site solar energy is associated with relatively lower capital cost and near-zero emissions. Thus, in this study, the integrated design of WDSs with on-site solar generation systems has been considered.

Considering the high capital investment as well as the long service lifespan of WDSs, the design of WDSs needs to account for uncertain future conditions to maintain their performance over time. Water demand is highly uncertain in the distant future due to the impact of climate change, population growth, and urbanization. Similarly, solar energy generation technologies are developing rapidly, and are expected to further improve overall system energy efficiency. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the design of robust WDS integrating on-site solar energy generation systems that perform consistently well under uncertain future conditions.

Methodology and Results

In this study, both plausible future water demand and solar energy generation technology development are considered. The combined impact of the two sources of uncertainty forms the future scenarios that have been considered in the design of WDS integrating on-site solar. Two major stages are considered for the design. In the first stage, the configuration of WDSs is optimised under individual future scenarios. Leading to one set of optimal design solutions (i.e., Pareto optimal solutions) for each scenario. In the second stage, the performance of all optimal design solutions obtained is evaluated across all future scenarios, and therefore the robustness of these optimal solutions can be calculated. Those solutions that remain non-dominated considering their performance across all future scenarios are the finally selected robust design solutions.

The results show that on-site solar generation reduces WDS's reliance on the traditional centralised grid energy supply. When more energy is consumed from the on-site renewable energy source, the performance of WDSs is improved in terms of lower operational costs and associated greenhouse gas emissions. This suggests that

on-site solar energy provides WDSs with cleaner and more sustainable sources of energy with relatively low capital investment. Moreover, on-site solar integration enhances WDS's resilience to changes in future water demand. WDSs are usually sized large enough to accommodate all future conditions. However, by improving WDS's energy performance across different water demand growth conditions, solar integration enables more medium-cost WDS designs to become robust design solutions. Therefore, it reduces the risk of oversizing the system when designing WDSs for an uncertain future.

Conclusions

This study considers the design of WDS integrating on-site solar energy generation for future water supply. The effectiveness of solar energy as a supplementary energy source has been demonstrated. Moreover, the impacts of two different sources of long-term uncertainty have been investigated. The results demonstrate the ability of on-site solar energy integration to enhance WDS's sustainability and robustness under uncertain future conditions.

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How to Size Behind-the-Meter Solar PV Systems for Water Distribution Networks?

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Summary

This research investigates three approaches to determine the optimal size of behind-the-meter (BTM) solar PV systems used for pressurised water distribution networks (WDNs). These approaches include: 1) the industry approach based on current practices for residential properties, 2) the minimum total life cycle cost (TLCC) approach aiming at minimising TLCC over the solar PV system's lifespan, and 3) the minimum payback period approach with a focus on minimising the duration for recovering the initial investment on the solar PV system. It has been found that the industry approach may lead to over-sizing issues, whereas the minimum payback approach tends to result in under-sizing. Conversely, the minimum TLCC approach provides a balanced performance. The outcomes provide guidance for water utility managers in choosing appropriate solar PV system sizes for WDNs.

Introduction

Water distribution networks (WDNs) play a critical role in both urban and rural areas. The operation of these systems especially for pumping water consumes a significant amount of energy. Water authorities around the world are making efforts to reduce the related energy consumption. For instance, in Victoria, Australia, the water sector has set a goal to reach net-zero emissions by 2035. To meet the increasing demand for water while reducing both environmental impacts and economic costs, many water utilities are exploring on-site renewable energy solutions, such as solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, commonly known as behind-the-meter (BTM) solar PV systems. Currently, there is a lack of a standardised approach for sizing these BTM solar PV systems for WDNs. Therefore, in this study different approaches for determining the optimal size of BTM solar PV systems for WDNs have been evaluated, considering the long-term efficiency and sustainability of the integrated systems.

Methodology and Results

This research examined three approaches for sizing BTM solar PV systems for WDNs. The first approach (known as the industry approach) is developed based on current industrial practices for sizing solar PV systems, particularly for residential buildings. The second approach (known as the minimum TLCC approach), aims to minimise the total life cycle costs over the solar PV system's 25-year lifespan. The third approach (known as the minimum payback approach) focuses on reducing the payback time for the solar PV system's initial investment, which is a critical factor in financial assessments.

Sizing solar PV systems based on the industry approach follows a heuristic process where the solar PV size is obtained from the worst month with the highest demand and the lowest solar energy generation. Sizing solar PV systems with the minimum TLCC or payback period approaches involves formulating a single-objective optimisation problem, where solar PV sizes are the decision variables. The objective is to minimise either the total life cycle cost or the payback period. The performance of these three sizing approaches is evaluated based on economic costs and benefits, energy consumption, and GHG emissions through two case studies. The two case studies include a hypothetical network named 'NET 1' where water is directly pumped to eight downstream users, and a real-world irrigation system in Robinvale, Victoria, Australia, providing service to 244 irrigators with water pumped from the Murray River.

The results from both case studies show that the industry approach tends to lead to the largest solar PV system, which minimises grid energy use and GHG emissions over the life cycle. However, this may result in surplus solar energy that has not been utilised by the integrated system. On the other hand, the minimum payback approach tends to recommend the smallest system, minimising initial costs but potentially leading to under-sizing issues. The minimum TLCC approach provides a balanced performance with the minimum TLCC achieved as well as reasonable performance across other metrics. Nevertheless, it is not feasible to achieve both the lowest total life cycle costs and GHG emissions simultaneously with a single solar PV size.

Conclusions

This research evaluates three approaches for determining the optimal size of solar PV systems for WDNs, against economic, energy and GHG emission performance criteria. The industry approach yields the largest solar PV size, which risks producing more solar energy than the system can use, potentially leading to oversizing issues. Conversely, the minimum payback approach tends to recommend the smallest systems, which may undersize the solar PV system. The minimum TLCC approach finds the minimum total life cycle cost of the integrated system and intermediate performance across other performance criteria. These approaches provide water utility managers with a framework for selecting proper solar PV system sizes for WDNs. People can also choose a tailored approach to meet their unique energy, economic, and environmental needs.

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**Stream E. Socio-environmental
systems modelling for planetary
health and environmental
sustainability**

**Addressing the Grand Challenges to
accelerate use of socio-
environmental systems modelling in
actionable science**

Exascale Computing is Here!

How Could we use it to Support Better Environmental Decision-Making With Agent-Based Models?

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Summary

Exascale computing entails 10^{18} floating point operations per second, and is roughly equivalent to a billion laptops. Use of computing infrastructure beyond personal computing devices is still not a routine feature of agent-based modelling. Empirical applications of agent-based models (ABMs), typically set in an environmental domain, are recognized to need more complicated models (Sun et al. 2016)¹, and hence computational power. Exascale computing is powerful enough that we could interact with empirical ABMs as part of decision-making processes in complex contexts (Polhill et al. 2023). We need new software tools that let us explore the potential of exascale computing.

Introduction

Though mooted as a possibility for more than 15 years, exascale computing was finally officially achieved for the first time in May 2022 on the Frontier exascale computer at Oak Ridge National Laboratory in the USA. Exascale computers are now planned, under construction, or already built in the UK, European Union, Japan and China. Macal and North² anticipated agent-based modelling as a use case for exascale computing as long ago as 2008. Exascale computers make extensive use of GPU (Graphical Processing Units) architectures; massive parallelism being needed to achieve the high rate of computation. While Axtell (2016)³ notes that it is challenging for ABMs to benefit from GPU architectures because of the interactions among the agents, Richmond et al.'s (2021)⁴ FLAME GPU provides a GPU ABM environment.

As we have already said,⁵ in terms of raw numbers, exascale computing could achieve sub-second interactions with empirical ABM simulation experiments that currently take days or weeks on high-performance computing infrastructure. This opens up the intriguing possibility that, with appropriate supporting software, and, critically, institutions for accessing exascale computing (see Polhill 2022⁶), empirical ABMs could be part of creative discussions over options for managing a developing crisis. However, other visions for the potential of exascale

¹ Sun, Z., Lorscheid, I., Millington, J. D., Lauf, S., Magliocca, N. R., Groeneveld, J., Balbi, S., Nolzen, H., Müller, B., Schulze, J. & Buchmann, C. M. (2016) Simple or complicated agent-based models? A complicated issue. *Environmental Modelling & Software* **86**, 56-67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2016.09.006>

² Macal, C. M. & North, M. J. (2008) Agent-based modelling and simulation for exascale computing. *SciDAC Review* Summer 2008, pp. 34-41

³ Axtell, R. L. (2016) 120 million agents self-organize into 6 million firms: a model of the U.S. private sector. In Thangarajah, J., Tuyls, K., Jonker, C. M. & Marsella, S. (eds.) AAMAS'16: Proceedings of the 2016 International Conference on Autonomous Agents & Multiagent Systems, May, 9-13, 2016, Singapore. ACM: New York, pp. 806-816.

⁴ Richmond, R., Chisolm, R., Heywood, P., Leach, M. & Kabiri Chimeh, M. (2021) FLAME GPU. *Zenodo* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5428984>

⁵ Polhill, G., Heppenstall, A., Batty, M., Salt, D., Colasanti, R., Milton, R. & Hare, M. (2023) Exascale computing and 'next generation' agent-based modelling. *Review of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* 29 September 2023. <https://rofasss.org/2023/09/29/exascale-computing-and-next-gen-abm/>

⁶ Polhill, G. (2022) Antisocial simulation: using shared high-performance computing clusters to run agent-based models. *Review of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* 14 December 2022. <https://rofasss.org/2022/12/14/antisoc-sim/>

computing to revolutionize the way we work with ABMs are also possible. We briefly report here on our efforts to elicit these visions from the ABM community.

Methodology and Results

The visions were co-constructed with members of the agent-based modelling community over the course of two workshops, a shorter workshop of two hours held at the Social Simulation Conference in Glasgow in September 2023, and a two-day workshop held in London with invited participants two months later. At each workshop, we developed causal loop models of the potential of exascale computing to support agent-based modelling, starting the conversation by asking participants about their current frustrations with developing and using empirical agent-based models. Hare et al. (2024)⁷ describe the process for the Glasgow workshop in more detail. Here we are more interested in the visions that emerged from these workshops:

Real-time crisis-prevention decision-making: We imagine here a one-day workshop in which an agent-based model to handle a developing social-environmental crisis (e.g. extreme weather event, global pandemic, disruption to trade, large-scale crop failure) is iteratively developed, experimented with, and modified, as part of a creative discussion among experts and analysts. This requires libraries of model components that can be semantically integrated, together with modules that access and process large-scale data to be used for input, calibration and validation.

Meta-modelling across multiple models: Here, we want to train a metamodel such as a generative adversarial network⁸ to reproduce the distributions of outputs from various agent-based models. The training needs large-scale training data, which is obtained by running the models using exascale computing. This requires the models to be executable in exascale computing environments (e.g. on GPUs), using tools that can take advantage of massive parallelism.

Formalization of qualitative social theories: As noted by Muelder & Filatova (2018)⁹, social theories in particular are insufficiently precisely specified that implementing them in agent-based models is a trivial process. Exascale computing enables multiple alternative implementations to be explored. While this adds to the ‘curse of dimensionality’, switching different options on and off scales with 2^N , where N is the number of options, while adding another scalar parameter scales with m^P , where m is the number of samples per parameter, and P is the number of parameters.

Conclusions

Exascale computing has arrived, and with the right software tools and institutions to gain access, has the potential to help with decision-making in complex social-environmental systems. Developing these tools will be of use not just for exascale social-environmental modelling, but for making high-performance computing more routinely used by the agent-based modelling community, and even potentially for improving desktop/laptop agent-based modelling.

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⁷ Hare, M., Salt, D., Colasanti, R., Milton, R., Batty, M., Heppenstall, A. & Polhill, G. (2024) Taking agent-based social simulation to the next level using exascale computing: potential use-cases, capabilities and threats. In Alechina, N., Dignum, V., Dastani, M. & Sichman, J. S. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems (AAMAS 2024) Auckland, New Zealand, May 6 – 10, 2024*.

⁸ Goodfellow, I. J., Pouget-Abadie, J., Mirza, M., Xu, B., Warde-Farley, D., Ozair, S., Courville, A. & Bengio, Y. (2014) Generative adversarial nets. In Ghahramani, Z., Welling, M., Cortes, C., Lawrence, N. & Weinberger, K. Q. (eds.) *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 27 (NIPS 2014)*, 2672-2680. https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2014

⁹ Muelder, H. & Filatova, T. (2018) One theory – many formalizations: testing different code implementations of the Theory of Planned Behaviour in energy agent-based models. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* **21** (4), 5. <https://www.jasss.org/21/4/5.html>

Applying Resilience as Pathway Diversity in a Lake Eutrophication Problem

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Summary

This study explores the concept of resilience in socio-ecological systems, focusing on its application in ongoing decision-making processes. Using a lake eutrophication model, we compare resilience as pathway diversity with other resilience approaches, analysing their similarities and complementarities. We then discuss how pathway diversity can assist decision-makers in uncovering complex dynamics and avoiding undesirable regime shifts. Therefore, this contributes to better operationalising resilience and capturing systemic change in socio-ecological systems.

Introduction

Resilience has been widely used in academia and policy documents. However, it is hard to use ecological resilience metrics to guide decision-making. A recent proposal to address this problem is to use resilience as pathway diversity (Lade et al., 2020). The idea is that a system is more resilient if decision-makers have more options and optionality is maintained through time. We demonstrate how using resilience as pathway diversity can be a more adaptable approach to assist decision-makers in building resilience using the lake problem.

Methodology and Results

We use the lake problem to demonstrate how pathway diversity compares to other resilience approaches. The problem involves developing pollution control policies to avoid lake eutrophication (Carpenter et al., 1999). This lake model has a clean and an eutrophicated steady state. However, depending on the parameters, upon crossing a pollution threshold, the lake goes to an irreversible eutrophicated state (Carpenter et al., 1999). We assume that higher levels of pollution lead to more restrictions on nutrient inflows into the lake. Based on this assumption, we model the pathway diversity of the decision-maker, considering that defining maximum pollution inflow will affect the system state and then feedback into which options are available in the future.

Preliminary results show pathway diversity corresponds with established resilience metrics, such as distance to the basin threshold and early-warning signals (Dakos and Kéfi, 2022). The most significant decline in pathway diversity occurs when crossing the basin threshold, indicating pathway diversity is sensitive to regime shifts. Pathway diversity also significantly decreases as a regime shift approaches, thus having the same behaviour as early-warning signal metrics. Lastly, we examine how pathway diversity can be used by decision-makers to avoid undesirable regime shifts, especially considering highly uncertain scenarios.

Conclusions

We use resilience as pathway diversity to integrate social (decision-making) and ecological (lake pollution) dynamics and develop a model capable of assisting decision-makers in making sense of complex and non-linear dynamics to avoid regime shifts. Given model and parameter uncertainties affect the decision-making process, the use of pathway diversity to assess resilience is examined through an exploratory modelling approach. This work contributes to a better understanding of the role of uncertainty in models and systemic change in socio-ecological systems, i.e Grand Challenges 2 and 5 identified by ElSawah et al. (2019).

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Behaviorally Rich Archetypes for Integrated Modeling of Climate Change Adaptations

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Summary

Modeling cross-scale interactions is a grand challenge for socio-environmental systems modeling (Elsawah et al., 2020), particularly in the context of climate change adaptation (CCA), where local autonomous adaptations and macroscale policies and climate impacts interact. Innovative scaling-up/out methods integrating simulated CCA responses from behaviorally rich agent-based models with macroscale models capable of assessing regional impacts are needed. Using drought and flood adaptation behaviors as examples, we articulate key opportunities and challenges for behaviorally rich integrated modeling of CCA using an archetypes approach.

Introduction

Formal climate policy models play a central role in navigating the societal trade-offs inherent in the cross-scale and cross-sector coordination challenges of CCA (van Maanen et al., 2023). Increased knowledge about behavioral change and social dynamics leading to autonomous CCA actions is shifting the frontier of computational modeling of CCA to more explicitly consider cross-scale feedbacks between autonomous behavioral change, social institutions, and macro-scale climate change impacts (Taberna et al., 2020). This requires integration of conventional Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models or Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) with ABMs (Davidson et al., 2024), however many CGEs/ still rely on a representative agent or types of agents that assume perfectly informed, rational optimizers (Stern et al., 2022). Recent findings, however, have shown that future Earth system states are more sensitive to departures from these simplified human behavioral assumptions than physical parameters of adaptation actions (Taberna et al., 2023) or internal variability of the climate system (Beckage et al., 2018). Despite these limitations, attempts to connect empirical ABM and CGE/IAM models are rare, with successful integration reaching only one-way soft linkages (Niamir et al., 2020). Scaling-up/out outputs from behaviorally rich computational models capable of simulating diverse CCA actions, such as agent-based models (ABM), to extents compatible with macroscales computational models remains an open challenge for the modeling community and CCA research specifically.

Empirical and modeling research efforts in other domains have used archetype analysis to address this challenge. Archetypes are contextually explicit generalizations, typically synthesized across case studies, increasingly used to understand recurrent patterns of variables and processes that shape the sustainability of social-ecological systems in different locations and at different times (Oberlack et al., 2019). While archetypes of behavioral outcomes have been developed for modeling purposes (Malek & Verburg, 2020; Rounsevell et al., 2012), they remain static, cross-sectional, and do not integrate behavioral dynamics from social simulation or behavioral microdata. Realistic models of CCA will require archetypes that embed the behavioral motivations and decision-making processes that drive autonomous adaptation, including disaggregate social interactions known to influence adaptation (i.e., innovation diffusion).

Methodology and Results

This presentation distills reflections from two climate adaptation projects—addressing adaptive responses to drought and floods, respectively—in which computational modeling plays a central. We articulated several open questions for the modeling community to consider for integrating ABMs and macro-scale models for CCA research. These include:

- Where in the model development process (i.e., input or output) and with what methods are behaviorally rich archetypes best produced or applied for ABM-CGE/IAM model integration?
- Do adaptive responses generated by independent archetypes lead to even greater ‘dis-equilibriums’ of the macro-systems, creating even larger computational burdens?
- Should archetypes as a means for model integration be dynamic or consistent throughout the simulation? If the former, how does that affect inputs/outputs exchanged between models? If the latter, how are agents allocated to archetypes over time and between regions explicitly modeled and those to which archetypal responses are extrapolated?
- How does the use of behaviorally rich archetypes impact the propagation of model structural uncertainty and the validations of model outcomes and the internal consistency of archetypes?

We will discuss alternative approaches to developing behaviorally rich archetypes, integrating simulated behaviors and empirical data, to scale-up and/or scale-out ABM outputs to integrate with macro-scale models.

Conclusions

Inverse generative social science simulation modeling or hierarchical, time series clustering of behavioral and attributional microdata emerged as promising approaches to generate archetypes suitable for modeling CCA behaviors. However, the approaches differ in their abilities to support scenario modeling, each presents unique uncertainty analysis and validation challenges, and both may introduce emergent dynamics that are incompatible with equilibrium-based macroscale models.

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Sustainability: From Intention to Risk Reduction

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Summary

Seeking sustainable and resilient futures is a daunting, grand challenge. Little research and practice exist to sufficiently frame and guide the requisite paradigm shift within complex social-ecological systems (SES). Using the State of Michigan environmental protection and redevelopment program, we reveal the frameworks, tools, and processes that achieved rapid innovation, adoption and diffusion, significantly reducing human health and environmental risk—and improving its alignment with a more sustainable SES. This case, with its transformative systems design, has the potential to inspire a SES governance paradigm shift. We aim to share the underlying cultural and structural design, processes, and lessons learned, contributing to the SES governance toolbox of knowledge and practice.

Introduction

Our understanding of the nature of hazardous waste within the environment grew, as did the regulations and technologies to assess the environmental conditions and human health impacts. The State program progressed as did the nation from an era of less program complexity and high environmental and public health risk reduction performance (the 1980s) to a litigious era of risk-based responses, increased program complexity, and less risk reduction (the mid-1990s to the early 2010s).

Addressing this trajectory and wicked problem required engaging with multiple social and ecological systems and addressing numerous SES archetypical traps. Consistent with most government institutions, the program's culture and structure aligned with linear, hierarchical governance and exhibited the dysfunction of one or more SES-decision archetypes with governance aligned to address tame problems—not wicked ones. In essence, there was a misalignment between the environmental and public health governance framework and associated competencies and the complexity of the SES.

Instead of a holistic SES approach, the program relied upon existing tools to control wicked problems by increasing the number of prescriptive regulatory rules. This SES governance approach is a positive feedback loop that feeds a system tipping point – resulting in decision gridlock and escalating environmental and public health risks. Instead, the program's governance needed to align with the complexity of its problems. Key system drivers required identification and leveraging for system balance. For instance, the uncertainty within this wicked SES should have been acknowledged, embraced, and managed through systems thinking and structured deliberative processes that assessed SES functions through quality governance and collaborative weighing of system trade-offs – not by further seeking hierarchical control of uncertain risks. However, social-ecological systems thinking is not a widely distributed skill within most populations or their institutions. Instead, hierarchical governance is normalized, resulting in simplified and routinized thinking and praxis, further stunting cognitive growth, decisions, and sustainable SES outcomes.

Methodology and Results

As part of the Governor's reinvention vision, the Michigan Department of Environmental Quality (MDEQ) partnered with Michigan State University Extension (MSUE) and external consultants and advisors to curate a more durable form of SES governance equipped to address the complexity of the problems it faced (e.g., moving from hierarchical toward participatory quality governance). See Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Comparative Transformative Governance Model

Using hierarchical governance, the red (darker top half) portions of Figure 1 increased risk to human health and the environment (resulting in a positive feedback loop or tipping point). While simplified in this conceptual model, the blue (lighter bottom half) of Figure 1 integrated the natural SES function with human governance – incorporating its combined complexity (i.e., aligning the human purpose, vision, and competencies with the function of the natural environment). This approach resulted in rapid and significant risk reduction to human health and the environment (e.g., balancing feedback).

The transformative design detail is supported by a decade of longitudinal mixed methods research, which incorporates diversity in collaboration and polycentric governance, systems thinking, the use of evidence-based decision support architecture, laws, and theories associated with our natural world (including human bio-evolutionary culture, systems thinking and decision-making), integrated into the cultural, structural, and process components of a new quality SES governance and implementation model (i.e., see McKay et al. 2017, 2020). The model and its diagnostic tool are valid and reliable.

The findings revealed a significant shift from hierarchical to quality governance and SES-focused thinking and governance capacities (McKay et al. 2017, 2020). Respondents were significantly more optimistic about the program's leadership, legitimacy, capacity-building ability, and governance one year later. This rapid transformation resulted in the rescission of over 400 prescriptive regulatory rules. Additionally, the program moved from a low of 150 completed risk-reduction actions in 2009 to an annual rate of 423 completed by the end of 2013.

Our research and practice analyzed the symptoms, diagnosed the disconnects within combined SES governance, and successfully treated the problematic behavior. However, this transition was insufficiently fortified to withstand a subsequent system shock. Our recent data collection reveals *how* and *why* this initiative fell short and how this intention-action gap can be remediated.

Conclusions

Our research and praxis integrate State stakeholders with governing and decision aiding structures and cultures for improved complex SES sustainability. Our study contributes to the SES framework and toolbox of knowledge associated with transformative quality SES governance research and practice. This form of transformative SES governance with higher levels of resource exchange and attributes such as trust, diplomacy, and reciprocity has universal application. This research and practice contribute to efforts to tackle our grand SES challenges.

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Attending to Ethical-Epistemic Decisions in Modeling and Data

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Summary

When researchers make decisions about what problems to prioritize, or how much evidence is enough to accept or reject a hypothesis, values are implicitly involved, and these decisions are ethical-epistemic in nature. In actionable research, these ethical-epistemic decisions present a source of risk. If producer and user choices are inconsistent with one another, the information being provided can be misleading or inaccurate, lead to mistakes in decision making, and possibly harms, such as maladaptation and misallocation of resources. Alongside the aim to provide actionable information, we have a responsibility to identify, communicate, and manage these ethical-epistemic decisions made during research.

Introduction

Values are an inevitable part of decision making throughout the scientific research process. Roughly understood, values are those attitudes influencing our reasons for judging something as important, good, or right. When researchers make choices about problems to pursue, evidence thresholds for accepting or rejecting a hypothesis, or metrics by which to determine a model's skill, values are involved. These choices are epistemic in nature but involve ethics, and are characterized as ethical-epistemic decisions (Tuana 2017). More specifically, these are decisions that can be viewed both from the perspective of how they advance a scientific aim, but also from the perspective how they relate to values and ethical considerations (Helgenson et al. 2023). In actionable science, these ethical-epistemic choices can enhance the usability of the information, especially given it is the user's values reflected in the decision. Conversely, when reasons underpinning research decisions are inconsistent with a user's values and interests, it can introduce hazards, such as the inadequacy of the results for the user's purposes, and cause harm by providing misleading, inaccurate, or irrelevant information.

Given the presence of values in scientific decisions, there have been increased calls to prioritize awareness of values, as many of the assumptions about suitable risk tradeoffs and interest can introduce biases in whose interest's information best serves, and results in information that is inadequate for certain purposes, or inconsistent with user aims and priorities (Pulkkinen et al. 2022). The development of awareness of values starts from an awareness of choices in scientific inquiry, and how these choices are coupled ethical-epistemic decisions. If scientists do not develop the capacity to identify and reflect on how their choices are informed by values then they cannot determine if their value judgments are suitable in relation to user values and interest, and they cannot manage those values in relation to the impacts they might have in terms of harmful consequences to those working with the information in actionable contexts.

Despite the recognition that values play a role in science, and require awareness, communication, transparency and management, there have been few studies that systematically identify key ethical-epistemic decisions that have impact the adequacy and usability of scientific research. This presentation lays out a beginning framework for guiding researchers on how they can bring awareness, enhance transparency, and manage these ethical-epistemic decisions in actionable science contexts, especially those that involve the use of models for informing adaptation and resilience decisions, where upstream decisions about what to represent in a model and how to represent it are ethical-epistemic decisions and carry considerable risk and hazards of inadequacy in model products.

This research more specifically serves two purposes in understandings of good modeling practice: 1) it directly improves the ability to achieve adequacy and fitness, of our scientific modeling for adaptation and resilience decision-making by bringing explicit attention to sources of ethical-epistemic decisions, and 2) it provides us with intentional ways to managed nuanced and implicit sources of risk in scientific results informing decision making. Ultimately, the proposed framework will improve our ability to provide the best information possible for use in

specific decision-making contexts, by intentionally achieving reliability of information and results in terms of responsiveness to user values and preferences.

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Integrated Modelling of Coupled Physical, Ecological and Social Systems: Describing Linkages to/from Ecological Components

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Summary

Interdisciplinary models are used increasingly to address today's most pressing environmental and societal problems. The challenges of integrating methodologies, epistemologies, and ontologies from different disciplines are well recognized and excellent reviews exploring these problems within the context of the integrated modelling of socio-ecological/socio-environmental systems (SES) are available. However, these reviews seldom focus on details describing linkages of physical and social model components with ecological components. We propose a general framework that facilitates the description of linkages to and from ecological components of integrated models, thus emphasizing feedback relationships, and use the framework to describe several existing models.

Introduction

It is widely acknowledged that addressing today's most pressing environmental and societal challenges requires the use of quantitative interdisciplinary models. Such integrated models are created by interdisciplinary teams working at the interfaces of the physical, ecological/biological, and social sciences and drawing heavily on the field of computer science and the expertise of non-scientist stakeholders. Thus, the development, evaluation, and use of integrated models to assess potential impacts such as changes in climate and policy on the resilience and sustainability of socio-ecological/socio-environmental systems (SES) require elicitation and integration of knowledge from physical, ecological/biological, social, and computer scientists, as well as system stakeholders. The challenge of integrating methodologies, epistemologies, and ontologies from different disciplines, all of which are permanently susceptible to being questioned (Dyke, 1988), is well recognized. Existing reviews of these challenges within the context of SES modelling, although excellent, tend to emphasize either technical computational aspects of integrating sophisticated models based primarily in the physical sciences, or conceptual aspects of integrating human decision-making models based primarily in the social sciences. Details describing linkages of physical and social model components with ecological model components are less often emphasized. In this paper we focus on identifying and describing linkages to and from the ecological components of integrated models within a general SES framework and then apply the framework to describe several existing models.

Methodology and Results

We first review terminology commonly used in descriptions of integrated models and define the terms we will use. We then characterize different types of linkages to and from ecological components of integrated models. Next, we consider the types of information and methodologies upon which physical, ecological, and social model components are based. We then suggest a general framework for describing linkages to and from ecological components of integrated models. Finally, we use the framework to describe several case studies.

We describe integrated models in terms of the number and direction (one way or with feedback) of linkages among physical, ecological, and social components. We also note if model components were developed from scratch (sensu the “integral models” of Voinov and Shugart, 2013) or if model components already existed as “legacy models” and then were integrated. Linkages with ecological components of integrated models appear to be primarily one way, most commonly from physical to ecological components or from social to ecological components. Feedback from ecological components seems less common. Physical components tend to be based on general laws of physics and chemistry, ecological components tend to be based on scale-dependent empirical relationships, and social components tend to be based on presumed management activities and/or policy decisions. We propose a general framework for describing both direct and indirect linkages to and from ecological components of integrated models, which emphasizes the feedback among components.

Conclusions

The predominance of one way linkages among components of integrated models in general, and to and from ecological components in particular, is understandable in that many integrated models focus on the potential impacts of changes in climate or policy on the resilience and sustainability of SES, often related to the management of freshwater resources. In such models, physical components most frequently act as exogenous “drivers” and social components most frequently act as exogenous “controllers/modifiers” of ecological processes. However, assuming no feedback from ecological components limits a model’s ability to explore the adaptive nature of coupled human-natural systems.

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Hybrid and data-driven approaches to assessing and attaining planetary health and environmental sustainability

NLP-Based Investigation of Interlinkage of Sustainable Development Goals in a Corpus of Documents

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Summary

The study was focused on investigation of NLP techniques for identifying document relevance to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This step is required for automation of the analysis of textual documents for monitoring attainment of SDGs on regional and local levels. The approach is based on abstractive text summarization and semantic similarity analysis, resulting in numeric scores which can be used for uncovering insights on relevance of a document to an SDG.

Introduction

UN 2030 Agenda articulated via 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outlines directions of societal transition towards a better future. To fulfil this agenda, however, monitoring and assessing the progress are necessary to direct the efforts and resources towards the articulated goals and do this in a sustainable way. The assessment of sustainability of undertakings or policies is done based on reporting of attainment of qualitative and quantitative targets of SDGs measured and observed at national and global levels. Several international initiatives, introduced lately, mandate to include such information in corporate reports. Growing number of textual data must be processed and comprehended to evaluate the current state of attainment of SDGs to make future decisions. This pressing need can be addressed by automated processing of textual documents and unstructured data utilizing advancements of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques. One of the steps in such analysis is to determine SDGs that are relevant to a document and the extent of such relevance.

The current study aims at investigation of interrelatedness and co-occurrence of SDGs presented in textual documents. It is based in the framework for automated identification of relevance of a document written in human language to the 17 SDGs based on NLP and semantic similarity scores reflecting the extent of such relevance (Erechtkoukova & Safwat, 2023).

Methodology and Results

The framework supports comparison of a document, e.g., a corporate report, with a target text describing an SDG. The comparison must be comprehensive. Therefore, semantic similarity scores, that takes into account not only words match, but the context as well must be calculated and analysed replacing popular approach of keyword counts. The result of such comparison will be expressed in a number. This opens an opportunity to further expand automation and process the obtained semantic similarity scores.

Both analysed textual documents and narrative description of SDGs are lengthy making the direct calculation of similarity scores inefficient and inaccurate due to noise introduces by repeating or irrelevant sentences. In addition, processing lengthy documents consumes significant computational resources and time. To overcome these issues, the full texts of documents are replaced by their automatically generated summaries. Natural language generation requires selection of a language model. The study was conducted using BART language model (Lewis et al., 2019). This pre-trained model available on HuggingFace platform was fine-tuned on the constructed corpus of documents representing area of sustainability. The fine-tuned version of the selected model was used to summarize documents following abstractive approach. The generated summaries were compared against brief descriptions of all 17 SDGs using the semantic similarity metric available in FastText library (Bojanowski et al., 2016). This metric enriches Word2Vec embedding with morphological word representations. The obtained numerical similarity scores were analysed further to determine relevance of the documents to each SDG and co-occurrence of SDGs in the documents. The analysis revealed that SDG 17

“Revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development” is the most popular (most represented) Goal in the investigated corpus. SDG 5 “Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls” appeared to be the least represented in this corpus. Co-occurrence of SDGs in the corpus documents was investigated using regression analysis of the semantic similarity scores. The aggregated results of the analysis are presented in

Table 1. Interlinkage of Sustainable Development Goals

Target goal	SDGs that are relevant to the same document as the target SDG					
Goal1	G3	G8	G10	G16		
Goal2	G8	G15	G6	G4	G5	
Goal3	G4	G1	G11			
Goal4	G3	G9	G16	G5	G2	G7
Goal5	G4	G16	G10	G2		
Goal6	G7	G15	G2	G3	G4	G1
Goal7	G6	G11	G12	G14	G9	
Goal8	G11	G17	G2			
Goal9	G17	G4				
Goal10	G1	G5	G12	G13	G16	G9
Goal11	G16	G7	G8	G3	G9	
Goal12	G7	G9	G10	G8	G15	
Goal13	G15	G17	G10	G4	G13	
Goal14	G15	G7				
Goal15	G14	G13	G6	G16	G9	G2
Goal16	G11	G15	G4	G5	G8	G1
Goal17	G9	G8	G13	G3		

Table 1. The SDGs are numbered according to UN 2030 Agenda document. Multifaceted nature of sustainability dictates the coherence of SDGs. There is no document focusing on a single SDG in the corpus. At the same time, number of SDGs topics reflected in the documents varies. Thus, aspect of SDG4 appear in the documents together with goals 3, 9, 16, 5, 2, and 7, while SDG9 issues are described together with only goals 17, and 4. Co-occurrence of the goals in a single document suggest that they have stronger interlinkage compared to other goals. Qualitative analysis of the uncovered interlinkage confirmed that they are reasonable. At the same time the results depend on the selected data model and its specific word embedding, dataset used for fine-tuning the language model which does not support the comprehensive analysis of each individual document.

Conclusions

The results demonstrated usefulness of NLP techniques for automated analysis of large corpora of textual documents to identify relevant SDGs for further analysis. The obtained similarity scores reveal not only corresponding SDGs, but also the extent of the relevance. Understanding of the impact of selection of word embedding and similarity metrics is the subject of further investigation.

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ML Methods in the Study of Mitigating Effect of Forest Ecosystems on SO₂ Atmospheric Pollution

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Summary

In this study, the case of SO₂ emission from the Athabasca Oil Sands Region (AOSR) in Alberta, Canada is considered. Surrounding forests can mitigate negative environmental effects acting as a sink for SO₂ pollution. Multiple machine learning algorithms are employed to predict the SO₂ concentrations under the forest canopy in comparison to the corresponding values above the canopy to assess the ability to maintain environmental health and air quality. The results can be useful for informing the policy- and decision-makers in the affected regions.

Introduction

The extraction of oil sands significantly affects environment having the release of sulphur dioxide (SO₂) as one of its negative consequences due to the potential acidification threat. It is, therefore, essential to predict SO₂ deposition rates accurately to evaluate the effects on environmental health and air quality. Forest ecosystems can act as a sink for SO₂ pollution through various processes like dry deposition, whereby gases are absorbed by vegetation part, litter, soil, water bodies, and other surfaces. In this study, we consider emissions of SO₂ from the Athabasca Oil Sands Region (AOSR) in Alberta, Canada, and the role of the nearby boreal forests. According to Aherne and Shaw (2010), the AOSR contributes to both wet and dry depositions of SO₂ in the adjacent areas which may lead to acidification of soils and surface waters (Cathcart et al., 2016; Whitfield et al., 2010), in extreme cases, resulting in surpassing the critical acidity loads (Makar et al., 2017). We apply machine learning algorithms to predict the SO₂ mixing ratio (ppb) under the forest in comparison to its values above the canopy as a measure of the forest ecosystem's ability to mitigate air pollution.

Methodology and Results

The datasets used in the study have been collected by the research team of Gordon et al. (2023) in a jack pine (*Pinus banksiana*) forest surrounding the AOSR in which a tower with a 43i Thermo Scientific analyzer has been installed. The average canopy height is approximately 19m. SO₂ (ppb) measurements above the canopy have been sampled with a sonde system mounted on a balloon.

Figure 1. Altitude changes of the balloon in the experiment

Altitude changes of the balloon in the experiment are shown in Figure 1. We apply several ML algorithms (e.g., Regression, Gradient Boosting and Random Forest) to predict SO₂ (ppb) under the forest (target variable) from the values of SO₂ (ppb) above the canopy (predictor variable) and compare the model-predicted values with the instrumental measurements.

Results: The percentage change in the SO₂ concentrations at the sonde and ground levels is presented in Figure 2 (a) and (b), respectively. Figure 3 (a) and (b) demonstrates actual vs. predicted SO₂ ground concentrations in the forest obtained by the Gradient Boosting and Random Forest models, respectively. However, the best performance is achieved by the Gradient Boosting algorithm with *R*² value of 0.9437 and MSE value of 0.5495.

Figure 2. Percentage change in the SO₂ concentrations at the: (a, left) ground level; (b, right) sonde level

Figure 3. Actual vs. predicted SO₂ ground concentrations in the forest obtained by: (a, left) Gradient Boosting model; (b, right) Random Forest model

Conclusions

This study provides insight into the fate of SO₂ pollution above and under the boreal forest. The scatter plots in Figure 2 (a) and (b) present a snapshot of how SO₂ concentrations change over time in the forest environment. ML experiments demonstrate predictability of under-the-canopy concentrations as a proxy measure characterizing the sink capacity of the ecosystem. These results are essential for understanding the impact of this type of pollutant on the environment and the efficacy of programs to mitigate it. This capability is pivotal for improving environmental monitoring and informing policy- and decision-makers in the affected regions. It is however evident that inherent complexity of SO₂ modelling, and prediction is best captured by a hybrid approach combining data-driven and process-based models capable of learning non-linear relationships and interactions of various contributing factors which can advance the state-of-the-art of environmental modelling in the domain of atmospheric chemistry.

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Model-Based Assessment of Environmental Footprints As Indicators of a National Bio-Economy Monitoring in Germany

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Summary

The transition from a fossil-based to a bio-based economy is a promising contribution to a more sustainable development of societies. Management and controlling of the transition process requires appropriate monitoring and assessment tools. In this context, we have conceptualized and implemented a software framework that combines economic, water, land use and vegetation models to provide critical input data necessary for the calculation of land- and water-related environmental footprints that serve as important indicators for the German bio-economy monitoring. Our paper describes the structure and functioning of the framework and presents selected simulation results.

Introduction

The transition from a fossil-based to a bio-based economy is a promising way towards more a sustainable development of societies. Numerous national and supra-national policy strategies describe visions of such a bio-economy. Central aspects of these strategies are often oriented on the achievement of the UN Sustainability Goals (SDGs) and address topics such as food security, closed material and nutrient cycles, high value products and energy from renewable raw materials while preserving natural resources and decreasing the emission of greenhouse gases. Management and controlling of these transition processes require appropriate monitoring and assessment tools. An important aspect that needs to be considered is that in a globalized economy, biomass is not produced exclusively in the countries where it is consumed, but is often imported from other world regions, either as raw materials or embedded in intermediate and final products. Accordingly, the environmental effects associated with production or processing occur at different locations on the globe, linked by trade and the corresponding material flows. In this context, footprint indicators are an established approach to relate biomass consumption in one country to the environmental impacts in exporting regions.

In this paper, we describe the structure and functioning of a software framework that combines different spatially explicit models to provide and integrate the information necessary for the calculation of land and water related environmental footprints. In order to explore options and to identify risks, it also supports elements of sensitivity and uncertainty analyses to systematically assessing how changing environmental (e.g. climate) and societal factors (e.g. water use) may affect these footprints. In addition, we present exemplary simulation results generated for a pilot monitoring study of the German bio-economy (Bringezu et al., 2021) and discuss further application potentials of the framework.

Methodology and Results

The software framework builds on a set of spatially explicit models and databases. Model communication and data exchange follow a soft-coupling approach where each model remains a separate software entity that exchanges data via structured ASCII-files. At the core of the framework is the global land-system model LandSHIFT (Schaldach et al., 2011) coupled with a material flow model that provides information on direct and indirect biomass flows between producer countries/regions (sources) and different sectors of the German bio-economy (consumers). In addition, the framework includes a variety of other spatial models to calculate environmental impacts from biomass production in agriculture and forestry on land, water, soil carbon sequestration and biodiversity.

The models operate on a database that provides harmonized initial conditions for all models and facilitate data exchange during the simulation experiments. For example, the models use the same aggregation of crop classes

(wheat, coarse grains, oilseeds, sugar crops etc.) and a common hierarchy of geographical scale levels. Land use and environmental impacts are assessed on a global raster with the cell size of 5-arcminutes. Each raster cell is part to one of 140000 water basins and a specific country. Each country in turn is part of to a world region. Last-but-not-least, the framework includes software components to determine the environmental footprints by combining environmental impacts with biomass flow data. Footprint calculations are workflows that determine the respective input data, the order of model execution and the necessary steps to perform impact analyses. Currently our framework includes workflows to calculate the water footprint, agricultural land footprint, timber footprint, climate footprint and biodiversity footprint.

The first application of the framework was in a pilot monitoring study for the German bio-economy. Results include time series of the above-mentioned footprints, documented in Bringezu et al. (2021), Hennenberg et al. (2022) and Egenolf et al. (2023). Communication of these results to policy makers and a wider public audience took place in form of traditional reports and by using a newly designed web-based tool that allows the interactive exploration of the generated footprint data. Using the water footprint as an example, we could also demonstrate that climate change and socio-economic developments affect this footprint in different producer countries.

Conclusions

We have developed a software framework that offers a consistent and transparent model-based approach for calculating a variety of environmental footprints. The application of spatially explicit models allows to accounting for spatial variability in societal and environmental factors and drivers. Further, we have the opportunity to go beyond historic analysis and to systematically assess effects of global change on footprints as well as to explore scenarios of future global developments, e.g. by using biomass flow data from global economic models. In particular, this sort of analysis might be a valuable contribution to evaluate and adapt bio-economy strategies. The design of the framework offers the flexibility to add additional data and methods for footprint calculations. An example could be the inclusion on information on soil degradation risk related to the agricultural land footprint. A first use case was the bio-economy monitoring for Germany but the framework can be relatively easily adapted to other countries or supra-national entities such as the European Union.

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Remote Sensing and Machine Learning in Vegetation Phenology and Climate Change Studies

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Summary

Understanding the vegetation phenology offers significant benefits for agricultural management and biodiversity conservation. It also facilitates valuable insights into the impacts of climate change on ecosystems. Researchers can analyze long-term phenological records to assess shifts in plant lifecycle events which may indicate climate-driven alterations. Furthermore, the integration of remote sensing techniques and geographic information systems (GIS) enhances the ability to monitor and analyze phenological patterns at larger scales, supporting global environmental monitoring and decision-making processes. However, extracting meaningful insights from the massive volumes of satellite data possesses significant challenges and requires the use of strong computational algorithms, such as machine learning (ML) methods. In this research, we are proposing a framework to study crop phenological stages using data obtained from remotely sensed devices (RSD). We investigate the shifts in phenological phases and in their correlation with meteorological variables. Finally, we use different ML models to forecast future trends in phenological phases.

Introduction

Satellite imagery with its vast coverage and high spatial resolution, has become an invaluable source of information for numerous applications in which GIS is an instrumental tool providing rich analytical capabilities. However, extracting meaningful insights from the massive volumes of satellite data presents significant challenges (Asokan et al., 2019). The integration of AI and ML algorithms with satellite imagery has emerged as a powerful solution, enabling automated analysis, pattern recognition, and predictive modeling.

One of the applications of satellite imagery combined with ML is for the investigation of vegetation phenology. Vegetation phenology refers to the study of recurring biological events and patterns in the lifecycles of plants, specifically related to their growth, development, and seasonal changes (Zeng et al., 2020). It focuses on the timing and duration of various stages in plant life described in terms of phenological parameters such as budburst, leaf emergence, flowering, fruiting, and senescence. Numerous ecological processes, as well as several biosphere-atmosphere feedback loops, are regulated by vegetation phenology. A study conducted on phenological control of vegetation feedback to the climate system (Richardson et al., 2013) reports vegetation phenology to be a particularly sensitive indicator of the biological effects of climate change on terrestrial ecosystems. Phenological studies offer a significant benefit through the facilitation of long-term and extensive natural experiments that are easily synchronized with massive amounts of climatic data (Menzel et al., 2006; Adole et al., 2016). They also facilitate valuable insights into the impact of climate change on ecosystems.

Researchers can analyze long-term phenological records to assess shifts in plant lifecycle events, such as earlier flowering or leaf emergence, which may indicate climate-driven alterations. For example, studies have demonstrated a significant advancement in spring phenological events, such as budburst and flowering, as a response to climate warming (Menzel et al., 2006; Parmesan, 2007). Information of this kind is helpful in assessing the vulnerability of plant species and entire ecosystems to changing climatic conditions. Furthermore, the integration of remote sensing techniques enhances the ability to monitor and analyze phenological patterns at large scales, supporting global environmental monitoring and decision-making processes (Hmimina et al., 2013). This information assists in land cover mapping, biodiversity assessments, and ecosystem modeling.

ML techniques offer a data-driven approach to vegetation phenology studies enabling researchers to derive valuable insights from the large and complex datasets, thus promoting a better understanding of the phenological dynamics of vegetation. The present research explores how ML and remote sensing can be used to study phenological dynamics. The objective of the research is to develop a methodology for working with satellite data and applying it for mapping the vegetation phenology. Subsequently, we investigate the influence of climate change by assessing variability of meteorological parameters and patterns in vegetation phenology.

Methodology and Results

The study of vegetation phenology is quantitative and exploratory in nature. It is based on the MODIS vegetation index products, such as NDVI (Normalized different vegetation index) and EVI (Enhanced Vegetation Index) obtained by NASA's Earth Observing Systems being used to analyze vegetation phenology of corn crops across the region of Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada. The data repositories include the Earth Data portal (NASA, 2022) and Google Earth Developer Engine Data Catalog (Google, 2022). The MOD09GQ Version 6.1 product provides an estimate of the surface spectral reflectance of Terra Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) 250 meter bands 1 and 2, corrected for atmospheric conditions including gasses, aerosols, and Rayleigh scattering. Canada AAFC Annual Crop Inventory of crop production is used to obtain the areas under corn crop for retrieving surface reflectance by those areas. The historical meteorological data is retrieved from Government of Canada climate historical dataset. The vegetation indices are smoothed using time series smoothing techniques like Savitzky-Golay by applying filtering and Fourier transformation. The smoothed time series is used to map crop growth stages based on growing degree days. The phenological mappings are further analysed to assess the shifts in growth stages across contiguous years and their correlation with meteorological features. Finally, ML algorithms are employed to predict the growth stages and analyze the future trends in corn crop phenology. The detailed results of this research will be demonstrated in the conference presentation.

Conclusions

Accurate monitoring and prediction of vegetation phenology provides critical information for climate change assessment, ecosystem health evaluation, biodiversity conservation, agricultural management, and carbon cycle assessments. It is an important domain of remote sensing applications. The studies of this kind enhance our understanding of ecological processes and support sustainable management practices in a rapidly changing world.

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**Stream F. Socio-environmental
systems modelling for planetary
health and environmental
sustainability**

F1. Intelligent water resources science and engineering

M4W SwaNET: A Cloud-Powered, Data-Enabled Global Watershed Modelling Platform

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Summary

We present a cloud-based, Big Data-enabled, real time interactive platform for watershed modeling, visualization, and analysis called M4W SwaNET (MAGNET4WATER Soil and Water Assessment NETWORK). By integrating the most widely used watershed water quality modeling tool, Soil Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) into a map-based, data-enabled, online GIS environment, an integrated watershed modeling platform has been developed. Physiographic and climatological data required for SWAT model building and model refinement have been seamlessly integrated into the platform making it a truly data-enabled modeling tool. Loaded with powerful processing and visualization tools, the platform offers a unique post-processing and visualization experience with 1D, 2D and 3D visualization of model inputs and outputs. Finally, we present how the platform can be used to build, refine, simulate, and visualize models at multiple scales.

Introduction

In recent years, access to enormous collections of environmental data and new modeling capabilities has enabled a diverse set of scientists to make significant improvements in our understanding of water quantity and quality dynamics within watersheds. However, translating Big Data and advancements in modeling and scientific understanding into concrete or localized management actions that improve watershed health continues to be a challenge. Hydrological modeling tools, such as Soil Water Assessment Tool (SWAT), are great resources for studying environmental fate and transport at the watershed scale. Modeling enables users to understand current conditions, predict future conditions and test hypothetical scenarios. Often the models require a number of physiographic and climatological datasets, which are, in some cases, difficult or time-consuming to acquire, process, and format into inputs for SWAT (or any other watershed simulator). In addition, parameter optimization is often done outside the modeling platform, which again requires a significant amount of time and resources. Finally, these models often do not have visualization capabilities and users need to spend considerable time and effort to create publication-ready outputs. Thus, there is a need for a simple yet powerful watershed modeling platform that is data-enabled, user friendly, and integrates model building, refinement, analysis and visualization in a single platform.

Methodology and Results

To overcome the present challenges in watershed modeling, a web-based data-enabled SWAT-based watershed modeling platform, called M4W SwaNET, has been developed. This platform consists of a global-scale data storage/retrieval system, python-based executables for backend processing, a Google/Bing map based platform for model/result visualization, and interactive model building/editing/calibration platform for model refinement and calibration.

Global raster/vector data storage system offers best available physiographic and climatological data required for model building and refinement. The system is loaded with ever expanding multi-scale watershed maps, stream networks, Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), soil maps, and land use maps for instantaneous model building. At the global scale, the platform contains Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) weather data, while additional National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) observed weather data is available for the US. Moreover, the platform is live-linked to USGS streamflow gauging stations for seamless access to the observed streamflow data. For estimating water quality parameters, Load Estimator (LOADEST) tool developed by the United States Geological Survey has also been integrated into the platform. Apart from the

built-in databases, the platform is also live linked to the global Web Feature Service (WFS) and Web Coverage Service (WCS) datasets providing endless data importing options. A python-based backend processing system integrates SWAT model building, simulation and data analysis tools. Watershed delineation is done using Terrain Analysis Using Digital Elevation Models (TauDEM). HRU creation processing code is based on QSWAT HRU processing codes. The processing system is capable of running SWAT model, reading inputs/outputs and creating publication ready images, charts, and much more.

M4W SwaNET platform also offers a seamless watershed model editing/optimization tools. A genetic algorithm-based auto-calibration tool allows users to perform multi-station and multi-parameter calibration with just a few clicks. A user-friendly interface system allows users to update model parameters based on local knowledge. M4W SwaNET platform contains powerful visualization tools that consist of 1D, 2D and 3D visualization. Users can create on-demand charts/plots at hydrologic response unit (HRU), subbasin and watershed levels. A Google/Bing map based visualization tool allows users to view the model and the results in 2D, while a powerful 3D visualization tool allows users to view the model input/outputs in 3D interactively. Additionally, a vast number of inputs/outputs can be mapped as time series charts, pie charts, bar charts etc. Various levels of water balances can be plotted that include overland flow, shallow aquifer, deep aquifer, reservoirs and streams. A flood mapping tool allows users to create flood hazard index maps and flood maps at selected return periods. Apart from visualization, SWAT model outputs can be directly used in groundwater modeling tools available on the same platform.

Unlike traditional platforms, M4W SwaNET is built directly on an international network of data services - a dynamically linked, high-resolution global database of diverse spatial data - allowing users to zoom anywhere to quickly build and visualize a watershed model that can be expanded/modified based on additional data collection and management goals. We demonstrate how M4W SwaNET's real time watershed modeling and visualization capabilities facilitates rapid watershed system characterization and analysis across scales and iterative, real time testing of diverse management and/or climate scenarios. Specifically, we developed a multi-scale system watershed models in the Great Lakes region of North America, spanning from the entire Great Lakes basin, to the Kalamazoo watershed in southwest Michigan, to sub-watersheds within the Kalamazoo watershed.

Conclusions

For the first time, we bring the SWAT modeling tool to the web by integrating Big Data, data processing tools, model calibration tools, and visualization tools into a single platform. M4W SwaNET's data-enabled, realtime modeling capabilities allows users to focus on what is most important: modeling, approximation, and conceptualization; analysis, data worth, and uncertainties; and problem-solving and management. The platform is expected to revolutionize the watershed modeling process by enabling users to focus on pertinent research questions rather than spending considerable time in model building, refinement and post-processing.

AI Framework to Model Chlorophyll Concentration Using Sentinel 2 Data in Inland Waters Across CONUS

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Summary

Water is a primary source of life, and the threat to water bodies worldwide highlights the need for their preservation. Chlorophyll concentrations are a critical evaluation indicator used for water monitoring. Recent technological advancements in remote sensing provide us with an accurate and economical way to investigate aquatic ecosystems. This study combines high-spatiotemporal Sentinel 2 data alongside in-situ chlorophyll concentrations and develops an advanced deep-learning system to retrieve chlorophyll concentration across the CONUS. Compared with previous research, this study is the first to retrieve the chlorophyll concentrations across CONUS.

Introduction

The increase in global temperature, climate change, and population growth brought critical challenges to water bodies, such as eutrophication, cyanobacteria harmful algal blooms (cHABs), and water quality deterioration. These challenges received significant attention from the research community and industry. The United Nations recently has included water bodies' management in their long-term sustainability development goals (Hakimdavar et al., 2020). Chlorophyll is a photosynthetic pigment present in algae, representing a key indicator of nutrient status and the overall health of water bodies. However, high chlorophyll concentrations represent the excess of algae, some species of which make up HABs. These HABs can drastically alter water quality, causing discoloration, unpleasant odors, and tastes, and can produce neurotoxins known as brevetoxins, adversely affecting human health.

Several studies (Kislik et al., 2022, Asim M et al., 2022, Shi X et al., 2022) have monitored and modeled chlorophyll concentration using remote sensing. However, three primary drawbacks exist: 1) Solely relying on in-situ measurements, which lack spatial distribution and represent only a limited area; 2) Using empirical or semi-analytical approaches for investigation only, which lacks the predictive capability; and 3) Limiting the study to a specific geographical location, which we believe is the most common issue. A modeling framework generalizable to other geographical locations would significantly contribute to water monitoring goals.

This study designs a novel advanced deep learning model to model the chlorophyll concentration using in-situ chlorophyll as targets and Sentinel 2 individual reflective indices alongside pre-defined chlorophyll estimation bands ratios as inputs. Various data extraction, augmentation, cleaning and filtering mechanisms are explored, and their impact on the system performance is studied.

Methodology and Results

The United States Geological Survey National Harmonized chlorophyll concentration data is downloaded and filtered to remove the cloudy data and values not aligned with Sentinel 2 observations. The time window of ± 2 days is used to find the alignment between Sentinel 2 and in-situ chlorophyll concentration values. Next, Sentinel 20m resolution data is interpolated to 10m resolution, and individual data values from all 10m resolution bands are extracted using a spatial window of 5 by 5 to increase the number of samples. All the valid

pixel values within the spatial window are considered, and the invalid values are replaced with means of the spatial window and used for modeling. If all the pixels are defective, the in-situ observation is discarded. The measurements are further analyzed to identify the unrealistic and outlier values using a spectral ratio of green and blue bands since a direct relationship between chlorophyll and the ratio of green and blue bands was observed previously (Asim M et al., 2022). Following (Asim M et al., 2022), a depth integration matchup is used to enhance the model's predictive performance. Next, the missing data is handled two ways: 1) modeling the missing data during the experimentation, or 2) Replacing with the mean from the same months across different year.

A deep neural network comprising multiple fully neural net-blocks estimates the chlorophyll concentration values. Each neural net-block comprises a fully connected layer, followed by layer normalization, leaky ReLU, and dropout layer, where the last block excludes the dropout layer. The input to the model consists of 11 individual reflective indices alongside four band ratios plus the depth at which the chlorophyll concentration values are extracted. The missing data is modelled by using masking information to identify the missing data and allowing the model to be filled out during training. The mean square error is used for loss calculation, and the network is optimized using AdamW optimizer. Various additional experiments are performed to evaluate the generalizability of the model to different US ecoregions. These experiments validate the potential usage of the proposed model across CONUS.

Conclusions

This research aims to provide a generalizable framework for chlorophyll estimation in inland waters using mainly Sentinel 2 data across CONUS. The complex and dynamic geo-graphic US locations allow the development of a single model that can be deployed outside the US with little or no fine-tuning. The obtained cross-section experimental result further validates this hypothesis. The future direction is integrating additional remote sensing data features, including temperature and precipitation, to enhance the model's robustness.

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Machine Learning-Enhanced Soil Moisture Estimation in South Korea Using Sentinel-1 SAR and Diverse Physical Data

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Summary

This study employs machine learning (ML) to estimate soil moisture (SM) in South Korea using data from the Sentinel-1 C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR). We aim to improve the accuracy of SAR-based SM estimation by incorporating diverse physical characteristics alongside the existing relationship between backscattering coefficients (σ^0) and SM. These characteristics include topography, soil properties, and 5-day antecedent precipitation, which plays a crucial role in influencing the initial SM condition. We evaluated the performance of various ML techniques through a comprehensive analysis.

Introduction

Leveraging its all-weather imaging capability, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) offers a distinct advantage over optical satellites for Earth observation. One key parameter extracted from SAR imagery is the backscattering coefficient (σ^0), which is sensitive to various surface properties, including soil moisture (SM). As SM content increases, the dielectric constant of the soil also rises, leading to a corresponding change in σ^0 . This established relationship between σ and SM has fueled ongoing research in utilizing SAR data for SM estimation, with a growing trend towards employing machine learning (ML) techniques.

To enhance the accuracy of SM estimation using Sentinel-1 C-band SAR data over South Korea, this study employed machine learning (ML) techniques. Beyond the established relationship between backscattering coefficient (σ^0) and SM, we incorporated diverse physical characteristics. Also, the performance of various ML models was then evaluated.

Methodology and Results

This study utilized Sentinel-1A Ground Range Detected (GRD) products in Interferometric Wide (IW) swath mode, acquired from 2014 to 2022 (8 years). Preprocessing was performed using the ESA (European Space Agency) tool, SNAP. Following preprocessing, co-polarized (σ_{VV}^0) and cross-polarized (σ_{VH}^0) backscattering coefficients, along with local incidence angle (LIA) images, were obtained at a 10-meter spatial resolution. LIA normalization (Mladenova et al., 2013) was applied to minimize the impact of LIA on σ^0 .

This study utilized two indices derived from Sentinel-1A polarimetric data to estimate SM. The relative soil moisture is estimated using the change detection model (Wagner et al., 1999), this index interprets variations in the σ^0 as changes in SM. The model generates dry and wet reference images based on long-term time series data and normalizes σ^0 to a range of 0-1, reflecting the relative moisture content of the soil. Polarimetric Radar Vegetation Index (PRVI) accounts for vegetation influence and is estimated using a theoretical volume scattering model and the degree of polarization along with σ_{VH}^0 (Chang et al., 2018).

This study employed various data sources to train the machine learning models: 1. SAR Data: Relative Soil Moisture (estimated from σ^0 using the change detection model), and PRVI. 2. Topographic Data: Altitude and slope information extracted from a Digital Elevation Model (DEM). 3. Soil Properties: Sand, silt, and clay content, Effective soil depth, Bulk density, and Saturated moisture content. 4. Hydrological Data: 5-day antecedent precipitation, 5. Seasonal Information: Nominal data representing seasonal classification. All data were spatially aligned by extracting point-level information from SM stations within the same area covered by the Sentinel-1 image. To account for seasonal variations in soil moisture and precipitation patterns specific to

South Korea, a seasonal classification was included as an input feature. The data was divided into a 7:3 ratio for training and testing the ML models, with cross-validation employed to prevent overfitting.

This study evaluated the performance of seven machine learning models (Multiple Linear Regression - MLR, Gaussian Process Regression - GPR, Random Forest Regression - RFR, Extreme Gradient Boosting - XGB, Light Gradient Boosting - LGB, Artificial Neural Network - ANN, Deep Neural Network - DNN) for SM estimation. Then, the models were assessed using three objective functions: Pearson’s correlation coefficient (CC), Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient (ρ), and Root mean square error (RMSE). Additionally, 82 Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) data points collected at a depth of 10 cm underground were used to validate the model’s accuracy.

Table 1 summarizes the performance of the evaluated machine learning models based on the objective functions (CC, ρ , and RMSE). Tree-based models (RFR, XGB, LGB) generally achieved the highest performance across all metrics. While XGB exhibited the best training performance (potentially indicating overfitting), RFR and LGB displayed comparable or even better performance during testing. ANN and DNN showed moderate performance, with DNN performing slightly better than ANN. GPR’s accuracy fell between the tree-based and neural network models.

Table 1. Comparative results of performance in soil moisture estimation of machine learning models

Model	*CC (train/test)	* ρ (train/test)	*RMSE(vol.%) (train/test)
MLR	0.544/0.437	0.570/0.513	7.346/8.867
GPR	0.941/0.789	0.928/0.755	2.991/6.142
RFR	0.981/0.814	0.979/0.803	2.208/6.021
XGB	1.000/0.806	1.000/0.816	0.035/6.071
LGB	0.989/0.812	0.988/0.823	1.380/5.818
ANN	0.586/0.438	0.633/0.585	7.237/9.044
DNN	0.810/0.678	0.814/0.697	5.333/7.591

*CC: Person’s correlation coefficient, ρ : Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient, RMSE: Root mean squared error

Conclusions

This study successfully estimated soil moisture (SM) in South Korea by leveraging Sentinel-1 C-band SAR data, alongside diverse auxiliary data and machine learning (ML) techniques. The implemented approach integrated the hydrological concept of 5-day antecedent precipitation with topographical and soil property data to enhance the estimation accuracy. The findings revealed a positive influence of incorporating auxiliary data on SM estimation. Notably, tree-based ML models demonstrated superior performance compared to their neural network counterparts. However, further exploration through specific hyperparameter selection and fine-tuning has the potential to optimize the performance of neural network-based models for SM estimation.

Acknowledgements

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Teamwork without talking: distributed system estimates maintain approximately centralized control of smart watersheds during communications outages

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Summary

Dynamic control of watersheds presents new opportunities to treat runoff while reducing flood risk. However, internet-connected controllers (e.g., pumps, valves) may become a liability during communications outages. Given that severe storms often cause both flooding and communications failures, it is critical that smart systems cope well with communications outages. We maintain approximately centralized control of a watershed under intermittent communication by hosting approximations of the total system’s dynamics and states on each networked controller. This allows individual controllers to act from an imperfect understanding of the total system, even when not communicating with the central server for days.

Introduction

Smart watersheds improve water treatment and prevent flooding using real-time monitoring and control (Kerkez, 2016). However, their reliance on communications networks presents a vulnerability as the same severe storms which cause flooding often also damage internet and cellular infrastructure. Because of this coupled vulnerability, it is crucial that smart watersheds continue to perform well during communications outages. Some have pursued this resiliency through distributed or cooperative control (Zhang, 2023). However, the optimal performance achievable under decentralized control is generally worse than that achievable under centralized control. In contrast to distributed control, we pursue resiliency to communications failures by *approximating centralized control* via locally stored and updated total system estimates.

Methodology and Results

A linear, time-invariant (LTI) dynamical system is identified to approximate the dynamics of a watershed model using the network’s connectivity and a month of response data (Dantzer, 2023). The system has 6 basins controlled by internet-connected valves at their outlets which are also equipped with water level sensors. The system is driven by four rain gauges. These are observed as real-time measurements and predictions out to 6 hours. The LTI system estimate uses a shift matrix to represent the rainfall predictions as current state values. This representation allows predictive control without performing optimization within the feedback loop. This design minimizes memory and compute expense, making system estimate storage on microcomputers possible.

Figure 1. Architecture diagram. Nodes (microcomputers with cellular modems, indicated by number) measure water levels, control valves, and communicate with a centralized server. When node 4 loses communication with the main server, a local instance of the total system estimate is updated using the local water level sensor measurement to approximate a centralized control decision.

Then, a linear-quadratic regulator (LQR) is defined for the entire system. LQR is a matrix-based, closed-loop feedback algorithm with minimal memory requirement and computational expense which make storage and computation on a networked microcontroller feasible. A Kalman filter is included in the feedback loop to update estimates of unobservable states using the available measurements. This fully centralized controller is then tuned to optimize performance on a cost function comprising flooding, valve flow thresholds, and sediment loading during summer 2020, where higher numbers indicate worse performance (ref Fig 2, right).

We evaluate controllers under varying likelihoods of data transmission success (conversely, packet loss) during summer 2021. The benchmark *Centralized* controller never experiences packet loss and fully observes and controls the entire system. The *high-fidelity* controller (ref Fig 1) uses distributed approximations of the total system dynamics and state to approximate centralized control when communication is lost with the server. For example, when node 4 loses connection with the server, it uses a locally-stored total system estimate (dx/dt) and local measurements from its depth sensor to infer the depths and flows for basins and valves 1, 6, 7, 8, and 10. This estimate informs how much flow will be released through valve 4.

Figure 2. Centralized control maintained under intermittent communication. (left) System trajectories are very similar even when reporting only every 5 days on average. Flows are in liters per minute while depths are in meters. (right) Performance does not degrade significantly until reporting frequency drops to weekly. Report frequency of 5 days indicated with black dotted line. Costs are shown for the entire summer.

The *Centralized* LQR control never floods and allows less than 250 grams of suspended solids to exit the network over the entire summer (March 1 to October 1). The *high fidelity* controller closely approximates the *Centralized* control even when nodes connect to the server as infrequently as every 5 days.

Conclusions

This software framework provides a practical solution increasing the resilience and performance of smart watersheds during communications outages by maintaining distributed system estimates. This work also contributes to theoretical developments in *networked model predictive control*.

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Water Resources Science and Engineering in the Era of BIGDATA and Networks

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SUMMARY

In this paper, we present a cross-cutting initiative on intelligent water resources science and engineering. In particular, we present the first ever big data-enabled, cloud-powered, global water modelling platform - MAGNET 4 WATER (Multiscale, Adaptive, Global Network 4 Water). The platform allows, for the first time, real-time modelling, visualization, analysis, and intelligent reporting and publication. Users can zoom in anywhere in the world to quickly build a model, analysis, and visualization that can be further refined with the user's own data. MAGNET 4 WATER consists of multiple modelling platforms, including: 1) AquaNET for groundwater modelling; 2) SwaNET for watershed modelling; 3) StormNET for stormwater, river system, and green infrastructure modelling; 4) PipeNET for water distribution system modelling; and 5) DataNET – a global digital twin data visualization and analysis platform. MAGNET 4 WATER is live linked to a massive, high resolution global water database containing information on climate, land, water, soil, aquifer, and geology.

MOTIVATION. Water sustainability is among the greatest challenges in the 21st century. Recent IT and data revolution offers unprecedented opportunities for potential breakthroughs in our ability to understand and manage complex systems, interactions, and sustainability. These possibilities, however, are largely unrealized, primarily because the technologies to produce big data are not matched by technologies to analyze them. We have reached a point in the evolution of science where many of the complex problems that exist can only be solved with a change in the technological infrastructure.

MAGNET 4 WATER INITIATIVE. In this paper, we present an integrated, cross-cutting research initiative on “big data” and data-enabled water science and engineering that has led to the development of the first ever global water modelling technology — MAGNET 4 WATER (Multiscale, Adaptive, Global Network 4 Water). The technology has the potential to shift the water research, education, and management paradigm, substantially reduce the costs of water system investigations, and transform how water is managed, how knowledge is created, and even how people learn and collaborate.

MAGNET 4 WATER is built on the achievements at the interface of water science and engineering, data science, IT and computer science and engineering. The platform integrates fundamental and technological advances in hydrologic and hydraulic modelling, remote sensing and geographical information systems, networking and communication, data intensive and distributed computing, and an international network of data services, including high resolution data services provided by the US Geological Survey, NASA, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, US Department of Agriculture, US Environmental Protection Agency, Federal Emergency Management Agency, US Army Corps of Engineers, US Fish & Wildlife Service, Environment Canada, British Geological Survey, German Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources, French Geological Survey, Geoscience Australia, and United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization.

REALTIME, DATA-ENABLED MODELING. The platform allows, for the first time, realtime and participatory modeling, visualization, analysis, reporting, and publication. Users can zoom in anywhere in the world to build almost instantly a model, analysis, and visualization that can be further refined with the user's own data.

The platform further allows users to publish instantly data and model results to the world to showcase their capabilities and achievements - in high impact 3D visualization, animation, and intelligent report. The instant publication provides an effective mechanism of spontaneous, mass collaboration in developing cyber-enabled environmental observatory network from the bottom-up by the global community.

BENEFITS AND IMPACT. MAGNET 4 WATER represents a new way of doing business, benefiting the global environmental and water resources community — students, researchers, professors, consultants, citizens, planners, managers, regulators, and decision makers.

The ability to quickly model and visualize the surface and subsurface environment, groundwater flow, surface water flow, and pressurized flow, and contaminant transport / water quality and geology — in a real-life setting — sparks pivotal insights into the complex interrelationships among components of the environment and human activities, and provides an intuitive grasp of implications of management actions and policy decisions that can't be readily obtained otherwise.

ILLUSTRATIONS. Figure 1 illustrates the MAGNET 4 WATER modelling capabilities and details of the MAGNET 4 WATER initiative are available at <https://www.magnet4water.net>.

AquaNET - Groundwater Modeling

SwaNET – Watershed Modeling

StormNET – Stormwater and River System Modeling

PipeNET - Pipe Network Modeling

DataNET - Data Visualization System

MAGNET 4 WATER – StormNET

A Global Digital Twin Modelling Technology for Integrated Urban Water System

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Leveraging the ongoing global digital transformation, especially the global spatial data revolution, we introduce MAGNET StormNET, a *next-generation global digital twin modelling technology for integrated urban water systems*, including: stormwater and sanitary drainage, and combined sewer overflow systems; water distribution and stormwater harvesting systems; river systems modelling and flood inundation mapping; green infrastructure and low impact design.

The platform is unique in that it is *data-enabled*. The platform allows real-time modelling, visualization, analysis, reporting, and publication. Users can zoom in anywhere in the world to quickly build using big data a model, analysis, and visualization that can be further refined with user's own data. The platform also allows users to publish instantly data and model results to the world, or cyber-enabled environmental observatories to showcase their capabilities and achievements - in high impact 3D visualizations, animations, and intelligent reports.

The StormNET platform makes use of the EPA's Storm Water Management Model (SWMM) – a program widely used by the international water resources community. The underlying SWMM modelling engine solves the full Saint Venant equation for unsteady flow using the dynamic wave routing method, allow modelling diverse flow scenarios or regimes, including pressurized or unpressurized flow, backwater, surcharging, and reverse flow, as well as surface ponding, street flooding, and flood inundation, in branched and/or looped networks in response to event-based, individual storm events or long-term continuous stresses and boundary conditions.

Figure 1. Introducing MAGNET 4 WATER *StormNET* - a Next-Generation Digital Twin Modelling Technology for Urban Water Systems. Additional information is available at <https://www.magnet4water.net>.

The platform provides real-time tools for data driven decision making, process-based modelling, and for planning, analysis, and design related to stormwater runoff, coupled stormwater/sanitary systems and combined sewer overflows, and other drainage systems. It can be used for evaluating grey infrastructure control strategies for stormwater, such as pipes and storm drains, and creating cost-effective green-grey hybrid stormwater control

systems; reducing runoff through infiltration and retention, and help to reduce discharges that impair waterbodies. StormNET supports local, state, national, and international sustainable development goals in relation to clean water and creation of resilient urban water infrastructures.

Typical Applications include: designing and sizing of drainage system components for flood control; sizing detention facilities and their appurtenances for flood control and water quality protection; mapping flood plains of natural channel systems— The modelling engine *SWMM 5 is a FEMA-approved model for National Flood Insurance Program studies*; designing control strategies for minimizing combined sewer overflows; evaluating the impact of inflow and infiltration on sanitary sewer overflows; generating nonpoint source pollutant loadings for waste load allocation; controlling site runoff using green infrastructure practices as low LID controls; evaluating the effectiveness of best management practices and low impact development for reducing wet weather pollutant loadings.

Figure 2 provides a visual illustration of some of the unique StormNET capabilities.

Figure 2. StormNET enables simulation and visualization of integrated urban water distribution, water drainage, green infrastructure, low-impact development, river system dynamics, and flood inundation.

Predicting Floodplain Dissolved Oxygen Concentrations Using Deep Learning

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Summary

Dissolved Oxygen (DO) concentrations in waters overlying floodplains have a significant impact on nutrient cycling, release of toxic metals, and greenhouse gas emissions. Advanced sensor technology allows for near-real time monitoring of DO, but sensors are expensive and spatially limited. Therefore, accurate modeling of DO concentrations is critical to effective water quality management. Due to the complex behavior of DO dynamics, machine learning has shown promise for accurately forecasting DO (Zhi et al., 2021). In this work, we illustrate the transfer learning capabilities of a deep learning model to forecast DO at intensively monitored floodplain sites in the Lake Champlain Basin of Vermont.

Introduction

Dissolved Oxygen (DO) is a critical measure of water quality and health of aquatic ecosystems (Ficklin et al., 2023). Riparian DO concentrations regulate soil reduction-oxidation processes and therefore have a significant impact on the internal cycling of nutrients between soils and floodwaters (A. Wiegman et al., 2022). Extended periods of hypoxia (e.g., $DO < 2\text{-}3 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) in rivers and floodplains can also increase greenhouse gas emissions (Rosamond et al., 2012) and impact aquatic life (Saari et al., 2018). A global analysis of DO in rivers found that short-lived periods of hypoxia in rivers are relatively common, and 12.6% of rivers globally experienced hypoxic conditions (Blaszczak et al., 2023). Widespread trends in river warming have been observed with climate change (Ficklin et al., 2023), so the frequency and persistence of hypoxia in rivers and riverine floodplains is likely to increase into the future and will remain a critical water resource management challenge. In addition to rising water temperatures, DO regimes and water quality more generally are also heavily influenced by catchment land use (Li et al., 2024), with the percentages of wetland and agricultural land use each having an outsized impact on DO dynamics across land use types (Blaszczak et al., 2023; Zhi et al., 2023). In turn, floodplain water quality is dependent on influent river water quality (A. R. H. Wiegman et al., 2024). Despite riverine floodplains' importance on DO dynamics and water quality more generally, minimal attention has been placed on predicting DO in floodplains, as there is a lack of floodplain DO data as compared to river DO data.

Methodology and Results

In this work, we illustrate the development and testing of a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network to forecast floodplain DO data up to seven days out at five riverine floodplain sites located in the Lake Champlain Basin of Vermont, where a two-to-three-year monitoring campaign has observed DO concentrations in the river and floodplain ranging from $\sim 0 - 14 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. To overcome the temporally and spatially limited record of floodplain DO data, the model was first pre-trained on low-frequency, long-term river DO data from sites across the CONUS (after Zhi et al., 2021) using hydrometeorological and catchment attribute data as inputs (Sterle et al., 2024). The pre-trained LSTM was then fine-tuned to high-frequency sensor data from our floodplain sites. This approach follows transfer learning methods that have been used for streamflow prediction to overcome data scarcity by leveraging data outside of the area of interest (Ma et al., 2021). The LSTM shows promise for forecasting DO up to seven days out, and fine-tuning of the LSTMs to floodplain site data decreased the RMSE by an average of 1.74 mg L^{-1} across all sites. The LSTM tracked closely with observed DO concentrations during well oxygenated periods, but generally struggled to predict periods of low DO.

Conclusions

Accurate forecasting of DO concentrations is of interest to restoration professionals, water quality managers, and other stakeholders working to protect water quality and restore or preserve floodplain habitat. A DO forecast model could also be used to generate forcing data for modeling other complex biogeochemical processes that are driven by oxygen availability (e.g., nutrient dynamics). A general lack of floodplain DO data would normally constrain the development of floodplain DO forecast models, but pre-training an LSTM on relatively abundant CONUS-wide river data and transferring that learning to our Lake Champlain region floodplain settings has helped to overcome the data limitations. Our approach not only overcomes issues of data-scarcity in terms of number of monitored floodplain sites, but also in terms of length of data record; each of the floodplain sites has only two to three years of data, yet the LSTM was still able to forecast accurately, potentially reducing the amount of time a site needs to be monitored before a model can be trained to forecast at that site.

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Water Resources Management: A Comprehensive Analysis of Elements and Emerging Synergies (Poster Presentation)

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Summary

This study explores the multifaceted challenges in water resource management and identifies key elements for effectively managing these resources. These elements include watershed models, surrogate models, optimization methods, artificial intelligence, decision support systems, and monitoring networks. The review assesses the roles, challenges, and shortcomings of these elements, proposing future solutions for improved management strategies. In conclusion, this study proposes innovative strategies to balance efficiency, precision, and stakeholder engagement for sustainable water resource management.

Introduction

In the 21st century, humans face major global challenges, including population growth, food security, climate change, water scarcity and security, and rapid urbanization, to name a few. Among these challenges, global concerns regarding water quality have escalated due to industrial and agricultural contaminants. Meanwhile, Best Management Practices (BMPs) are commonly employed to enhance water quality, but high costs limit these practices (Chen et al., 2022). Moreover, **Monitoring** is crucial in evaluating BMP effectiveness and supplying critical environmental impact data. However, due to the expensive nature of implementation and monitoring, **Watershed Models** are used to examine various BMP implementation scenarios as they simulate pollutant movement and distribution within complex systems (Sharma et al., 2023). Given the enormous number of possible BMP scenarios, randomly applying BMPs to determine the most cost-effective approach is not feasible. Combining **Optimization** algorithms with watershed models seeks to identify the most cost-effective BMP strategies for reducing pollution, although this requires extensive computational resources (Boddiford et al., 2023). To overcome this, **Surrogate Models** have been developed that offer a compromise between accuracy and efficiency, taking much less time than traditional hydrological models (Chen et al., 2016). Furthermore, incorporating data-driven methodologies, and **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** in these models boosts the efficiency of optimization algorithms, potentially enhancing their ability to select the most effective BMP scenarios (Kropp et al., 2022). Finally, combining **Decision Support Systems** and all other components enhances water management's efficiency, sustainability, and resilience. This study aims to analyze the operation and challenges of key elements in water resources management (highlighted above in italics and bold) and to identify future directions for enhancing management practices.

Methodology and Results

The research question in this study is "How do individual elements of water resources management operate, and what are their specific advantages, challenges, current and future solutions and applications in water resources management?" To address this, we used criteria including publications that apply methodologies in large-scale case studies, are relevant to the study's scope, and address the research question and objectives. We followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. During the identification phase, we employed a combination of keywords such as "AI," "Water Quality," "Watershed," "Data Mining," and "Optimization," search engines like Google Scholar and Scopus. This approach initially returned 31,587 documents. By refining our keywords to target our research focus, we narrowed it down to 184 papers. After removing duplicates, conducting title and abstract screenings, and using exclusion criteria, 68 papers remained. This review thoroughly explores the essential elements of water resources management, stressing their significance and needs. Next, we thoroughly examine the challenges

and benefits associated with these elements and propose enhancements to improve the reliability and thoroughness of water resources management. Following the detailed methodology described earlier, our findings lead to future recommendations to fill the knowledge gaps and challenges identified in each of the six major elements of water resources management. Examples of these results are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Key challenges across six fundamental elements of water resources management

Figure 2. Future prospects within six core elements of resources management

Conclusions

By analyzing six vital elements of water resources management independently, we uncovered challenges and opportunities for future research. Among the challenges reviewed, the most significant is the inability to interpret and explain AI model outcomes, which remains largely unexplored. The “black box” characteristic of AI systems, marked by their opacity and lack of transparency, complicates decision-making due to unclear interpretability. Another significant challenge in developing watershed models is the restricted access to comprehensive, real-time, high-resolution spatial and temporal datasets needed for parameter input and calibration. A promising solution to this issue is the implementation of Advanced Sensor Networks, which enable the collection of real-time, high-resolution data across watersheds. In real-world optimization problems, many variables and uncertainties lead to large search space and high computational time. Additionally, future studies in watershed management should focus on strengthening engagement with stakeholders and working on ease of use of decision support systems.

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Advancing Water Quality Management Through Conversational AI: The Development of a Data Expert System

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Summary

The Water Quality Data Expert (DE) is a novel system which enables water quality analytics through natural language to enable non-technical users to interact with data. This feature enables user-friendly, ad-hoc data analysis by leveraging ChatGPT's capabilities in geocoding, sentiment analysis, and response generation to facilitate intuitive interaction with data. Enhanced with chat controls, integration with an information system, and an in-depth analysis mode, the system significantly improves data accessibility and analysis for various users. This system poses a potential in democratizing environmental data access, thereby encouraging informed decision-making and active participation in environmental conservation from a variety of community stakeholders.

Introduction

Targeting the critical issues of water quality management is a vital concern due to its significant impact on ecosystems and human health (Conley et al., 2009; Meyers et al., 2021; Pericherla et al., 2020). Nutrient pollution from agricultural runoff, urban activities, and boat traffic leads to detrimental effects like harmful algal blooms and oxygen depletion in water bodies (Salerno et al., 2018; Rosyida et al., 2022). To foster a better understanding of these issues, the DE was created. By leveraging ChatGPT's unique capabilities (Pursnani et al., 2023), the DE enables intuitive, natural language-based data analysis, making water quality data more accessible and understandable to a broad audience. Features such as chat customization, direct data inquiry, and a data interpretation mode are designed to cater to diverse user needs, facilitating easier data retrieval and analysis.

The project centers on improving access to environmental data to empower informed decision-making and proactive action towards water quality improvement (Mount et al., 2023). By developing the DE, the initiative aims to foster more informed public participation in environmental conservation. It not only tackles the technical aspects of water quality management but also promotes community engagement, offering a comprehensive platform for users to learn about water quality issues, assess local conditions, and identify actionable steps for improvement.

Methodology and Results

DE utilizes a system architecture developed in Python, with a frontend designed in ReactJS for user interaction. The DE incorporates ChatGPT for Named Entity Recognition (NER) to identify key entities like locations in user inputs and geocoding to convert place names into geographical coordinates. This process enables the system to accurately retrieve water quality data from the closest monitoring sites based on user queries. The system also features multilingual support through ChatGPT, allowing it to understand and respond in various languages, thus broadening user accessibility. The backend is managed with Flask, facilitating the deployment of web services, while the frontend leverages ReactJS for a dynamic and modular user interface. This methodology focuses on practicality and user-friendliness, aiming to make environmental data more accessible to diverse user groups.

The development of the DE introduced several key functionalities aimed at optimizing the user experience for diverse audiences. Geocoding capabilities, enabled through NER, allow the DE to accurately identify user-specified locations and fetch relevant water quality data from the nearest monitoring sites. The system's data interpretation mode facilitates an interactive Q&A session, enabling users to delve deeper into specific water quality data points. Additionally, the chat bypass feature integrates the DE directly with the Information System's map interface, allowing for seamless transition and immediate inquiry about specific data visualized on the map. These advancements not only enhance the DE's usability but also transform it into a robust platform for ad-hoc water quality data querying and analysis. The multilingual support extends the system's reach, ensuring users from various linguistic backgrounds can interact with and derive valuable insights from the platform.

Conclusions

The development of the DE marks an advancement in making water quality analytics more accessible and intuitive for a broad audience. This novel DE system aligns with the objectives of enhancing interdisciplinary cooperation and decision-making in environmental management. Future research will focus on expanding the agents' knowledge base for specialized queries and integrating multimodal data analysis, further empowering users to understand and contribute to water quality improvement. This approach not only fosters informed public participation in environmental conservation but also sets a foundation for developing comprehensive frameworks that bridge the gap between scientific research and practical environmental stewardship.

The potential future of systems like the DE in the water quality domain and hydrology at large is expansive. As technological advancements continue, these systems could integrate more sophisticated AI-driven analytical techniques, such as predictive analytics and machine learning models that forecast water quality trends based on historical data and real-time inputs. The next phase may also see an enhanced integration of IoT devices, providing real-time, localized water quality monitoring that feeds directly into such systems for immediate analysis and community alerts. This evolution could transform water management practices, making them more proactive rather than reactive, and significantly increase the precision and personalization of water resource management across diverse ecosystems.

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Soft Computing Techniques for Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation in Eurasian Crossroads: A Systematic Review (poster presentation)

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Summary

The review, conducted following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, explores artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques to better understand the impacts of climate change in Iran, Turkey, and Pakistan (Eurasian Crossroads) and potential adaptation and mitigation strategies. Using Scopus database search and systematic review processes, it identifies applications across water resources management, climate prediction, land and agriculture, and ecosystem. Techniques that are reviewed include classical ML, neural networks, and meta-heuristic algorithms, highlighting enhanced predictive capabilities and the pivotal role of AI/ML in addressing climate change challenges.

Introduction

Climate change presents formidable challenges for Iran, Turkey, and Pakistan, affecting crucial aspects such as water resources, agriculture, biodiversity, and vulnerability to natural disasters. Situated at a pivotal juncture between Europe and Asia, these nations hold significant geographical importance. They are also founding members of the Economic Cooperation Organization. The crucial use of AI and ML is vital in addressing challenges through data analysis and forecasting. This review explores their application in climate change adaptation within the region to enhance resilience and sustainability.

Methodology and Results

Following PRISMA guidelines, 76 relevant articles were identified from Scopus, covering water resources, climate prediction, agriculture, ecosystems, and natural disasters. Classical ML, neural networks, and optimization/meta-heuristic algorithms are highlighted. The study aims to summarize algorithms, identify research priorities, and suggest future investigation areas.

Figure 1. An overview of AI/ML published articles relevant to different spectrum of climate change

Across various fields addressing climate change, classical ML techniques are pivotal. Ensemble models, adept at combining algorithms for robust predictions, are widely used (Nourani et al., 2023). Notably, techniques like Random Forest, Boosted Trees, and SVM are prominent, offering sophisticated tools for insights and decision-making. SVM, particularly favoured for crop yield prediction, handles high-dimensional datasets effectively (Arefinia et al., 2022). Dimension reduction techniques complement ensemble models in ecosystem impact

assessment. In natural disaster prediction, ensemble models coupled with Random Forest and Boosted Trees effectively forecast events like floods and landslides (Pham et al., 2022).

Neural networks are integral in diverse fields addressing climate change challenges. In water resources management, they excel in forecasting parameters like evapotranspiration, reservoir evaporation, and surface runoff. Various models such as LR-ANN, ANFIS, FFNN, LSTM, and ANNs with wavelet transformations are employed (Nourani et al., 2023). Neural networks significantly contribute to climate prediction, temperature modelling, precipitation pattern analysis, and assessing hydrological cycle changes. In land and agriculture, they aid in predicting virtual water content, crop yields, reservoir inflow projections, and soil erosion risks (Arefinia et al., 2022). Additionally, neural networks play a crucial role in biodiversity conservation, ecosystem assessments, and managing natural disasters like floods, droughts, and wildfires, offering accurate forecasts essential for adaptation and disaster risk reduction strategies.

Meta-heuristic algorithms like GEP, WSVR, and MGPP are crucial in climate change impact assessments for hydrological and agricultural systems, as shown by studies by Niazar et al. (2023), and Zeydalinjad & Dehghani (2023) offering improved predictive models for precipitation, groundwater levels, and daily temperatures, marking significant advancement in climate change research.

Conclusions

In summary, the review underscores the pivotal role of AI and ML techniques in addressing climate change challenges across Iran, Turkey, and Pakistan. From classical ML methods to neural networks and meta-heuristic algorithms, these tools offer valuable insights and predictive capabilities crucial for sustainable environmental management practices, highlighting the need for continued research and innovation in this critical field.

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